

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

**PROCEEDING BOOK OF
THE INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON**

**EMERGING
TRENDS IN
MANAGEMENT, IT
AND EDUCATION**

16/08/2019 AND 17/08/2019

EDITORS

DR. P. S. AITHAL

PROF. SHREEPATHY RANGABHATTA B.

ISBN NO. : 978-81-941751-2-4

VOLUME 1

**SRINIVAS PUBLICATION
MANGALURU**

ORGANISING TEAM

Chief Patron

Sri. CA. A. Raghavendra Rao

Chancellor, Srinivas University
President, A. Shama Rao Foundation
Mangaluru

Patrons

Dr. A. Srinivas Rao

Pro- Chancellor, Srinivas University
Vice-President, A. Shama Rao Foundation, Mangaluru

Smt. A. Mitra S. Rao

Secretary
A. Shama Rao Foundation, Mangaluru

Dr. P. S. Aithal

Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University

Prof. Shreepathy Rangabhatta B.

Conference Convenor

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

City Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru- 575 001
Karnataka State, India

Website: www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CONTENTS

Sl. No	Title	Page No.
1.	SCHOLARLY PUBLICATION BASED RESEARCH JOURNALS CLASSIFICATION – NEW INSIGHT-BASED MODEL <i>Dr. P. S. Aithal, Dr. Shubhrajyotsna Aithal</i>	1
2.	IMPACT OF DIGITALIZED EDUCATION ON STUDENTS – A STUDY IN MANGALORE <i>Ms Deshel Levines Fernandes, Mr. Gavin Abner Pinto</i>	15
3.	A STUDY ON REINVENTION AND CHALLENGES OF IBM <i>Kiran Raj K. M., Krishna Prasad K.</i>	24
4.	DIGITAL SERVICE INNOVATION USING ICCT UNDERLYING TECHNOLOGIES <i>Dr. P. S. Aithal, Dr. Shubhrajyotsna Aithal</i>	33
5.	INNOVATIVE AND CREATIVE TEACHING TO STIMULATE PARTICIPATION OF STUDENTS AT HIGHER EDUCATION FOR SOCIAL CHANGE <i>Aditi Jha</i>	64
6.	A STUDY ON THE MEASURES TAKEN BY COGNIZANT TECHNOLOGY SOLUTIONS FOR ACHIEVING SUSTAINABLE GROWTH IN THE DIGITAL MARKET <i>K. Geetha Poornima, Krishna Prasad K.</i>	71
7.	NETWORK SECURITY: THREAT & MANAGEMENT <i>P. K. Paul, P. S. Aithal</i>	85
8.	A STUDY ON CUSTOMERS OPINION ON BANKING PRODUCTS AND SERVICES WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO SELECTED BRANCHES OF KASARAGODU DISTRICT COOPERATIVE BANK <i>Mr. P V Joseph, Dr. P N Raghunathan</i>	99
9.	A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS POLICIES OF TATA CONSULTANCY SERVICES LIMITED (TCS) <i>K. Vikranth, Krishna Prasad K.</i>	108
10.	INFORMATION ASSURANCE: THE WAY TO INTRODUCE IN UG EDUCATION IN INDIA—A POLICY FRAMEWORK <i>P. K. Paul, P. S. Aithal, A. Bhuimali</i>	121
11.	A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY ON THE IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM FOR THE SOCIAL CHANGE <i>Maithri, S. M. Riha Parvin</i>	129

12.	IMPLEMENTING PRODUCT DIVERSIFICATION STRATEGIES FOR THE SUSTAINABILITY OF A TECHNOLOGY COMPANY - A CASE OF MICROSOFT CORPORATION <i>Vinayachandra, Krishna Prasad K.</i>	134
13.	A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY ON COMPARISONS OF STOCK PRICES PREVAILING IN THE CASH MARKET AND FUTURES MARKET WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO BANKS <i>Wilma Carol Martis, Priyanna Noeline Dcunha</i>	144
14.	A CRITICAL CASE STUDY ON QUALCOMM AS PIONEERS OF WIRELESS REVOLUTION <i>Sangeetha Prabhl, Krishna Prasad K</i>	157
15.	IMPULSIVE BUYING AND ROLE OF AI IN PERSONALISED MARKETING: OPINION OF THE YOUTH OF DAKSHINA KANNADA <i>Sushma M. Marebal</i>	166
16.	WOMEN IN STEAM: A PERSPECTIVE OF PRESENT TRENDS, OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES IN ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY <i>Dr. Ramakrishna N Hegde, Mr. Srinidhi Kukkila</i>	172
17.	THE GROWTH OF A SERVICE ORIENTED IT COMPANY THROUGH OUTSOURCING –A CASE STUDY OF INFOSYS LTD. <i>M. Rajeshwari, Krishna Prasad K.</i>	179
18.	SWACCH BHARATH’ A STEP TOWARDS SUSTAINING CLEANLINESS - A CASE STUDY OF MRPL MANGALORE. <i>Pratheeksha</i>	190
19.	NETFLIX BIGDATA ANALYTICS-A STUDY ON IMPROVING CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE <i>Srivatsa Maddodi, Krishna Prasad. K.</i>	200
20.	PRODUCTION CULTURE IN MICRO AND SMALL INDUSTRIES AND THE USE OF COMPUTER-ASSISTED KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT IN MANUFACTURING PROCESSES <i>Sathyaprakash A.,Shrinivasa Mayya D.</i>	210
21.	CONTENT DELIVERY NETWORK'S PIONEERING LEADER- A CASE STUDY ON AKAMAI TECHNOLOGIES INC. <i>Yogish Pai U., Krishna Prasad K.</i>	226
22.	THE STUDY OF PSYCHOLOGICAL PARAMETERS ON FEMALE VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS <i>Ashwini Venkanagouda Patil, Dr. Hanumanthayya Pujari</i>	239

23.	TEACHING FOR SOCIAL CHANGE: CAN EDUCATION BRING A SOCIAL CHANGE IN A SOCIETY? <i>Prof. Ketan V., Sutaria, Jay V, Gala</i>	243
24.	OUTSOURCING: RECENT TRENDS IN MANAGEMENT FOR DEVELOPING INDIA <i>Dr. Pradip M. Joshi</i>	251
25.	CREDIT RISK MANAGEMENT WITH FOCUS ON THE COOPERATIVE BANKING SECTOR <i>Arati N. Rawal</i>	257
26.	ROLE OF TEACHERS IN SOCIAL CHANGE: A STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO SOCIAL WORK TEACHERS <i>Ganesh Prasad G. Nayak, Dr. Duggappa Kajekar</i>	264
27.	SELECTIVITY AND MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE: AN EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION OF SELECTED EQUITY DIVERSIFIED SCHEMES IN INDIA <i>Mrs. Akshatha Suvarna</i>	273
28.	JOB FAIR AND CSR <i>Varun Shenoy & P. S. Aithal</i>	299
29.	APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN DIGITALIZATION OF HUMAN RESOURCES <i>Dr. Babu Tejavath, Dr. Wahed Mohiuddin</i>	303

Paper 1

**SCHOLARLY PUBLICATION BASED RESEARCH
JOURNALS CLASSIFICATION – NEW INSIGHT-
BASED MODEL**

Dr. P. S. Aithal* & Dr. Shubhrajyotsna Aithal**

*Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Srinivas University, Mangalore – 575 001, India

**Dept. of Chemistry, College of Engineering & Technology, Srinivas University,
Mangalore-575001, India

*E-mail : psaithal@gmail.com

Abstract

Research is an essential activity in Society for technology, industrial, and social progress. Based on the historical review, higher education institutions focus on basic, conceptual, explorative, empirical, and analytical research methods whereas industries focus on new products and new processes development. In this paper, based on a survey on closed and open access scholarly publications, a new Scholarly Publication based Research Journals Classification model is proposed by defining an ideal scholarly publication process, analysing scholarly publication process, determining necessary and sufficient conditions to call an article as Scholarly article, identifying and analysing various factors affecting Journal classification, and developing a new model of Scholarly Journals grading.

Keywords : Scholarly publication, Scholarly journals, ABCD journal ranking, Journal classification, Ideal model of scholarly publication.

1. INTRODUCTION :

Research is an important activity in higher education institutions, research institutions, and industries. Research and Development is an essential activity for technology, industrial, and social progress. Based on the historical review, higher education institutions focus on basic, conceptual, explorative, empirical, and analytical research methods whereas industries focus on new products and new processes development. It is also known that the end of every piece of research of HEIs and Research Institutions is the scholarly publication and having the copyright of such basic or conceptual invention whereas the end of every piece of research of industries is acquiring a patent in inventor/company name. As mentioned in previous publications, scholarly research is basically involved in generating *new knowledge* through a systematic method or it is a method of a *new interpretation* of existing knowledge about any system by means of analysing it using suitable framework [1], [2], [3], [4].

As per one school of thought, there are two universally practiced and easily comprehensible types of research. They are exploratory research and descriptive research. Explorative research is based upon the objectives of solving the problem of study to make a decision related to it and is usually unstructured and qualitative in nature. The descriptive study is involved in describing a system mainly in terms of its functions and characteristics, and environment and end up to a conclusion about the system based on the purposes of the study and is usually structured and quantitative in nature.

2. RELATED WORKS :

There are many research work and scholarly publications in the area of Scholarly publication, Journal quality, Journal citation based impact factors, and Journal indexing. Table 1 depicts some of such scholarly papers in the field with the corresponding reference.

Table 1 : Some of the related scholarly work and publications during last few years.

S. No.	Issues	Focus	Reference
5	Problems in Conventional Scholarly Publications	Publishing delay	Björk, B. C., et al. (2013). [5]
6	Problems in Conventional Scholarly Publications	Publisher monopoly power and third-degree price discrimination	Chressanthis, G. A., (1993). [6]
7	Open Access Scholarly Publication	To provide open educational resource everybody with no cost	Anderson, T. (2013). [7]
8	Open Access Scholarly Publication	As a new scholarly communication model	Yiotis, K. (2005). [8]
9	Open Access Scholarly Publication	Challenges of open access publication	Ramalho Correia, A. M., et al. (2005). [9]
10	Open Access Scholarly Publication	Use of electronic media for open access publication to the globe	Oppenheim, C. (2008). [10]
11	Open Access Scholarly Publication	How internet changed the scholarly publications	Bartling, S. et al. (2014). [11]
12	Open Access Scholarly Publication	study of conflicting paradigms of Institutional repositories, open access, and scholarly Publication	Cullen, R. et al. (2011). [12]
13	Open Access Scholarly Publication	Study of innovative features	Björk, B. C. (2011). [13]
14	Open Access Scholarly Publication	Characteristics based on multidisciplinary study	Kousha, K. (2009). [14]
15	Predatory publishers	Predatory open-access scholarly publishers	Beall, J. (2010). [15]
16	Predatory publishers	Predatory publishers are corrupting open access	Beall, J. (2012). [16]
17	Predatory publishers	Unethical practices in scholarly, open-access publishing	Beall, J. (2013). [17]
18	Predatory publishers	Criteria for determining predatory open-access publishers	Beall, J. (2015). [18]
19	Predatory publishers	Essential information about predatory publishers and journals	Beall, J. (2016). [19]
20	Predatory publishers	What value do journal whitelists and blacklists have in academia?	da Silva, J. A. T., et al. (2018). [20]
21	Predatory publishers	Predatory journals in library	Nelson, N., et al.

		databases: How much should we worry?	(2015). [21]
22	Innovations in Scholarly Publication	Rethinking scholarly communication: building the system that scholars deserve] Sompel, H. V. D., et al. (2004). [22]
23	Innovations in Scholarly Publication	Why Smart Researcher Hesitate to Publish in/with Top Ranking Journals/Publishers	Aithal, P. S., et al. (2016). [23]
24	Innovations in Scholarly Publication	Comparative Study of Various Research Indices used to measure quality of Research Publications	Aithal, P. S., et al. (2016). [24]
25	Innovations in Scholarly Publication	A study comparing commercial and nonprofit/university publishers	Moghaddam, G. G. (2007). [25]
26	Innovations in Scholarly Publication	Wikipedia and academic peer review: Wikipedia as a recognised medium for scholarly publication	Black, E. W. (2008). [26]
27	Innovations in Scholarly Publication	Opening up institutional repositories: social construction of innovation in scholarly communication	Rieger, O. Y. (2008). [27]
28	Journal Rating & Ranking	How robust is journal rating in Humanities and Social Sciences	Ferrara, A., (2016). [28]
29	Journal Rating & Ranking	Towards a consolidation of worldwide journal rankings—a classification using random forests and aggregate rating	Tüselmann, H., et al. (2015). [29]
30	Journal Rating & Ranking	A Google Scholar h-index for journals: An alternative metric to measure journal impact in economics and business	Harzing, A. W., (2009). [30]
31	Journal Rating & Ranking	The journal impact factor: a brief history, critique, and discussion of adverse effects	Larivière, V., et al. (2018). [31]
32	Journal Rating & Ranking	On the stability of citation-based journal rankings	Pajić, D. (2015). [32]
33	Journal Rating & Ranking	Ranking the management journals	Harris, C. (2008). [33]
34	Journal Rating & Ranking	Ranking journals using altmetrics	Loach, T. V., et al. (2015). [34]
35	Journal Rating & Ranking	Journal ranking by citation analysis: Some inconsistencies	Over, R. (1978). [35]

3. OBJECTIVES :

- (1) To define ideal scholarly publication process
- (2) To analyse Scholarly publication process
- (3) To determine necessary and sufficient conditions to call an article as Scholarly article
- (4) To identify and analyse various factors affecting Journal classification
- (5) To develop a new model of Scholarly Journals grading

4. METHODOLOGY :

Conceptual study on ideal system model [36] based on explorative research using trend analysis. The methodology uses the definition of ideal system in a given topic in terms of its properties and studies present status or trend of the same system and analyse how the present system can be improved towards ideal system with ideal characteristics.

5. IDEAL RESEARCH MODEL :

As per the concept of ideal research, it is a process of creating new knowledge open to society without any intension of retaining its control in the form of copyright or patent. Any invention or finding should end with open access publication to the entire world to share the generated new knowledge to the society for solving existing problems or for further research by interested researchers or research groups.

According to present model, any research can be broadly classified into two types as Scientific research and Industrial research. Scientific research is also called pure research and industrial research is also called applied research. All research related to new concept based knowledge creation is considered under scientific or pure research and all research related new product or new process based knowledge creation is considered as industrial research or applied research as summarized in table 2.

Table 2 : Type of scholarly research and the nature IPR generated

S.No.	Classification of Research	Input	Output	IPR Generated
1	Scientific or Pure Research (Academic research)	Intangible/ Tangible resources	Theory/ Concept/ Models	Copyright
2	Industrial or Applied Research	Tangible Resources	Product/ Process/ Service	Patent

6. SCHOLARLY PUBLICATION PROCESS :

6.1 Scholarly Article Format :

The outcome of research presented systematically in the form of a structured document is generally called as scholarly research paper or scholarly article. The format of a scholarly article in general consists of following parts in its structure :

- (1) Introduction
- (2) Review of Literature / Related work
- (3) Objectives of research
- (4) Experimental Details / Methodology
- (5) Result & Discussion / Analysis & Interpretation
- (6) Findings/Suggestions/Recommendations

(7) Conclusion

(8) References of citations in MLA/ APA/ Chicago/ Harvard/ Vancouver style

The structural difference between a scientific and social science scholarly article is depicted in table 3.

Table 3 : Structural Difference between the Scientific Scholarly article framework and Social science & management Scholarly article framework

S. No.	Scientific Scholarly article framework	Social science & management Scholarly article framework
1	Abstract	Abstract
2	Introduction	Introduction
3	Review of Literature	Related work
4	Objectives	Objectives
5	Experimental Details	Methodology
6	Result & Discussion	Analysis & Interpretation
7	Findings	Suggestion/Recommendation
8	Conclusion	Conclusion
9	References of citations in APA/ Vancouver style	References of citations in MLA/ APA/ Chicago/ Harvard style
10	Formatted document	Formatted document

The objective of every author while writing a Scholarly Article is to publish it freely to the entire world immediately at no cost. Before the advent of the internet and online open publication model, authors used to find suitable publishers who publish scholarly articles in a similar subject in the form of a book called scholarly journal. The scholarly journal publishers are mediators to check the article quality (language in terms of grammar, novelty, plagiarism, and format) of such an article by means of a checking process called review of scholarly article. After the advent of the internet and various application software, checking the grammar mistakes (language quality), detecting plagiarism (originality), and systematic formatting as scholarly article became easy and the author of the article can take care of these things independently using a well supportive computer system. The peer review process became important only to know the novelty in the form of new knowledge, or a new interpretation of it. In olden days, since, all researchers had no access to computers, publishers took responsibility of language improvement including grammar, checking the plagiarism to confirm the originality of the paper as scholarly article and to check the novelty to publish and supply it to all research & higher education libraries across the globe. In return, they bargained heavily to capture the copyright of the scholarly article for a lifetime. The poor researchers had no alternative to showcase their research findings to the entire world so that they have accepted the proposal of scholarly publication. The publishers not only became successful in grabbing the copyright of the research papers developed by the poor researchers but also tried to create a monopoly by creating the process called blind peer review process. The blind peer review process is publisher focussed and has an objective of adding business value (selling value) of the paper along with improving the grammar, checking the plagiarism, and formatting the paper as per journal publication format to make the printed version of scholarly journal attractive which intern enhanced the Journal subscription across the globe. Usually, the peer review is done by three people, one is internal from the publishing house and the other two are outsiders usually chosen from the author

suggestive list. The internal reviewer checks the subject for suitability of the paper for including in a requested journal, check grammar and language for any corrections, check the plagiarism, and format it. Then the paper is reviewed by two reviewers positively related to that subject to ensure novelty in the form of new knowledge, or new analysis-based interpretation. Since the journal publishers are not paying for the external review process, the external reviewer usually does not give priority and hence review process takes a long time. The publisher takes the decision to accept the paper if they feel that the paper is sellable for a long time and ask the author to transfer the copyright of the paper in publisher name and enjoys the revenue of selling that paper throughout the globe forever. The poor author will get satisfaction by seeing the published paper and the copies of the printed papers he received. Once the copyright is transferred, the author cannot share the paper officially in any form. Hence scholarly publication became big business and many journals started to charge the author in the name of journal submission charges along with earnings by selling the copyright received articles. Thus, the scholarly publication model became an attractive business model with high profit, which further increased competition. Many publishers encashed this opportunity and grown as multinational publishers with several millions of annual revenues. Table 4 lists some of the prominent multinational publishers with an approximate number of journals they publish in different subjects. These publishers called big-players in the journal and books publication field started to control their monopoly by means of a strategy to block new entrants in scholarly publications. The two strategies the big-player used to protect themselves are (1) Scopus & Web of Science Indexing, (2) Creation of a new field of publishers called predatory publishers. The big players in scholarly publications have started their own Journal indexing database and blocked the new players entry to their journal indexing database. They created a lobby that started to call new entrants to scholarly Journal Publication business as “predatory journals”. It is assumed that many researchers are sponsored for such hue and cry against small journal publishers and new publishers and they started to write articles continuously for every two years to keep the predatory publication issue alive. For example, it is difficult to find out why Mr. Beall, J. [15-19] continuously wrote against predatory journals and has gone to such extent to list such journals without much supporting documentary evidence.

Table 4 : List of Top multinational publishers with number of Journals and annual revenue

S. No.	Top multinational publishers	Number of Journals [23]	Annual Revenue
1	Elsevier Journals	3,352	£2.54 billion (2018)
2	Springer-Verlag	2,700	Euro1.64 billion (2017)
3	John Wiley and Sons	2,380	\$1.80 billion (2019)
4	Taylor and Francis	2,100	£530 millions (2017)
5	Sage Publications	1,300	£2.54 billion (2018)
6	Walter de Gruyter	913	\$15 million (2018)
7	Inderscience Publishers	391	-
9	Hindawi Publishing Corporation	366	-
10	Cambridge University Press	329	£327 million (2019)
11	Oxford University Press	310	£840 million (2018)
12	Emerald	308	£380 million (20 8)

6.2 Re-defining Predatory Journals :

As per our model, scholarly publication is the contribution from researchers for society and for the continuation of research further by many other related research groups for the development of science and society. Hence scholarly publication should not be a business proposition and only charitable organizations should involve in publication of research output. It can be argued that the organizations who involve in scholarly journal business are looking for profit and hence they cannot give justice for scholarly publication. Their strategy would be to create a business model which subsequently make them monopoly to get highest revenue and huge profit by exploiting both scholarly authors and other researchers who wants to read and continue such work as further research. A real and genuine scholarly journal will not profit motivated and start publishing service under charity model to help the researchers and the society to spread the research results for promoting research and extension to society. Using internet based online publication model, the charitable organizations which involve in scholarly publication can decrease their cost to minimum so that they can sustain for longer time using charity based free publication and free distribution model. Such journals published by charity motivated publishers with no cost to authors and readers is called non-predatory journals. Table 5 compares non-predatory and predatory journals.

Table 5 : Comparison of non-predatory and predatory journals based on 5 factors

S. No.	Factors	Non-predatory Journal	Predatory Journal
1	Submission charge	Free	Paid
2	Processing Charge	Free	Paid
3	Copyright	With authors	With Publishers
4	Subscription charge	Free open access	Paid subscription
5	Time delay	Minimum	Long waiting
6	Availability	Online open access copy	Printed copy
7	Review (Free/Paid)	No payment to reviewer	No payment to reviewer
8	Profit	Not profit motivated	Profit motivated

Based on table 5, the new definition of predatory journal is a journal published by profit motivated publishers and they charge either to author or to reader or both. The authors should voluntarily ban such predatory publishers to retail the copyright of their scholarly paper and to publish it globally without much time lag and for free distribution.

7. SCHOLARLY JOURNALS :

As mentioned in the previous section, the objective of scholarly publication is the distribution of the research results systematically in the form of a scholarly article to every person who has the interest to read or use it as reference information in their research without constraints which keep him to avoid such publication. Thus, scholarly journals should have the intention to fulfil the objective of scholarly publication. As per table 7, scholarly journals should have the following objects from authors and readers point of view :

- (1) Low time lag between submission & publication by accelerating review process.
- (2) Moderate review to check the novelty, plagiarism, language, and format of the research publication.
- (3) Zero submission and processing charge for the authors since research is a social contribution effort.

- (4) Open online publication with no article download cost for readers.
- (5) The copyright should be with the author so that he can use and distribute the paper in other means like sharing through various social media in addition to the journal website.
- (6) A unique identification number has to be given to the article for easy search and downloading purpose.
- (7) The published paper should be available for download forever for DOI based searching by storing it in multiple locations.

7.1 Types of Scholarly Journals :

As per the present model, scholarly journals can be classified as :

- (1) Non-profit & charitable organization supported Journals
- (2) Non-profit motivated independent Journals,
- (3) Profit motivated organizations Journal as a business product
- (4) Profit motivated individuals published Journals as their business products
- (5) Self publication by authors using social networks or open online libraries

The above publishers follow either open access or closed access scholarly publication model [37]. Open access model (new model) may follow either free publication without Article processing charge (APC) or collect APC from the authors which usually vary from \$ 20 to \$ 5,000. In an open access publication model, some journals insist APC and compulsory copyright to publisher name but many other journals allow authors to retain copyright in the author's name. In the closed access model (old model) the publisher is controlling the system by following the subscription model of journal distribution. For this, the publisher insists the author to transfer the copyright of the article and earns huge money by selling the paper & journal thereafter. In this model, some publishers even charge article submission charges and APC from authors along with copy transfer to sell the article through subscription and online downloads. The closed publication model is a rude (one sided) model where both the author and the reviewer will not get any financial benefit for their efforts.

7.2 Necessary & Sufficient conditions to call an article as Scholarly article :

In this section, an attempt is made to systematically explain scholarly article by postulating its properties under necessary and sufficient conditions.

Necessary Conditions for Scholarly Article :

- (1) Novelty /New knowledge or new interpretation of existing knowledge.
- (2) Plagiarism free.
- (3) Related works.
- (4) Systematic Study : to prove that the research is systematic.
- (5) An abstract of the research work.

Sufficient Conditions for Scholarly Article :

- (1) Systematic scholarly Format : language.
- (2) Objectives of study.
- (3) Citations in the article.
- (4) Conclusion about the findings.
- (5) Scholarly references.

A journal which publishes non-scholarly articles is called Magazine or Predatory Journal.

7.3 Factors affecting Journal classification :

Factors Affecting Journal Classification are :

- (1) New Knowledge, based on New Analysis/ New experiment,
- (2) Open & free Access to entire globe
- (3) Free Publication for authors
- (4) Copy right is with Authors

7.4 New model of Scholarly Journals grading :

Presently there are different models and methods of ranking the journals which include, based on citations, based on indexing, based on altmetrics, etc. Table 6 list the features compared in such ranking.

Table 6 : Features used in Journal ranking

S. No.	Journal Ranking Model	Features used / compared
1	Citation Based Approach	Citation based impact factor [38]
2	Altmetrics based Approach	Social Media Approach [39]
3	Impact factor of the Journal	Impact factors of Journals [40]
4	H-Index of the Journal	H-index values of Journals [24, 41]

7.5 Scholarly Journal Categories :

As per our observations, a scholarly journal falls into one of the following categories :

- (1) Closed access based Paid subscription, with author processing charge (APC) and Copyright transferred from the author.
- (2) Closed access based paid subscription, without author processing charge (APC) and Copyright transferred from the author.
- (3) Open Access Free Publication by taking APC and Copyright from the author.
- (4) Open Access Free Publication without taking APC and Copyright from the author.

Accordingly, they can be divided into different grades as shown below :

- (1) **A Grade** – University/HEI owned Open access, Free Publication Journals without taking Copyright.
- (2) **B Grade** – University/HEI owned Open access Journals with copyright or APC.
- (3) **C Grade** – Commercial Organizational Publishers Journals with Closed access with copyright or APC.
- (4) **D Grade** – Individually/commercial organization owned Journals with Closed access, APC & copyright.

This new Journal grading model from authors and readers point of view is further explained using table 7.

Table 7 : ABCD Model of Researcher Centric Scholarly Journals Grading

S. No.	Grade	Open Access	No Article Processing Charges	Copyright with Authors	Example
1	A	Yes	Yes	Yes	Open access Journals published by the charitable organization, sponsored by Universities, etc.

					without any APC and copyright transfer. (Diamond OA Journals)
2	B++	Yes	Yes	No	Open access but follows subscription model also to take care of expenses by collecting copyright. (Gold OA journals)
3	B+	Yes	No	Yes	Open access but collects a small amount of APC from authors or their sponsoring organization. (Silver OA Journals)
4	B	Yes	No	No	Open access but collects a small amount of APC from authors or their sponsoring organization and also follows subscription model to libraries.
5	C++	No	Yes	Yes	Closed access but no APC and copyright transfer, but sells paper through a library subscription.
6	C+	No	Yes	No	Closed access and copyright transfer, but no APC but sells paper through subscription and article download charges.
7	C	No	No	Yes	Closed access and no copyright transfer, but collects APC and sells paper through a library subscription.
8	D	No	No	No	Closed access, copyright transfer, collects APC and sells paper through library subscription and article download charges.

8. CONCLUSION :

The objective of research and development is simplifying complex things to generate new knowledge or new interpretation. The continuous progress in technology is supporting the researchers to improve the quality and decreasing the time duration required for each research process. Scholarly publication is a part of every research and has the objective of spreading the research results to other researchers in the same field to boost the further research by many groups with an intention to accelerate the continued growth of the subject in society. Currently, many publishers involved in scholarly publications treated it as a profitable business model and all processes under scholarly publications are publisher centric. Hence, they controlled the scholarly publication model from their survival point of view by creating many lobby-based survival strategies including Journal indexing. In the process, they imposed article submission charges, article processing charges, copyright transfer to their name to sell the articles and journals to the public. Since this publication model is publisher centric and in the name of peer review, they have hijacked the entire research effort of the

researcher to their control and hesitated to share the revenue with the authors. The researchers were handicapped to raise their voices against this system due to the continued lobby of international publishers to the scholarly publication process. As we know, changes are inevitable in any and every system, the advent of technology gave a solution to researchers to come out of the monopoly of publishers' model. Now, through online open access and holding copyright with the researcher, scholarly publication is expected to be researcher centric. Many philanthropic and charitable organizations started to support this researcher centric model to give justice to researchers and fulfil the real objective of scholarly publication. In this proposed researcher centric scholarly article publication model, three parameters are considered to classify research journals which include, (1) Open access publication, (2) Article Processing Charge (APC), and (3) Retaining copyright with the authors. Based on these three parameters eight grades of research journals are identified and named them as A grade, B++ grade, B+ grade, B grade, C++ grade, C+ grade, C grade, and D grade as listed in table 7. The developed model of journal classification is compared with existing Journal grading models and some suggestions made on scholarly publications and citations from different stakeholders' points of view. Based on our arguments, it is observed that the online electronic journals published by universities, libraries, organizations with research publication grants, and the scholarly societies in each specialty areas are optimum journals to support researchers honestly by falling the category of A grade Journals to uphold the objective, freedom, integrity, and self-respect of the researchers in their endeavour of serving the society. This Researcher centric Scholarly Journals grading and publication model is expected to surpass the prevailing Publisher centric model in future days.

REFERENCES :

- [1] Aithal, P. S., & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal (2019). New Directions in Scholarly Research- Some Fearless Innovations & Predictions for 21st Century Research. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 4(1), 1-19. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2557222>.
- [2] Aithal P. S. & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal (2018). Patent Analysis as a New Scholarly Research Method. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT, and Education (IJCSBE)*, 2(2), 33-47. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1404184>.
- [3] Aithal, P. S. (2017). An Effective Method of Developing Business Case Studies based on Company Analysis, *International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME)*, 2(1), 16-27. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/Zenodo.400579>.
- [4] Aithal, P. S. (2017). Company Analysis – The Beginning Step for Scholarly Research. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 1(1), 1-18. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.573769>.
- [5] Björk, B. C., & Solomon, D. (2013). The publishing delay in scholarly peer-reviewed journals. *Journal of Informetrics*, 7(4), 914-923.
- [6] Chressanthis, G. A., & Chressanthis, J. (1993). Publisher monopoly power and third-degree price discrimination of scholarly journals. *Technical Services Quarterly*, 11(2), 13-36.

-
- [7] Anderson, T. (2013). Open access scholarly publications as Open Educational Resources (OER). *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 14(2), 81-95.
- [8] Yiotis, K. (2005). The open access initiative: A new paradigm for scholarly communications. *Information technology and libraries*, 24(4), 157-162.
- [9] Ramalho Correia, A. M., & Carlos Teixeira, J. (2005). Reforming scholarly publishing and knowledge communication: From the advent of the scholarly journal to the challenges of open access. *Online information review*, 29(4), 349-364.
- [10] Oppenheim, C. (2008). Electronic scholarly publishing and open access. *Journal of information*.
- [11] Bartling, S., & Friesike, S. (2014). *Opening science: The evolving guide on how the internet is changing research, collaboration and scholarly publishing*. Springer-Verlag GmbH.
- [12] Cullen, R., & Chawner, B. (2011). Institutional repositories, open access, and scholarly communication: a study of conflicting paradigms. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 37(6), 460-470.
- [13] Björk, B. C. (2011). A study of innovative features in scholarly open access journals. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 13(4), e115.
- [14] Kousha, K. (2009). Characteristics of open access scholarly publishing: a multidisciplinary study. In *Aslib Proceedings* (Vol. 61, No. 4, pp. 394-406). Emerald Group Publishing Limited.
- [15] Beall, J. (2010). Predatory open-access scholarly publishers. *The Charleston Advisor*, 11(4), 10-17.
- [16] Beall, J. (2012). Predatory publishers are corrupting open access. *Nature News*, 489(7415), 179.
- [17] Beall, J. (2013). Unethical practices in scholarly, open-access publishing. *Journal of Information Ethics*, 22(1), 11.
- [18] Beall, J. (2015). Criteria for determining predatory open-access publishers. *Scholarly open access*. <https://crescent.education/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/Criteria.pdf>
- [19] Beall, J. (2016). Essential information about predatory publishers and journals. *International Higher Education*, (86), 2-3.
- [20] da Silva, J. A. T., & Tsigaris, P. (2018). What value do journal whitelists and blacklists have in academia?. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 44(6), 781-792.
- [21] Nelson, N., & Huffman, J. (2015). Predatory journals in library databases: How much should we worry?. *The serials librarian*, 69(2), 169-192.
- [22] Sompel, H. V. D., Payette, S., Erickson, J., Lagoze, C., & Warner, S. (2004). Rethinking scholarly communication: building the system that scholars deserve. *D-Lib Magazine*; 2004 [10] 9.
- [23] Aithal, P. S., and Shubhrajyotsna Aithal (2016). Scholarly Publishing : Why Smart Researcher Hesitate to Publish in/with Top Ranking Journals/Publishers,. *International*

-
- Journal of Current Research and Modern Education (IJCRME)*, 1(1), 829-845. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.62019>.
- [24] Aithal, P. S. (2017). Comparative Study of Various Research Indices used to measure quality of Research Publications. *International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research (IJAASR)*, ISSN : 2456 – 3080, 2(1), 81-89. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.569763>.
- [25] Moghaddam, G. G. (2007). Scholarly electronic journal publishing: a study comparing commercial and nonprofit/university publishers. *The Serials Librarian*, 51(3-4), 165-183.
- [26] Black, E. W. (2008). Wikipedia and academic peer review: Wikipedia as a recognised medium for scholarly publication?. *Online Information Review*, 32(1), 73-88. Rieger, O. Y. (2008).
- [27] Rieger, O. Y. (2008). Opening up institutional repositories: social construction of innovation in scholarly communication. *Journal of Electronic Publishing*, 11(3).
- [28] Ferrara, A., & Bonaccorsi, A. (2016). How robust is journal rating in Humanities and Social Sciences? Evidence from a large-scale, multi-method exercise. *Research Evaluation*, 25(3), 279-291.
- [29] Tüselmann, H., Sinkovics, R. R., & Pishchulov, G. (2015). Towards a consolidation of worldwide journal rankings—a classification using random forests and aggregate rating via data envelopment analysis. *Omega*, 51, 11-23.
- [30] Harzing, A. W., & Van Der Wal, R. (2009). A Google Scholar h-index for journals: An alternative metric to measure journal impact in economics and business. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and technology*, 60(1), 41-46.
- [31] Larivière, V., & Sugimoto, C. R. (2018). The journal impact factor: a brief history, critique, and discussion of adverse effects. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1801.08992*.
- [32] Pajić, D. (2015). On the stability of citation-based journal rankings. *Journal of Informetrics*, 9(4), 990-1006.
- [33] Harris, C. (2008). Ranking the management journals. *Journal of Scholarly Publishing*, 39(4), 373-409.
- [34] Loach, T. V., & Evans, T. S. (2015). Ranking journals using altmetrics. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1507.00451*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1507.00451>.
- [35] Over, R. (1978). Journal ranking by citation analysis: Some inconsistencies. *American Psychologist*, 33(8), 778.
- [36] Aithal, P. S. (2016). Review on Various Ideal System Models Used to Improve the Characteristics of Practical Systems. *International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research*, 1(1), 47-56. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.159749>.
- [37] Björk, B. C. (2017). Scholarly journal publishing in transition—from restricted to open access. *Electronic Markets*, 27(2), 101-109.
- [38] Loach, T. V., & Evans, T. S. (2015). Ranking journals using altmetrics. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1507.00451*.

- [39] Over, R. (1978). Journal ranking by citation analysis: Some inconsistencies. *American Psychologist*, 33(8), 778.
- [40] Osterloh, M., & Frey, B. S. (2015). Ranking games. *Evaluation review*, 39(1), 102-129.
- [41] Jacobs, J. A. (2016). Journal rankings in sociology: Using the H Index with Google Scholar. *The American Sociologist*, 47(2-3), 192-224.

Paper 2

**IMPACT OF DIGITALIZED EDUCATION ON
STUDENTS – A STUDY IN MANGALORE**

***Ms Deshel Levines Fernandes, **Mr. Gavin Abner Pinto**

*Research Scholar, Srinivas University, Mangalore
Lecturer, St.Aloysius College (Autonomous) Mangalore
deshel31@gmail.com

**Student, St.Aloysius College (Autonomous) Mangalore
gavinabner0@gmail.com

Abstract

Education plays a prominent role in the present. Over a period of time numerous changes have taken place in all the sectors including the Education sector. Eventhough the evolution of Education primarily had an open space teaching with a relationship of ‘guru-shishya’, technology has changed the Education sector and has given a different shape to this sector in terms of accessibility, convenience and affordability. Conventionally there was only a uniform method of teaching that was chalk and talk but today education is provided through various teaching aids like projector and power point presentations, video learning, online classes, social networks, other online visual platforms etc. Most of the students have benefited from the digitalization of education, but in reality is this form of education helpful for the better prospects of students? The study relating to impact of digitalized education on students is aimed at analyzing the modern processes of education and its impact on the present day students.

1.Introduction

The concept of education had a long endeavor in the past and the same is expected in future. The conventional approach towards education as known empirically and also can be factually verified has seen a gradual decline and there is a transition towards digitized forms of education today in this turbulent globalized world. Education plays a vital role in the socio – cultural sphere especially in a country like India where the Hindu sect revere Goddess Saraswati’ that is the goddess of knowledge. Also historically in the Indian context especially in south India educating children was and is still considered a sacred duty among people of all religions.

However the digitalization of education has been synonymous with the term “modernization” of education and has given opportunities for many people to monetize on this sector. While it cannot be denied that digitization of education has opened the doors to affordability and limitless access to information there seems to be a gradual decline in the perspective of education in terms of its sacredness. While in developed states the digitization of education has absorbed well in the up gradation of quality of education it also becomes important to

have a study in the developing countries that adopt similar methods. This research paper has taken Mangalore a city in India for the same. Has Digitization worked well for students in Mangalore? Read below to find out.

2.Objectives

The main objectives of this research is to ascertain the impact of digitization of education on students with reference to the city of Mangalore. Besides the above mentioned the document seeks to attain the following:

- Affordability and accessibility of education post the digital era.
- Form a blueprint for further research by students/ research scholars in the field of education.
- Ascertain satisfaction of students with the digital modes of education.
- Pose a maverick view of the weightage of value of education in the present.

3.Methodology

For the purposes of this study, data and information has been collected from primary as well as secondary sources.

Primary Data: The data was collected through questionnaire and interview. A survey was conducted among the people of Mangalore. The respondents were asked to fill the questions from the scheduled questionnaire.

Secondary Data: Information was collected through Internet, magazines, research journals and articles.

- **Sample and Sample Size**

A sample size of 100 people has been taken through random sampling method. The study has been conducted among the people of the areas without considering their qualification or profession.

4.Review of literature

G.N. Wikramanayake: In his paper Impact of Digital Technology on Education describes the process of generation, creation and acquisition of knowledge through the technology. The paper also describes how technology is used to access and apply such knowledge. The paper relates how these technologies have been used in education and its impact in general. Using examples the paper highlights some of the changes that has taken place in the Sri Lankan education sector. He highlights that Paradigm shifts in today's world have identified the Machine / Industrial era being replaced by Technology / Information era. Similarly production process has moved from Products to Knowledge, Workplace has moved from Physical to Virtual and its focus has changed from Worker to Customer. His study is with reference to Sri Lanka.

Carlo Perrotta, Laura Czerniewicz and Helen Beetham in the paper ‘The rise of the video-recorder teacher: the sociomaterial construction of an educational actor’ draws on actor-network theory and on the sociology of cultural consumption to examine the phenomenon of corporate Massive Open Online Courses. Through an analysis of texts available in the public domain, the paper argues that over a short period (between 2012 and 2013) digitisation technology became associated with the emergence of a hybrid ‘actor’: the digital video-recorder teacher. A parallel is drawn between the ‘interactive affordances’ of digital instruction and the playback and cataloguing options that have contributed to shifts in television viewing habits. The digital video-recorder teacher is described as an artefact in the service of a postmodern project of self-improvement through cultural consumption, which recruits digitisation to meet a growing demand for ‘upgrades to the self’. In the conclusion, the paper explores how the study of digital education could benefit from an interface between sociomaterial studies and the sociology of culture.

Lousie Katz: In a report published in the conversation.com titled ‘Report shows consequences of monetised education system, but does little to dispel it’, the paper considers, among other things, how universities meet international students’ perceived needs and expectations, and the role of government in regulating quality. It rightly recommends that “learning standards have a greater role” and that education agents should have a lesser one in student recruitment. Explicitly it implies profitability has become a priority and not quality in providing education.

5.Charts

1.1) Method of teaching

1.2) Digitization and skill training

1.3) Mode of Digitisation

1.4) Applications Vs Internet sites

1.5) Digitisation and accessibility

6.Body and observations

This study is mainly empirical and after having a fruitful discussion with the students there were mixed responses but with regard to certain issues the responses recorded are as under:

CONVENTIONAL VS DIGITAL METHOD OF TEACHING: Around 75% of the students were in favour of digitized modes of education and argue that such modes are more attractive

as they use more diagrams, pictures and concise sentences in power point presentations. 10% of the students/ respondents do not find any changes in both the methods. The saying “Old wine in a new bottle” is an appropriate metaphor to describe their response. However 15% of the respondents still feel that conventional methods are better since it has worked for centuries and that a nation like India is not equipped to adopt digital platforms in the field of education.(Ref: Chart 1.1)

DIGITISATION AND SKILL TRAINING : With regard to skill training a 95% of the students still feel that the kind of sphere that digitized forms of education work in Mangalore don't equip students with the appropriate skills that they need for industry and say in this respect conventional and digitized forms of education have not integrated with industry and skill requirements. 10 respondents gave the example of Tally, SAP, and computers to learn not being used in colleges. (Ref: Chart 1.2)

MODE OF DIGITISATION: Around 85% of the respondents prefer mobile phones as an electronic device as compared to computers (15%). The prime argument being that smartphones are handy and that features like notes help them to record bookmarks. Portability of smartphones here is a clear advantage as compared to desktop computers or laptops. (Ref: Chart 1.3)

APPS VS INTERNET SITES: The internet has provided accessibility of information in 2 forms direct site login and the second one being accessibility of the application where applications of the requisite site can be downloaded and the icons will appear at the desktop/home screen. Which reduces the time lag required to access the required information. Applications like INSHORTS, BYJU'S, and INVEST YADNYA were some of the popular applications recommended by the respondents. Statistically 90% of the respondents favour the applications for accessing educational material. (Ref: Chart 1.4)

DIGITISATION AND ACCESSIBILITY: 80% of the respondents feel are of the opinion that digitization of education has bridged the gap between the seekers and suppliers of knowledge as information is available in a number of sources through the internet. Even colleges today are providing their students access to certain online educational sites subscribed by the college where students can get access to a number of books from various streams by Indian as well as foreign authors. But the remaining 20% argue that India still does not have the required infrastructure required and to an extent needs more time for digitized forms of education to be accessible. The main barrier being a number of people do not have access to smartphones still and need to be educated to use them. (Ref: Chart 1.5)

DIGITISATION VS AFFORDABILITY: There is an integration and a phenomenal inclusion of the 'have not's to the 'have's' due to digitization of education. Costs due to digitization have reduced the cost of educational products and services and has brought inclusion due to massive affordability. The only barrier the researchers have found in this paper is that payment of digitized educational products and services that is the mode of payment where there is a need to get greater financial inclusion to facilitate digital payments. Some respondents have also stated that digitized forms of education have been “Perverted” by certain coaching centres and institutes have created an impression with the help of the “Mad marketing machine” that expensive tutorials are due to digitized forms of education and

teachings that institutes not offering such services are underrated institutions. Digitization also gives room for “Yellow Educational Journals and educational potboilers.”

VALUE OF EDUCATION: More than 60% of the respondents agree that the “sacred value of education” as reflected in our culture, is diminishing but also agree that the commercial value of education is rapidly increasing which is a cause of worry. As rightly put forward by George Macaulay Trevelyan “Education has produced a vast population able to read, but unable to distinguish what is worth reading.”

Based on the above findings the researchers would like to propose the inverted cone, frustum cylinder theory.

“There is a saying in school you are taught a lesson and then you are put to the test, in life you are put to the test and then you learn a lesson. The truth is that practicality is what works in life.”

Figure 2.1 – cone cylinder

Figure 2.2 – frustum

Figure 2.3-

The above 3 diagrams represent 3 different scenarios. The first represents learning through the conventional system. The second diagram shows the digitized system and the 3rd diagram represents a model that needs to be developed to have a strong skill base in industry.

Background: This theory seeks to explain how educational models really equip today’s students to face industry.

Explanation: These 3 diagrams represent 3 structures with the bottom points/ surfaces representing the foundation (life/ industry skill) and the top surfaces representing the education system.

In the first diagram the student is sent into industry after graduating with the conventional educational method. The student is in a jeopardy as he enters industry as he is ill equipped with the skills he needs to be in industry. The knowledge he has amassed in his college/ educational institution is mostly not useful and thus is funneled down as the student goes to industry. Thus it can also be said that the foundation is not strong and the structural surface on top puts massive pressure on the structure to stand still. (Refer figure 2.1)

The second structure represents the digitized education system that is the present generation students. These represent both the students who have graduated from wholly and also from quasi – digitized platforms. Here too digitization of education has to some extent broadened the knowledge and skills the students need for industry. But still the foundation is under pressure and the structure is exerting massive pressure on the respondents to stand still (Refer figure 2.2).

The first two models still prevail in society but it is important to note that these systems have failed. Empirically when the students graduating from the above 2 systems/structures admitted that 95% of the information they get from the above systems don't work in industry and they find it hard to cope up with industry requirements. Some company "Trainers" have also confessed that they have to spend massive amounts to train employees (Students who have just graduated/ freshers) as the education system is not equipped to do so. When the researchers enquired about the role of the digitized education era, they mentioned that it could have helped in skill development but has been "Perverted" by greedy education monetary capitalists with the help of the "Mad marketing machine".

The third structure represents a student who has been "learning while doing" that is learning while constantly interacting with industrialists and using digitized education platforms to update him with the latest trends. This model is still not in existence and presently there are very few students who might have been educated to be like the 3rd structure. Here the student is equipped with the necessary educational tools and skills to be applied in industry. As a result the foundation is strong and the structure stands comfortably. (Refer figure 2.3)

7. Suggestions

More than 90% of the students represent either the cone or the fructrum. To ensure that students are competitive and are trained for industry. Here are some suggestions to have improvements in digitized forms of education:

- New products like Educational games based on industry can be a great source of learning. Example – the cash flow game at www.richdad.com
- Conventional systems need to be more evolved to make education interesting. Digitized platforms and not curriculum in digitized platforms ought to be used to see growth in skill in India.
- Establishment of new digital training centres.
- Models and curriculum offered by certain digitized education platformssuch as simplus financial consultants and investyadnya academy can train students for the industry to an extent.

8. Conclusions

- Digitised forms of education have outperformed conventioanl methods.
- There needs to be safeguards in digitised forms of education from the mad marketing machine.
- Governments need to come up with legislations to encourage educational institutions to develop models like the "cylinder structure" as mentioaned above.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Digital_learning
2. <https://elearningindustry.com/digitization-of-education-21st-century>
3. <https://gosa.georgia.gov/what-digital-learning>
4. <http://www.forbesindia.com/blog/education/digital-education-among-students-in-rural-areas>
5. <https://www.indiatoday.in/education-today/featurephilia/story/digitisation-education-1045356-2017-09-18>
6. <https://www.mapsofindia.com/my-india/india/digital-education-in-india-and-classroom-teaching-advantages-and-disadvantages>
7. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/216361364_Impact_of_Digital_Technology_on_Education
8. <http://theconversation.com/report-shows-consequences-of-monetised-education-system-but-does-little-to-dispel-it-41179>

Paper 3

**A STUDY ON REINVENTION AND CHALLENGES OF
IBM****Kiran Raj K. M¹ & Krishna Prasad K²**¹Research Scholar College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India²College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India
E-mail: kiranraj224@gmail.com**Abstract**

International Business Machine Corporation (IBM) is one of the first multinational conglomerates to emerge in the US-headquartered in Armonk, New York. IBM was established in 1911 in Endicott, New York, as Computing-Tabulating-Recording Company (CTR). In 1924, CTR was renamed IBM. Big Blue has been IBM's nickname since 1980. IBM started with the production of scales, punch cards, data processors and time clock now produce and sells computer hardware and software, middleware, provides hosting and consulting services. It has a worldwide presence, operating in over 175 nations with 3,50,600 staff with \$79.6 billion in annual income (Dec 2018). It is currently competing with Microsoft, Google, Apple, and Amazon. 2012 to 2017 was tough time for IBM, although it invests in the field of research where it faced challenges while trying to stay relevant in rapidly changing Tech-Market. While 2018 has been relatively better and attempting to regain its place in the IT industry. With 3,000 scientists, it invests 7% of its total revenue to Research & Development in 12 laboratories across 6 continents. This resulted in the U.S. patent leadership in IBM's 26th consecutive year. In 2018, out of the 9,100 patents that granted to IBM 1600 were related to Artificial Intelligence and 1,400 related to cyber-security. In artificial intelligence, blockchain, safety/security, cloud technology, nano-technology, quantum computing, silicon, and post-silicon computing architecture IBM researchers are doing pioneering job. In this paper, we will discuss Global Market, Strategies, Services, Contribution to Research, Social Responsibility, and Finance.

Keywords: IBM, Computing-Tabulating-Recording, Big Blue, Reinvention, Challenges.

1. INTRODUCTION

Over a whole century, IBM has developed into a worldwide incorporated company from a small business which manufactures scales, time clocks & tabulations. IBM is a multinational conglomerate company based in the United States founded by Ranlett Flint and Thomas J. Watson currently Virginia M. Rometty as the current Chairman, President and CEO [1]. Established in Endicott, New York in June 1911, by the consolidation of three companies, the Tabulating Machine Company, the International Time Recording Company and the Computing Scale Company, as a

new company known as the Computing-Tabulating-Recording Company (CTR). CTR was renamed International Business Machine Corporation in 1924.

Headquarters moved to Armonk, New York, in the next few years. It was subsequently renamed IBM. It plays a major role in medical science, data technology, electronics, communication and mechanical systems innovation and growth. It is not limited to one specific sector and is engaged with the implementation of high-end technology in every prominent sector. Although it grew steadily, in the past eight to ten years it confronted its problems. IBM's 2018 income and operating income of \$79.6 billion per share amounted to \$13.81 [2]. For the entire year we returned to sales development, income per share increased and margins were stabilized even though it has competitions from Microsoft, Google, Apple, Amazon and many more. Nicknamed as "Big Blue," IBM is one of 30 Dow Jones industry average firms with over 350,600 staff and is one of the world's largest companies, known as "IBMers." There are at least 70% of IBMers outside the U.S. and India has the highest IBMers. IBM's staff won five Nobel Prizes, six Turing Awards, ten National Technology Medals(USA) and five National Science Medals (USA) for their contribution [3].

2. PRODUCTS AND MILESTONES

In order to develop in different fields, IBM manufactured numerous products and innovation. Trust in science, pursuit of understanding and belief in making worldfunction better together.

- **1928: U.S. Census and Punch Card.** It has been used as storage instruments and it has enabled a U.S. census.
- **1932: The IBM Service Bureau** is set up to support businesses that do not permit IBM machines to be purchased. It helped many small companies
- **1936: IBM enables social security.** IBM cooperates with the state to draw up records of 26 million Americans on the US Social Security Act of 1935.
- **1937: International Test Scoring Machine IBM Type 805** gave way to familiar test sheets of fill-in the bubble.
- **1952: Digital storage** start-up. IBM enables magnetic tape to become a feasible data storage device that introduces the concept of digital storage to the globe.
- **1953: The world's first effective open-heart surgery** on a person was done by **the first heart and lung machinery.**
- **1956: First IBM 704 self-study program.** The notion of artificial intelligence is regarded as the first demonstration.
- **1957: FORTRAN** opens the door to modern information technology..
- **1961: The launching of speech recognition device *Shoebox*.**
- **1962: SABRE: ecommerce's genesis.** The first computer-driven airline booking scheme is launched by IBM and American Airlines..
- **1969: IBM constructs PC's** and writes many of the complicated **Apollo mission software programmes.**
- **1970: The Magnetic swipe strip.** The start of IBM's magnetic credit card swipe strip changes the way business is done.

- **1971: The world's first floppy disc.** First portable, affordable, powerful Storage device is created.
- **1973: The Universal Product Code.** UPC is 12 digit number given to particular product. Because of it business sector rapidly changed since we can track every orders.
- **1980: IBM patents LASIK surgery.** They can write on human hair with lasers very accurate. LASIK surgery is improving sight and quality of life for millions of individuals not only in the matter of quality but it is also cost efficient and time efficient in nature.
- **1981: IBM PC** introduction. The PC revolution starts with IBM Personal Computer's debut, the most economical and smallest computer ever.
- **1986:** The Nobel prize is awarded to **scanning tunnel microscopes** that are ultimately used in manipulating nuclear energy
- **1997: IBM Deep Blue** a supercomputer which used the Artificial Intelligence and defeated the champion in the field of chess
- **2011: first liquid language comprehension AI.** Jeopardy, the champion of TV-quiz! **IBM Watson** is derided. In his unprecedented demonstration of natural voice recognition and cognitive computation, Watson rightly acknowledges and responds to colloquialism, jokes and sarcasm. Transactions are implemented.
- **2018: The Summit of supercomputing.** Summit is a supercomputer which is present at Oak Ridge National laboratories created with Integration of Artificial Intelligence for the purpose to support all the technologies reaches speeds of 200 petaflops [4].

3. FINANCIALS

We will be using financial statements and annual report to analyze company's status. In the table contains the financial statement (Revenue and Net Income) and Number of Employees from 2014-2018 [2][5][6]. IBMs annual revenue is took a huge dip from 2014-2016 because of it brand value was also decreased. IBM has seen decreased profits and revenue is therefore attempting to restructure its company model, which could partially explain how present staff is decreasing. In 2018, the American technology firm IBM employed about 350, 600 individuals around the globe, and over the previous six years there has been a general downward trend of staff[2]. IBM has faced a class action suit since early 2019 claiming that it breaches federal legislation against age discrimination while IBM maintains that it takes skills-based choices in its jobs. In the economic areas, fiscal 2018, Q1 and Q2 2019 are a bit better, with the trend slowly stabilizing and rebounding. IBM is acquiring / merging with different companies of different size in different field so that it can use their market and can have strong foot in different field. In 2018, IBM has acquired Red Hat with U.S. \$34 million which has prominent in field of cloud and open source. A numbers of drastic steps were required to decrease the loss business, such as decreasing the amount of staff, financing research areas etc. From the table given we can see the decrease in Revenue, Net Income, and Number of Employees etc. Revenues of U.S. \$18.2 billion and U.S. \$19.2 billion respectively were generated in the first and second quarters of 2019 [7] [8]. With a total of U.S. \$37.4 billion in two quarters, with enormous contribution from field of cloud and cognitive software.

Table 1: Revenue, Net Income, Employees With respect to Year [2] [5] [6]

Year	Revenue (in mil. \$ U.S.)	Net Income (in mil. \$ U.S.)	No. of Employees
2014	92793	12022	379592
2015	81741	13190	377757
2016	79919	38294	380300
2017	79139	36943	366600
2018	79591	36936	350600

4. IBM CLOUD GARAGE

Cloud computing is about the use of remote server networks in data storage, administration and processing. Recently most of the software / applications are shifting from data centers to cloud because of its ease of use and low maintaining cost. Cloud computing produces billions of dollars annually in income as a section of IT services and shows little sign of a slowdown. In 2017, public cloud market share was U.S. \$146 Billion in 2019 market grown by 17.5% with cloud data center ip traffic growth of 10.6ZB/yr. in 2018 [9].

IBM cloud has very little Public Cloud market share but it is better in private and hybrid clouds and it is expected to grow since people are shifting from public cloud to private and hybrid cloud. Although it is very late in entering the cloud market and faces strong competitions from giants like Amazon, Alibaba, Microsoft and Google it is striving hard to do better. IBM generated about \$1.14 billion in income from its hosting of true private cloud services in 2017, making it a market share of around 12% more than other true private cloud providers [10]. In 2018 and 2019, cloud and cognitive software is a major contributor to the stabilization of IBM. In the 1st and 2nd Quarter, cloud and cognitive software contributed \$5.0 billion and \$5.6 billion [7][8]. In 2018, Red Hat Company was bought for U.S. \$34 million, a company which is well known for open source and cloud services, and is therefore expected to do better [11]. IBM uses a cloud garage technique to enhance customer services where workshops are conducted so that client can take advantage of it.

As mentioned in the fig1 IBM cloud garage is mainly made up of Themes, workflows, and practices which cover the entire lifecycle of software delivery from start to finish, including the collection and response of client feedback and changing markets [12]. Different customer may require cloud with different functionality and architecture which they can fully utilize. In IBM garage clients will be helped by the business model which is

currently in use and experts so that they can create and implement their own architecture. This will be specific and unique to them.

Themes: Following prescriptive pathways for Cloud transformation goals: Advise, Build, Move, and Manage.

Workflows: Practice procedures from beginning to end in order to achieve goal.

Practices: Culture, Discover, Envision, Develop, Reason, Operate, and Learn.

Fig 1: IBM Cloud Garage [12]

5. SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESEARCH

5.1. Research

IBM is one of the companies which contribute hugely on Research so that it can innovate new ideas, products and be responsible for the development of society. It utilizes 7% of Total Revenue for Research and Development. But since they are going through rough patch for the financial contribution was decreased in fiscal year 2018. The Group has employed 3,000 scientists/researchers in 12 laboratories on six continents, working in the areas of Artificial Intelligence, Quantum Computing, Block-Chain, Safety/Security, Cloud Computing, Nanotechnology, Silicon & post-Silicon Computing Architecture mainly concentrates in the field of Financial Services, Health Care, Internet of Things and Block-Chain. As a result of its contribution to Research and Development produced more than 100000 patents since 1993. For the consecutive 26 years it is leading in number of patents. In 2018, IBM was awarded with 9,100 patents out of which 3,000 belong to the field of AI, Cloud, Cyber Security, Quantum Computing. Different techniques / fields are made to combine so that clients can achieve maximum results and boundary between fields can be broken [2] [5] [6].

5.2. Social Responsibilities

IBM is one of the biggest companies of the century and generates \$79 billion in total revenue in 2018. It never forgets its social responsibility, recognizes its worldwide significance fully and continually contributes to society. Some of them are listed below

IBM is Founding member of “Call for Code” in 2018. Where more than 100,000 developers from 156 countries globally competed. They have built over 2500 applications with IBM Cloud technology to reduce impact of natural disaster.

In order to avoid illegal human trading a by using analytical software, IBM has entered a pact with "STOP THE TRAFFIK" Law Enforcement and Financial Services Institution, which recognizes suspected patterns, hotspots, and financial transactions. It has also introduced

"**AI Fairness 360**", an open source toolkit to help designers actively detect and reduce deformation and misrepresentations of information sets because of Artificial Intelligence.

It also has 12 months training program in the field of education, including cyber security, digital design, mainframe administration and software development, through the implementation of the "**IBM Apprenticeship Program**". The program has included training and online work experience, guided by an IBM mentor, led by hundreds of apprentices. Stated **Skills Build an IBM voluntary** initiative that allows more than 3 million students to know about new and advanced technology in primary and secondary schools. Early College High School in 200 colleges with over 125,000 in 13 nations in the 11 U.S. States, "**Pathways to technology (P-TECH)**". It also conducts workshops regularly. It is also took the initiative to train people with disability so they can work in IT company without any difficulty [2].

IBM is working with many Government Institutions where it is helping them in the field of data security and improves the skills of officials by periodic training. In 2018 IBMers spent 1.3 M hrs as volunteer and donated \$24 Million [13].

6. REINVENTIONS

IBM is facing the rough patch in last 8 years, and it is just trying to stabilize itself. As a result it is also trying to take some of the drastic steps. Number of Employees currently working at IBM has been continuously decreasing from year 2017 so that they will not have huge burden. Since it was using enormous amount of money on research since past decade the new research work are starting to take shape. Company is also hoping because of the new products which will be concentrating on Artificial Intelligence, Quantum Computing, Blockchain, Security, Cloud Technology will be able to take back the market.

6.1. Integrated Solutions

IBM has been engaged in various technologies such as cloud, AI, security etc. IBM therefore provides its customers embedded alternatives and products to use other technologies. Since it is working in different fields transition or integrating solutions is pretty easy. The end product will also have benefits since it contains characteristics of many techniques.

6.2. Strategic Business Units

IBM is spreading out on wide categories of projects that have helped the business focus and to compete with its strong competitors as well as keeping ahead of them. They are present in different fields they can identify the business opportunity very quickly and since they are working in different fields combining of solutions will be also very easy.

6.3. Migration to Higher Technology

IBM is doing the researches on new technology like AI, Cloud, Security, Blockchain for a very long time so shifting to higher technology will not be a problem to them. Shifting to new technologies has attracted many customers.

6.4. Data Analytics

Increasing IBM capacity in data analytics has invested over U.S. \$30 billion i.e. One third of their research expenditure relates to data analysis and cognitive computing [14].

7. CHALLENGES

7.1. Differentiating its Hardware from Rivals

IBM has many competitors like Dell, Intel etc. who are making the similar products. So it is unable to make its customer differentiate between them. When the hardware is not brought by the customers Software's which is coming together it will also not be brought.

7.2. Dip in Global Technology / Business Services

Hosting and consulting services are provided by IBM. There is enormous competition from many companies offering the same sort of services. Global technology and business services revenues decreased by 10% in 2018. Cloud rivalry is also enormous, even if the private and hybrid IBM cloud has been doing better; it was late for market access.

7.3. Data Privacy

Since it is working on cloud and data analytics it will be dealing with huge amount of data. And obviously customers will be having doubts about the security of the Data.

8. SWOT ANALYSIS

To be able to understand how the business operates in the market so that we can concentrate on companies strengths, the weakness of our business in this area or we can work on them and weakness can be changed into opportunity or strength, the opportunity for us to understand which products or type we need so that we can focus on particular area of industry at the same time and utilize it. The threat of knowing factors which will cause harm to the company so that they can be avoided. SWOT analysis is used to comprehend inner and external product or company influencing factors and how can they used in our advantage.

8.1. Strengths

- **Brand Strengths:** In 2018, IBM was at 12th Place. The brand was decreased by 8% and value was U.S \$42.97 Billion with top performing factors commitment, Responsiveness and consistency [15].
- **Business Model:** IBM focuses on long term growth strategy. It focuses on innovation, efficiency, competitiveness so that it will be able to provide long term advantages.
- **Being Updated:** IBM is keeping on changing regularly with technology so that it can keep up with demands of the world. It acquires company which is doing well and uses new technology like AI, Cloud, Blockchain etc. Recently it has acquired Red Hat for U.S. \$34Million.

- **Data Analytics:** IBM deals with data analysis and cognitive computing, it realizes the importance of it and allocates more or less one-third of its Research and Development budget.
- **Middleware Market:** IBM is leading the middleware market with 30% market share. The application infrastructure middleware market was valued at USD 29.38 billion in 2018 and is expected to reach a value of USD 44.54 billion by 2024 [16],
- **Research and Development:** IBM has committed R&D facility with 12 labs across 6 continents. It is providing 7% of its total revenue to Research where it working in new technologies like AI, Cloud, Blockchain, Security etc [2].

8.2. Weakness

- **Brand Value Drop:** In the last 5-8 years IBM is going through rough patch where its total revenue decreased as a result brand value also took its hit.
- **Litigations:** IBM has been continuously involved in litigations and disputes which in turn decreases brand value. This will be also responsible in decreasing faith in company.
- **Analysis:** Since IBM is a multinational company which works in most of the fields analyzing, finding problem and solution becomes difficult.

8.3. Opportunities:

- **Data Analytics:** The assessment of Data analytics market is \$125 billion. IBM is investing U.S. \$1 billion in Watson, \$100 million for start-ups building cognitive applications. It also integrates with Twitter into the cloud-based analytics of IBM.
- **Cloud-Based Solutions:** Cloud computing services demand is increasing and is set to reach over \$1.9 billion by 2018. Public cloud services are expected to expand at 33%. IBM is doing well in Private and Hybrid Cloud.
- **Business Expansion:** The Company has purchased 23 mobile, social and security-based companies. IBM and Apple have partnered for easy-to-use private applications in the business setting. The company's activities can be expanded.
- **Consulting Business:** Even though IBM consulting business has been decreased by 10%. IBM is expecting to invest in consulting business by seeing its opportunity.

8.4. Threats

- **Competition:** Since IBM is involved in different fields it has more competitors. In cloud it has the competitors like Amazon, Google, Microsoft, Alibaba etc. In Technology with HP, Dell, Intel, EMC, Cisco Systems etc. In software business with Oracle, SAP, CA etc. some other companies are Accenture, Xerox, CSC, Fujitsu, Infosys and Wipro etc.
- **Global Economy:** In the face of global turbulence, the multinational company must ensure that prices of raw materials, labor, shipments etc. remain inspected to ensure competitive pricing. This also changes the currency that can influence its income and income per share [17].

9. CONCLUSION

In the past eight years, IBM remains one of the best multinationals with an extremely strong reputation and social engagement. Its annual revenue may have fallen but still retains profit by taking some dramatic steps with a slight deviation. In 2019, IBM decided to evaluate its trimester development so that it could make clear progress and take action against adverse events. As the

trend moves from the public cloud to the private cloud where IBM is doing better, it will develop more rapidly. IBM's cloud garage technique helps the client with the assistance of mentors / company specialists to create better product. IBM also helps researchers move to greater technology, which attracts more clients. It is feasible to produce better and more effective products by integrating between distinct techniques.

REFERENCES

- [1]. SuccessStory. (2018). *Ibm successstory*. Retrieved on August 5, 2019. from <https://successstory.com/companies/ibm>
- [2]. Ibm. (2019, January 22). *2018 Annual report Ibm*. U.s.a. Retrieved on July 30, 2019. From https://www.ibm.com/annualreport/assets/downloads/IBM_Annual_Report_2018.pdf
- [3]. Wikipedia contributors. (2019, August 23). IBM. In *Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia*. Retrieved on July 31, 2019 from <https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=IBM&oldid=912119908>
- [4]. Ibm. (2019). *Ibm. Iconic moments in Ibm history*. Retrieved on August 7, 2019. From <https://www.ibm.com/ibm/us/en/>
- [5]. Ibm. (2018, January 18). *2017 Annual report Ibm*. U.s.a. Retrieved on July 31, 2019. From https://www.ibm.com/investor/att/pdf/IBM_Annual_Report_2017.pdf
- [6]. Ibm. (2017, January 19). *2016 Annual report Ibm*. U.s.a. Retrieved on July 31, 2019. From https://www.ibm.com/investor/att/pdf/IBM_Annual_Report_2016.pdf
- [7]. Ibm (2019, April 16) *IBM REPORTS 2019 FIRST-QUARTER RESULTS*. Armonk, N.Y. Retrieved on August 8, 2019. from <https://www.ibm.com/investor/att/pdf/IBM-1Q19-Earnings-Press-Release.pdf>
- [8]. Ibm. (2019, July 17). *IBM REPORTS 2019 SECOND-QUARTER RESULTS*, Armonk, N.Y. Retrieved on August 8, 2019. From <https://www.ibm.com/investor/att/pdf/IBM-2Q19-Earnings-Press-Release.pdf>
- [9]. Liu, S. (2019, April 1). *Cloud Computing - Statistics & Facts*. 1–7.
- [10]. Liu, S.,(2018, September 27). *Hosted true private cloud (TPC) vendor market share worldwide in 2017 - Statistics & Facts*
- [11]. Wikipedia contributors. (2019, August 9). *List of mergers and acquisitions by IBM*. In *Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia*. Retrieved on August 9, 2019. from https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=List_of_mergers_and_acquisitions_by_IBM&oldid=910080445
- [12]. Collins, B. (2017). *Field Guide. Questions about angels*, 44–44. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctt9qh75r.23>
- [13]. Ibm. (2019). *Ibm, Our Impact*. Retrieved on August 15, 2019. From <https://www.ibm.org/>
- [14]. Bhasin H. (2018, September 3). *Marketing Strategy of IBM – IBM Marketing Strategy*. Marketing91. Retrieved on August 8, 2019. from <https://www.marketing91.com/marketing-strategy-ibm/>

- [15]. Interbrand. (2019). *Ibm rankings 2018*. Interbrand. Retrieved on August 19, 2019. From <https://www.marketing91.com/marketing-strategy-ibm/>
- [16]. Mordor Intelligence. (2019). *Application infrastructure Middleware market - growth, trends, and forecast (2019 -2024)*. Retrieved on August 20, 2019. from <https://www.mordorintelligence.com/industry-reports/middleware-market>
- [17]. Bhasin H. (2019, January 13). *Swot Analysis of IBM*. Marketing91. Retrieved on August 20, 2019. from <https://www.marketing91.com/swot-analysis-ibm/>

Paper 4

DIGITAL SERVICE INNOVATION USING ICCT UNDERLYING TECHNOLOGIES

Dr. P. S. Aithal^{1*}, & Dr. Shubhrajyotsna Aithal²

¹Professor, College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore – 575 001,
India

E-mail : psaithal@gmail.com

²Faculty, College of Engineering & Technology, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

E-mail : shubhraaithal@gmail.com

Abstract

Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT) is considered as a general purpose universal technology due to its ability to address many problems in the human society related to basic needs, advanced wants, and dreamy desires. In this chapter, initially, various quality attributes of Digital Service are determined. The important underlying technologies of ICCT which are emerging as technologies of 21st century including Artificial intelligence & robotics, Big data & business analytics, Blockchain technology, Cloud computing & storage, Digital marketing, 3D printing, Internet of Things, Online ubiquitous education, Optical computing, Information storage technology, and Virtual & Augmented Reality are considered for possible innovations in service industries. The applications of ICCT underlying technologies in some of the prominent service industry sectors are identified and the management of ICCT underlying technology usage strategies for digital service innovation in tertiary sector industries are predicted and analysed.

Keywords : ICCT, Digital technologies, Universal technology, Digital service innovation, Tertiary industry sector.

1. INTRODUCTION :

1.1 Business & Technology:

Business is defined as an act of doing anything with profit motivation is considered as business. Profit may be tangible or intangible based on some kind of resources which include, money, material, machine, men, information, or time. All business organizations are profit motivated and have the objective of earning long term sustainable profit. Business entities are divided into four types of industry sectors called the primary industry sector, secondary industry sector, tertiary industry sector, and quaternary industry sector. Primary industry sector consists of business entities which produce raw materials for secondary industry sectors like agricultural industry, mining industry, fisheries industry, etc. Secondary industry sector converts raw materials into finished tangible products called goods and is includes all manufacturing industries like food processing, automobiles, cement, steel, computer hardware, Electronic devices, etc. Tertiary industry sector consists of all services industries which provide intangible services to the customers like banking, insurance, tourism, education, healthcare, legal services, etc. Quaternary industry sector consists of supporting services to all other three types of industry sectors which include information technology services, research & development, business consulting, etc. Doing business in the society can

be influenced by various things but adopting technology in business and managing it effectively increases the productivity, efficiency, and hence the profit from the business. Technology is an application of science in a systematic way to solve many complicated challenges in society to make human life comfortable and happy. Some of the technologies have developed and expanded to many areas as branches in such a way that they have been considered as General-Purpose Technologies. Such general purpose technologies are identified and used in many industries to do business and to solve or simplify the problems of industries. General Purpose Technologies' (GPT) show a special character named pervasiveness with an inherent potential for improvements, both for technical and innovation complementarities, and through innovative research and development, the productivity of industry sectors can be increased [1].

A general-purpose technology or GPT is a term coined to describe a new method of producing and inventing that is important enough to have a protracted aggregate impact. Electricity and information technology (IT) probably are the two most important GPTs until the 20th century. A GPT can be a product, a process, technology or an organisational system. Whole eras of technical progress and growth appear to be driven by a few 'General Purpose Technologies' (GPT's), such as the steam engine, the electric motor, and semiconductors. GPT's are characterized by pervasiveness to many sectors, inherent potential for technical improvements, and innovation complementarities to many applications, giving rise to increasing scale of operation. Economist Richard Lipsey and Kenneth Carlaw [2] suggested that there have only been 24 technologies in history that have been identified as true GPTs. They define a transforming GPT follows four criteria which are listed below [3]:

- (1) GPT is a single, recognizable generic technology.
- (2) Initially, GPT has much scope for improvement but comes to be widely used across the economy.
- (3) GPT has many different uses in many areas to solve problems or to provide comfortability.
- (4) GPT creates many spill-over effects to spread its base to many sectors.

General purpose technologies have the potential to reshape the economy of the world and boost productivity across all sectors and industries. Such transformations are far more than simple technical innovation, or a new discovery. However, such technologies often require a wholesale remaking of infrastructure environments, of business models, and of cultural norms. There are three fundamental features of GPTs that differentiate them from other technologies which are (1) Pervasiveness, (2) Improvement, and (3) Innovation spawning. Most technologies show many of these characteristics to some degree, and hence a GPT cannot differ qualitatively from other technologies [1].

A new research method called Ideal System analysis is developed based on identifying the research gap by comparing present characteristics and ideal characteristics of a system [4]. An ideal system is a system which shows ideal characteristics i.e., perfect in every aspect. An ideal system is what the mind of a human being pictures as being perfect. The characteristics of the real system can be compared and improved towards the characteristics of an ideal system by means of research and innovation. Accordingly, the ideal business model is developed to specify the ideal characteristics of business under input characteristics, output characteristics, system requirement, market conditions, and are can be explained based on their effectiveness in improving the revenue and creating value to the stakeholders [5]. Similarly, an ideal technology is defined as a technology with ideal characteristics with the capability to solve all problems of human beings under both basic needs and advanced wants

to provide comfortable living and to realize their needs, wants and dreams. By considering various factors which decide the ideal technology system characteristics, a systematic model consisting of input conditions, output conditions, environmental conditions, and system requirements are identified and analyzed [6].

1.2 Service as Intangible Product /Asset of Service Industries :

Companies in the service industry provide professional work called service performed in an expert manner by an individual or team for the benefit of its customers. The typical service business provides intangible products, such as accounting, banking, education, insurance, health treatment, transportation services, computer services, restaurants, tourism, etc.

The service industries can be innovative and quality and other related attributes of services can be improved to satisfy the service providers and end consumers by means of using a new business method or by means of new technology. Information Communication & Computation Technology (ICCT) is one kind of general purpose universal technology for the 21st Century which can be used to innovate services of the service industry. ICCT is used as digital technology in the services industry sector to provide and enhance values of various services offered in business management in the society. The attributes of service like method, quality, accuracy, timeliness, efficiency, effectiveness of various services provided are affecting the business management of service industry organizations.

Table 1 : Various attributes used to evaluate service quality in the business field

S. No.	Attributes	Type	Explanation
1	Content	Intangible	Content of the service is the useful information contained in the service to the user.
2	Method	Intangible	Method of a service is the procedure to adopt the service by the user.
3	Quality	Intangible	Quality of service is a description or measurement of the overall performance of service.
4	Accuracy	Intangible	Accuracy of a service implies how close a measurement comes to its true value.
5	Timeliness	Intangible	Availability and accessibility of service in time to get the full benefit of the service by the customers.
6	Frequency	Intangible	Number of times the service is provided to the user during a given period of time.
7	Speed	Intangible	How quick the service is reachable to the end user.
8	Reliability	Intangible	Ability to perform expected objective for a given time period and to meet the expectation of the customers.

1.3 Digital Service :

Digital service is an automated service delivered using digital technologies via the internet, or an electronic communication network. Digital service is usually automated and its supply involves only minimal human intervention. The essential characteristics of digital service include [7-9] : (1) intangibility, (2) high technology, (3) invariance, and (4) scalability. The efficiency and the effectiveness of digital service are measured using many attributes in addition to attributes of a service. These quality attributes of digital service are determined

using focus group method [10] and are listed in table 1, which include : Safe & Secure, Ubiquitous, Simple & Easy, Customizable, Flexibility, Adaptability, Reusability, and Innovability as shown in figure 1.

Fig. 1 : Block diagram representing the various quality attributes of Digital Service.

- (1) **Safe & Secure :** Services which are developed using digital technology should be safe to use at development and usage stage for the provider and the consumer respectively so that fearless usage is expected. Further, the services developed using digital technology should protect the data and information, as well as the consequence benefits of the service, should be secured for considerably long time.
- (2) **Ubiquitous :** Offering the service and availing the service anywhere globally, at any time throughout the day, and any amount of time continuously.
- (3) **Simple & Easy :** Need simple and easy processes to communicate, offer, and use the service by everyone without implementation & understanding difficulty.
- (4) **Customizable :** Ability to adapt to any system by making suitable changes, or ability to adapt to any customer for their variable environment and variable background.
- (5) **Flexibility :** Digital service offered electronically can be stored and retrieved at any time and it can be used or processed online or periodically depending on the end users comfortability. Thus the flexibility of digital services offers anytime, anywhere, and any amount of time usage opportunity. Further, such services are flexible in terms of processing further at any stage to add value.
- (6) **Adaptability :** It is the ability of digital service to withstand, to sustain, and to respond to the demands and changes of the moment. When the applications change, the service with the strength of Adaptability easily adapts and changes like flexibility.
- (7) **Reusability :** Digital services are reusable platforms typically contains extra functionality that could be reused in future requirements. This encourages digital services due to their extra capabilities built around possible future service usage scenarios.
- (8) **Innovability :** Innovability is an ability of a service to adopt innovation either through (i) improvements in the processes of the service leading to new service model or (ii) improvements in technology adopted in the service & its delivery leading to a radical change in the quality of the service.

1.4 Digital Service Innovation :

A digital service innovation benefits for both the service providers and service receivers called customers and it improves the competitive edge of the service provider. Digital service innovation is an effort of adding novelty in the existing process of a service product or service process that is based on usage of some digital technology systematically for the enhanced comfortability of the customers and business providers. Innovation is a culture of adding value to an existing system by means of creative thinking and it leads to adding further economic and social value in terms of its users and by doing so, it generates new or improved products, services, or processes. Many researchers working on various aspects of digital service innovation and some of the important scholarly publications are reviewed and listed in table 2.

Table 2 : Some of the related works in digital service innovation

S. No.	Issues on Digital Service Innovation	Focus	Reference
1	Service innovation in the digital age	key contributions and future directions	Barrett, M., (2015) [11]
2	Digital innovation strategy	A framework for diagnosing and improving digital product and service innovation.	Nylén, D., (2015) [12]
3	Information technology and product/service innovation	A brief assessment and some suggestions for future research	Nambisan, S. (2013) [13]
4	Exploring digital service innovation process	Innovation process through value creation	Häikiö, J. (2016) [14]
5	Service innovation	Disruptive digital innovation	Agarwal, R. et al. (2015). [15]
6	Service sector innovation	Understanding service sector innovation	Sheehan, J. (2006) [16]
7	IT-related service innovation	Signs and practices as resources	Löbler, H., et al. (2014) [17]
8	Product–service innovation and performance	The role of collaborative partnerships and R&D intensity	Bustinza, O. F. et al. [2019] [18]
9	Digital public service innovation	Framework proposal	Bertot, J. C., et al. (2016) [19]
10	Disruptive innovation in health care delivery	A framework for business-model innovation	Hwang, J., et al. (2008) [20]
11	Flexible generification:	ICT standardization strategies and service innovation	Hanseth, O., (2015). [21]
12	Service chain management	Technology innovation for the service business	Voudouris, C., (2007). [22]
13	Incremental and radical innovation	Design research vs. technology and meaning change	Norman, D. A., (2014). [23]
14	Digital business innovation	Trends and challenges in digital business innovation	Morabito, V. (2014). [24]
15	ICT based service innovation	A challenge for project	Bygstad, B., (2009).

		management	[25]
16	Innovation as the core competency of a service organisation	The role of technology, knowledge and networks	Kandampully, J. (2002). [26]
17	Key service innovation drivers in the tourism sector	Empirical evidence and managerial implications	Jiménez-Zarco, et al (2011). [27]
18	How big data analytics enables service innovation	materiality, affordance, and the individualization of service	Lehrer, C., et al. (2018). [28]
19	Service innovation	Using the Internet of things	Xu, X. (2012). [29]
20	Shaping, organizing and rethinking service innovation	A multidimensional framework	Rubalcaba, L., et al. (2012). [30]
21	Innovation and regulation in the digital age	A call for new perspectives	Benghozi, P. J., (2009). [31]

It is observed that service innovation is possible in major two ways which include service model based innovation and technology based innovation. Service model innovation includes providing new model using new processes to offer a service from an organization or service provider to end customers. Technology based service innovation uses digital signal based Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT) which is also called digital technologies. In this paper, we discussed the progress in digital technologies and how they can contribute to the digital services innovation and add value to them from both service provider and service receiver points of view.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE CHAPTER :

The chapter discusses the concept of using various prominent ICCT underlying technologies in the process of innovation of digital products of various sectors of the service industry. Being explorative research in nature, the chapter focuses on the following objectives :

- (1) To know various attributes used to evaluate service quality in the business models
- (2) To find quality attributes of digital service using the focus group method.
- (3) To identify important underlying technologies of ICCT which are emerging as technologies of the 21st century and useful for digital services innovation.
- (4) To discuss the applications of ICCT underlying technologies in some of the prominent service industry sectors.

3. ICCT UNDERLYING TECHNOLOGIES & THEIR IMPORTANCE :

In history, many killer applications technologies were invented which were found to be initially less productive and costly but eventually grown as General Purpose Technologies (GPTs). There are many GPTs identified which include the wheel, steam engine, railroad, electricity, semiconductor electronics, automobile, computer, Internet, mobile phones, Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT), Nanotechnology (NT), etc. Recently, based on the analysis, it is found that two general purpose technologies viz. ICCT & NT are capable solve many problems of the society especially related to problems of basic needs, problems of advance wants, and problems on dreamy desires of a human being in the society and renamed as Universal Technologies [3]. ICCT, being a digital signal based technology, is responsible for information generation, communication, processing, storing,

and retrieval and represents a single unified technology called Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT). ICCT is a combined version of Information Communication Technology (ICT) and Computer Technology (CT). In the 21st century, ICCT is grown and spread its roots from primary to tertiary sectors due to its pervasiveness, growth, and innovation opportunity properties [32-33]. The Improvement and Innovation spawning properties of ICCT is capable to innovate many services offered by service industries and hence capable & qualified to be called as universal technology. As time progress, during the 21st century, ICCT has created many underlying technologies which were further developed as independent technologies under the umbrella of ICCT as universal technology. The important ICCT underlying technologies which offer general purpose technology characteristics including pervasiveness, growth oriented, and innovation opportunity and hence have potential to make digital service innovations to a high extent are listed in table 3.

Table 3 : ICCT underlying technologies, their objectives, and ultimate goal

S. No	Underlying Technologies of ICCT	Objectives	Ultimate Goal
1	Artificial Intelligence Technology	Performing by thinking and doing things better than human beings	Ideal artificial brain & connecting brains with computers
2	Big data and Business Analytics	Developing effective information using hidden patterns, unknown correlations, market trends, and customer preferences to help organizations for making better business decisions	Ideal Business prediction [5]
3	Blockchain Technology	Blockchain consists of a growing list of records which are linked using cryptography and such chain has the property of transparency, decentralization, and immune to modifications	Ideal blockchain is capable to trace history of everything which created a footprint in the past
4	Cloud Computing Technology	Using computer infrastructure at cost effective and optimum level from ubiquitous location	Ideal Computer [4]
5	Digital Business & Marketing	Ubiquitous mobile business and e-marketing using digital and internet technology	Ideal Business [5, 34]
6	3D printing Technology	Preparing three dimensional structures from a digital file. This is achieved using additive processes using less material than traditional <i>manufacturing methods</i>	Ideal Production of components & Devices
7	Internet of Things (IoT)	Interconnection and integration of the physical world and the cyber	Ideal interconnection & Control

		space remotely to control the devices from distance	
8	Online Ubiquitous Education & Training	Education for everybody irrespective of location, age, economic level using technology	Ideal education system [35, 36]
9	Optical Computing Technology	High speed data processing	Ideal Computers [37, 38]
10	Information Storage Technology	Huge amount of information storage in a small region using suitable technology	Ideal storage system
11	Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality	Virtual reality is an immersion experience which gives the physical world feelings	Ideal virtual experience [39]

3.1 Artificial intelligence Technology:

Artificial intelligence (AI) is an area of computer science focuses on discovering intelligent machines which can make decisions with a level of intelligence like human beings. AI technology has its primary objective to develop intelligent machines which can think and perform things better than human beings. The artificial intelligence machines can recognize the environment with various abilities such as speech recognition, Understanding, Learning, Planning, Problem solving, and hence decision making. AI machine mimics cognitive functions of human beings associated with other human minds, such as learning & memorizing and hence capable of optimum decision making for problem solving. Being an important underlying technology of ICCT, AI has been introduced and developed for adding intelligent thinking components in electronic systems to be used in any industrial sectors. Artificial intelligence has potential applications in almost all industries and industry sectors including the primary sector, secondary sectors, tertiary sectors, and quaternary sector.

3.2 Big data & Business analytics :

Big data and business analytics is an emerging underlying technology of ICCT which focus on handling the continuously generated huge amount of data in any business applications or data capturing process and used to analyse it using various mathematical models and quantitative analytical techniques to determine the pattern of information. It also helps to generate descriptive information, predictive information, and prescriptive information of a business process for supporting the decision makers to take optimum decisions to the problems related to future aspects of the business. Predictive analytics are finding their applications in various functional areas like Human resource analytics, Marketing analytics, Retail Analytics (Customer Analytics/Supply Chain Analytics), Pricing Analytics, Financial analytics, Social media analytics, sports analytics, and Healthcare analytics for effective decisions. Prescriptive Analytics are used for optimizing the decisions with multiple objectives/portfolio analytics, optimizing complex decisions/sales force analytics, and Retail Analytics, etc are also have a futuristic impact on effective business decisions.

3.3 Blockchain Technology :

Blockchain consists of a growing list of records which are linked using cryptography and such chain has the property of transparency, decentralization, and immune to modifications.

It is a technology for record creation across many computers or digital devices of a process or an activity which cannot be altered retroactively, without altering its subsequent processes or activities. Blockchain technology allows a system to own digital goods, assets, and data and capable to trace the history of everything which is created as a footprint in the past transactions. Thus an ideal blockchain technology is expected to have the capability to trace the history of everything which created a footprint in the past. In simple words, blockchain technology can be used in each financial transaction and is digitally signed to ensure its authenticity and not allowed to tamper it, so that a ledger created with the existing transactions within it are assumed to be of high integrity. It is expected that blockchain technology is expected to help total stoppage of financial frauds and hence contributing to eradicate corruptions in this world. Blockchain technology has applications in financial transactions, healthcare systems, education, supply chain systems, etc.

3.4 Cloud Computing :

Cloud computing is another important underlying technology of ICCT group. Due to the ubiquitous nature of cloud computing technology with flexibility in scaling it has identified as an important area of research and provides an easy way for using computing processes in the business. The cloud computing technology also provides an innovative application called Business Intelligence (BI) for effective decision making in business processes using the Internet. The prominent feature of the Cloud computing model is that it provides to its clients both hardware as well as software to process the data and information online as a rental service. Cloud computing model provides three variations in its ubiquitous computing service solutions to the business as Software as a Service (SaaS), Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS), and Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS). The advantages of cloud computing solution used by any business organization include reduction in their (1) investment cost, (2) maintenance cost, and hence total business cost without compromising with the quality of services. Cloud computing is a subfield of the Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT).

3.5 Digital Business & Marketing :

ICCT created a new online business model called E-business/ M-business model using its internet technology. This model consists of the ubiquitous selling proposition. Digital marketing uses digital technology to market various products or services using mainly on the Internet, but it also includes computers, mobile phones to display advertising, and any other digital medium. Digital marketing technology represents advertisements delivered through digital channels and internet including search engines, websites, social media, email, and mobile apps. Digital business and marketing are emerged as an essential future business & marketing activities using ICCT general purpose technology.

3.6 3D Printing :

3D printing is another ICCT underlying technology where various input materials can be joined or solidified using various processes under the control of the computer program to create a three-dimensional object. 3D printing technology creates an object by laying down successive layers of material until the entire object is produced. 3D printing allows using different materials as input as per printing requirement which includes metals, fabrics, bio and a whole host of other industry based materials to support many applications in many industries globally. 3D printing technology has a wide scope in industrial automation and

even home automation processes. 3D printing technology is expected to revolutionize material fabrication processes in future industries. 3D printing comprises of many other technologies including nanotechnology where it utilizes nanomaterials and nanocomposites for anything, anywhere manufacturing.

3.7 Internet of Things :

Internet of things (IoT) is a network of various electronic, computing, and optical devices/objects including human beings connected each other virtually utilizing internet or intranet for enabling them to exchange (send and receive) data and information. These devices/objects are identified with unique identifiers (UIDs) and are programmed to transfer data and information over the internet without requiring human-to-human or human-to-computer interaction by using IoT technology. Such a connection of physical things/objects to the Internet makes it possible to access remote sensor data and to control the physical world from a distance. The mash-up of captured data with data retrieved from other sources, eg, with data that is contained in the Web, gives rise to new synergistic services that go beyond the services that can be provided by an isolated embedded system. Internet-of-Things (IoT) is not in any new disruptive technology but is the pervasive deployment and innovation of ICCT.

3.8 Online Ubiquitous Education :

To provide education to everybody, the transformation of traditional campus based education system into Massive Online Open Courses (MOOC) system is essential. Even though initially MOOC is considered as complementary to traditional campus based education HE system, as time progress, it may replace campus based HE system completely. Higher education focuses on enhancing knowledge, skills, experience, and hence confidence to make innovations and better decisions can be offered equally effective through online using wireless video channels. Ubiquitous online education offered through multidisciplinary areas using simulation may out pass the traditional laboratory based education in the HE system. The other underlying ICCT technologies also support online ubiquitous education system to make it more effective, efficient and easily accessible system for everybody without their geographical locations and economical conditions. Some of such growing brands include EDX, COUSERA, NPTEL, SWAYAM, etc.

3.9 Optical Computing :

High speed computers are required for computing a huge amount of data for certain complex applications. Optical computers which use the principles of optical signal switching and optical signal processing are expected to make a breakthrough in the 21st century with their full potentials and capabilities using optical logic gates and flip-flops fabricated by nanocomposites. High speed computation and data storage using nanotechnology based optical computers are expected to revolutionize the computation industry. Optical computation is joining both general purpose technologies, i.e., Nanotechnology and ICCT through the processes of design & production as well as operation & applications respectively. Many optical technology principles like photo-refraction, optical spatial solitons, and optical logic gates are under development for building all-optical computers.

3.10 Information Storage Technology :

Information storage technology supports to develop devices to store & retrieve information in digital format. The trend in this field is to enhance the capability of devices to store huge amount of information in a small region at high speed and low cost. Various storage devices used and under consideration include Semiconductor Storage, Hologram Storage, Optical Storage, DNA Based Digital Storage, etc. which should have capability to store information in Terabytes, Petabytes, Exabytes, Zettabyte, and even Yottabyte in order to cater the forthcoming information storage applications.

3.11 Virtual & Augmented Reality :

Virtual reality technology is an artificial environment used to simulate real systems created with the help of computer-based software and presented to the user to believe it as a real environment. Virtual reality is primarily experienced on a computer through two of the five senses: sight and sound. Virtual reality is initially developed and used in simulated training and education as well as the simulated game environment. But now it found many applications in many areas including business as augmented reality and may enter the group of general purpose technology.

ICCT has many applications in the many Industries and Industry sectors. Almost all industries and industry sectors belonging to Primary, Secondary, Tertiary, and Quaternary Industry Sectors are basically supported by and get benefits from ICCT. In the next section, the applications of ICCT underlying technologies in some of the important service industry sectors are discussed.

4. DIGITAL SERVICE STRATEGY IN TERTIARY INDUSTRY SECTOR :

Industries and industry sectors in tertiary sector called services sector are expected to get benefit from ICCT. Table 4 lists some of the services sector gets benefit from underlying technologies of ICCT.

Table 4 : Some applications of ICCT in Tertiary Industry Sector

S. No.	Underlying technologies of ICCT	Applications in Tertiary Industry Sector	Useful quality attributes
1	Artificial Intelligence Technology	Artificial Intelligence technology is used in many areas of service industry sector including tourism, telecommunications, citizen services, Banking sector for loan decisions, retail sector, etc. [40-44]	Safe & Secure, Customizable, Flexibility, Adaptability, Reusability, and Innovability
2	Big data and Business Analytics	In Supply chain management, Banking sector, Tourism sector, health sector, financial & insurance sector, fashion industry, [45-49].	Ubiquitous, Safe & Secure, Customizable, Flexibility, Adaptability, Reusability, and Innovability

3	Blockchain Technology	In Advertising, Supply chain management, Banking sector, Education, Tourism sector, health sector, financial & insurance sector, fashion industry etc. [50-53]	Ubiquitous, Safe & Secure, Simple & Easy, Flexibility, and Innovability
4	Cloud Computing Technology	Financial service industry, Education industry, Security industry, Brokering service, Healthcare, Gaming industry, Supply-chain industry, Telecommunication industry, [54-56]	Ubiquitous, Safe & Secure, Customizable, Flexibility, Reusability, and Innovability
5	Digital Business & Marketing	Digital Marketing and customer relationship in all kind of industry including hotel industry, tourism industry, health industry etc. [57-58]	Ubiquitous, Safe & Secure, Simple & Easy, Customizable, Reusability, and Innovability
6	3D printing Technology	Health sciences, Forest industry, [59-60]	Safe & Secure, Simple & Easy, Customizable, Flexibility, Adaptability, and Innovability
7	Internet of Things (IoT)	Service innovations are possible using IoT. Smart city services including Tourism, Healthcare, Telecommunication, Logistics, Transportation, Retail, etc. [61-65]	Ubiquitous, Safe & Secure, Simple & Easy, Customizable, Flexibility, Adaptability, Reusability, and Innovability
8	Online Ubiquitous Education & Training Technology	Education industry, Library services, Retail banking, Healthcare services, etc. [66-68]	Ubiquitous, Safe & Secure, Simple & Easy, Flexibility, Reusability, and Innovability
9	Optical Computing Technology	Optical technology based high speed computers are essential in future Retail industry sectors, Logistics & Supply chain industry sectors, Telecom industry sector, Information security industry, etc. [69-70]	Flexibility, Adaptability, Reusability, and Innovability
10	Information Storage Technology	All services industry sectors where huge amount data and information related to the business are to be stored and retrieved at high speed in small device.	Safe & Secure, Flexibility, Reusability, and Innovability
11	Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality	Education & Training, Tourism, Travel industry, Finance, etc. [71-73]	Customizable, Flexibility, Adaptability, and Innovability

ICCT underlying technologies are considered as emerging breakthrough technologies of the 21st century with many types of innovative applications in all industrial sectors. When service sector industries are concerned, there are many opportunities to radically change the service models, service methods, service processes, service development, service transformation, service utilization, and service feedback. The entire lifecycle of the service as an output product of service industries and as an intangible input resource for the customers can be modified using ICCT digital technologies. The emerging underlying technologies of ICCT are so powerful and innovative so that they are really capable to destruct the existing models and methods of offering the services as disruptive technologies and able to create new avenue to realize the ambitious wants and dreamy desires of the customers. Tables 5 list some of the prominent service industries and the predicted ICCT underlying technologies which may re-define the way the services are offered by different service industries.

Table 5 : ICCT based Service Innovation in Tertiary Industry Sector

S. No.	Service Industries	Applications of ICCT digital technology for service innovation
1	Advertising industry	Artificial Intelligence Technology, Big data and Business Analytics, Blockchain Technology, Cloud Computing Technology, Internet of Things (IoT), Online Ubiquitous Education & Training Technology, Optical Computing Technology, Information Storage Technology, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality.
2	Education industry	Artificial Intelligence Technology, Big data and Business Analytics, Cloud Computing Technology, Digital Business & Marketing, 3D printing Technology, Internet of Things (IoT), Online Ubiquitous Education & Training Technology, Information Storage Technology, Blockchain Technology, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality.
3	E-Commerce industry	Artificial Intelligence Technology, Big data and Business Analytics, Cloud Computing Technology, Digital Business & Marketing, Information Storage Technology, Blockchain Technology, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality.
4	Entertainment industry	Blockchain technology, Cloud Computing Technology, Digital Business & Marketing, 3D printing Technology, Internet of Things (IoT), Online Ubiquitous Education & Training Technology, Information Storage Technology, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality.
5	Fashion industry	3D printing Technology, Internet of Things (IoT), Online Ubiquitous Training Technology, Optical Computing Technology, Information Storage Technology, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality.
6	Financial services industry	Artificial Intelligence Technology, Big data and Business Analytics, Blockchain Technology, Cloud Computing Technology, Digital Business & Marketing, 3D printing Technology, Internet of Things (IoT), Online Ubiquitous

		Education & Training Technology, Optical Computing Technology, Information Storage Technology, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality.
7	Healthcare industry	Artificial Intelligence Technology, Big data and Business Analytics, Blockchain Technology, Cloud Computing Technology, Digital Business & Marketing, 3D printing Technology, Internet of Things (IoT), Online Ubiquitous Education & Training Technology, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality.
8	Hospitality industry	Artificial Intelligence Technology, Big data and Business Analytics, Blockchain Technology, Digital Business & Marketing, 3D printing Technology, Internet of Things (IoT), Online Ubiquitous Education & Training Technology, Optical Computing Technology, Information Storage Technology, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality.
9	Insurance industry	Big data and Business Analytics, Blockchain Technology, Cloud Computing Technology, Online Ubiquitous Education & Training Technology, Optical Computing Technology, Information Storage Technology, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality.
10	IT services industry	Artificial Intelligence Technology, Big data and Business Analytics, Cloud Computing Technology, Digital Business & Marketing, Internet of Things (IoT), Online Ubiquitous Education & Training Technology, Optical Computing Technology, Information Storage Technology, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality.
11	Media industry	Artificial Intelligence Technology, Big data and Business Analytics, Cloud Computing Technology, Digital Business & Marketing, Internet of Things (IoT), Optical Computing Technology, Information Storage Technology, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality.
12	Online services industry	Artificial Intelligence Technology, Big data and Business Analytics, Digital Business & Marketing, Internet of Things (IoT), Online Ubiquitous Education & Training Technology, Optical Computing Technology, Information Storage Technology, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality.
13	Public service industry	Big data and Business Analytics, Cloud Computing Technology, Internet of Things (IoT), Online Ubiquitous Education & Training Technology, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality.
14	Retail industry	Artificial Intelligence Technology, Big data and Business Analytics, Cloud Computing Technology, Digital Business & Marketing, Internet of Things (IoT), Information Storage Technology, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality.
15	Sports industry	Artificial Intelligence Technology, Big data and Business Analytics, Cloud Computing Technology, Digital Business &

		Marketing, 3D printing Technology, Internet of Things (IoT), Online Ubiquitous Training Technology, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality.
16	Tourism industry	Artificial Intelligence Technology, Big data and Business Analytics, Cloud Computing Technology, Digital Business & Marketing, 3D printing Technology, Internet of Things (IoT), Online Ubiquitous Education & Training Technology, Optical Computing Technology, Information Storage Technology, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality.
17	Travel & Transport industry	Artificial Intelligence Technology, Big data and Business Analytics, Blockchain Technology, Cloud Computing Technology, Digital Business & Marketing, 3D printing Technology, Internet of Things (IoT), Information Storage Technology, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality.
18	Event management industry	Artificial Intelligence Technology, Big data and Business Analytics, CDigital Business & Marketing, Internet of Things (IoT), Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality.

5. HOW ICCT UNDERLYING TECHNOLOGIES USED FOR DIGITAL SERVICE INNOVATION IN THE TERTIARY INDUSTRY SECTOR :

The use of top ten digital technologies under ICCT in innovating various services offered by some of the prominent service industries are predicted using predictive analysis technique [74-75] and listed in following eleven tables from Table 6 to Table 16.

Table 6 : Artificial Intelligence Technology based Service Innovation in Service Industries

S. No.	Service Industries	Applications of Artificial Intelligence Technology
1	Advertising industry	Interactive advertising, Agent mediated advertising, Intelligent advertising, Pervasive advertising etc.
2	Education industry	Knowledge management, Educational cobots and smart classrooms, Artificial intelligence in auditing, Educational simulations, Online distributed learning, Improving mobile learning environment
3	E-Commerce industry	Intelligent Techniques for E-commerce, E-commerce intelligent agents, Order products online, track orders, and perform other ecommerce activities using AI, Intelligent e-business models, Electronic auditing, fuzzy intelligent agents for e-commerce automation, etc.
4	Entertainment industry	Adaptive robotics in the entertainment industry, Computer games, Development of entertainment robot, Entertainment software agents, etc.
5	Fashion industry	Sales forecasting for fashion retailing, Fuzzy association rule mining for fashion product development, intelligent clothes search system based on fashion styles, Artificial multi-agent

		system, AI based designs for fashion industry, Intelligent fashion styling, etc.
6	Financial services industry	For managing fraud and identity theft, To advise clients, Strategic issues for financial services marketing, Prediction of financial health of organizations using AI, AI to create value in insurance, Neuro-based AI model for loan decisions, Service automation using AI, Blockchain techniques, etc.
7	Healthcare industry	Designing smart health care technology, AI in behavioral and mental health care, Applying agent technology to healthcare, Remote monitoring of high-risk patients AI based agent-mediated healthcare systems, For agent-mediated healthcare systems, AI assisted medical reference system, etc.
8	Hospitality industry	Experience-based travel, AI based service automation, AI based Yield-management approach to hotel-room pricing, Agent technology in hotel business, Exploring customer experiences, Design of fuzzy expert system for hotel selection, Development of intelligent robot, etc.
9	IT services industry	Automation of Software development & coding, Knowledge management, Information security services, Semantic web services, decision automation, etc.
10	Media industry	Social media analytics and intelligence, Effective knowledge sharing, Ambient intelligence in multimedia, Restructuring newsroom, AI based new media model, etc.
11	Retail industry	Marketing decision making, Multivalent negotiations, Work flow automation, Marketing intelligence, Price adjustment, Expert systems with AI,
12	Sports industry	Sports performance prediction, Automation, Sports informatics, Emotion calculation based on AI, Sports strategies implementation, etc.
13	Tourism industry	Smart tourism, Tourism information technology, Tourism service automation, Knowledge management, Robotics & service automation, Tour itinerary planning, Personalizing recommendations, Travel recommender system, Tourism forecasting, etc.
14	Travel & Transport industry	Intelligent transport system using AI, Improving parking efficiencies, Agent based logistics, Traffic forecasting, Travel time prediction, Experience based travel, Intelligent agents in traffic, Swarm intelligence, Technology assisted travel counselling, Artificial transportation system, etc.
15	Event management industry	Automatic computing, Artificial surface development, etc.

Table 7 : Big data and Business Analytics based Service Innovation in Service Industries

S. No.	Service Industries	Applications of Big data and Business Analytics
1	Advertising industry	Advertising analytics, Privacy and user control, Analytics based decision making, Big data analytics as service,
2	Education industry	Analytics for education, Learning analytics, Teaching analytics, Predictive analytics, Optimizing quality, etc.
3	E-Commerce industry	E-commerce data analytics, market analytics, Big-data warehouse, Customer demand & supply chain analytics, Big data as a service, Text analytics, Big data driven e-commerce architecture, Validating e-commerce metrics, Online marketing, Intelligent service for e-commerce customers, Combating e-commerce identity fraud, etc.
4	Entertainment industry	Games analytics, Music based big data analytics, Multimedia analytics, Branded Entertainment, etc.
5	Fashion industry	Knowledge co-creation, Customer Analytics in Fashion industry, etc.
6	Financial services industry	Detecting fraud, Financial auditing, meta-analytics for risk forecast, Smarter fraud investigations, financial data modeling and analysis, etc.
7	Healthcare industry	Reduce healthcare costs, Predictive analytics, Appointment brokering, scheduling, e-referral and e-discharge, for better health planning, Making healthcare green, Clinical Decision Support,
8	Hospitality industry	Smart hospitality, Knowledge management, Decision support, Online customer service, etc.
9	Insurance industry	Customer profitability forecasting, Increasing customer orientation, Secure cyber incident analytics, Fraud Detection, Knowledge discovery, Intelligent Multi Agent Systems, etc.
10	Media industry	Social media analytics, Antecedents and Business Value, Empathic media and advertising, New business model,
11	Retail industry	Retail business analytics, intelligent operational dashboards for smarter commerce, Performance measurement, etc.
12	Sports industry	Sports analytics, Risk monitoring, Smart clothing, Predictive analytics on performance, etc.
13	Tourism industry	Smart tourism, Tourism analytics, Social media analytics in tourism, Monitoring and forecasting tourist activities, Sentiment analysis, Forecasting tourism demand, Customer knowledge management, data analytic tourism dashboard, etc.
14	Travel & Transport	Travel search engine optimization, Transport analytics,

	industry	Railway transportation optimization, Revenue management and pricing analytics, Passenger travel behaviour, Risk management using predictive analytics, Smart transportation, Multi-model travel policies, etc.
15	Event management industry	Event risk management, Smart event management, etc.

Table 8 : Cloud Computing Technology based Service Innovation in Service Industries

S. No.	Service Industries	Applications of Cloud Computing Technology
1	Advertising industry	Advertising analytics, Mobile advertising, Alphanumeric indexing, Social media advertisement, etc.
2	Education industry	Cloud Computing prototypes, Education platforms, Improving research productivity, Alternative IT sourcing, Value addition to education project, Micro-learning platforms, E-learning, etc.
3	E-Commerce industry	SME e-commerce model, E-commerce cloud, Anti-Counterfeit Scheme, etc.
4	Entertainment industry	Cloud based smart home, Sounds in cloud, Cloud gaming, Mobile cloud gaming, Music in cloud, etc.
5	Financial services industry	Security enhancement, Cyber risks handling, etc.
6	Healthcare industry	Mobile cloud computing, Improved healthcare, Security platform for healthcare system, Cloud computing model for patient data collection, Cloud healthcare as service, e-Healthcare, Cloud based Hospital Information system, Medical imaging, etc.
7	Hospitality industry	Smart hospitality
8	Insurance industry	Cyber security insurance in Cloud computing,
9	Media industry	Service oriented architecture, Cloud storage solutions, Edge to cloud virtualization.
10	Retail industry	Customer behaviour analysis, Cloud based mobile commerce,
11	Sports industry	Bodycloud, Prediction cloud computing demand, etc.
12	Tourism industry	Smart tourism, e-tourism framework, Decision support, etc.
13	Travel & Transport industry	Autonomous vehicular clouds, Cloud based intelligent transport system, Traffic safety, etc.
14	Event management industry	Security information and event management in the cloud computing infrastructure, Automated cloud computing, etc.

Table 9 : Digital Business & Marketing based Service Innovation in Service Industries

S. No.	Service Industries	Applications of Digital Business & Marketing
1	Advertising industry	Digital media advertisement, Mobile advertising, Real time bidding, Banner advertising, Online advertisement, Social media advertising platforms, etc.
2	Education industry	MOOCs, SPOCs, social media, and the Cookie Monster,

		Digital fabrication, Enterprise architectures and portals in digital transformation, Virtual technology, etc.
3	E-Commerce industry	Digital platforms, Digital e-commerce adoption models, Digital marketing for e-commerce, etc.
4	Entertainment industry	Mobile gaming, Digital music, Digital transformation, Digital business platforms for entertainment, Online video entertainment, Digital video game, Localization of digital games, Social media marketing for entertainment, etc.
5	Fashion industry	Fashion bloggers as communication tools, Trend analysis, Predicting purchase intentions, Interactive communication, Brand building, Virtual fitting room, Handling Counterfeiting, Use of social media, Digital Transformation for Fast-Fashion Brands, etc.
6	Financial services industry	Blockchain finance model, Digital finance, Supervision of financial markets, etc.
7	Healthcare industry	Internet based observation, Patient portals and online clinical consultations, Open digital platforms, Blockchain technology in healthcare, Cyber security aspects, Medical tourism, Digital medicine, Cloudlet-based mobile cloud computing, R&D and clinical practice models etc.
8	Hospitality industry	Digital tools for innovations, Hospitality robots, Use of digital social media, Digital sharing platform, Risk analysis, etc.
9	Insurance industry	Digital imaging of documents, Cyber risk management, Creative contracting, Smart business networks, Blockchain based insurance models, Secured claim processes, Digital insurance, etc.
10	Media industry	Digitization of Media business models, Digital social media support, Digital publication, etc.
11	Retail industry	Web analytics, Strategic tool, Supply chain automation, Online services, Consumer centric retailing, Web services, etc.
12	Sports industry	Internet sports marketing, Digital games, Online sports betting, etc.
13	Tourism industry	Social media on tourism, E-tourism, Website based tourism service, Digital ecosystem in Tourism, Web marketing, Agent-based cybermarketing, etc.
14	Travel & Transport industry	Web services for travel industry, Location based services, Virtual logistics, Digital lifestyle and online travel, Digital travel record, Digital sustainable travel services, etc.

Table 10 : 3D printing Technology based Service Innovation in Service Industries

S. No.	Service Industries	Applications of 3D printing Technology
1	Education industry	Low cost 3D printing, Anatomy education, Teacher education, Design thinking & education, Engineer design education,

		Additive manufacturing in classroom, In pre-engineering curriculum, Tool for teaching & learning in STEAM education, etc.
2	E-Commerce industry	Mass production, Networked market place, Customized production, Smart manufacturing, etc.
3	Entertainment industry	Surprise object advances for the 3D printing entertainment industry, Game object advances for the 3D printing entertainment industry, etc.
4	Fashion industry	In garments production, Virtual design & production, Digital 3D printing in fashion, Fashion textiles by 3D printing, Collective design for 3D printing in fashion, 3D printing on textile substrates, etc.
5	Healthcare industry	3D printing of biomaterials, 3D printing for personalized medication, 3D printed medicine, 3D printing in pharmaceutical and medical applications, For personalized drug delivery, Organ printing, etc.
6	Hospitality industry	3D food printing.
7	Retail industry	For rapid manufacturing, Personal fabrication, etc.
8	Travel & Transport industry	Influence of 3D printing on transport, Freight miles: the impact of 3D printing on transport, etc.

Table 11 : Internet of Things (IoT) based Service Innovation in Service Industries

S. No.	Service Industries	Applications of Internet of Things (IoT)
1	Advertising industry	IOT as Disruptive Innovation for the Advertising Ecosystem, Wireless advertising software library for distributed IOT,
2	Education industry	New education architecture, IOT learning systems, Mobile education using IOT, Smart university using IOT, IoT-based flipped learning platform for medical education, etc.
3	E-Commerce industry	IOT for cyber security, IOT based services access for e-commerce, IOT reference architecture for E-commerce, etc.
6	Financial services industry	Service innovations by providing new applications or upgrading the existing one by providing enhanced security, Blockchain convergence, Value creation through enhanced privacy, Etc.
7	Healthcare industry	IOT platform for efficient healthcare services, For smarter healthcare services, For enhanced security & privacy of healthcare services, IOT to manage big data based services, Data validation services in personalized healthcare, IOT based information system for emergency healthcare, Etc.
8	Hospitality industry	Smart hospitality using IOT, Paperless buffer management, Security improvements, CRM using IOT, etc.
9	Insurance industry	Risk analysis of IOT based cyber insurance, Blockchain based for digital insurance management, Self organized framework for insurance using IOT, etc.

11	Media industry	IoT architecture for multisensory media, etc.
14	Retail industry	Improving the customer experience, Controlling supply chain, New opportunity for revenue creation, Value co-creation for customers, IOT as marketing tool, etc.
15	Sports industry	Sports analytics management, Occupancy monitoring system for campus sports facilities, Security issues and creation in sports, etc.
16	Tourism industry	Smart tourism, Managing mobile smart tourism destinations efficiently, Independent mobility of tourists in smart cities, Geo targeting for marketing tourism.
17	Travel & Transport industry	IOT ensures efficient delivery and food safety, For smart transport, Ultra low power IOT based traffic monitoring system, IoT can integrate transports with human responses, travel behaviours, inter jurisdictional interoperability, environmental changes, city and building ambiances, sound and video, etc.
18	Event management industry	Automation including time and process of event management.

Table 12 : Online Ubiquitous Education & Training Technology based Service Innovation in Service Industries

S. No.	Service Industries	Applications of Online Ubiquitous Education & Training Technology
1	Advertising industry	Mobile advertisement through online awareness creation, Digital training with internet video advertising, Online direct-to-consumer advertising, etc.
2	Education industry	Ubiquitous Education programmes, MOOC, Vocational education & training, Mobile learning, Online education with global quality, Online engineering education, Flexible learning toolboxes, Online workforce training, etc.
3	E-Commerce industry	Awareness creation in online banking, Online training for e-commerce workforce, Online education for e-commerce models, etc.
4	Entertainment industry	Online educational game, Digital game-based learning, Online video games for education & learning, etc.
5	Fashion industry	Global online training in fashion design sector to reduce the cost, Mapping e-learning courses in the fashion domain, etc.
6	Financial services industry	Customer education, Financial planning education & training, Education for financial advisors, etc.
7	Healthcare industry	MOOC on health & medicine, Processes of e-health, Clinical education & training, Mobile health, Web-based training for public health practitioners etc.
8	Hospitality industry	e-learning in hospitality, Mobile learning, Web-based training, etc.
9	Insurance industry	e-training, online ubiquitous service, online claim clearance, etc.

11	Media industry	Web-based training in media,
13	Public service industry	Public sector training, Online training, Online services, etc.
14	Retail industry	Online retail services, Online after sales services, Retail training, etc.
15	Sports industry	Online training in sports,
16	Tourism industry	Sharing tourism knowledge online, Simulation based tourism education, E-learning applications in tourism sector, etc.
17	Travel & Transport industry	Online intermediates, Online travel purchase processes, Travel data exchange,
18	Event management industry	Online event management education, Online event management training, etc.

Table 13 : Optical Computing Technology based Service Innovation in Service Industries

S. No.	Service Industries	Applications of Optical Computing Technology
1	Advertising industry	High speed computation based advertising models, Online advertising, Digital advertising & processes, Resource advertising and optical research networks, Optimizing advertisement – systems & methods, etc.
2	Education industry	Optical computing alternative for high speed interconnectivity and storage for global MOOC, High ending computing for education, etc.
3	E-Commerce industry	Modern high performance computing for large scale e-commerce,
4	Entertainment industry	Entertainment computing, Computing at speed of light for high speed entertainment, All optical devices, etc.
5	Healthcare industry	High speed optical computers for healthcare applications.
6	Hospitality industry	Hospitality automation based on fully functioning robots which are based on high speed optical computers.
7	Insurance industry	High end computing in insurance information processing.
8	Sports industry	High speed computing for video games.
9	Travel & Transport industry	Intelligent transportation systems using high speed computers.

Table 14 : Information Storage Technology based Service Innovation in Service Industries

S. No.	Service Industries	Applications of Information Storage Technology
1	Advertising industry	Pervasive advertising
2	Education industry	Storage of information in MOOC
3	E-Commerce industry	Data management, Data analytics, Huge information storage
4	Entertainment industry	High density digital storage
5	Fashion industry	High density digital storage
6	Healthcare industry	High density digital storage

7	Hospitality industry	High density digital storage
8	Media industry	High density & high speed digital storage
9	Retail industry	High density & high speed digital storage
10	Sports industry	High density & high speed digital storage
11	Travel & Transport industry	High density & high speed digital storage

Table 15 : Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality based Service Innovation in Service Industries

S. No.	Service Industries	Applications of Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality
1	Advertising industry	Augmented reality effectiveness in advertising, Personal augmented reality advertising, Augmented reality 3d interactive advertisements on smartphones, Exposure time and self-efficacy in augmented reality advertising environments, Adoption of mobile augmented reality advertisements, etc.
2	Education industry	Collaborative augmented reality in education, AR as visual and spatial learning tool in technology education, VR based educational games, Potential of augmented reality for teaching primary school science, Augmented reality to promote collaborative and autonomous learning in higher education, Virtual reality-based spatial skills assessment and its role in computer graphics education, AR in experimental education, In immersive training system, Educational video game design, etc.
3	E-Commerce industry	Virtual fitting room augmented reality techniques for e-commerce, Augmented reality E-commerce assistant system, Adoption of Augmented Reality Technology for E-Commerce, etc.
4	Entertainment industry	Digital interactive entertainment, Product realization, Achieving total immersion, Video games, Museum effects, Interaction techniques with virtual humans, Interactive storytelling and mobile augmented reality applications for learning and entertainment, Applying mixed realities in entertainment, etc.
5	Fashion Industry	Fashnology perspective on the perception and adoption of augmented reality smart glasses.
6	Healthcare industry	Digital surgical environment using VR & AR, Patient-specific virtual reality simulation, Use of virtual, augmented, and mixed reality to urology, VR & AR in dentistry, Virtual reality-assisted robotic surgery simulation, Clinical utility of an Augmented Reality musical software among health care professionals, Augmented reality system to guide radio-frequency tumour ablation, Trauma decision-making simulator in Oculus virtual reality. etc.
7	Hospitality industry	Augmented reality instructions in a hospital setting, Virtual

		reality rehabilitation and therapy, Customer emotions study in virtual restaurant, Virtual collaboration, Smart hospitality, etc.
8	Media industry	Virtual studio, Virtual simulated world, Social media with virtual
9	Online services industry	To enhance online service experiences, visual integration of virtual content into a person's real-world environment, etc.
10	Retail industry	Social mobile augmented reality for retail, Smart retail settings via mobile augmented reality shopping apps, Bringing online shopping experience to offline retail through augmented reality, Multisensory augmented reality in the context of a retail clothing application, Mobile augmented reality for retail environments, etc.
11	Sports industry	VR simulation for football & other sports, VR based training models for sports & games, etc.
12	Tourism industry	New realities: a systematic literature review on virtual reality and augmented reality in tourism research, VR in tourism marketing using mobile device, AR as an Innovation Tool in Digital Tourism Marketing, Smart tourism, Effects of virtual reality on theme park visitors' experience and behaviours, etc.
13	Travel & Transport industry	To synthesize & immerse virtual environment with no touch-points to the real world, Virtual reality for travel planning, VR as a travel promotional tool, VR in automotive and aerospace sector, VR as travel promotion tool, etc.

Table 16 : Blockchain based Service Innovation in Service Industries

S. No.	Service Industries	Applications of Blockchain Technology
1	Advertising industry	Online advertising solutions, Preventing fake news, Decentralizing advertisement, Price auction, Digital Advertising Media Promotion System, etc.
2	Education industry	Education tracking, Recruitment and human resource management, Higher education credit platform, Validating degree certificates, Competency based education, etc.
3	E-Commerce industry	Supply-chain & Logistics, Digital marketing, Fraud detection, etc.
4	Entertainment industry	Smart contracts for streaming, Copyright in Music industry, Digitizing the music value chain. Protecting intellectual property, Playing and trading, etc.
5	Fashion Industry	Blockchain enhanced emission trading framework in fashion apparel manufacturing industry, Fashion Supply chain, etc.
6	Healthcare industry	Electronic health records system, prescription drug fraud detection, patient-centered medical records, user-oriented medical research and drug counterfeiting in the pharmaceutical

		sector, solving traceability issues and ensuring transparency, etc.
7	Hospitality industry	Booking, reservation and payment systems using blockchain, Tracking guests, Tracking food, Secured and confirmed payments, etc.
8	Media industry	User controlled social media, Trusting news and records, etc.
9	Retail industry	Logistics & supply chain of retail industry, Payments, Food traceability, secured transactions in retail banking, Transparency, consumer profiling, immutability and reduced total cost of ownership, etc.
10	Sports industry	Online gambling, Record management in water sports, Data security, E-sporting, etc.
12	Tourism industry	Smart Tourism, Trust in Tourism via blockchain, increased disintermediation, blockchain platform to boost tourism revenue etc.
13	Travel & Transport industry	Transport record storage, To establish a secured, trusted and decentralized intelligent transport systems, etc.
14	Financial services industry	Financial Regulation, Facilitate Anti-Money Laundering Efforts, Secured banking transactions, Venture capital funding, Future of money, To overcome financial fraud from public sector services, etc.
15	Education industry	Formative evaluation, learning activities design and implementation, and keep tracking the whole learning processes, construct a balance to measure learning process and outcomes, potential applications in instructional design, behaviors recording, and analysis, etc.

6. MANAGEMENT OF ICCT STRATEGIES FOR ENHANCING PRODUCTIVITY & EFFECTIVENESS :

ICCT can be used for digital service innovations in many tertiary industry sectors as seen in previous section but planning and managing them systematically to get real benefit to fulfilling the objectives of the organization is a challenge. There are many strategies used in planning and implementation of their service products. Proper strategy should be identified and implemented in a given business organization to add values and to get expected benefits. As per one school of thought in strategic management, an organization may use five types of strategies while promoting a business which include : (i) Survival strategy or black ocean strategy [76], (ii) Sustainability strategy or green ocean strategy [77], (iii) Monopoly strategy or blue ocean strategy [78], (iv) Competitive strategy or red ocean strategy [79], and (v) Growth & prosperous strategy or while ocean strategy [80]. These strategies can be applied to service sector industries while managing their technology adaption to promote digital service innovations.

7. CONCLUSION :

The various underlying technologies of ICCT in the tertiary industry sector are used to analyse, and predict the suitable technologies and suitable strategies using predictive analysis model. The potential applications of ICCT as a strategic tool for survival, sustainability, differentiation, and development of various service sector industries are identified and listed. It is found that Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT) is having applications in many areas of society to solve problems of society as Universal general purpose technology of 21st century is one of the effective & efficient technologies for digital service innovation. By identifying, implementing, and managing these digital technologies in the service sector, industries can add value to their existing services, and develop new related services to get business benefits.

REFERENCES :

- [1] Boyan J., Peter L., Rousseau (2005). Handbook of Economic Growth, Vol. 1B. pp. 1182-1224, Edited by Philippe Aghion and Steven N. Durlauf, Elsevier B.V. DOI: 10.1016/S1574-0684(05)01018-X.
- [2] Lipsey, Richard; Kenneth I. Carlaw; Clifford T. Bekhar (2005). *Economic Transformations: General Purpose Technologies and Long-Term Economic Growth*. Oxford University Press. pp. 131–218. ISBN 0-19-928564-0.
- [3] Aithal, P. S. and Shubhrajyotsna Aithal. (2018). Study of various General-Purpose Technologies and their contribution towards developing Sustainable Society. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 3(2), 16-33. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/Zenodo.1409476>.
- [4] Aithal, P. S. (2016). Review on Various Ideal System Models Used to Improve the Characteristics of Practical Systems. *International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research*, 1(1), 47-56. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.159749>.
- [5] Aithal, P. S. (2015). Concept of Ideal Business & Its Realization Using E-Business Model. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 4(3), 1267 – 1274. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.61648>.
- [6] Aithal, P. S. & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal, (2015). Ideal Technology Concept & its Realization Opportunity using Nanotechnology, *International Journal of Application or Innovation in Engineering & Management (IJAIEM)*, 4(2), 153 – 164. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.61591>.
- [7] Saunila, M., Rantala, T. & Ukko, J. (2017). Characteristics of customer value creation in digital services. *Journal of Service Science Research*, 9(2), 239-258. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12927-017-0012-4>.
- [8] Bharadwaj A., El Sawy O. A., Pavlou P. A., & Venkatraman N. (2013). Digital business strategy: Toward a next generation of insights. *MIS Quarterly*, 37(sn2), 471–482.
- [9] Salminen, J. (2014). Digital Services – How Are They Different? In Proceedings of International Conference on Business, Information, and Cultural Creative Industry (ICBIC14), Taipei, Taiwan, 6–8 August. http://jonisalminen.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/digital-services_taipei.pdf.

-
- [10] Kitzinger, J. (1995). Qualitative research: introducing focus groups. *BMJ*, 311(7000), 299-302. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.311.7000.299>.
- [11] Barrett, M., Davidson, E., Prabhu, J., & Vargo, S. L. (2015). Service innovation in the digital age: key contributions and future directions. *MIS quarterly*, 39(1), 135-154.
- [12] Nylén, D., & Holmström, J. (2015). Digital innovation strategy: A framework for diagnosing and improving digital product and service innovation. *Business Horizons*, 58(1), 57-67.
- [13] Nambisan, S. (2013). Information technology and product/service innovation: A brief assessment and some suggestions for future research. *Journal of the Association for Information Systems*, 14(4), 1.
- [14] Häikiö, J., & Koivumäki, T. (2016). Exploring digital service innovation process through value creation. *Journal of Innovation Management*, 4(2), 96-124.
- [15] Agarwal, R., Selen, W., Roos, G., & Green, R. (Eds.). (2015). *The handbook of service innovation*. Springer.
- [16] Sheehan, J. (2006). Understanding service sector innovation. *Communications of the ACM*, 49(7), 42-47.
- [17] Löbler, H., & Lusch, R. F. (2014). Signs and practices as resources in IT-related service innovation. *Service Science*, 6(3), 190-205.
- [18] Bustinza, O. F., Gomes, E., Vendrell-Herrero, F., & Baines, T. (2019). Product–service innovation and performance: the role of collaborative partnerships and R&D intensity. *R&D Management*, 49(1), 33-45.
- [19] Bertot, J. C., Estevez, E., & Janowski, T. (2016, March). Digital public service innovation: Framework proposal. *Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Electronic Governance* (pp. 113-122). ACM.
- [20] Hwang, J., & Christensen, C. M. (2008). Disruptive innovation in health care delivery: a framework for business-model innovation. *Health affairs*, 27(5), 1329-1335.
- [21] Hanseth, O., & Bygstad, B. (2015). Flexible generification: ICT standardization strategies and service innovation in health care. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 24(6), 645-663.
- [22] Voudouris, C., Owusu, G., Dorne, R., & Lesaint, D. (2007). *Service chain management: Technology innovation for the service business*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- [23] Norman, D. A., & Verganti, R. (2014). Incremental and radical innovation: Design research vs. technology and meaning change. *Design issues*, 30(1), 78-96.
- [24] Morabito, V. (2014). *Trends and challenges in digital business innovation*. New York: Springer International Publishing.
- [25] Bygstad, B., & Lanestedt, G. (2009). ICT based service innovation—A challenge for project management. *International Journal of Project Management*, 27(3), 234-242.
- [26] Kandampully, J. (2002). Innovation as the core competency of a service organisation: the role of technology, knowledge and networks. *European journal of innovation management*, 5(1), 18-26.

-
- [27] Jiménez-Zarco, A. I., Martínez-Ruiz, M. P., & Izquierdo-Yusta, A. (2011). Key service innovation drivers in the tourism sector: empirical evidence and managerial implications. *Service Business*, 5(4), 339.
- [28] Lehrer, C., Wieneke, A., vom Brocke, J., Jung, R., & Seidel, S. (2018). How big data analytics enables service innovation: materiality, affordance, and the individualization of service. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 35(2), 424-460.
- [29] Xu, X. (2012). Internet of things in service innovation. *Amfiteatru Economic Journal*, 14 (Special No. 6), 698-719.
- [30] Rubalcaba, L., Michel, S., Sundbo, J., Brown, S. W., & Reynoso, J. (2012). Shaping, organizing, and rethinking service innovation: a multidimensional framework. *Journal of Service Management*, 23(5), 696-715.
- [31] Benghozi, P. J., Gille, L., & Vallée, A. (2009). Innovation and regulation in the digital age: A call for new perspectives. In *Telecommunication Markets* (pp. 503-525). Physica, Heidelberg.
- [32] Madhushree L. M., Revathi Radhakrishnan & P. S. Aithal (2019). A Review on Impact of Information Communication & Computation Technology (ICCT) on Selected Primary, Secondary, and Tertiary Industrial Sectors. *Saudi Journal of Business and Management Studies*, 4(1), 106-127. ISSN 2415-6663, Scholars Middle East Publishers, Dubai, United Arab Emirates. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.21276/sjbms.2019.4.1.14>.
- [33] Aithal, P. S. & (2019). Emerging Trends in ICCT as Universal Technology for Survival, Sustainability, Differentiation, Monopoly and Development. *Proceedings of National Conference on Advances in Information Technology, Management, Social Sciences and Education*, (2018), pp. 130-141. ISBN No.: 978-81-938040-8-7.
- [34] Aithal, P. S. (2015). Mobile Business as an Optimum Model for Ideal Business. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, 5(7), 146-159, DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.163880>.
- [35] Aithal P. S. and Shubhrajyotsna Aithal (2014). Ideal education system and its realization through online education model using mobile devices, *Proceedings of IISRO Multi Conference 2014*, 140 - 146, ISBN No. 978-81-927104-33-13. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.62059>.
- [36] Aithal P. S. and Shubhrajyotsna Aithal (2015). An Innovative Education Model to realize Ideal Education System. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM)*, 3(3), 2464 - 2469. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.61654>.
- [37] Aithal, P. S. & Vaikuth Pai, T. (2016). Concept of Ideal Software and its Realization Scenarios. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME)*, 1(1), 826-837. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.160908>.
- [38] Aithal, P. S. & Priyesh Pai, T. (2017). Opportunity for Realizing Ideal Computing System using Cloud Computing Model. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education(IJCSBE)*, 1(2), 60-71. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1094995>.

- [39] Aithal, P. S. & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal (2015). A review on Anticipated Breakthrough Technologies of 21st Century. *International Journal of Research & Development in Technology and Management Sciences*, 21(6), 112 – 133. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.61617>.
- [40] Qi, J., Wu, F., Li, L., & Shu, H. (2007). Artificial intelligence applications in the telecommunications industry. *Expert Systems*, 24(4), 271-291.
- [41] Zsarnoczky, M. (2017). How does Artificial Intelligence affect the Tourism Industry?. *VADYBA*, 31(2), 85-90.
- [42] Mehr, H., Ash, H., & Fellow, D. (2017). Artificial intelligence for citizen services and government. *Ash Cent. Democr. Gov. Innov. Harvard Kennedy Sch., no. August*, 1-12.
- [43] Eletter, S. F., Yaseen, S. G., & Elrefae, G. A. (2010). Neuro-based artificial intelligence model for loan decisions. *American Journal of Economics and Business Administration*, 2(1), 27.
- [44] Gang, T., Kai, C., & Bei, S. (2008, September). The research & application of Business Intelligence system in retail industry. In *2008 IEEE International Conference on Automation and Logistics* (pp. 87-91). IEEE.
- [45] Sanders, N. R. (2016). How to use big data to drive your supply chain. *California Management Review*, 58(3), 26-48.
- [46] Srivastava, U., & Gopalkrishnan, S. (2015). Impact of big data analytics on banking sector: Learning for Indian banks. *Procedia Computer Science*, 50, 643-652.
- [47] Xiang, Z., & Fesenmaier, D. R. (2017). Big data analytics, tourism design and smart tourism. In *Analytics in smart tourism design* (pp. 299-307). Springer, Cham.
- [48] Wang, Y., Kung, L., & Byrd, T. A. (2018). Big data analytics: Understanding its capabilities and potential benefits for healthcare organizations. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 126, 3-13.
- [49] Erickson, S., & Rothberg, H. N. (2016). Intangible dynamics in financial services. *Journal of Service Theory and Practice*, 26(5), 642-656.
- [50] Guo, Y., & Liang, C. (2016). Blockchain application and outlook in the banking industry. *Financial Innovation*, 2(1), 24.
- [51] Seebacher, S., & Schüritz, R. (2017, May). Blockchain technology as an enabler of service systems: A structured literature review. In *International Conference on Exploring Services Science* (pp. 12-23). Springer, Cham.
- [52] Hyvärinen, H., Risius, M., & Friis, G. (2017). A blockchain-based approach towards overcoming financial fraud in public sector services. *Business & Information Systems Engineering*, 59(6), 441-456.
- [53] Rabah, K. (2017). Challenges & opportunities for blockchain powered healthcare systems: A review. *Mara Research Journal of Medicine and Health Sciences*, 1(1), 45-52.
- [54] Lin, G., Fu, D., Zhu, J., & Dasmalchi, G. (2009). Cloud computing: IT as a service. *IT professional*, (2), 10-13.

-
- [55] Shi, A., Xia, Y., & Zhan, H. (2010, August). Applying cloud computing in financial service industry. *International Conference on Intelligent Control and Information Processing*(pp. 579-583). IEEE.
- [56] Khanna, P., & Babu, B. (2012). Cloud computing brokering service: A trust framework. *Cloud Computing*, 206-212.
- [57] Gilbert, D., & Powell-Perry, J. (2001). Exploring developments in web based relationship marketing within the hotel industry. *Journal of Hospitality & Leisure Marketing*, 9(3-4), 141-159.
- [58] Vaccaro, V. L., & Cohn, D. Y. (2004). The evolution of business models and marketing strategies in the music industry. *International journal on media management*, 6(1-2), 46-58.
- [59] Liaw, C. Y., & Guvendiren, M. (2017). Current and emerging applications of 3D printing in medicine. *Biofabrication*, 9(2), 024102.
- [60] Li, T. I. N. G. J. I. E., Aspler, J. O. S. E. P. H., Kingsland, A. R. L. E. N. E., Cormier, L. M., & Zou, X. U. E. J. U. N. (2016). 3d printing—a review of technologies, markets, and opportunities for the forest industry. *J. Sci. Technol. For. Prod. Process*, 5(2), 30.
- [61] Da Xu, L., He, W., & Li, S. (2014). Internet of things in industries: A survey. *IEEE Transactions on industrial informatics*, 10(4), 2233-2243.
- [62] Shah, S. H., & Yaqoob, I. (2016). A survey: Internet of Things (IOT) technologies, applications and challenges. In *2016 IEEE Smart Energy Grid Engineering (SEGE)* (pp. 381-385). IEEE.
- [63] Andersson, P., & Mattsson, L. G. (2015). Service innovations enabled by the “Internet of Things”. *IMP Journal*, 9(1), 85-106.
- [64] Elhoseny, M., Abdelaziz, A., Salama, A. S., Riad, A. M., Muhammad, K., & Sangaiah, A. K. (2018). A hybrid model of internet of things and cloud computing to manage big data in health services applications. *Future generation computer systems*, 86, 1383-1394.
- [65] Balaji, M. S., & Roy, S. K. (2017). Value co-creation with Internet of things technology in the retail industry. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 33(1-2), 7-31.
- [66] Aithal, P. S., & Aithal, S. (2015). An innovative education model to realize ideal education system. *International Journal of scientific research and management (IJSRM)*, 3(3), 2464-2469.
- [67] Barnhart, F. D., & Pierce, J. E. (2012). Becoming mobile: Reference in the ubiquitous library. *Journal of Library Administration*, 52(6-7), 559-570.
- [68] Lee, Y., & Chang, H. (2012). Ubiquitous health in Korea: progress, barriers, and prospects. *Healthcare informatics research*, 18(4), 242-251.
- [69] Feldman, M. P., & Lendel, I. (2010). Under the lens: the geography of optical science as an emerging industry. *Economic Geography*, 86(2), 147-171.
- [70] Zhang, Y., Chowdhury, P., Tornatore, M., & Mukherjee, B. (2010). Energy efficiency in telecom optical networks. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 12(4), 441-458.

- [71] Navab, N. (2004). Developing killer apps for industrial augmented reality. *IEEE Computer Graphics and applications*, 24(3), 16-20.
- [72] Lee, K. (2012). Augmented reality in education and training. *TechTrends*, 56(2), 13-21.
- [73] Keller, B., Möhring, M., & Schmidt, R. (2015). Augmented reality in the travel industry: a perspective how modern technology can fit consumer's needs in the service industry. *Naples Forum on Services*.
- [74] Shubhrajyotsna Aithal & Aithal, P. S. (2018). The Realization Opportunity of Ideal Energy System using Nanotechnology Based Research and Innovations. *International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology*, 3(2), 1-15. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2531876>.
- [75] Aithal, P. S. & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal (2019). New Directions in Scholarly Research- Some Fearless Innovations & Predictions for 21st Century Research. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 4(1), 1-19. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2557222>.
- [76] Aithal P. S., Suresh Kumar P. M., (2015). Black Ocean Strategy - A Probe into a New type of Strategy used for Organizational Success. *GE International Journal of Management Research*, 3(8), 45 - 65. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.163423>.
- [77] Hou, Shengtian (2007). Green ocean strategy: Obtaining sustainable competitive advantage, Beijing: Tsinghua University Press, pp. 183-197.
- [78] Kim, W. C., & Mauborgne, R. (2005). Blue ocean strategy. *California Management Review*, 47(3), 105-121.
- [79] Porter, M. E. (1997). Competitive strategy. *Measuring Business Excellence*, 1(2), 12-17.
- [80] Aithal, P. S. (2016). The concept of Ideal Strategy & its realization using White Ocean Mixed Strategy. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research (IJMSBR)*, 5(4), 171-179. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161108>.

Paper 5

**INNOVATIVE AND CREATIVE TEACHING TO
STIMULATE PARTICIPATION OF STUDENTS AT
HIGHER EDUCATION FOR SOCIAL CHANGE**

Aditi Jha

Associate Professor,
Rachana Sansad college of Applied Art and craft,
Mumbai.

Abstract

“Human existence depends upon compassion and curiosity leading to knowledge, but curiosity and knowledge without compassion is inhuman and compassion without curiosity and knowledge is ineffectual”. – Victor Weisskopf, nuclear physicist [Shapiro, 2011]. Yet one of the most important and difficult jobs in the world is teaching. In education, student participation refers to the degree of attention, curiosity, interest, optimism and passion that students show when they are learning, or being taught. This extends to the level of motivation that they have to learn and progress in their education.

1. RESEARCH PROBLEM

How can we as educators nurture students of design Institute to be good future engaged citizens for sustainable development of the society.

1. OBJECTIVE

This paper aims to discuss the fact that responsibility towards the society needs to be inculcated through education system into the mindset of the students to prepare them to be good citizens for the betterment of the community as a whole. We as educators have the key role not only to develop knowledge but also to promote a social responsibility culture.

Secondly, through explorative case studies, the involvement of students in social change is brought forth.

We also determine some obstacles faced while promoting and initiating such initiatives.

3. VIEWS AND DEFINITIONS

The philosopher John Dewey wrote, "Education is not a preparation for life but life itself." He believed that classrooms aren't just places to study social change, but a place to spark social change.

Socrates himself said, "Education is a kindling of a flame, not the filling of a vessel". It then follows that using Socrates' method of discourse as a teaching tool will line-up well with Dewey's goals for the classrooms. Design education is no exception.

According to Plato, the purpose of education is to cultivate the intellect, pursued for its own sake, in order to uncover the universal themes and natural laws that the prepared mind can discern beneath the surface confusion of life. (Berman, 1990)

Socrates states, the purpose of an education is to prepare citizens to participate in public affairs. (Berman, 1990).

Change is an inevitable law of life. Change should by all means happen for good. "What you leave behind is not what is woven into lives of others". – Pericles (circa 495-429 BCE), the most promising and prominent Greek statesman.

Aristotle states, "Educating the mind without educating the heart is no education at all" So how do we as educators, bring change in the society for the betterment of life?

Social Responsibility is an ethical framework and suggests that an entity be it an organization or individual has an obligation to act for the benefit of society at a large.

"Be the change that you want to see in the world" as stated by Gandhiji. "The world is moved along, not only by the mighty shoves of its heroes, but also by the aggregate of tiny pushes of each honest worker – "Helen Keller".

"We need to help young people recognize their own capacity to do good, and help them discover the rewards of generosity" – Bill Clinton. Social responsibility is a personal investment in the well-being of others and the planet [Berman, 1990].

Social responsibility of education is a process whereby the whole community transmits to the next generation appropriate values, traditions, skills and cultural norms. Service learning not only promotes good deeds but also academic success.

2. METHODOLOGY

As the paper aims to discuss the fact that social responsibility needs to be inculcated in the students through education system, the focus group are students of Design School of Fourth

Year. The number of students is 54. The focus of the task is to observe and understand the participation and creative output of the students towards various social issues identified by them.

Students were encouraged to identify a problem around them which needed attention. They were further led towards research regarding the social issue. They moved out of the classrooms, mixed with their target group, interviewed them; spend time with them to understand the root cause of the problem and the expectations of the target group. Later several brainstorming sessions were conducted; problem solving processes were carried out, material exploration done to narrow down upon ways to resolve the problem. Then companies were approached to carry out a docket project with the CSR funds of the companies.

5.DISCUSSION

Students' participation in any noble cause had always been and will always continue in future.

STUDENTS' PARTICIPATION IN INDIAN FREEDOM MOVEMENT

During the struggle for independence in India, the youth had actively participated which is noteworthy. They had selflessly taken up the leadership and contributed immensely, plunged into the streets protesting the wrong governance of the British rule. During participation of Bengal in 1905, the young students were in the leadership to protest against the British, all for a social cause, political freedom of the motherland. The whole world is aware of the contribution of young freedom fighters Khudiram Bose, Bhagat Singh, Chandra Shekhar Azad, Bagha Jatin, Subhash Chandra Bose and innumerable more, in the freedom struggle.

Students of various socio-cultural backgrounds come together in the institutions. Out of India's total population projected close to 1.37 billion [Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, Government of India, 2017], 34.6 million are enrolled into higher education. [All India Survey on Higher Education, 2015-16, Govt. of India, Ministry of Human Resource Development, Dept. of Higher Education]. The future of our country is in their hands. So if we as educators can motivate them to participate in social responsible projects, we see immense scope of prospective students who can develop the future of our country into a sustained and empathetic environment. Youth force is dynamic in nature as many skills are developed during this period.

Social empathy and responsibility of social well-being should be nurtured right from the early childhood days, ie. from school level, like keeping the surrounding clean, helping others, hygienic habits like washing of hands before food, cover the mouth while coughing or planting trees for a greener environment, not wasting food, etc. this is also a part of the curriculum in environmental science, moral values etc. The young students at school follow the instructions and acts accordingly. But, when the child reaches higher education, he is matured enough and has his own developed ideas. He has his set of understandings and beliefs. He now focuses more on his own well-being and the whole world is a competition now. He has immense energy ready

to be channelized. So interception at this point of time is very necessary to guide them to understand their responsibilities, not only towards themselves, their family but the society as a whole. They can achieve bigger goals (towards society) along with academics and career. They can be leaders of social change. This realization can only be fostered within them by the teachers through various curriculums and projects.

In any formal education system, most learning activities take place in classrooms. It is an important context where both students and instructor come into contact to share information in their quest of knowledge. Teachers and students are the two major stakeholders in Higher Education System. Teachers are believed to be the key actors and agents of social change. It is a long drawn debate that whether teachers should be tasked to preparing students to confirm or to actively push for progress and improvement where there is necessary.

It is therefore a challenge to inculcate awareness, social responsibility and leadership well in the minds since the formative years by sensitizing them about social issues. This is a renewed concern for educators of today. Nurturing their talents and interests to address various aspects of social responsibility, co-operative learning, developing morals, thus leading them towards global education is the primary focus.

TEACHER'S RESPONSIBILITY TO STIMULATE SOCIAL PARTICIPATION

The teacher needs to open a window regarding the problems pertaining to the society; to be informed about the problem is the first step towards solving it.

6.ACCEPT THE RELATIONSHIP WITH SOCIETY

With today's classroom curriculum the complete focus is on self-development. The student just tries to excel in academics. On the contrary, our goal should be holistic development of the students. Teachers should make them realize that they are a part of a greater community and understand and accept their responsibility towards it. The self-realization of responsibility will build an empathetic outlook in the students. Students prefer hands-on activities and to get to collaborate with their peers.

In the Case study carried out, the focus group was given a task to explore and study problems in the society which needed immediate attention. They moved out of the classroom, interviewed people, did some surveys and finally came up with very interesting problems which caught their attention.

Some of the interesting problems traced by the students are as follows:

- Children in slums suffer illness due to germs that go to their body through food, because they do not wash their hands before eating.
- Spitting on roads and on the walls, thinking it is dirty anyways. This causes a dirty and unhygienic environment as many germs are transmitted by spit.

- Increased rate of crime in youth due to lack of Emotion Management and influence of violence in movies.
- Plight of farmers of Vidharva districts of Maharashtra
- Water logging problems in Mumbai during rains.
- After festivals, Idols are immersed in the water resources. Idols being made of plaster-of-paris do not dissolve and cause pollution and kills water-life.
- Lack of education or learning help to poor kids or kids of domestic help.

There were several problems that were identified. After identification of the problems, brainstorming and research, a unique and creative design solution was derived for each.

Options of clay idols with seeds embedded in them, which can be re-turned to the soil. Seeds embedded in-turn would germinate into new plants thus helping in developing a green environment. Adopting BMC primary schools and taking out a little time to teach a poor child, as an extension of 'each one teach one' initiative would help the society immensely. While adopting schools, the premises were painted thematically for children to encourage them and give them a happy environment for learning. Teaching kids through animated story-telling sessions about the importance of washing hands before eating or other hygienic habits, judicious use of plastic, designing app for support of youth who are suffering from emotional management issues with the use of technology. These were some of the very creative solutions proposed by students of a design school. It made them aware of the society and connected them to the needs and problems around them.

What they learned from the project:

- ▶ Create leadership development opportunities and foster a commitment to social and civic responsibilities
- ▶ Exploring real world issues
- ▶ Motivate students to be empathetic towards social causes and encourage them to think of innovative and creative approaches
- ▶ Developing participatory activities and social skills
- ▶ Experiments related to social responsibility
- ▶ Build a co-ordination with industry experts to join hands with students for social cause.

Students can be motivated to participate in various types of social responsibility activities like:

- Environment sustainability activities
- Direct philanthropic giving
- Spreading knowledge and education
- Ethical business practice and

- Help in empowerment by building entrepreneurship
- Fund raising activities
- Help to eradicate substance abuse
- Health, hygiene and sanitation activities
- Cleanliness drives
- Drives to fight taboos with scientific logic and train the society to think likewise
- Product development for sustainable society and emergencies and manufacture with minimum cost or from refused material.

Some innovative teaching techniques and strategies that can be implemented:

- Inquiry based learning. This technique triggers curiosity in students. The teachers in this case act as facilitators.
- QR codes. For quick response, QR codes can be developed in the study material for quick response. It can lead students to information just by scanning the code on a students' digital device.
- Problem or project based learning (PBL). This system develops deeper learning competencies. Students are introduced to using real world scenarios, challenges and problems thus engaging students in critical thinking, problem solving, team work and self-management.
The problems students solve can be presented to community leaders to solve problems in actual society. Hence, collaborative project based learning (PBL) is actually helping to bring social change and the major stakeholders, teachers and students functioning as the actual agents of the social change. Thus, PBL techniques connect students and institutes to the real worlds.
- Wisely managed classroom technology. ICT in education, digital tools and problem solving skills will help to connect more with these real-time projects.

Challenges faced by students during the experimentation

- ▶ Lack of information
- ▶ Not able to reach target group
- ▶ Obstacles from parents
- ▶ Pressure of classroom curriculum
- ▶ Lack of funds
- ▶ Challenge of creative output

7.CONCLUSION:

As Rabindranath Tagore states in his poetry “Let My Country Awake” to inspire individual and social change: “Into the heaven of freedom my father, let my country awake”. Let our country awake in a tomorrow where today’s youth has taken and lead responsibility to eradicate social problems, into a world of free and global learning sensitization, innovative teaching, sustainable development.

References:

3. <http://soeonline.american.edu>
4. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/danielnewman/2017/01/10/how-to-build-an-innovative-workplace-culture-with-experimentation/#46b963c7c222>
5. <https://www.jagranjosh.com/articles/how-school-students-can-make-a-difference-in-the-society>
6. <http://www.preservearticles.com/education/short-essay-on-qteacher-as-an-agent-of-change-and-a-social-workerq>
7. <https://fourthambit.com/fa/blogs/102022>
8. <https://www.sharda.ac.in/blog/student-social-responsibilities/> written by Admin August 24, 2017
9. <https://www.news24.com/MyNews24/role-and-importance-of-students-in-society-20160315> ‘Educating for SocialResponsibility’/SEMINAR%202019/e1_199011_berman.pdf

Paper 6

**A STUDY ON THE MEASURES TAKEN BY
COGNIZANT TECHNOLOGY SOLUTIONS FOR
ACHIEVING SUSTAINABLE GROWTH IN THE
DIGITAL MARKET**

K. Geetha Poornima¹ & Krishna Prasad K²

¹ Research Scholar College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India, Email: poornima.sanjay@spcputtur.org

² College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

Abstract

Information Technology is a sector that has experienced swift change. Whatever is new today becomes obsolete tomorrow. A company providing Information Technology solutions has to respond quickly to the change in technology. The company has to develop strategies to provide services in emerging technology. The sustainable growth of an IT company depends much on the service areas. The company has to analyze market trends customer requirements and plan accordingly. Cognizant Technology Solutions is a multinational company whose headquarters is in Teaneck, New Jersey, United States. The Company was founded in the year 1994 by Kumar Mahadeva. The major services provided vary from Business and Technology, Consulting, Application Development and Maintenance, IT Infrastructure, Business Intelligence, Data Warehouse, Health Care, Mobile Computing Customer Relationship Management, Supply Chain Management, R&D Outsourcing and Testing Solutions. To achieve sustainable growth, the company has to set long-term goals, provide necessary skills to the workforce, evaluate its performance against the performance of the competitors and provide the best quality of products/services in cost-effective way. In our paper we have tried to study the business model of Cognizant Technologies, business strategies, measures taken by the company in terms of skill development of its employees, role-based career structure followed, marketing strategy, and Customer retention as steps towards sustainable growth. We also focus on company's contribution towards green initiative and Corporate Social Responsibilities and SWOC analysis of the company. Finally, we have analyzed Cognizant company's best practices and innovations towards latest digital business such as Internet of things, Data Science, Data Analytics, Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Cloud Computing etc. to consider it as global leader in digital business.

Keywords: Cognizant, Business Model, Business Strategy, Customer Retention, Digital Market, Digital Services.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cognizant Technology Solutions Corporation was founded in the year 1994. It is world's prominent professional service oriented multinational organization. Its headquarters is in Teaneck, New Jersey, United States. Its motto is to transform what is envisioned by the clients into a product or service suitable in digital era. The tagline of Cognizant is "Keep

changing”. Its service areas include banking and insurance, healthcare and life sciences, retail and consumer goods, manufacturing and logistics, travel and hospitality, energy and utilities, communications and media, and technology industries.

Vision and Mission Statement

Vision

Eco friendly policies and effective use of natural resources achieve sustainable development

Mission

The single-minded objective of Cognizant is to devote the knowledge and experience in the field of business and the global resources available to work with customers and strengthen their organization.

2. OBJECTIVES OF CASE STUDY

The case study to identify measures taken by Cognizant Technology Solutions in sustainable growth is based on the information collected from Company’s website and other resources available on the Internet [1, 2]. The objectives are

- To study company’s business models
- To learn about employee company’s workforce training and development strategies
- To know about the growth of the company in terms of revenues and workforce
- To understand recruitment policies of the company
- To know the organizational structure and operational divisions of the company
- To make use of SWOC analysis for identifying the aspects which require more focus
- To know about the company’s competitors

3. HISTORY

Dun & Bradstreet and Sathyam Computers jointly founded the business during early 1994. It was named as Sathyam Systems Dun and Bradstreet (DBSS). As the inner technology department of Dun & Bradstreet Company, it aimed on developing large-scale IT projects for companies in Dun & Bradstreet. It began tracking customers beyond Dun & Bradstreet from 1996 onwards. DBSS was renamed Cognizant in 1997. Teaneck, New Jersey of the United States became the headquarters of the company in March 1998 and Kumar Mahadeva became the first CEO. The main focus of the company during those days was on Y2K and Web Technology related projects. In 1998, Cognizant Corporation was divided into two organizations and they were named as IMS Health and Nielsen Media Research. In the same year, the focus of the company got shifted from Y2K related projects to applications management. In the year 2002, the revenue of the company was \$229 million. The company started to grow further by taking projects related to maintenance which were rejected by larger IT companies of the time. Cognizant was the company to be assessed by industry-process certifications, such as P-CMM level 5, BS 7799, SEI-CMMi Level 5 [3, 4].

In 2003, Lakshmi Narayanan was appointed as the CEO. During his tenure, the service area of the company got widened into Business Process Outsourcing (BPO). Furthermore, the company started to provide its services in the field of business consulting. In the year 2006, Fransico DSouza became the third CEO of the company. During early 2000s the company started to experience a swift growth rate both horizontally and vertically. In the year 2004, Cognizant was recognized as a leading provider of IT services by Gartner, Forrester, AMR

and IDC. In the same year it was added to the prominent NASDAQ 100 Index. In 2006, it got emerged as the fastest global IT service provider to reach \$1 billion revenue.

The year 2008 happens to an important one in the history of Cognizant as it entered Fortune 1000 with more than \$2.8 billion revenue. In 2011, the company was enlisted in Fortune 500 with a ranking of 484. By its increased revenue the ranking got improved and is currently at 193 in Fortune 500. From 1st of April 2019, the company is being lead by Brian Humphires in the position of CEO.

Round the globe, the company has 288,200 employees of which more than 150,000 are in India. The company has totally ten centers in India with Chennai being the largest in terms of head count. The other centers include Bangalore, Coimbatore, Gurgaon, Noida, Hyderabad, Kochi, Kolkotta, Mangalore, Mumbai and Pune. There are 166 centers spread across the world. The global delivery centers are located in the UK, Hungary, The Netherlands, Spain, China, Philippines, Canada, Brazil, Argentina, Mexico etc.

4. GROWTH

The firm has extended its business over the years beginning with providing financial solutions and projects concerned to Y2K, banking, healthcare and consulting. The growth in terms of revenue and workforce is enlisted in Table-1. [3, 4, 5].

Table-1 Growth of the company in terms of workforce and revenue

Year	Revenue in Billion \$	Workforce	Fortune 500 Rank
2019	16.12	288200	193
2018	14.66	281600	195
2017	14.14	260000	205
2016	13.48	244000	230
2015	12.41	211500	288
2014	10.26	211500	308
2013	8.84	171400	352
2012	7.34	156700	398
2011	6.21	137700	484
2010	4.54	104000	-

4.1 Products/Services Offered

During early years the company aimed to provide quality solutions to the projects related to Y2K. Early 2000s is considered as the growth period of the company. During this period, it started to open up for providing business solutions. This has become a prominent reason for the increase in growth rate, which was consistently high at that time. At present, the services

offered by the company are broadly categorized as Cognizant Digital Business, Cognizant Digital Operations and Cognizant Digital Systems and Technology [3, 4].

The theme of Cognizant Digital Business is "Keep it human." It provides the impression that there is no human intervention when a particular business or service is automated. Cognizant Digital Business, however, is organized so that people are at the core of business service. This type of business works on Digital Maturity Diagnostic framework. Here the customer will conduct quality assessments and check the advancement of the project against its objectives and quality parameters of the industry. This will assist the new business to handle its transformation into digital form. The popular services provided under this category include projects based on Artificial intelligence, Digital; Product Engineering, Digital Strategy, Interactive, Internet of Things etc.

The motto of Digital Operations is "Make the promise of digital real". The company involves its clients in envisioning the new products. Creative employees along with the help of their R&D department build the new solutions and the entire business infrastructure of the client is re-engineered quickly and efficiently to thereby increasing the growth in business. The major services offered by the company under this category are Enterprise Services, Industry & Platform Solutions, Intelligent Process Automation etc.

The motto of Cognizant Digital Systems and Technology is "Modernize your core IT". When running a digital enterprise there will be several hurdles, risks and unforeseen threats. Cognizant will partner with its clients and re-build their code IT infrastructure in a cost-effective way taking care of all possible risks, hurdles and security issues. The major services in this section are Application Services, Cloud Enablement, Cognizant Infrastructure Services, Cognizant Security, Core Modernization, Digital Product Engineering, Enterprise Application Services, Quality Engineering and Assurance etc.

It offers services to a wide range of business sectors including Banking, Healthcare, Communications, Consumer Goods, Education, Capital Markets, Information Services, Insurance, Life Sciences, Manufacturing, Media & Entertainment, Oil and Gas, Retails, Technology, Transportation & Logistics, Travel & Hospitality and Utilities, Cognizant provides a wide range of information technology consulting and business processing outsourcing services, including Project-based application services, Business process services, Business and technology consulting, Complex systems integration, Application outsourcing, IT infrastructure and cloud services, Data Analytics, Business Intelligence, Customer Relationship Management, Data Warehousing, Supply Chain Management, Engineering Management Solutions, ERP Testing Solutions. This stands as the testimony for the growth of the company.

4.2 Executive Leadership

Cognizant has a strong leadership team that upholds the ethical values and objectives, takes care of business affairs and decision making. This team will set core values and objectives for the company as per the policies of Corporate Governance. It includes Brian Humphries as Chief Executive Officer, Karen Mc Loughlin as Chief Financial Officer, Malcom Frank as President, Cognizant Digital Business, Srinivasan Veeraraghavachary as Chief Operating Officer, Debashis Chatterjee as Executive Vice President and President, Global Delivery, Ramakrishna Prasad Chintamaneni as Executive Vice President and President, Global Industries and Consulting, Matthew Friedrich as Executive Vice President, General Counsel, Chief Corporate Affairs Officer and Secretary, Sumithra Gomatam as Executive Vice

President and President, Digital Operations, James Lennox as Executive Vice President, Chief People Officer, Sean Middleton as Senior Vice President and President, Cognizant Accelerator, Issam Allen Shaheen as Executive Vice President, North American Digital Hubs, Dharmendra Kumar Sinha as Executive Vice President and President, Global Client Services and Santosh Thomas as Executive Vice President and President, Global Growth Markets [6].

4.3 Product Category [Corporate Groups and Workforce Hierarchy]

To categorize its products Cognizant uses three-horizon strategy. The products or services offered by the company fall under one or the other category. It has a well defined corporate structure and workforce hierarchy.

Table-2 Product Category Corporate Groups and Workforce Hierarchy[3][5].

Product Category	Corporate Groups	Workforce Hierarchy
Cognizant Digital Business Cognizant Digital Operations Cognizant Digital Systems & Technology	Office of CEO Corporate Delivery Global Legal Global Mobility Global Talent Acquisition Strategic Partnership Delivery Excellence Analyst Relationships Ethics and Compliance Corporate Security Global Finance Global IT Global HR	Executive VP Senior VP Vice President (VP) Associate VP Senior Director Director Associate Director Senior Manager Manager Program Analyst Associate Program Analyst Program Analyst Trainee

4.4 Acquisitions

Acquisitions play important role in the growth of a company. The company firmly believes that the performance of the company will increase by collaborating with the business activities of the competitors. When competitor’s company is acquired, it eliminates the competition in the field of business and increases the market share. Cognizant started to acquire other companies from the year 2002. [15] The latest acquisition is Zenith Technologies

in June 2019. Over the years Cognizant has acquired 56 other companies Table-1 gives the list of important acquisitions made by Cognizant. The financial deals of acquisitions are not disclosed by the company[7].

Table-3 List of Companies acquired by Cognizant

SN	Name of the Company	Country	Business	Year
1	Zenith Technologies	Ireland	Life Sciences Automation	2019
2	Meritsoft	Ireland	Fintech	2019
3	Oy Samlink	Finland	Technology Provider	2019
4	Softvision	USA	Digital Solutions	2018
5	SaaSFocus	Australia	CRM Consulting	2018
6	Hedera Consulting	Belgium	Consulting	2018
7	Bolder Healthcare Solutions	USA	Health Care IT	2018
8	Zone	UK	Digital Agency	2017
9	Netcentric	Switzerland	Digital Marketing	2017
10	Mirabeau BV	Netherlands	Digital Marketing, Customer Experience	2016
11	UnitedHealthcare Ireland Limited	Ireland	Healthcare	2002

- 1) **Zenith Technologies:** This company was founded in the year 1998. It is a leading company that develops softwares to ensure supply of vital treatments to patients across the world. It operates across five continents, providing stable and reliable software to top Pharma and Biotech companies [8].
- 2) **Meritsoft:** It is a top financial service company founded in the year 2000. It provides customized solutions to cash management, tax management, and cash flow functions between different financial organizations. The products developed by this company are used in world's top most investment banks. Because of the policy, the names of banks and details of transactions are not disclosed. This company is recognized as Deloitte Best Managed Companies in Ireland 2018.
- 3) **Oy Samlink AB:** This company offers solutions to financial sector and E-Commerce applications. It has two delivery centres in Finland and several top-level banks are the clients of this company.
- 4) **Softvision:** It is an outsourcing company in the field of software development in Romania. It was founded in the year 1998 by Laurențiu Russo and Cristian Motioc. The main service areas of this company include designing and engineering of digital products, transforming existing applications into digital form etc.
- 5) **SaaSFocus:** It is an agile consulting company that provides cloud technology services to consulting firms. It was founded in the year 2011. The basic focus of this company is sales force consultancy.
- 6) **Hedera Consulting:** This Company provides specialized services in the field of business advisory and data analytics to many industry sectors. Founded in the year 2009, it deals with leading customers across the world in the field of business data analytics.
- 7) **Bolder Healthcare Solutions:** Provides financial solutions to groups of hospitals in US. It focuses on cash flow management in the healthcare field. It operates at 15

location in the United States and all the top-level hospitals in the United States are the clients of this company[16].

- 8) **Zone:** It provides interactive digital contents to the business firms. It was founded in the year 2000. Headquartered in London, it provides services to brands such as adidas, Aviva, Deutsche Telecom etc.
- 9) **Netcentric:** It is a leader in marketing the digital business whose headquarters is in Zurich. It works for leading business brands in Switzerland and provides wide variety of digital solutions to business organizations.
- 10) **Mirabeau BV:** it is a digital marketing and customer service agency founded in the year 2001. The specializations of this company include travel and hospitality, financial services B2B sectors etc. The acquisition of this company is Cognizant's step towards expansion of its business across Europe.
- 11) **UnitedHealthcare Ireland Limited:** This is the first company acquired by Cognizant in the year 2002. It is an expert in the healthcare industry providing solutions United Healthcare groups comprising of UnitedHealthcare, Uniprise, Ovations, Specialized Care Services and Ingenix.

4.5 Layoffs

All IT companies follow a strict lay-off strategy. The justification of the companies for this strategy is realignment of business. To control over expenses and redundancies in job, Cognizant has slashed hundreds of employees this year. Cognizant follows a strict appraisal strategy. Employees whose performance is marginal are separated from the project. Cognizant claims that the headcount growth is more when compared to revenue growth. To control the overhead expenses, employees with 8+ years of experience who recorded average or below average performance are slashed from the company.

5. BUSINESS MODELS

Use of a business model plays a key role in the success of Company's business. Developing a business model is more like planning the business itself. Revenue of a company depends much on the business model it follows. Proper business model will mainly focus on the type and quality of services to be provided along with the revenue and cost factors associated with the business. Cognizant is has adopted several customer friendly business models [4]. Some of them are

1. Two-in-a box model
2. Global delivery model
3. Cognizant unique operating model
4. C-2020 Model

1) Two-in-a-Box Model

This model is also called as "Co-leading model" [3]. In case of complex projects one may not have all the necessary skills to meet the varying needs of the customers. Hence company assigns two leaders for the same project. This is most suitable for offshore projects. Cognizant follows 'focused offshore development policy' all its offshore projects are handled in India. So one leader of the project will be in India and the other one will be his/her offshore counterpart. This model tries to bridge the communication gap between the offshore

clients and the developers. When two leaders put their 100% efforts with all dedication and utmost commitment the outcome will be 200%. The success of this model depends much on the coordination between the two leaders. If they work by complementing each other's strengths and overcoming each other's deficiencies then project will be completed fast. Cognizant expects two leaders to have one voice and are focused on the work they are expected to carry out.

2) Global Delivery Model

This model is followed by companies offering services related to consultancy. Cognizant uses this business model mainly for its offshore projects. Offshore projects are distributed among different locations to provide uninterrupted services across the globe. When the service providers are globally available, they can respond to customer needs quickly. This model also ensures that the resources can be accessed in a cost-effective way. Costlier on-shore resources are combined with cheaper offshore resources to provide good service to the customer for a reasonable charge. It also ensures that the company works round the clock ensuring all-time availability of service to its customers [3, 4].

3) Digital Operations Solution Model

This model is used to re-engineer client's business process to improve customer satisfaction, reduce operation cost and increase performance. it adopts emerging technologies such as Artificial Intelligence, IoT and Cloud Computing to re-build clients' business by creating interesting jobs [4].

4) C-2020 Model

This model contains three different entities involved namely Client Partner, Engagement Partner and Delivery Partner. Combining clients and employees in a project not only bridges the communication gap between the two but also increases the efficiency. When customers and employees become partners business, they too will play an important role in the overall growth of the company. Company sacrifices some percentage of its profit for the sake of customers, as it focuses on growth strategy rather than high margin strategy [4].

6. JOB RECRUITMENTS AND SKILL DEVELOPMENT

6.1 Job Recruitment

Cognizant follows well defined strategy for hiring new graduates for the post of Program Analyst Trainees or Programmer Trainees [9]. Graduates in engineering will be program analyst trainees and BSc, BCA, BCS graduates are recruited for the post of Programmer Trainees. Students with 70 or higher percentage of marks in 10th, 12th and qualifying exams with without backlogs at the moment of interview are eligible for applying. The method of recruitment comprises of consists of

1. Written Test
2. Technical Round
3. HR Round

Written test contains two major sections Aptitude Test and Verbal Ability Test. In aptitude test questions related to mathematical reasoning, current affairs etc will be asked. Verbal ability test is to check the language proficiency of the candidate.

Candidates who clear the aptitude test are eligible for technical interview. There is no strict rule for the way this technical interview is to be carried out. It all depends on the members or interview panel. There may be group discussions and questions on basic computer concepts such as Operating Systems, Database Management, Data Structures, and Programming Languages. Candidates may also be asked to code the puzzles. Once technical interview is completed, then candidate has to face HR interview. To analyze the skills, strengths, weaknesses of the candidate, this round is carried out. It happens to be the final round of the recruitment process.

6.2 Employee Training Policies

Cognizant expects every employee to learn about the Policies of the company, the products and services offered by the company and so on. In turn, the employees are asked to share their knowledge with the peers [3][10]. Cognizant firmly believes that if the employee has complete knowledge about the company then only he/she can work better for the same to achieve the goals and objectives set by the company.

The management of the company believes that their business is a knowledge enterprise. It upholds the fact that learning is a continuous process. As a result of this, it creates a full-fledged learning environment and inspires its employees to acquire necessary skills that are much needed for their long-term career in the company. To achieve this, the company has a unique learning program named Cognizant Career Architecture. The company supports role-based career model rather than the traditional designation based career model. There are different career tracks such as Technical career track, Program management career track and Domain career track. This helps the employees to choose a career track that is most suitable for their interest and competence.

There is a complete Cognizant Learning platform which contains syllabus, learning material, exam pattern and certification. Company expects its employees to acquire right skills for the right job. As per the skill-levels, the roles are categorized as Beginner, Learner, Practitioner, Expert and Guru. Every employee starting from the newly recruited one to middle level managers, have to get at least two certifications every year. The training program opted by an employee may be an instructor lead one or on the job training. At the end of the learning period, the employee has to undergo two assessments namely knowledge based assessment and skill based assessment. Knowledge base assessment involves theory exams and skill based assessment involves practical exams. The ultimate goal of the training and certification process is to making the employees of Cognizant ready towards the digital journey.

In addition to this, Cognizant provides special training programs on personality development, soft skills, presentation and communication skills and customer interaction skills. Furthermore, jobs are designed in such a way that every employee is assigned one or other responsibility to make the job more interesting one. Furthermore, there will be job rotation and job enrichment opportunity for the all-round development of the employees.

Digital Engineering, Cloud Computing, Internet of Things, Artificial Intelligence, Data Analysis, Machine Learning, and Deep Learning are the emerging technologies of today. Cognizant expects its employees to gain more proficiency in creating and marketing the product related to these emerging technologies. Cognizant Career Architecture helps them build their career so as to make them ready to take up projects related to emerging technology and develop projects more efficiently.

The company has a tie-up with BSchool for management which offers several customized courses for the Middle-level management. This will enable the employees across the globe to be suitable for the change in scenario in terms of technology or business models.

Initially the company had to invest more to make to train its employee acquire necessary skills. The employees who have undergone this rigor, have performed exceptionally well in their respective fields. The company needs fewer efforts to train them further to make them suitable for the change and advancement in technology.

7. IMPORTANT CUSTOMERS

Cognizant is known for its customer friendly policies [3]. 90% of its annual revenue is from the loyal customers who renew their agreements with the company. The policy of the company is not to disclose its customer details. The services offered by the company include Healthcare, Insurance, Banking and Financial Services, Manufacturing, Logistics, Energy and Utilities, Retail, Travel and Hospitality, Information Media and Entertainment, Technology and Communications.

- All the top 30 pharmaceutical companies, 16 of the top 20 U.S. healthcare plans, 3 leading U.S. PBM industries, 12 of the top 15 medical device firms are taking Cognizant's healthcare services. This is the clear proof of the healthcare consultancy knowledge of the company.
- In Insurance sector, among the top 10 Global Insurances 7 are the clients of Cognizant. 33 Among 50 US insurance companies are taking Cognizant's services in the field of Insurance consultancy.
- In banking, 17 of top 20 North American Financial institutions and all the European Banks are the client partners of Cognizant.
- In Manufacturing, Logistics, Energy and Utilities sector 7 of top 10 American OEM, 8 of top 15 industrial manufacturers, 5 Of top 15 chemical manufacturers, 5 of top 15 utilities in Na, 5 of top 10 Electric utilities in Europe, 4 of top 6 Oil and Gas super majors are the clients of Cognizant.
- 9 of the top 30 Global Retailers, 3 of the leading US Airlines, 3 of the World's leading Restaurant Chains and 2 of the top 4 Global Distribution System companies take the services of Cognizant in Retail, Travel and Hospitality sector.
- In the field of Information Media and Entertainment the prominent clients of Cognizant include 10 of top 10 Global Media Companies, 4 of top 6 major US movie studios, 5 of top 10 information services and 13 of top 15 publishers.
- Technology and Communications sectors 4 of top 5 OEMs, 5 of top 10 information service providers across the world, 7 of top 10 Communications Service Providers and Equipment Venders and top 3 Cable providers are the client partners of Cognizant Technology Solutions.

8. SWOC Analysis

The purpose of SWOC analysis is to understand the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and challenges of the company in the field of Business [11, 12]. Cognizant Technology Solutions is a US based multinational service provider company that provides IT services in Healthcare, Insurance, Banking and Financial Services, Manufacturing, Logistics, Energy and Utilities, Retail, Travel and Hospitality, Information Media and Entertainment, Technology and Communications.

Strengths

1. **Customer friendly nature:** All business models and the strategies of the company are client friendly in nature.
2. **Focused digital technology and innovation:** The company's three horizon strategy is very much useful to focus the development of IT solutions.
3. **Friendly environment for the workforce:**
4. **Highly skilled workforce:** Top-level managements are recruited from IITs IIMs and similar institutions across the world. Skill development policies of the company make every employee to acquire right skills for the right job.
5. **Well defined disaster recovery model:** The company provides a well structured disaster recovery plan. If the project is to be delivered from the Chennai centre and there is flood in Chennai, then the same project will be delivered from nearest centre without charging extra on its clients.
6. **Cost effective services:** The main focus of the company is Speed of Service (SoS). When quality business solutions are created by taking less time, the services will always be cost effective
7. **Big data and Cloud Computing:** The company is ahead in big data capabilities and cloud computing technologies compared to peers or competitors
8. **Branded for Healthcare and Financial Consultancy:** The Company has established a brand name in the field of Healthcare and Consultancy. The big list of clients in this field stands the testimony for this.
9. **Round the clock availability of Services:** Being a multinational company, its branches are spread all over the world. It provides services round the clock as it follows Global Delivery Model.

Weakness

1. **More focus to North America Markets:** Most of the clients are from North America. When the focus of the company is limited to one geographical area, it directly affects to the growth of the company.
2. **Limited depth in Infrastructure management:** Though company provides services in almost all fields of business, it lacks expertise in Infrastructure and management field. If more focus is given to this field, it can attract wide range of customers.
3. **High investment on training the employees:** The Company trains every employee starting from newly recruited ones to middle level managers. Training will become a overhead if the employees do not perform up to the mark after

Opportunities

1. **To accept projects related to Government:** Major clients of the company are from private sectors. In developing countries, there is a lot of scope for catching hold of Government projects as all Government projects are

- 2. Concentrate more on the European market:** In the emerging technologies the Company has to focus more on European Markets.
- 3. Explore more avenues in Service and Healthcare sectors:** Exploring new avenues in the field of expertise will always become the main reason for the growth of any company.
- 4. Acquire more competitors in the global market:** When more and more competitors are acquired, their expertise and markets will also become the assets of the company there by increasing the growth.
- 5. Take up more projects in emerging technologies:** Digital market has observed rapid growth over in past few years. There are several emerging technologies in the field of IT that are to be focused more.
- 6. Focus more on potential customers:** For the sustainable growth and development, the company has to widen its market. Hence it has to find strategy for its potential customers.
- 7. Integration of existing business with emerging technologies:** The existing decision making strategies can be automated by applying Artificial Intelligence techniques to make decision making more effective one.

Challenges

- 1. Tough competition in the global market:** The Company has to compete with several well-established multi-national companies such as Tata Consultancy Services, Infosys, Wipro, Accenture and so on.
- 2. Stringent Government policies in case of outsourcing:** Government has enforced strict policies on outsourcing. Munch of Cognizant's business is in the field of outsourcing. When government enforces strict policies,
- 3. Increase in inflation in developing countries:** In developing counties like India, there is high inflation rate. This will have a direct impact on the revenue of the company.
- 4. Increase in wages and decrease in profitability:** Information Technology is a field where the wages of employees are more as most of the work is to be carried out manually [13, 14, 15].

9. CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITIES

A company's initiatives towards the development of downtrodden or underprivileged also plays as key factor in its growth [16]. For this purpose, Cognizant Foundation was established. It works in association with several NGOs such as Development of Humane Action (DHAN), Self Help Groups and Hand in Hand (HIH India)[17]. It has launched a unique program called Rebuilding Communities Program (RCP) for the rehabilitation of people affected by natural calamities. Cognizant's CSR focuses on the following fields:

- **Education:** Cognizant's employees volunteer during weekends, conduct classes to students of rural schools. In India, Cognizant Foundation has been working on different projects to provide quality education to underprivileged students. It had identified 160 different schools in rural areas and provided IT infrastructure. The volunteers of Cognizant Foundation prepare syllabus and educate teachers in the field of Information Technology. It also provides scholarships for the less-privileged students.

- **Outreach and Skill Development Programs:** Volunteers of Cognizant Foundation conduct number of activities such as awareness programs on health and hygiene, Nutrition, solid waste management are some of the outreach programs organized by Cognizant Foundation. It also organizes number of skill development programs such as beautician course, fashion designing course, cell phone servicing, and four wheeler driving course for the benefit of economically backward communities.
- **Healthcare:** Providing advanced Heart treatment to the poor and needy, providing artificial limbs for the differently abled, setting up of mobile Eye care units for visually impaired people, sponsoring dialysis treatment for the downtrodden are some of the programs organized by Cognizant Foundation for the benefit of society.
- **Community Development:** Re-construction of damaged schools, rehabilitation of people who were affected by exceptional rain in Chennai, rehabilitation of differently abled children, women empowerment programs organized by Cognizant Foundation come under this category.

10. GREEN INITIATIVES

The company is bound to uphold its vision statement to preserve natural resources[17]. The green initiatives taken by the company include

- Planting of trees
- Limited usage of natural resources
- Recycling of water
- Energy conservation
- Rainwater harvesting
- Avoiding the use of plastic cups, use and throw plates and paper cups on the campus
- Effective ways of solid waste management

11. COMPETITORS

Being multinational company it faces tough competitions in the global digital market from IT giants such as Infosys Limited, Wipro Limited, Accenture, HCL Technologies, Tata Consultancy Services, IBM Global Solutions, CGI, Tech Mahindra, Larsen & Toubro InfoTech, Insight, Capgemini etc. Because of its customer centric business model, creative workforce, accelerated quality of service (QoS) and Cost effectiveness, it is considered as one of the most admired IT company in the world [3, 4].

12. BEST PRACTICES

- “Focused Offshore Development Company”[3]: All the offshore centers are being operated From India. Cognizant calls them as Global In-house Centers or GICs. This has considerably reduced the cost of development and maintenance and increased the revenue.
- “Engage customers to build the growth”: [3] Cognizant treats its customers as partners. Customers who bring business are called as client partners and the company

involves them in its business. Some percentage of revenue generated will be given to the clients. This way it also helps in the growth of its customers.

- “Three horizon strategy”: To increase the focus of service and revenue, the entire business is divided into three horizons namely Cognizant Digital Business, Cognizant Digital Operations and Cognizant Digital Systems and Technology [3]. This has given a positive result and the company has reached its expected target.

13. AWARDS

- Cognizant is ranked 193 on the Fortune 500 in the year 2019.
- In the year 2019, the company received IBM’s beacon award for its outstanding services in the field of hybrid cloud solutions.
- It is ranked at 16 in Barron’s 100 Most Sustainable Companies for the year 2018,
- It is at 17th place on Fortune 50, at 18th place on the Fast Tech 25 by Forbes
- It is awarded as Forbes’ Best Employers for Women in the year 2018.
- It is regarded as Fortune’s one of the most admired companies from the past 11 years.
- It is named as a leader in services like Application Testing, Application Modernization and Artificial Intelligence by Gartner
- It is ranked among the Top 3 employers in the software industry by IDC with a higher ranking based on several key parameters such as employee satisfaction index, job satisfaction and career development, compensation and benefits [3, 4]

14. CONCLUSION

In the field of Information Technology, whatever new today becomes outdated one very fast. The company that provides services in the field of Information Technology has to change its strategy, products and it should try to respond to the current trends and needs of the customers. The success of any company in general and an IT company in particular depends much on how it responds to the change and advancement in technology. Being a Multinational company, it has spread the services round the globe. In the beginning Cognizant Technology Solutions was providing services to the customers in the field of healthcare and business. At present it is providing services in new technologies such as Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Cloud Computing and Internet of Things. Company’s Employee training strategies, Flexibility, Diversified business sectors, Employee retention policies, Customer Retention Policies, efforts towards green initiatives and Corporate Social Responsibilities are the testimonies for the success of the company.

References

- [1] Aithal, P. S., (2016). Study on ABCD Analysis Technique for Business Models, business strategies, Operating Concepts & Business Systems, *International Journal in Management and Social Science*, 4(1), 98-115. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161137>
- [2] Madhushree., Revathi, R., Anil Kumar, & Aithal, P. S. (2018). Business Strategy of Top Indian IT Company: MindTree. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 2(1), 22-36. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1249871>.

- [3] Cognizant Technology Solutions <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cognizant/>
- [4] Digital Solutions To Advance Your Business: Cognizant
<https://www.cognizant.com/> Date Accessed August 11, 2019
- [5] Number Of Employees At Cognizant 2008-2018
<https://www.statista.com/statistics/328322/cognizant-employee-numbers/> Date Accessed August 05, 2019
- [6] Cognizant Executive Leadership
<https://www.cognizant.com/about-cognizant/executive-leadership> Date Accessed August 02, 2019
- [7] Cognizant Acquisitions
https://www.crunchbase.com/search/acquisitions/field/organizations/num_acquisitions/cognizant-technology-solutions/ Date Accessed August 03, 2019
- [8] Eccles, Robert G., David Lane, and Prabakar 'PK' Kothandaraman. "Cognizant Technology Solutions." Harvard Business School Case 408-099, January 2008. (Revised May 2011.), [Online]. Retrieved on 10 August 2019.
- [9] "Cognizant Recruitment Process." *GeeksforGeeks*,
<https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/cognizant-recruitment-process/>[Online]. Retrieved on 10 August 2019.
- [10] Fyfe-Mills, K. (2017, October 11). Commitment to Talent Development Excellence. Retrieved from <https://www.td.org/magazines/td-magazine/commitment-to-talent-development-excellence> [Online]. Retrieved on 10 August 2019.
- [11] Aithal, P. S. and Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2015). Applying SWOC Analysis to an Institution of Higher Education. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, 5(7), 231-247. DOI :<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.163425>.
- [12] Aithal, P. S., (2016). Study on ABCD Analysis Technique for Business Models, Business Strategies, Operating Concepts & Business Systems. *International Journal in Management and Social Science*, 4(1), 98-115. DOI :<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161137>.
- [13] Zigu. (n.d.). Cognizant SWOT Analysis: Competitors & USP: BrandGuide. Retrieved from <https://www.mbaskool.com/brandguide/it-technology/14967-cognizant.html> [Online] Date Accessed August 04, 2019
- [14] Cognizant Swot & Pestle Analysis
<https://www.swotandpestle.com/cognizant/> Date Accessed August 05, 2019
- [15] <https://www.mbaskool.com/brandguide/it-technology/14967-cognizant.html> Website Title MBA Skool Study.Learn.Share. Article Title Cognizant SWOT Analysis: Competitors & USP: BrandGuide Date Accessed August 05, 2019
- [16] Thomas Andre., (2014). Corporate Social Responsibility Boosts Value Creation at the Base of the Pyramid. *Cahier de recherche*, 11, 10-20. <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-00989791>.
- [17] Social-alleviating Disparities in Education: Cognizant
<https://www.cognizant.com/about-cognizant/sustainability/social#panelvt5> Date Accessed August 06, 2019

Paper 7

NETWORK SECURITY: THREAT & MANAGEMENT

P. K. Paul¹, P. S. Aithal²

¹Executive Director, MCIS, Department of CIS, Raiganj University (RGU), West Bengal, India

²Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India

Corresponding Author: pkpaul.infotech@gmail.com

Abstract

Security these days is very important issue and required in all the organizations and institutions irrespective of nature. Computer Security is closely associated with Information Technology Security. Network Security is a vast world and it has a close connection with the Database Security, Web Security and Cloud Security. Network Security is required due to various issues viz. vulnerabilities, malware, spyware, ransomware, Trojan, virus, phishing, denial of services, web shells etc. There are different threat management defending systems viz. computer access control, application security, authentication, authorization, firewall, intrusion detection systems, mobile secure gateway etc. Day by day the intelligence system is developing and as a result threat is also increasing. Corporate world, industries are employing different smart devices and there threat management systems is highly required. This is a basic paper on Network Security and talks about the aspects of Network Security with special reference to the threat management. Paper deals the fundamentals affairs of threat management as well.

Keywords: IT Management, Information Assurance, Threat Management, Network Security, IT Security Policies

1. Introduction :

Network Security is an important concept and field within IT Security. The field is responsible for dealing different network related securities viz. technologies that prevent or defend network privacy and security related issues. Initially during the development of the concept of security in respect of computing; there was no as such concept. That time only Computer Security concepts was there but gradually other security related concepts have been emerged and among these Network Security is treated as important and most valuable [1], [5]. Network security is actually the responsible for the authorization of access to data within the network, and normally it has administrated by the network administrator. Network security is deals different types of computer networks including public and private. And most of these are used in everyday jobs. Network Security is applicable and important in different sectors and fields viz. healthcare and medicine, business and commerce, research and development, education and training, government and administration sectors etc. Network Security and Management is the need of

hour [2], [3], [7]. Today, Network Security is concern about different areas viz. Trojan, worms, virus, malware, spyware etc. Similarly, backdoor, denial of services etc are also important name these days.

2. Objective and Agenda

The current paper entitled ‘Network Security: Threat Management’ is theoretical and nature and deals with basics affairs related to the Network Security viz.—

- To learn about the basics of Network Security including its basic characteristics and nature.
- To know about the importance and need of Network Security in different sectors and fields at a glance.
- To learn about the root and threats related to the Network Security in basic sense.
- To know about the basics of Network Security threat management.
- To learn about the challenges and issues in response of Network Security Management.

3. Network Security Threats

Network Security initially started with the authentication by using user name and password. And the one step verification to two step or even three step verification methods can be adopted. Firewall is another name for securing information and contents [4], [8], [10]. Apart from these firewall few other are also important viz. – antivirus etc. The following contents is concentrated on different threats like—

Computer Crime & Network—

This is the crime related to the computer and network itself. Computer crime may be done the individuals or group to the individuals or group. Cyber crime may also called the affecting or harming any computer or whole computer system viz. networks, database, mobile phones, internet systems etc.

Vulnerability & Network —

In Network Security, another important name is vulnerability. It is simply the weakness of the network. Normally the attacker finds the vulnerability to perform unauthorized attack or performs. Initially it was called as security risk. There are certain things that can be fall under the vulnerability viz. security bug, password management flaws, unchecked user input, intrusion detection systems, vulnerability inventory etc [6], [9], [11].

There are different types of vulnerability viz. hardware vulnerability, software vulnerability, network vulnerability etc. However apart from these, vulnerability can be of following viz.—

- Vulnerability related to the Organization (like failure or lacking in planning, audits);

- Vulnerability in respect of Physical sites (may be in inappropriate place, threats of natural disaster etc);
- Vulnerability in respect of Human Resources (may be inadequate or less awareness of vulnerability or security technologies) etc [12], [13], [16].

There are different ways to exploits vulnerability viz.

- An attacker can find out the vulnerability in the systems and based on this, the attacker can install the malware to collect the sensitive data etc.
- An attacker can send any suspicious email for getting any personal information using malware or spyware etc [14], [15], [18].
- There may be invalid validation that exploits vulnerability viz. code injection, cross site scripting, email injection, SQL injection, clickjacking, FTP bounce attack, side channel attack.

Malware & Network —

Malware is a kind of program responsible for damaging computer systems that includes computer, server, network or databases. There are different kinds of Malware viz. computer virus, worms, trojan, adware, scareware etc. Malware has a malicious intent. Initially Malware based attack was started in the government organizations and institutions but gradually it has become common tool for attack to the common people by the network [17], [21], [22].

Malware is also designed for the monitoring user's web browsing history including the spyware related activities. Malware is affected following, normally—

- Software
- Database
- Network etc

USB port can be used to spread malware and thus it is an important way which is used by the attackers. There are different types of malware and these category are increasing. Ransomware is also a kind of malware responsible for financial fraud and extort money from computer users. Ultimately malware is dedicated to infected the systems. It is thus designed to damage to a standalone system/ computer or even a network. Initially malware was created by the hackers, but in recent past Government agencies are also used the same. There are different means for malware management and among these important are—

- Not to use suspicious or strange emails.
- Double checks the systems and contents before its downloading.
- Only reliable advertisement is better to check or click.
- Careful viewing of reliable and trusted websites are very important.

It is worthy to note that; phishing websites, fake apps, and unofficial app stores are these days dangerous for mobile devices (android based) as well. There are different threat management

system developed and among these in Windows 10 ‘Windows Defender Security Center’ important one.

Spyware & Network —

Spyware is a kind of malware. It is mainly dedicated to collect the information and content from the device without acknowledging the users. Even spyware is able to control the whole device (i.e. hidden). It normally uses cookies for the same. Spyware mainly may be classified into following four, mainly—

- Adware
- System Monitor
- Tracking Cookies
- Trojans etc

Spyware is mostly uses pop-ups to collect the data. However, sometimes few Spyware (like Keyloggers) may be used in the organizations to collect the information from the employee. Through spyware, one can collect any type of information of the devices and specially internet habit these days. Some spyware can change the internet systems and settings as well. In Some countries Spyware is allowed in Governmental affairs to deal the task and here another concept is arrived called ‘*Govware*’ and this is mainly common in German countries. A spyware installation is the result of changes in unwanted CPU activity, disk usage, network traffic. Some spyware is even able in removing anti-spyware, anti-virus and few even able in reducing less network security function [12], [19], [20].

There are different anti-spyware, block spyware available in the market and their usages are also rising rapidly due to market need. But it is worthy to note that still many such anti- Spyware are not working to remove all Spyware from the systems especially in Symantec, Microsoft etc. Here re-installation of the OS and data transformation is the only way to solve the problem.

Hence for a secure Network System needful should be provided in respect of Spyware and allied malware.

Virus & Network —

Computer Virus or simply, ‘Virus’ is a kind of malware. It is an important and most popular threat to the Network Systems. Though, apart from the network systems the general computer and electronic devices also affected with the Virus. Though it is a kind of malware but the term Virus is widely known and popular in public space. The main reason for the Virus is to infecting the vulnerable systems use administrative control and to get users personal, sensitive data. Some Virus are also responsible for the replicate the data. There are different ways to get or infected Virus and among these few important are—by email attachment, infected files, executable files etc. There may be different infection vectors viz.—

- Software Bugs

- Poor security practices in Social Media and Engineering places
- Weak Operating Systems etc

There are different kinds of Virus viz. Resident Virus, Non Resident Virus, Resident Virus, Macro Virus, Boot Sector Virus, Email Virus etc. A Virus can infected different computer in a same network if enters and thus System and Network Administrator need to handle the task very carefully. Sometimes, Viruses can be available in the free apps, funny videos, images etc.

Worms & Network —

Worms normally not changes or deletes the contents, it is generally responsible for the replicate the files or objects. It is a kind of Malware, the virus whereas need a host to infect or to operate, but worm doesn't requires any host. A worm once enter into the system it start its operation of replicate the files etc. Many a times, it enters by the network system or internet etc. The worm can be following types viz. –

- Email Worm
- IM Worm
- IRC Worm
- Net Worm
- P2P Worm etc

It is worthy to note that worm normally enters as network packets. Moreover worm can exploit the network configuration error. Hence instead of locally like virus, a worm can infected the computer systems or network worldwide instantly. Hence in Network system, worms are more essential to care off. The following table: 1 shows the worm and virus features in general sense.

Table: 1-Depicted the differences and characteristics of the virus and worms

Characteristics	Virus	Worms
Dependencies	Host File Based	No host file needed, it is standalone
Human affiliation	Human intervention	No Human intervention needed
Infected Facets	The files and infected files can be shared one by one	Normally act by the Network Operation
Core Activity	Normally damages files and systems	It can consume the network bandwidth and replicate files
Working zones	Work via executable files	Work by the vulnerable network
Corrupting systems	Can corrupt/ shutdown the system	Can corrupt/ shutdown the network

Backdoors & Network —

Backdoor in Network is an important concept. Network or system administrator may install a backdoor program for solving a problem. *This is enable threat to gain command-and-control and moreover move laterally across the targeted network. In otherword, it is a method that hackers use for the establishment of unauthorized access to a network from a remote place.* Backdoor may also take the form of a hidden program [8], [14], [19].

Backdoor threat is noticeable when many users in an organizations and used network operating systems. There are different example may be noticeable in backdoors viz—

- Emilla Attack
- Object Code Backdoor
- Asymmetric Backdoors

Hackers can use backdoor to install malware for the purpose of modify code or detect files and gain system or data access.

Denial of Service & Network —

Denial of Service (DoS) is a kind of attack in Information Technology Security. It is a kind of cyber attack in which whole network resources may be unavailable temporarily from the host network. There is a subfield of DoS called, Distributed Denial of Service and Network (DDoS). Another field is—Advanced Persistent DoS. According to the US-CERT following may indicate an Denial of Service (DoS) attack—

- Degradation of the network performance; mainly during the opening files stored in a network.
- Less network strength in when accessing websites and web portals.
- When a particular website is unable to reach.
- The Denial of Service (DoS) may be notified when higher volume of spam email is noticeable.

Phishing & Network —

Phishing is a kind of Cyber Security attack in this kind of cyber offence email play a big role for the attack. In Phishing, attackers normally send the malicious virus by a message or email with the attachment. Normally in phishing attackers are plans to collect users information mainly confidential and financial in nature. It is one of the early cyber attacks which exists in 1990s. It is still most popular and useful. With the Phishing Kit, one can easily do the Phishing; the following diagram (source: CSO-India i.e. <https://www.csoononline.com/article/2117843/>) shows it clearly.

Fig: 1-Anatomy of a Phishing Kit.

There are two types of Phishing, ‘handover sensitive information’ and another is ‘Download malware’. In other words, Phishing can be classified as Spear Phishing Attacks and Whaling Attacks [4], [9], [21].

Eavesdropping & Network —

Eavesdropping is concerned with the network technology and security. It is more clearly associated with the telecommunication systems. Eavesdropping is the technique and procedure that is dedicated to the listing private conversation of communication without consent. This is most illegal practice and treated as worldwide. Eavesdropping is includes the vectors viz. cellular network, email, VoIP, telephone lines etc. It is a kind of unauthorized real-time in the private communication viz. phone call; instant message and even this include the videoconference or fax transmission. With IP-based calls (than that of TDM-based calls), eavesdropping become very easy to perform. Here with the help of protocol analyzer one can pick as well as record the calls and without acknowledging the callers and even they couldn’t here the same. Different software are available of PCs which can convert digitized sound from general CODECs into WAV files.

In other word, Eavesdropping is as an electronic attack and here listening to digital or analog voice communication can be possible with the proper tools. Thus these days, Network

Administrators have to be aware about these due to safety of information privacy. It is worthy to note that, there is an allied concept Network Eavesdropping which is a network layer attack having lack of encryption. Here when a computer send a file of text from one computer to another or one network to another the data privacy become lost. This is important to note that, this is linked to the collection of metadata. These are normally performed by the black hat hackers. However, in recent past Government agencies are also practicing the same, in case of exception requirement.

Advanced Persistent Threat & Network —

Advanced Persistent Threat in short called as APT. It is an important Network related issues and techniques. This is a systematic and robust cyber attack program responsible to collect data and information from an individual computer or group of computer from the same or different network. Advanced Persistent Threat is managed by the group of attackers and that may be hackers or ethical hackers. It is may be undertaken by the government agencies as well. These kind of threat run by the experiences hackers and can run few months and even year/s to reach the goal. As mentioned in the Wikipedia, there are different Advanced Persistent Threat group and among these few important are include—

- American Advanced Persistent Threat Group
- Chinese Advanced Persistent Threat Group
- Vietnamese Advanced Persistent Threat Group
- North Korean Advanced Persistent Threat Group
- Russian Advanced Persistent Threat Group etc.

It is important to note that traditional security technologies are ineffective in detecting or mitigating Advanced Persistent Threat. There are hundreds of variations in malware and their attack normally done in a same way. Moreover firewall, defense in depth, antivirus etc cannot protect the Advanced Persistent Threat [15], [22].

5. Network Security Threats Management

Computer and network surveillance is very much important and required in the information technology security system in recent days. Computer and network surveillance is need to maintain by the network manager to monitor the computer activity and database or stored data in a storage devices or hard disk. Moreover, Computer and network surveillance is responsible for the monitoring of data transformation of the network (within or outside of the network).

It is worthy to note that, in Computer and network surveillance monitoring is often carried out. And this may be performed by the government bodies, corporations and criminal organizations, or even individuals in many cases. Moreover this may be legal or illegal. In addition to this, Computer and network surveillance may required authentication or may not, based on requirement.

Apart from the Computer and Network Surveillance, a Network and System Administrators need to maintain following threat management principles and methods for secure, reliable, robust Information and Computer Network.

Computer Access Control is very much important and valuable for a healthy network administration. Computer Access Control includes the identification, authorization, authentication, access control over the computer systems and networks. In generally, Computer Access Control may also define as the techniques for allowing the computer system. Access is actually approved based on successful authentication and that may be based on following single/multiple facets.—

- Token including the Passwords
- Physical Keys
- Biometrics scan
- Electronic Keys
- Social barriers etc

Computer Access Control can be managed by capability based model or ACL based model. *Authorization* is the core job of Computer Access Control which allows following operations viz. Read, Write (including adding, updating, deleting, renaming etc), Execute. In Computer Access Control following are important viz.—

- Identification and Authorization
- Access Approval
- Accountability

Based on requirement, three most widely recognized models may be used for this methods viz. Discretionary Access Control (DAC), Mandatory Access Control (MAC), and Role Based Access Control (RBAC). However in special circumstances Network administrator can use following methods viz.—

- Attribute based Access Control
- Break Glass Access Control
- Access Control based on Responsibility
- Host based Access Control etc.

Hence, *Access control* is a kind of method of limiting access to a system or to physical or virtual resources and for secure and modern network management professionals need to manage all by proper strategies [2], [8], [17].

6. Application Security—

Application Security is very much important is Network Management and Administration and administrator should think about the security related affairs carefully. The Application Security

is responsible for the finding, fixing and preventing vulnerabilities in a system. There are different techniques in Application Security and among these few important are—

- Whitebox Security Review
- Blackbox Security Audit
- Design Review
- Tooling

All the computational programs may get the vulnerability and mobile devices in recent past may have various weakness. Some of the vulnerabilities are include—

- The application white listing
- Transport layer security consideration
- Strong and sophisticated authentication and authorization
- Sandboxing of applications and software.
- Processes associated with an user ID
- Interaction and relation of the mobile application and the OS
- Requiring user input for privileged access etc.

Application Security is requires different threats and attack and an Network Administrator need to solve all these routinely. And for proper application security following could be adopted—

- Antivirus and Malware
- Secure Coding
- Secure Operating Systems
- Secure Design etc.

Anti Virus and Anti Malware

It is worthy to note that different antivirus software and anti malware are very important for secure and robust security system establishment in a network or system; as modern antivirus is able to protect following—

- Malicious browser helper objects
- Browser hijackers
- Keyloggers and Backdoors
- Trojan horses and worms
- Spyware and adware etc.

Even few products are able in securing and threat management from the infected URLs, Spam, Online banking attacks etc. During the early days, antivirus become very rare in market but in late 2010's it is become important and mandatory in almost all types of organizations and

institutions and even individuals. Apart from the nontraditional files and documents, antivirus is become essential in general files protection as well such as in word file Macros can be inbuilt. In Security market, F-Secure was the first security organization that developed the Anti-Rootkit technology, called *BlackLight* and this was happens in the year 2005. In 2008, McAfee launched the McAfee Virus Scan in the market. In 2011, Protective Cloud Technology was developed by the AVG. There are different types of methods which antivirus engine may use to identify malware and among these following are important and valuable—

- Sandbox Detection
- Data Mining Techniques
- Signature based detection
- Heuristics systems
- Rootkit detection etc

However, in recent past organizations and institutions are providing importance in the Unified Threat Management, Hardware Firewall, Network Firewall, Cloud Antivirus, Online Scanning etc for protecting the system and networks [6], [19].

Secure Coding

Secure Coding is important for healthy and sophisticated information systems designing and development. Secure coding is a kind of technique in which special attention is provided on the designing and programming with security concern. The main reason for the vulnerabilities in software are include (but not limited to the following)—

- Insecure Defects
- Insecure Bugs
- Insecure logic flaws etc.

Today due to many insecure coding issues and incident, programmers and developers become aware of insecure coding causes and their remedies. For securing coding following methods may be adopted—

- Buffer Over-flow Protection
- Format String Attack Protection
- Integer Overflow Protection etc.

Hence it is worthy to apply defensive programming (Defensive programming is a technique which helps in improving software and source coding) for the development of secure software engineering.

Secure Design

Secure Designing is very important concept these days. Here software engineer need to think about the designing of securing software systems and programs from the foundation or initially. In recent past secure software development become core of attention and mainstream development. Domain driven designing is also very close with the secure designing concept. Fault tolerant program can be implemented for healthy and sophisticated programming. The two example of insecure designing are—

- Buffer Overflow
- Format String Vulnerabilities [5], [13].

In client server model, third party or hacker can be enter into the systems and based based on vulnerabilities can break the security.

Secure Operating System

Operating Systems security is the process for securing operating systems with different tools, techniques and mechanism. Operating Systems security is also responsible for the ensuring OS with better integrity, confidentiality, and availability. The OS Security is requires to built for the purposes like—

- Securing OS from the Threats and Virus
- Securing OS from the worms and malware
- Securing OS from the remote hacker intrusion

According to the TechnoPedia, the core aim of the Operating Systems security is include but not limited to the following—

- Performing a general and regular OS patch updates
- Installing as well as updating antivirus engines as well software
- For a securing Operating Systems, scrutinizing all incoming and outgoing network traffic through a firewall is very important and required.
- Creating secure accounts with proper user management is highly essential.

Throughout the world, companies are involved for the design and development of trusted operating systems and among these few important are listed (Wikipedia) in Table: 2

Table: 2- Few companies developed secure operating systems

Few Companies that developed Secure Operating Systems
Addamax (BSD, SVR3, SVR4, HP/UX) Argus Systems Group (Solaris, AIX, Linux) AT&T (System V) Bull (AIX) Digital Equipment Corporation (Ultrix) General Dynamics C4 Systems (Linux) Hewlett-Packard (HP/UX) Honeywell (Multics) IBM (OS/390, AIX) SCO (SCO Unix) SecureWare (Apple A/UX, HP/UX, SCO) Silicon Graphics (IRIX) Sun Microsystems (SunOS, Solaris) Trusted Information Systems (Xenix, Mach)

Network Administrators need to think and proper efforts for the development of Operating Systems with security.

Security by Default

This is another concept for the securing information systems designing and development. Security by default means keeping the systems and mechanism by default secure. Means keep the systems user friendly and by default secure. This approach may be developed and applied in the following—

- In operating systems
- In processor and Hardware
- In software development
- In Applications etc.

Secure by default thus very important and required concept these days for the development of overall secure information and network systems [7], [18].

Conclusion

Day by day, the concept of Security and Trust is very important. Initially security considered as Computer Security only, but these days this is increasing rapidly and thus the areas of Network security, web security, database security become important and valuable. There are different kind of attacks viz. Active attack and Passive attack and security measure is essential in all these areas. A Network Administrators these days need to hold the skills sets for other security areas as well. The skill set production is also very important and thus universities and training institutes

should establish different units and programs to produce human resources in the field. Cloud Computing Security and Mobile security is also very important for the secure systems these days.

References

- [1] Bellavista, P., Corradi, A., & Stefanelli, C. (2001). Mobile agent middleware for mobile computing. *Computer*, 34(3), 73-81.
- [2] Bishop, M. (2003). What is computer security?. *IEEE Security & Privacy*, 1(1), 67-69.
- [3] Bonner, W., & Chiasson, M. (2005). If fair information principles are the answer, what was the question? An actor-network theory investigation of the modern constitution of privacy. *Information and Organization*, 15(4), 267-293.
- [4] Borselius, N. (2002). Mobile agent security. *Electronics & Communication Engineering Journal*, 14(5), 211-218.
- [5] Brooks, R. R. (2004). Mobile code paradigms and security issues. *IEEE Internet Computing*, 8(3), 54-59.
- [6] Chen, X., Makki, K., Yen, K., & Pissinou, N. (2009). Sensor network security: A survey. *IEEE Communications Surveys and Tutorials*, 11(2), 52-73.
- [7] Deng, H., Li, W., & Agrawal, D. P. (2002). Routing security in wireless ad hoc networks. *IEEE Communications magazine*, 40(10), 70-75.
- [8] Djenouri, D., Khelladi, L., & Badache, N. (2005). Security issues of mobile ad hoc and sensor networks. In *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials* (Vol. 7, No. 4, pp. 2-28). IEEE Communications Society.
- [9] Donald, A. C., Oli, S. A., & Arockiam, L. (2013). Mobile cloud security issues and challenges: A perspective. *International Journal of Engineering and Innovative Technology*, 3(1), 401.
- [10] Geneiatakis, D., Kounelis, I., Neisse, R., Nai-Fovino, I., Steri, G., & Baldini, G. (2017, May). Security and privacy issues for an IoT based smart home. In *2017 40th International Convention on Information and Communication Technology, Electronics and Microelectronics (MIPRO)* (pp. 1292-1297). IEEE.
- [11] Goth, G. (2012). Mobile security issues come to the forefront. *IEEE Internet Computing*, 16(3), 7-9.
- [12] Jain, A. K., & Shanbhag, D. (2012). Addressing security and privacy risks in mobile applications. *IT Professional*, 14(5), 28-33.
- [13] Jansen, W. A. (2000). Countermeasures for mobile agent security. *Computer communications*, 23(17), 1667-1676.
- [14] Kannhavong, B., Nakayama, H., Nemoto, Y., Kato, N., & Jamalipour, A. (2007). A survey of routing attacks in mobile ad hoc networks. *IEEE Wireless communications*, 14(5), 85-91.
- [15] Martínez-Pérez, B., De La Torre-Díez, I., & López-Coronado, M. (2015). Privacy and security in mobile health apps: a review and recommendations. *Journal of medical systems*, 39(1), 181.

- [16] Ngai, E. W., & Gunasekaran, A. (2007). A review for mobile commerce research and applications. *Decision support systems*, 43(1), 3-15.
- [17] Nkosi, M. T., & Mekuria, F. (2010, November). Cloud computing for enhanced mobile health applications. In *2010 IEEE Second International Conference on Cloud Computing Technology and Science* (pp. 629-633). IEEE.
- [18] Siau, K., Lim, E. P., & Shen, Z. (2001). Mobile commerce: Promises, challenges and research agenda. *Journal of Database Management (JDM)*, 12(3), 4-13.
- [19] Siau, K., & Shen, Z. (2003). Mobile communications and mobile services. *International Journal of Mobile Communications*, 1(1-2), 3-14.
- [20] Siau, K., & Shen, Z. (2003). Mobile communications and mobile services. *International Journal of Mobile Communications*, 1(1-2), 3-14
- [21] Varshney, U., Vetter, R. J., & Kalakota, R. (2000). Mobile commerce: A new frontier. *Computer*, 33(10), 32-38.
- [22] Welp, Y., Urgell, F., & Aibar, E. (2007). From bureaucratic administration to network administration? An empirical study on e-government focus on Catalonia. *Public Organization Review*, 7(4), 299-316.

Paper 8

A STUDY ON CUSTOMERS OPINION ON BANKING PRODUCTS AND SERVICES WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO SELECTED BRANCHES OF KASARAGODU DISTRICT COOPERATIVE BANK

Mr. P V Joseph*, Dr. P N Raghunathan**

*PhD Scholar, Bharathiar University- Coimbatore

**Research Guide, HOD- Management Studies, Govt. Arts College, Coimbatore

Abstract

Banking sector is the service industry which has shown a dramatic growth and development consistently for the last several decades. Banking industry of any country is highly instrumental in determining the magnitude of the developments of the industry and citizens of that country. India's banking sector has been characterized by the strong presence of public sector, private sector, cooperative and foreign banks. Cooperative banks that include the primary cooperatives, district cooperative banks and the state cooperative banks cater to the needs of the common man especially of the people working in the primary sector to a great extent. The district cooperative banks in Kerala are grown-up to a higher level that now they offer the services and facilities that are as competent as the one offered by any other well established commercial bank. This study has made an attempt to evaluate the opinion of the customers towards the products, services and facilities offered by the selected six branches of the Kasaragodu district cooperative bank. Twenty respondents were chosen from each of these banks taking the sample size of the study to 120. The information was collected on factors such as Service capabilities, Customer services, ATM services, Employees, Paperless banking, Service quality and Product features. Statistical tools such as Kruskal Wallis Test and Mann-Whitney, Weighted average and Percentage analysis, were used to analyze the data collected.

Keywords: service industry, banking sector, district cooperative banks, customer services

1.Introduction to the research problem

India's banking industry is portrayed by the well-built existence of public and private sectors, cooperative and foreign banks. Cooperative banks accommodate to the needs of the common man especially of the people engaged in agriculture or small business. The district cooperative banks in Kerala play a substantial role in satisfying the banking needs of the people, especially the rural and sub-urban areas. The products, services and other facilities offered by the district cooperative banks are as competent as that of a well established commercial bank. Therefore, it is very important for the bank to know the level of satisfaction of its customers about the products, services or the facilities provided to the customers. The most comprehensive definition of customer satisfaction has been offered by Kotler and Keller who define satisfaction as

“person’s feeling of pleasure or disappointment which resulted from comparing a product’s perceived performance or outcome against his/ her expectations” (Kotler and Keller, 2006) .This study has made an attempt to evaluate the opinion of the customers towards the products, services and facilities offered by the selected six branches of the Kasaragodu district cooperative bank.

2.Review of literature

M. Selvam (2005) in his article entitled, “Customer Satisfaction of Banking Services: An Overview” has studied to assess the measurement criteria and to evaluate customer satisfaction regarding banking services and evaluate the level of satisfaction of customer services provided by the banks. He concluded that the bank has to keep in mind the mantra that “Customer is the King” and banks exist to serve them and should practice a range of services which fulfill customers’ satisfactions.

Nikhil Chandrashil & Bhagban Das, August (2008) conducted study on Customer Satisfaction with regard to Banking: An Application of QFD –Management Research, Vol.7, No.8. The study reveals that Customers nowadays are very choosy about the way they spend their money. Quality is the first and foremost preference. Therefore, it is of utmost importance for every organization to understand, respect, and satisfy their customer’s needs and feelings continuously.

Ashok Kumar and Rajesh (2009) found from the study that both public sector banks and private sector banks lack one or the other aspect of service quality and there is no significant difference between overall customer satisfactions in the banks, and concluded that banks should aim at satisfying the customers by providing maximum features in their banking services. Technological up gradation can be undertaken through implementation of core banking solutions and development of techno-savvy innovative products and services should be carried out.

Satendra Thakur (2011) examined the effect of service quality and customer satisfaction on customer loyalty among the group of customers in Indian banking industries. The results of the study indicated that customer satisfaction is significantly and positively related with customer loyalty and customer satisfaction is found to be an important mediator between service quality and customer loyalty. The author concluded that banking service providers should take right course of action to win customer satisfaction by providing better service quality in order to create loyal customer.

Ravi and Kundan basavaraj (2013) analyzed the customer preference and satisfaction towards banking services both private and public banks in Shivagangai district. The authors found business and vehicle loans are fast moving than other services and overall satisfaction resulted at 50%. Further, overall satisfaction on bank deposit schemes resulted positively while other services of banking still need to be given attention by focusing on customer issues. They authors suggested that, bankers should work towards 100% customer satisfaction that automatically fosters customer delight and to sustain customers on a long term basis.

3.Research Methodology

Sample for the study: Respondents for this study are the individuals who hold an active account with the randomly selected six branches of Kasaragodu district cooperative bank. The branches

selected are Kasaragodu main, Kanjangadu, Neeleswaram, Trikkarippur, Cheemeni and Chittarickkal.

Sample size: 120 respondents were chosen, twenty respondents each from the six branches

Type of sampling: Judgmental sampling, a type of non- probability sampling method has been used to select the respondents from the branches.

Type of research: The study fall under the category of descriptive research.

Data collection method: The researcher has approached the respondents by visiting them in the bank with a structured questionnaire and requested them to fill it up

Instrument used for data collection: The questionnaire developed and validated by P C Mandal S Bhattacharya, of Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, has used for data collection by slightly modifying the instrument.

Types of data used: Both primary and secondary data are used for this study. Primary data was collected with the help of a structured questionnaire directly from the respondents while secondary data was collected from the websites

Tools used for data analysis: Percentage analysis, weighted average, Kruskal Wallis Test and Mann-Whitney U methods are used for the data analysis

4.Objectives

- To understand the variable with the strongest association to the underlying latent construct
- To study whether there is a significant difference between the education of customers and their opinion on banking products and services
- To examine the difference between the gender of the customers and their opinion on banking products and services

5.Hypothesis

1. H0 : There is no statically significant difference between various levels of education of the respondents and their opinion on various attributes of customer satisfaction factors
2. H0 : There is no statically significant difference between the gender of the respondents and their opinion on various attributes of customer satisfaction factors
- 3.

6.Analysis and Findings

Table No. 1 Description of the sample

		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	81	67.5
	Female	39	32.5
	Total	120	100.0
Age	less than 20	2	1.7
	20 to 40	34	28.3
	40 to 60	44	36.7
	Above 60	40	33.3

	Total	120	100.0
Education	School	44	36.7
	Higher secondary	29	24.2
	Degree	39	32.5
	P G	7	5.8
	others	1	.8
	Total	120	100.0
Occupation	Govt employed	10	8.3
	Pvt. employed	20	16.7
	Self employed	30	25.0
	Professional	3	2.5
	House wife	25	20.8
	Retired	22	18.3
	Agriculture	7	5.8
	Others	3	2.5
Total	120	100.0	
Marital Status	Married	110	91.7
	Unmarried	10	8.3
	Total	120	100.0
Monthly Income	less than 10000	26	21.7
	10001 to 20000	58	48.3
	20001 to 40000	28	23.3
	40001 to 60000	7	5.8
	Above 60001	1	.8
	Total	120	100.0

Source: Primary data

The table given above gives a description of the sample taken for the study. We can see that majority of the respondents are male with just school education who are aged 40 years and above. Almost all of them are married and their monthly income was less than rupees twenty thousand a month.

Objective 1

Table No. 2: Weighted average score for various attributes of the factors of customer satisfaction

Sl.No.	Particulars	Weighted average score
	Factor1: Service Capabilities	
1	Availability of Computerized Banking System	486
2	Less waiting time for customers	491

3	Availability of Centralized Banking System	481
4	Standardized procedures followed for services provided by banks	486
	Factor2: Customer Services	
5	Availability of a prompt customer complaint mechanism	476
6	Availability of customer helpline phone numbers	428
7	Database for maintenance of updated customer information	429
	Factor3: ATM services	
8	Availability of ATM services round-the-clock	472
9	Fast replacement of ATM cards on expiry by banks	392
10	Universal accessibility of ATM cards at ATMs of other banks	396
	Factor4: Employees	
11	Proper attitude shown by the employees while serving customers.	440
12	Efficiency of the employees of banks.	494
13	Domain knowledge of the employees of banks.	516
	Factor5: Paperless Banking	
14	SMS alerts on mobiles provided by banks for different transactions	485
15	Debit card/credit card facilities at various outlets.	446
16	Availability of online banking services.	416
	Factor6: Service Quality	
17	Security of online transactions in ATMs.	460
18	Overall service quality provided by banks.	507
19	Prompt service provided by banks.	519
	Factor7: Product Features	
20	Low processing charges by banks for various types of loans.	413
21	Low money transfer charges by banks.	351
22	Low interest rates charged by banks for various types of loans.	293
23	Low installment amount charged by banks for loans	309
24	Less processing time for getting loans.	459

Source: Primary data

The above table shows that ; Less waiting time for customers, Availability of a prompt customer complaint mechanism, Availability of ATM services round-the-clock, Domain knowledge of the employees of banks, SMS alerts on mobiles provided by banks for different transactions, Prompt service provided by banks and Less processing time for getting loans have the strongest association with the respective factors such as Service Capabilities, Customer service, ATM Services, Employees, Paperless banking, Service quality and the product features.

Objective 2

Table No. 3 :Statistics^{a,b}

	Computerized	Waiting time	Core Banking	Procedures	Complaint Mechanism	Helpline
Chi-Square	.796	5.892	.421	2.429	1.961	2.780

df	3	3	3	3	3	3
Asymp. Sig.	.850	.117	.936	.488	.581	.427

a. Kruskal Wallis Test
 b. Grouping Variable: Education

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	Customer Database	Round the clock	Card replacement	Accessibility	Attitude	Efficiency
Chi-Square	.996	1.908	.348	.957	.616	8.850
df	3	3	3	3	3	3
Asymp. Sig.	.802	.592	.951	.812	.893	.031

a. Kruskal Wallis Test
 b. Grouping Variable: Education

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	Knowledge	SMS Alert	Card facilities	Online banking	Security	Quality
Chi-Square	3.927	1.106	.204	.648	2.973	4.427
df	3	3	3	3	3	3
Asymp. Sig.	.269	.776	.977	.885	.396	.219

a. Kruskal Wallis Test
 b. Grouping Variable: Education

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	Promptness	Processing charges	Transfer charges	Interest rates	Instalment amounts	Processing time
Chi-Square	6.963	2.626	4.811	2.247	2.263	6.396
df	3	3	3	3	3	3
Asymp. Sig.	.073	.453	.186	.523	.520	.094

a. Kruskal Wallis Test
 b. Grouping Variable: Education

The above tables show the variance among the respondents with different levels of educational qualification and their opinion on various attributes of the customer satisfaction factors. It is found that *employee efficiency* (p-value 0.031) is the only variable, so the null hypothesis rejected and we can conclude there is statistically significant variation among the respondent's levels of educational qualifications and their opinion on employee efficiency.

Objective 3

Table No.4: Test Statistics^a

	Computerized	Waiting time	Core Banking	Procedures	Complaint Mechanism	Helpline
Mann-Whitney U	1506.000	1423.500	1564.500	1383.500	1379.000	1568.000
Wilcoxon W	4827.000	4744.500	2344.500	4704.500	2159.000	4889.000
Z	-.680	-.963	-.099	-1.351	-1.542	-.072
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.496	.336	.921	.177	.123	.943

a. Grouping Variable: Gender
Test Statistics^a

	Customer Database	Round the clock	Card replacement	Accessibility	Attitude	Efficiency
Mann-Whitney U	1570.000	1438.000	1376.000	1471.500	1456.000	1556.500
Wilcoxon W	4891.000	4759.000	2156.000	2251.500	2236.000	4877.500
Z	-.060	-1.059	-1.663	-.752	-.906	-.140
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.952	.289	.096	.452	.365	.889

a. Grouping Variable: Gender
Test Statistics^a

	Knowledge	SMS Alert	Card facilities	Online banking	Security	Quality
Mann-Whitney U	1575.500	1353.000	1399.000	1514.000	1551.500	1414.500
Wilcoxon W	2355.500	2133.000	4720.000	2294.000	2331.500	4735.500
Z	-.025	-1.675	-1.293	-.393	-.198	-1.103
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.980	.094	.196	.695	.843	.270

a. Grouping Variable: Gender
Test Statistics^a

	Promptness	Processing charges	Transfer charges	Interest rates	Instalment amounts	Processing time
Mann-Whitney U	1481.500	1366.000	1493.000	1519.000	1551.500	1466.500

Wilcoxon W	4802.500	4687.000	4814.000	4840.000	4872.500	4787.500
Z	-.628	-1.328	-.516	-.404	-.176	-.910
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.530	.184	.606	.686	.861	.363

a. Grouping Variable: Gender

We can see from the above tables that, all the p- values are above 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and it can be concluded that there is no significant difference between the gender of the respondents and their opinion on various attributes of customer satisfaction factors.

7. Conclusion

The district cooperative banks in Kerala are grown-up to a higher level that now they offer the services and facilities that are as competent as the one offered by any other well established commercial bank. The present study has made an attempt to evaluate the opinion of the 120 sample customers towards the products, services and facilities offered by the selected six branches of the Kasaragodu district cooperative bank. The information was collected on factors such as Service capabilities, Customer services, ATM services, Employees, Paperless banking, Service quality and Product features. Statistical tools such as Kruskal Wallis Test and Mann-Whitney U, Weighted average and Percentage analysis, were used to analyze the data collected. It was found that here is statistically significant variation among the respondent’s levels of educational qualifications and their opinion on employee efficiency as the educated customers expect for higher efficiency. The study has also revealed that there is no significant difference between the gender of the respondents and their opinion on various attributes of customer satisfaction factors.

8. Limitations of the study and further scope of research:

Here the researcher has made an effort to study the customer’s opinion on various factors of customer satisfaction of Kasaragodu district cooperative bank by investigating a sample of one hundred and twenty respondents. The customers of the Kasaragodu district cooperative bank branches were the center of the study and therefore it suggests for like studies in other regions. The research was mainly on the data collected through the slightly modified instrument developed by Mandal PC, Bhattacharya S and the assessments of the responses confines to the items in that standard instrument. If a further modified version of the instrument is used, more pertinent information could be collected and hence more comprehensive studies could be conducted in future. Increased sample size and use of more of statistical tools for analyzes shall increase the accuracy and will furnish extra findings to the study.

References

- Ashok Kumar and Rajesh, “Whether Today’s Customers are Satisfied? – A Study with Banks”, Indian Journal of Marketing, Volume 39, No.9, Sep 2009, pp.56-62
- C. R. Kothari (2009) "Research Methodology: Methods & Techniques"(Second Revised Edition), New Age International Publishers, New Delhi.
- Kotler, P. and Keller K. L, Marketing Management, Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall, 2006.

- Mandal PC, Bhattacharya S, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India. ISSN: 2278-3369, Customer Satisfaction in Indian Retail Banking: Scale Development and Validation, International Journal of Advances in Management and Economics, www.managementjournal.info
- Nikhil Chandra Shil & Bhagban Das, August (2008) conducted study on Customer Satisfaction with regard to Banking: An Application of QFD Management Research, Vol.7,
- Ravi and Kundan basavaraj (2013) “Customers Preference and Satisfaction towards Banking Services with Special Reference to Shivamoga District in Karnataka”, Trans Asian Journal of Marketing & Management Research, Vol.2, Issue 1, pp. 28-38
- Satendra Thakur(2011), “Service quality, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty: A study with special reference to Indian banking industries”, Journal on Banking Financial Services and Insurance Research, Volume 1, Issue 5, August 2011, pp.83-93
- Selvam. M., (2005). “Customer Satisfaction of Banking Services: An Overview”, South Asian Journal of Socio-Political Studies, pp.85-90 and 120, July-December.

Paper 9

**A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS
POLICIES OF TATA CONSULTANCY SERVICES
LIMITED (TCS)**

K. Vikranth¹ & Krishna Prasad K²

¹Research Scholar, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India

²College of Computer Science & Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangaluru,
Karnataka, India

Email: vikranth.kadya@gmail.com

Abstract

Company analysis is one kind of tactic in research methodology to study the different aspects of the company such as growth in terms of asset or economy or employee strength etc. There are several industries and numerous companies in each industry. Here each company follows different strategies to step up the industries there by to survive and make profit. Software industry is also a type of industry is a big boon for most of the young population who are anticipating to beginning their career in this field. Software and Information Technology (IT) is one of the segments where number of departments are working together to develop product or to give services. TCS (Tata Consultancy Services Limited) is one of the most reputed Indian based IT company particularizes its business all over the world around 46 countries. It is leading information technology firm and software outsourcing organization in the world. In its journey of business, it was partner with many companies from past 50 years. TCS deals with consulting-led, cognitive powered, incorporated selection of business, machinery, facilities and solutions. In terms of market capitalization, TCS become the second top company in India. According to Forbes' most innovative company list TCS placed 64th rank in all over the world and 1st rank in India. It service provider sector TCS has second place in all over the world. In this paper is scrutinized how the company's growth takes place from 1968 to till date. And what are the other software companies in India that compete with TCS, Different industries in which TCS expands its business wings, different products and services of the company and various strategies used by the company to expand its business and market capital. Contribution of the company to software industry as well as our nation and listed number of awards and accolades received by the company and also explored some problems faced by software companies in India including TCS. And finally we analyze the business strategies of the company using SWOT analysis.

Keywords: SWOT, ERP, CSR, Consultancy, Artificial Intelligence, Cloud compute, software Technology.

1. INTRODUCTION

The software industry is a unique type of industry where different software companies are running with a greater potential of serving the society with their unique working style. Of course, India is one of the leading countries in software development because of the skilled people and the ability to work efficiently with a considerably less salary. So that software companies in India can successfully compete with other MNC software companies. The Indian software companies are well reputed in globe because of its quality in product and service. In fact, export of software from India accounts for more than 65 percent of the total software revenue. The domestic software market largely depends upon the sale of software packages and products, which constitute a major part of revenues. Software products account for almost 40 percent of the domestic market. On the other hand, more than 80 percent of revenue from software exports comes from software services like custom software development and consultancy services, etc. the different services given by software companies like Custom Trade solutions, Joint Content Management, Internet Promotion, Web Branding Services, Database Immigration services, Customization Services, Application Development, Outsourcing, ERP solutions, iPhone Apps development, Collaborative Commerce, Programming Services, Quality assurance and testing services.

India, home of the world's fastest-growing economy, is quickly becoming one of the globe's greatest technology hubs. That is partially thanks to the country's abundance of highly skilled technical graduates, whose numbers are growing at a rate of 7 percent per year, according to the latest study from India's ministry of commerce and industry.

2. OBJECTIVES

- Analyzing the background details of top Indian based IT companies which is competitors of TCS.
- A brief analysis of management structure and business strategies of TCS from the year it was established.
- Contribution of the company to different industries by its products and services.
- Different products and services provided by the TCS.
- Analyzing the performance of the company in terms of revenue, profit, employee metrics, etc...
- Contribution of the company to the society by its various CSR activities.
- Achievements of the company based on awards and accolades received.
- Performing the SWOC analysis of a company in different dimensions.

3. Background details of top software companies in India:

S.no	Company name	Head quarters	Established	Founder	CEO
1	TCS	Mumbai	1968	J. R. D. Tata, F. C. Kohli	Natarajan Chandrasekaran
2	Infosys	Bangalore	1981	N. R. Narayana	Vishal Sikka

				Murthy, K. Dinesh, Nandan Nilekani , Ashok Arora, S. D. Shibulal, Kris Gopalakrishnan, N. S. Raghavan	
3	Wipro	Bangalore	1945	M.H. Hasham Premji	Abidali Z. Neemuchwala
4	HCL	Noida	1991	Arjun Malhotra, Shiv Nadar	Anant Gupta
5	Tech Mahindra	Pune	1986	Anand Mahindra	CP Gurnani

All these top five companies are listed here are big competitors for TCS. Compare to all other companies TCS was founded very early in 1968 except the Wipro which founded on 1945. All these companies have the good founder's fame and headquarters located in most reputed cities of India.

4. Tata Consultancy Services(TCS):

Tata Consultancy Services Limited (TCS) is an Indian based worldwide information technology (IT) service and consulting company. Headquarters of TCS located in Mumbai, Maharashtra, India. It is a subordinate of the Tata Group and having its operations in worldwide over 46 different countries. TCS is one of the parts of the Tata group, and also it is recognized as India's largest multinational corporate company. Around 50 countries in worldwide TCS has over 4, 20,000 of globally recognized best consultants. After endangereed the revenue of twenty billion in US dollar, it was listed in BSE (Bombay Stock Exchange) and NSE (National Stock Exchange) in India.

In stand of market capitalization, TCS is the second biggest company in India. According to Forbes' most innovative company, TCS placed 64th rank in all over the world and 1st rank in India. It has a 2nd place in the service provider sector in all over the world. It also stood in top position in India to reach 100 dollar billion in market capital and placed second in m-cap at rupees above 102.6 billion dollar in BSE.

5. Evolution and year wise strategy towards development:

The Company was founded in the year 1968. In the beginning, when the company was started it took punched card services to the sister company called as TISCO. In 1975, it delivers electronic and trading system called SECOM for the Swiss company. In 1980, it starts India's first dedicated software research and development center called TRDDC (Tata Research Development and Design Center) in Pune. In 1981, it establishes India's first client-dedicated offshore development center. Later in 1993, it acquires Canada based Software Company called Integrity Software Corporation.

After 2005 it was the first company to enter the bioinformatics market, in 2006 it develops a product called Indian Railway Catering and Tourism Corporation for the railway department. In 2011, it enters into small and medium enterprises with cloud computing. After this TCS becomes the highest market capitalization on any India based company. In the 2011-12 fiscal years the first time, it achieves highest annual revenue over \$10 billion. In 2015, it was the first Indian company to cross market capitalization over 5 lakh core. In 2015 TCS become the most profitable software company in India. In 2017, it announces its partnership with another payment technology company called Aurus. In 2018 TCS BaNCS ranked the number two best-selling Universal Banking system by UK based IBS Intelligence in its 2018 Sales League Table. And in 2019 it became the first company in India to cross 7 trillion (\$100 billion) in market valuation, making it the country's most valued firm.

6. Management structure:

Board of directors			Management Team		
S.No	Name	Designation	S.No	Name	Designation
1	N Chandrasekaran	Chairman	1	Rajesh Gopinathan	Chief Executive Officer and Managing Director
2	Rajesh Gopinathan	Chief Executive Officer and Managing Director	2	N G Subramaniam	Chief Operating Officer and Executive Director
3	N G Subramaniam	Chief Operating Officer and Executive Director	3	V Ramakrishnan	Chief Financial Officer
4	Aarthi Subramanian	Director	4	MilindLakkad	Global Head Human Resources
5	O P Bhatt	Independent Director	5	Ravi Viswanathan	Chief Marketing Officer
6	Dr Ron Sommer	Independent Director	6	K Ananth Krishnan	Chief Technology Officer
7	Aman Mehta	Independent Director	7	MadhavAnchan	General Counsel
8	DrPradeep Kumar	Independent	8	RajendraMoholkar	Company

	Khosla	Director			Secretary
9	Hanne Birgitte Breinbjerg Sorensen	Independent Director	9		

7. To Different Industries the TCS contributed by its product and services:

- i) **Banking and financial industry:** It gives fast track open banking adoption with a pre-built, preconfigured, cloud-based platform. Open banking revolutionizes the banking and financial service and insurance industry.
- ii) **Communication, media and technology:** It achieves seamless connectivity across using cloud applications. To service, today's, the ecosystem telecommunication system needs to upgrade to next-generation integration architecture that includes API management microservices, IPaaS and high weight ESB, digital data architecture.
- iii) **Manufacturing:** helps manufacturers to monetize the product, operations, and customers. It explores how a connected, collaborative, and cognitive supply chain can enable customer business and also delivers cost and efficiency benefits.
- iv) **Retail Industry:** helps retailers to deliver great buying experience to digital customers. The retailer can increase his profit by using artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning.
- v) **Energy, Resources and utilities:** It is a dream of new revenue stream. It provides how utilities are embracing new revenue streams.
- vi) **Life sciences and health care:**Is one of the incipient technology that whittling the life science and healthcare industry. As drug and healthcare industries approved digital technologies to improve their business, they must adopt 4.0TM that enables them to use artificial intelligence and cloud technology platform to improve their business.
- vii) **Travel transportation and hospitality:** TCS involved a project with Malaysia airline with cloud based technology, so that, it increases its data centers and able to reach its whole transportation in very less time which meets their expected project. Because of this it's overall cost declined to 51 percent and its productivity improved up to 80 percent in over 5 years.

8. Different products of TCS:

- i) **CHROMA™:** is a solution for enterprises to adopt best practices for human resource (HR) and different human resource-related activities. Thereby helping those persons to achieve a high level of business activities to realize their potential. The main features of CHROMA™ are talent acquisition, talent core, talent development, talent performance, and talent pay. CHROMA™ is a cloud technology platform offers flexibility for the organization to choose and host already configured modules by the human resource team to accelerate their digital journey. It empowers the HR organization by lowering the risk and uncertainty by providing rapid time to value. Some of the benefits are rehearses through agile HR, collective work environment, Supported endowment, etc...

ii) **ignio™**:

Is a unique cognitive automation solution that judiciously blends intelligence and automation to transform the Enterprise IT operation into a proactive, fast and reliable IT operation. ignio™ helps enterprise IT teams solve pain points, maneuver through the chaos, identify the source of problems, and fix it automatically. With ignio™, enterprises face no business disruption and no irate customers. The key features and benefits are, Assimilates data from multiple sources and combines it to construct a comprehensive blueprint. Identifies and highlights areas that need attention with detailed reasoning and evidence proactively. Manages every aspect of the alert lifecycles such as alert prediction, detection, suppression, reprioritization, and resolution. It uses the most advanced form of ML and AI for its forecasting and prioritization abilities respectively. Eliminates up to 95% of alert noise. Triage systematically to identify the root causes of an incident. Identifies and prescribes the best context-based action to fix the incident. Reduces up to 60% of manual effort. Automates all technology lifecycle operation activities such as provisioning, commissioning, configuration, validate, backup & restore, and decommissioning. Meets enterprise needs, Performs end-to-end activities. After 3 years of inauguration this automation software has tremendous growth in both customers gaining as well as in terms of revenue. Now it also manages more than million technologies all over the world of more than 500 corporations.

iii) **Jile™**: An Agile DevOps platform enables an organization to adopt Agile, Scale, and Transform into innovative Agile enterprises. Adopt Agile helps teams adopt agile methods and practices to deliver software such that backlog management, release management, iteration planning, task management, and continuous integration and delivery. Scale jile helps scale methods on programs and portfolios to deliver integrated solutions such as a team of teams support, multi-level backlog, synchronize release and iteration planning, road mapping and dependency management. Transform Jile helps Enterprise to align business strategy to execution, deliver innovation faster, track outcomes, and provide continuous value to all stake holders. Some of the benefits are Easy to try, buy and use. Available in cloud and on-demand trail and usage, simple to scale, built for enterprise, benefit from industry experience.

iv) **Quartz Blockchain solutions**: is the solution power that take along different firms or organizations by making the environment that improves the value provided by each organizations. It was reconnoitered in different areas like payments, archive, exchange of informations, finance sector, digital government, health care, insurance, music, art and so on. This solution also covers solutions for business related activities across industries, developing quality of code for various technology, easily combines already developed technologies, management and monitoring of entire eco system. There are lot of benefits for the industry from this solution to reduce the duplication of data, integrity of data, encryption of data through cryptography, to provide high level security for the data, to make data unchangeable, to provide restriction towards unauthorized access and helps to integrate legacy systems.

v) **TCS BANCS**: The TCS BANCS is a universal financial platform with the digital-first, cloud-first platform. This product has a solution for banking, capital market, and insurance. For banking product named as TCS BaNCS Digital which delivers as impressive digital experience and stays ahead of the curve. For the capital market, it has a solution like BaNCS ADK and for insurance it has a product like TCS BaNCS cloud lets our enterprise connect to

anything, anywhere and anytime. According to 2018 Sales League Table it was second top selling banking system surveyed by UK based IBS intelligence.

vi) **iON**: It is an ERP for manufacturing and education that also considered as worlds largest digital valuation system that valued over 2 million candidates in 2019.

And over 162.5 million candidates are accessed by the date. In this package over 87,677 courses available. And under 345 clients over 2.67 million learners are learning in this platform. This product contains 289 clients in manufacturing and 142 clients in education.

vii) **TCS ADD**: It is a package for medicine production and clinical laboratory experiment with digital touch.

viii) **TCS HOBBS**: It is a package based on SaaS for business, transformation of business and management of revenue. And also spreads its business wings in to prepaid direct to home, plane engine, marketing by influencing current technologies like RPA, big data and other familiar interfaces.

ix) **Optumera™**: It is a business suit especially for people who doing selling business to optimize the process using artificial intelligence.

x) **Omnistore™**: It also a software suit for store keepers to interconnect various stores with trouble less customer experience and forecasting the operations with using artificial intelligence.

xi) **TCS MasterCraft**: It is digital package especially for IT firms to systematize and accomplish IT processes.

9. Highlights of the performance in revenue, profit, share and employee metrics in last 5 year:

All these 4 charts actually depict the trends in revenue, profit, employee and earnings in the last 5 financial year of the company.

10. Achievements:

- Awarded as number one employer in the world from last 4 decades by employer's institute. #1 top employer in 16 countries including India, Australia, Netherlands, UK, etc...
- Among 3 brands in the same segment TCS was considered as number 1 brand.
- In Germany, UK, Nordics, Benelux and Switzerland TCS secured first place in customer satisfaction in terms of individual ranking sector from last 6 years.
- Invented a product known as PACETM is a brand product for research, innovation and digital transformation service was very helpful for customer's business journey.
- Invented airline solution for Singapore airlines to improve airline operations that enables digital technology, effectiveness in operation and enhances the experiences of customer.
- Implemented a solution for power plant that is used by power generating companies to convert their operation to digital way using artificial intelligence and internet of things like technology.
- Successfully launched a solution for rail customers to avoiding component failure, maintaining safety by using the digital solution intelligent rail with the help of SAP.
- Acquired London based award winning digital studio W12 studios.
- Successfully launched a cloud based product Agile DevOps to track production and deliver within the enterprise.
- Acquired top position in IT service and software field by survey conducted by Asia executive team.
- Gets best CEO award in 2018 by survey conducted by Asia executive team.
- Gets second place in best CFO award by survey conducted by Asia executive team.
- Acquires first place in IR Professional award, Corporate governance award and IR program award and ESG/SRI metrics by survey conducted by Asia executive team.
- Become World's most valuable company by crossing it's the market valuation above hundred million dollars.
- Successfully launched a solution for banking and it became the top selling banking system in universe.

11. Contributions to the nation:

- CSR(Corporate Social Responsibility) program “Impact Through Empowerment” makes the people to allow betterment on their life.
- Edification, growth in terms of skill, health and green conservation are the key area of the company that always focused.
- Company always spreads its hand in time of natural disaster.
- Given moral support to rebuild some historical sites.
- A total of 542 crores of rupees are spent on the CSR activities last year.
- Overall it contributes 36 crores of rupees in last year for different social activities such as children’s education, better employment generation, scholarship, etc...
- Overall it contributes 296 crores of rupees in last year for relief fund, cancer hospital to improve technology in cancer treatment and sponsoring healthy foods to the people.
- It also spent rupees 3 crores in last year for conservation of water. This amount spent for the activities like repair, preservation, renewal, flood protection, etc...
- 92 crores of rupees are contributed to the TCS foundation.
- In India’s IT and ITeS sector TCS registered more than ten percent revenue, thus became the leader of the market.
- In India TCS is the only private sector company having huge number of employees thus became the largest employer of the nation.
- After government sector organization such as army, railway and post office, TCS is the only company became the largest employer in nation.
- Started an IT literacy program for adults called ALP that eliminates the weakness in literacy of adult people.
- Started a program called UDAAN to help Kashmiri youth people to increase employability in cooperation with NSDC.
- Over 59000 youth to be trained in Jammu & Kashmir under the project UDAAN.
- MedMatra is an integrated ‘Hospital Management System, along with IT infrastructure fully integrated, web-based solution provides free of cost to cancer institute at Chennai.

12. Identifying strategies used by company using SWOC analysis:

SWOT analysis is a predefined tool to identify the Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, and Threat in an organization.

Strength:

- Clients from the different market: here the company does not depend on single market clients rather than it has the client from different distinguished markets like Telecom, software, banking, financial, retail, media, entertainment, medicine, etc... reduces the market risk
- A geographically large area of coverage that helps the company to spread its business to different continents or nations or cities so that it reduces the business risk and improves the appearance of the country in world.

- TCS has a strong business partnership with other companies such as Adobe, Amazon, Bosch, Dell, and HP, etc... across the world, so because of this it can able to provide viable and advanced business in terms of product and services,
- Strong and balanced wings of TCS like BPO, IT, development, etc. ...are able to attract different clients that really help to improve the business.
- The well reputation of founder's image helps the company to develop.
- Good infrastructure and innovative labs that enable the TCS employees to update themselves in order to know the latest technology.

Weakness:

- In 2014 TCS was involved in a legal battle against the epic system for misuse of the epic system's confidential information. This type of incident really damages the company's reputation.
- The subsidiary companies of TCS are Deligenta which was not performed up to the mark, which affects the performance of TCS in the bottom line.
- Being a company TCS mainly working in outsourcing the project should have a strong consultation team, but the consultation team which shows a strong reflection of the decline in the growth cycle of TCS.

Opportunities:

- Digital technology and digital transformation are one of the big opportunities for the company. In the entire world, the business is digitalized and TCS encases this opportunity by coming up with products on a different platform.
- The whole world is moving towards technology like cloud-based technology, so the company has very well infrastructure to develop a cloud-based solution.
- Machine to Machine (M2M) solution is the future trend and the company is all having a comprehensive suite of M2M service that takes advantage of the demand for M2M solution.
- Enterprise mobility solution is now having a high demand in the business market and is expected to grow up to 24.7 percent until 2022. So the TCS having more focus on developing enterprise mobility solutions.

Challenges:

- As we know the TCS is a multinational company, so some of the immigration restrictions of foreign countries will affect the profitability of the company.
- There is some intense competition from other Indian companies like Wipro, Infosys, Accenture, and Cap Gemini, etc...
- Indian IT industry is subjected to a high attrition rate which increases cost in providing skills and leadership for newly hired employees.
- Demands from the employees to increase the cost for the employee.
- Increasing the value for rupees against the dollar is always a big challenge for the company.

13. Awards and accolades received:

In 2018, Asia's outstanding company's poll, TCS received the most outstanding company of India award; Named as the fastest-growing brand of the year in 2019 and TCS brand value

crosses 12.8 billion in last year. According to Europe's large independent survey, TCS secured 1st rank in terms of customer satisfaction. By ICICI Lombard and CNBC-TV18 at the prestigious India risk management awards won the best risk management framework and systems in the IT ITES sector. In large industry category at the CII industrial intellectual property award won the best patent portfolio award in 2018. According to the Forbes best company list, TCS secured 35th rank all over the world. In finance, Asia's managed survey in 2019 TCS got 1st rank in investor relations and 2nd rank in the best-managed company. And the industrial investor's all India Asia's team ranking TCS clinches first place in best corporate governance and second place in best investors relation in 2018. In individual ranking CEO and MD of TCS, Mr. Rajesh Gopinathan secured first rank and best CEO award. And Ramakrishnan secured the best CFO award and KedharShiralise secured with the best IR professional. TCS BaNCS, along with its customer DBS, won the 'Financial Markets Technology Implementation of the Year – Best Custodian System Implementation' at The Asian Banker Financial Markets Awards 2018. ignio™ won an award for First Use of Machine Learning within the Workload Automation Analytics Industry from the enterprise Management Association.

TCS employers are recognized as a global top employer for the 4th consecutive year by top employer institute. I also won the 2018 Canadian National HR Award for the 'Best Recruitment Campaign', for the fourth straight year. Won 11 Stevie– 5 Gold Stevie, 2 Silver Stevie, and 4 Bronze Stevie – at the 2018 Great Employers Awards for achievements in Talent Acquisition and Development, Leadership Training, and Creative Use of Technology Awarded 2018. Won the 2018 Pega Partner Excellence Award. Won the Social Responsibility Award at the North American Employee Engagement Awards for the third year in a row. Named America's Most Community-Minded Information Technology Company in the 2018 Civic 50 by Points of Light. Likewise, TCS secured with a lot of other awards and accolades during the year 2018 and 2019.

14. Conclusion:

Out of several software companies, only a few companies in India reached a global level and extend their market to several countries all over the world. TCS is also one of those companies that reached this level only because of its dedication shown to achieve the goal. In this paper, I conclude that one of the reasons TCS reached to global level because it understands the market requirement properly and comes out with software product that was able to meet market requirement, so every product comes out from TCS has more clients in a global level. TCS has a good research lab and research team that can able to forecast the future market scenario and thereby looking to develop products that meet necessity at that point in time. TCS business policies are studied in this paper based on guidelines provided in the company analysis case study methodology

15. Reference:

[1] Owolabi, Ajao&Obida, "Liquidity Management and Corporate Profitability: Case Study of Selected Manufacturing Companies Listed on The Nigerian Stock Exchange" Business Management Dynamics, Volume.2, No.2 , pp.10-25, August 2012.

- [2] Wafi S Ahmed Hassan HassanMabrouk Adel, “ Fundamental analysis models in financialmarkets- Review study”, *Procedia economic and finance* 30, 2015 pp 939-947.
- [3] Wafi S Ahmed Hassan HassanMabrouk Adel, “ Fundamental analysis models in financial markets- Review study”, *Procedia economic and finance* 30, 2015 pp 939-947.
- [4] Hansen Randall S. and Hansen Katherine; “Using a SWOT Analysis in Your Career Planning”, Published by Quint Essential Careers, Deland, Florida, 1996, pp. 1-4.
- [5] KhuranaAjeet; “Understanding and Using SWOT Analysis”, from *businessmajors.about.com*, About, Inc., New York Time Co., 2005, pp 1-5.
- [6] Aithal, P. S. (2017). *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, ISSN: 2581-6942, Vol. 1, No. 2, July 2017. *SRINIVAS PUBLICATION Google Scholar Citation: IJCSBE International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE) A Refereed International Journal of Srinivas University, India. Aithal, P. S, 1(2), 2581–6942. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.810347>*
- [7] Aithal, P. S., &Aithal, S. (2019). *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, ISSN: 2581-6012, Vol. 4, No. 1, February 2019. *Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS) A Refereed International Journal of Srinivas University, 4(1), 2581–6012. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2557222>*
- [8] Prasad, K. (n.d.). *A Critical Study on Applications of Machine Learning Algorithms in Business Analytics*.
- [9] Publication Jithin Raj, S. (2018). *A Critical Study on Business Strategies of 3i Infotech Ltd. International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE) (Vol. 2)*. Retrieved from www.srinivaspublication.com
- [10] Publication Sneha, S. (2018). *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (Analysis of Business Strategies of Salesforce.com Inc (Vol. 2)*. Retrieved from <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3184087>
- [11] Brindha G., Emerging trends of telemedicine in India, *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, v-6, i-SUPPL5, pp-4572-4578, 2013.
- [12] Kothari,C.R., “Research Methodology Methods & Techniques”, New Age International Publishers, New Delhi, Second Edition, 2008.
- [13] Delmas, M. (2001). Stakeholders and competitive advantage: the case of ISO 14001. *Productionand Operations Management*, 10(3), 343-358.

- [14] Noor, K. B. M. (2008). Case study: A strategic research methodology. *American journal of applied sciences*, 5(11), 1602-1604.
- [15] Aithal, P. S. (2017). An Effective Method of Developing Business Case Studies Based on Company Analysis. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME)*, 2(1), 16-27. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.400579>.
- [16] Aithal, P. S. (2017). An Effective Method of Developing Business Case Studies based on Company Analysis, *International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME)*, 2(1), 16-27. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.400579>.
- [17] Jithin Raj, K. & Krishna Prasad, K. (2018). A Critical Study on Business Strategies of 3i Infotech Ltd. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 2(1), 13-21. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1247319>.
- [18] Aithal, P. S., (2017). ABCD Analysis as Research Methodology in Company Case Studies. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 2(2), 40-54. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.891621>.
- [19] Aithal, P. S. (2017). Industry Analysis – The First Step in Business Management Scholarly Research. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 2(1), 1-13. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.810347>.
- [20] Varun Shenoy and Aithal, P. S. (2016). Changing Approaches in Campus Placements - A new futuristic Model. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME)*, 1(1), 766 – 776. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.160966>.
- [21] Noor, K. B. M. (2008). Case study: A strategic research methodology. *American journal of applied sciences*, 5(11), 1602-1604.

Paper 10

**INFORMATION ASSURANCE: THE WAY TO
INTRODUCE IN UG EDUCATION IN INDIA—A
POLICY FRAMEWORK**

P. K. Paul¹, P. S. Aithal² A. Bhuimali³

¹Executive Director, MCIS, Department of CIS, Raiganj University (RGU), West Bengal, India

³Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India

²Vice Chancellor, Raiganj University, West Bengal, India

Corresponding Author: pkpaul.infotech@gmail.com

Abstract

Information Assurance (IA) is an important and emerging concepts related to the information security. Information Assurance (IA) is also required for the managing and implementing information security related policies. There are two types of security; firstly traditional security and another one is computational security. Traditional security is about the manual documents and content related security whereas; computational security is deals with various components based security viz. Network Security, Web Security, Database Technology, Multimedia Technology etc. Information Security is very close with the Information Assurance (IA), as it is also deals with Manual and Computational areas; though it is additionally deals with the policies, regulation and guidelines of security. Many universities internationally offered degrees and academic programs on Information Assurance (IA) and allied fields viz. Information Assurance and Security, IT and Information Assurance, Computer and Information Assurance, IT Security and Assurance etc. The degrees are offered in different levels viz. Bachelors Degree, Masters Degree, PG Diploma, PG Certificate, Doctoral and Post Doctoral level; there are different universities. In India, a very few universities have started security related degrees and most of these are offering traditional nomenclatures. There are potentialities to offer the degrees at UG levels with little initiatives and policies. This paper is talks about such potentiates and situation in detail.

Keywords: Information Assurance, UG Education, Indian Higher Education, Research Degrees, IT Security

1. Introduction :

Information Assurance is an emerging field of Computing and Information Technology responsible for the privacy and security management in the institutions and organizations [4], [24]. Information Assurance is responsible for different affairs leading to designing, development, as well as management computational systems and additionally manual

information systems. It is a broader field than Information Security and emerged in recent past. Moreover, the field is interdisciplinary in nature. The need of cyber security including data privacy different universities are providing academic programs and courses on these areas leading to Cryptography, Computer Security, Information Technology Security, Information Security etc. Information Assurance is a broad field that incorporates all the subjects related to the security and privacy both in technological and managerial way. Information Assurance is an emerging concept in government and administration as well [1], [3], [8]. The leading, innovative and emerging universities worldwide is offering different program on Information Assurance and its subfields. In India huge number of educational institutes offers IT and Computer related education in different levels. And few of such universities started specialization and subfield in Information Technology [4], [5], [14].

2. Objective and Agenda

The paper is conceptual in nature and theoretical as well, it deals with formulation of following agenda and objective—

- To learn about the basics of Information Assurance including its smaller and broader area.
- To find out the nature and characteristics of Information Assurance.
- To learn about the function and need of Information Assurance education program at present day context.
- To learn about the availability of the programs on Information Assurance and allied discipline in international educational institutes.
- To find out the way to introduce Information Assurance and allied fields at Under Graduate level in Indian universities.
- To learn about the challenges and issues in introducing Information Assurance subject in Indian universities.

3. Information Assurance: Overview

Information assurance is dedicated to different form of information and data management; hence it is responsible for healthy digital and physical content management. Electronic device privacy and security is also the concern in Information Assurance field [6], [7], [11]. National Institute of Standards and Technology defined Information Assurance dealing *any measures that protect and defend information and information systems by ensuring their availability, integrity, authentication, confidentiality, and non-repudiation. These measures include providing for restoration of information systems by incorporating protection, detection, and reaction capabilities.*

Information Assurance is also deals policy and process of its different sub field and it may include IT Security, Information Security etc. Technological system fulfillment is the ultimate goal of Information Assurance and apart from these Management principle are also important

aspects of this field [9], [10], [15]. There are different affairs to be performed by the Information Assurance professionals—

- Corporate Governance using Information Assurance principles
- Planning, formulation of the regulation and standard of Information Assurance
- Auditing of Information Security and its products
- Disaster recovery related to information system and infrastructure

Information Assurance is composed with different sub fields viz. Information Security (and this is composed with IT Security), Information Technology Security (It composed with different part viz. Database Security, Web Security, Network Security, Software Security etc), Computer Security (focused on Cryptography and Encryption) etc [12], [13], [18].

4. Information Assurance and Allied Education

Information Assurance is today not a concept rather it is an emerging research area and academic program in many international universities [10], [16], [22]. However different universities used different nomenclatures of this field which include but not limited to—

- Information Assurance
- Cyber Security and Information Assurance
- Information Assurance & Security
- Information Assurance & Information Systems Management etc

However the curricula differ from university to university and focused on different areas viz. Communication Technology, IT Risk Management, Advanced Network Security Design, Web System Security, Cybercrime Management & Response etc. STRAYER University, US offers the degree of MS Information Assurance with Cyber Security as a specialization and comes with following

- Information Systems for Decision Making
- Theories of Security Management
- Communication Technology
- Advanced Computer Architecture
- IT Risk Management
- Advanced Network Security Design
- Web Application Security
- Cybercrime Techniques & Response
- IT Audit & Control
- Security Access and Control Strategies

Similarly, the field Information Assurance is also comes with UG Degree in few universities and offers both technological and managerial affairs of the security the in course contents.

5. India and UG Education in Computing and Information Field

India is a largest education system in the universe composed with different types of educational institutes. The UG education is normally offered by the Colleges and few universities. India holds 40000+ HEIs (Higher Educational Institutes). The UG Degrees in Computing and allied field available with following degrees—

- Bachelor of Science
- Bachelor of Technology
- Bachelor of Engineering
- BCA (Bachelor of Computer Applications)
- Bachelor of Vocation

Whereas these degrees are offered with different computing related subjects and specializations viz.—

- Computer Science
- Computer Application
- Computer Science and Engineering/ Technology
- Information Science
- Information Technology
- Information Systems
- Information Science and Engineering etc

6. Way to Introduce IA in Indian Academics at UG

It is worthy to note that as per the study adopted, following international universities offers Information Assurance and allied subjects—

- BS-IT (Information Assurance and Cyber Security), offered by the Capella University, United State/ 180 Credit
- BS-Cyber Security and Information Assurance, offered by the City University of Seattle, United State/180 Credit
- BS-Cyber Security and Information Assurance, offered by the University of Michigan-Dearborn, United State/ 106 Credit

The syllabus also varies, instead of only core subjects of Information Assurance, the universities offers wide range of courses based on requirement. Here in Table: 1 depicted curricula of City University of Seattle, United State with 180 Credit.

Table: 1- Information Assurance program at UG level, City of University of Seattle

Programs and University	Curriculum Focus on the Security
<p>BS-Cyber Security and Information Assurance,</p> <p>Offered by the City University of Seattle, United State.</p> <p>Having 180 Credit</p>	<p>Basics for the Degree</p> <p>Fundamentals of Accounting Introduction to Web Design Any Two Research Methods & Practice Justice and Ethics Criminal Procedural Law Principle of Micro Economics</p> <p>Governance, Risk Management, and Compliance Core (45 Credits)</p> <p>Cybercrime, Technology, and Social Change (5) Cyber and Surveillance Law and Governance (5) Investigation of Cyber Crime (5) Applied Criminology and Crime Prevention (5) Enterprise Risk Management (5) Homeland Security and Espionage (5) Policy and Audits (5) IT Compliance (5) Investigation of Business Crimes (5) Or Risk Assessment and Prevention (5)</p> <p>Cybersecurity Technology Core (40 Credits)</p> <p>Network Communications Basics (5) Network Security (5) Data Management Communications and Networking (5) Internet Technologies (5) Information Systems (5) Information Security (5) Tools and Techniques (5) Computer Science I: C++ (5) Or</p>

	<p>Programming with Python (5)</p> <p>Required Electives (10 Credits) Any Two</p> <p>Legal Issues in the Workplace Operations Management (5) Fundamentals of Criminology (5) Investigation of Business Crimes* (5) Organizational and White-Collar Crime (5) Communicating Crisis, Emergency, and Social Change (5) Systems Analysis and Design (5)</p> <p>Capstone (5 Credits) Bureaupathology (5)</p>
--	---

It is important to note that most of the universities offers the field Information Assurance with focus on technologies and managerial aspects leading to security and privacy [17], [19], [20]. The mentioned syllabus includes Governance, Risk Management, and Compliance Core Courses for 45 Credit and Cyber Security Technology Core for 40 Credit.

Hence as far as India is concerned, the field may be started as a full-fledged degree nomenclature and some of such degrees are mentioned in Table: 2; though the field may also offer as a Major or Specialization in Information Assurance and allied nomenclature. In India, Computing related Bachelor Degrees are available in different forms and thus different major based degrees are proposed in the field and these are depicted in Table: 3 and 4.

Table: 2 Possible UG Degrees in Information Assurance in Indian Context

Information Assurance Full fledged Degrees
BSc/BTech/BE in Information Assurance BSc/BTech/BE in Cyber Security and Information Assurance BSc/BTech/BE in Information Assurance & Security BSc/BTech/BE in Information Assurance & Information Systems Management etc

Table: 3 Possible specialized UG Degrees in Information Assurance in Indian Context

Information Assurance in BSc Programs (Major)
BSc- Information Technology (Information Assurance) BSc- Information Science (Information Assurance)

BSc- Computer Science (Information Assurance)
 BSc- Computer Applications (Information Assurance)

It is worthy to note that these programs may also be available in other merged nomenclature and these include— Information Assurance, Cyber Security and Information Assurance, Information Assurance & Security, Information Assurance & Information Systems Management etc as a major.

Table: 4 Depicted possible specialized UG Degrees in Computer Applications in Indian Context

Information Assurance in BCA Programs (Major)
BCA in Information Assurance
BCA in Cyber Security and Information Assurance
BCA in Information Assurance & Security
BCA in Information Assurance & Information Systems Management etc

This way, the field Information Assurance may be offered in different form in existing programs as well as full-fledged

7. Issues and Challenges

- The field Information Assurance is emerging and interdisciplinary in nature and thus the skill providers needs knowledge in both technological and managerial areas.
- Different allied departments or possible collaborative departments may be tied-up for offering the interdisciplinary areas if possible or available viz. law, management, public administration etc.
- Industrial tie-ups is required to built to offer the Information Assurance programs in skill based context.
- Universities and educational institutions are not interested to change the traditional systems, and there is a less awareness about the field in the academic institutes, faculties and students.
- The emerging sub fields of Information Assurance such as Cloud Security, Big Data and Mobile Security is an emerging issues.

8. Conclusions with Suggestion

Information Assurance and Privacy is the need of hour, today almost all kind of organizations and institutions are using technological systems for their operation data management [14], [21], [23]. Additionally the organizations are also doing the traditional data management and thus knowledge organization tools may be used. The emerging Cloud Security, Big Data and Mobile Security should be incorporated in the curricula, moreover the industrial skill based vendor certification curricula may also required to incorporate in the syllabus for more suitable product

development. India is a largest educational systems and variety of Bachelors degrees are offered in the Computing field and thus with proper initiative and strategy easily Information Assurance may be started.

References

- [1] Bonner, W., & Chiasson, M. (2005). If fair information principles are the answer, what was the question? An actor-network theory investigation of the modern constitution of privacy. *Information and Organization*, 15(4), 267-293.
- [2] Borgesius, F. Z., Gray, J., & van Eechoud, M. (2015). Open data, privacy, and fair information principles: Towards a balancing framework. *Berkeley Technology Law Journal*, 30(3), 2073-2131.
- [3] Bulgurcu, B., Cavusoglu, H., & Benbasat, I. (2010). Information security policy compliance: an empirical study of rationality-based beliefs and information security awareness. *MIS quarterly*, 34(3), 523-548.
- [4] Burkell, J., & Carey, R. (2011). Personal Information and the Public Library: Compliance with Fair Information Practice Principles/Les renseignements personnels dans les bibliothèques publiques: le respect des principes d'équité dans les pratiques de collecte de renseignements. *Canadian Journal of Information and Library Science*, 35(1), 1-16.
- [5] Cannoy, S. D., & Salam, A. F. (2010). A framework for health care information assurance policy and compliance. *Communications of the ACM*, 53(3), 126-131.
- [6] Chakraborty, R., Ramireddy, S., Raghu, T. S., & Rao, H. R. (2010). The information assurance practices of cloud computing vendors. *IT professional*, 12(4), 29-37.
- [7] Chen, Y., Ramamurthy, K., & Wen, K. W. (2012). Organizations' information security policy compliance: Stick or carrot approach?. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 29(3), 157-188.
- [8] Cherdantseva, Y., & Hilton, J. (2015). Information security and information assurance: discussion about the meaning, scope, and goals. In *Standards and Standardization: Concepts, Methodologies, Tools, and Applications* (pp. 1204-1235).
- [9] Cooper, S., Nickell, C., Piotrowski, V., Oldfield, B., Abdallah, A., Bishop, M., ... & Pérez, L. C. (2010). An exploration of the current state of information assurance education. *ACM SIGCSE Bulletin*, 41(4), 109-125.
- [10] Ezingear, J. N., McFadzean, E., & Birchall, D. (2005). A model of information assurance benefits. *Information Systems Management*, 22(2), 20-29.
- [11] Hamill, J. T., Deckro, R. F., & Kloeber Jr, J. M. (2005). Evaluating information assurance strategies. *Decision Support Systems*, 39(3), 463-484.
- [12] Höne, K., & Eloff, J. H. P. (2002). Information security policy—what do international information security standards say?. *Computers & security*, 21(5), 402-409.
- [13] Knapp, K. J., Marshall, T. E., Kelly Rainer, R., & Nelson Ford, F. (2006). Information security: management's effect on culture and policy. *Information Management & Computer Security*, 14(1), 24-36.

- [14] Paul, P.K., Chatterjee, D., Bhumali,A., Atarthy, A. (2016). Cyber Crime: An Important facet for promoting Digital Humanities—A Short Review in *Saudi Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 1(1), 13-16.
- [15] Paul, P.K. & Aithal, P.S. (2018). Cyber Crime: Challenges, Issues, Recommendation and Suggestion in Indian Context, *International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology* 3(1), 59-62.
- [16] Paul, P.K., and Aithal P.S. (2018) Cyber Security to Information Assurance: The Changing World of Cyber Sciences in Proceedings of National Conference on Quality in Higher education challenges & opportunities (ISBN: 978-93-5311-082-6), Srinivas University, 11-18.
- [17] Pérez, L. C., Cooper, S., Hawthorne, E. K., Wetzel, S., Brynielsson, J., Gökce, A. G., ... & Philips, A. (2011, June). Information assurance education in two-and four-year institutions. In *Proceedings of the 16th annual conference reports on Innovation and technology in computer science education-working group reports* (pp. 39-53).
- [18] Proia, A., Simshaw, D., & Hauser, K. (2015). Consumer cloud robotics and the fair information practice principles: Recognizing the challenges and opportunities ahead. *Minn. JL Sci. & Tech.*, 16, 145.
- [19] Rees, J., Bandyopadhyay, S., & Spafford, E. H. (2003). A policy framework for information security. *Communications of the ACM*, 46(7), 101-106.
- [20] Reidenberg, J. R. (1994). Setting standards for fair information practice in the US private sector. *Iowa L. Rev.*, 80, 497.
- [21] Li, Y., Stewart, W., Zhu, J., & Ni, A. (2012). Online privacy policy of the thirty Dow Jones corporations: Compliance with FTC Fair Information Practice Principles and readability assessment. *Communications of the IIMA*, 12(3), 5.
- [22] Safa, N. S., Von Solms, R., & Furnell, S. (2016). Information security policy compliance model in organizations. *Computers & Security*, 56, 70-82.
- [23] Schou, C. D., & Trimmer, K. J. (2004). Information assurance and security. *Journal of Organizational and End User Computing*, 16(3), 123-145.
- [24] Twitchell, D. P. (2006, September). Social engineering in information assurance curricula. In *Proceedings of the 3rd annual conference on Information security curriculum development* (pp. 191-193). ACM.

Paper 11

A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY ON THE IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM FOR THE SOCIAL CHANGE

Maithri, S. M. Riha Parvin

1ST M.com St. Agnes Centre for Post Graduate Studies and Research
Mangalore, Karnataka, India.
Email: maithri98@gmail.com
riharafiq123@gmail.com

Abstract:

The present article studies the importance of education in the personal, social and economic development of the nation. Education empowers our mind that will be able to conceive good thoughts and ideas. It also enables the students to do the analysis while making life decision. Unfortunately, schools and college teachers is only behind completing the syllabus for the year and the results of the examination. Today the result is excessively focused on memorization. Let's understand the essence and the purpose of education as articulated by the National Policy of Education,1986. The initiatives should be brought up by the teachers which helps in instilling the values and a greater sense for the purpose to prepare the future generations for the effective social makers. The education provided in schools and colleges and the efficient need for the society's growth should go hand in hand. Education must promote knowledge and integration among the people by broadening the visions of students and nationalism in the students.If we accept that, the education should influence on shaping society, then it is clear that we must focus on the real goals of education.

Keywords: Teaching, Educational system, Transformative learning, Development of personnel, Economic growth

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is the process of facilitating learning or the acquisition of knowledge, skills, value, belief and habits. Education empowers minds that will be able to conceive good thoughts and ideas. It is important to people of all the ages and it has no limit. It also enables the student to do the analysis while making life decision. Education can help the society in personal and National level. It has been shown to increase economic growth and stability. One of the most important benefits of education is how it improves personal lives and help societies to run smoothly. Education promotes fulfilling, fuller lifestyle.

When we look back 70's and 80's, many people survived without education. But in current situation, much more competition raised among students. At the same time, students have lot of facilities for their higher studies. Since we have all facilities and technologies, students can study hard and compete with their level of a student.

Education plays a vital role in social change but the present Educational Policies doesn't give the exposure to social change. It must assist in molding the attitude of people but also in creating a desire for change by providing right knowledge and their thinking. Education Policy must make people aware of their Social Evils like dowry, caste system, infanticide, rape, alcoholism, drug addiction, gambling, corruption bribe, prostitute etc. Even though the educational policies have improved, social problems haven't found any solution.

2.OBJECTIVES:

- To determine innovative and creative teaching techniques
- To Understand the Need of self defense education.
- To upgrade the education system

3.LITERATURE REVIEW :

SL. NO.	TITLE	RESEARCHER	YEAR	SUMMARY
1.	TEACHING FOR SOCIAL CHANGE	DILEEP RANJEKAR	2015	In this article he says that it is not merely the teaching of math, social, science or language but how they are taught, keeping in mind the purpose of teaching them and how they are integrated in our day to day life, which would contribute to education and society being better.
2.	EDUTOPIA	BEN JOHNSON	2019	In this article, Creativity and innovation starts with thinking. Imagination and history shows that many things we imagine are later actually created to encourage for creative thinking. Teachers can plan and frame curriculum and provide tools that give students option, voice and choice in order to enable them to be creative.

3.	INDIATODAY		2019	According to the article, Maharashtra government wants to bring self defense as a part of school curriculum in the state. The Maharashtra education minister responded to an online petition fixed by the women self defense coach, Neha from Pune, after hearing many rape cases.
4.	TIMES OF INDIA		2019	In this article, it says that India remains largely unsafe for women. In 2016, 3.38 lakh crimes against women, rape case made up to 11.5% of them. But with only 1 in 4 cases ending up in conviction, it's a painfully slow down to justice for rape victims in the country. This article makes us feel that women should be protected from all kinds of abuses.

4.LIMITATION:

- No importance is given for creative thinking in Government schools
- Compulsion of self defense education is not made in draft educational policy 2019
- Lack of accuracy in case of primary data

5.RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Research is based on secondary data i.e., journals, internet.

6.FINDINGS:

Education has become an object of fear and competition, wherein students and their parents wage war to win a battle to earn money, fame and rank, here no importance is given to creative thinking. The notes, guide books and text are loaded in human gun & shot in exams with an aim to earn the rank. Less conceptual learning by the students but excessively based on memorization.

No proper education is given in government institution. Lesser standard of education is provided in government school when compared to other private schools.

The educational syllabus is outdated not completely but partially. Education is based on traditional form, which focuses on manufacturing our people to become clerk, servant etc but should be focusing on forming practical dreamer, inventor, entrepreneur, and leader rather than Labour and employee. Today's graduates don't take initiatives to start up a business they only employ themselves to work.

The major five countries which are marked as the most dangerous for women by the survey conducted in the year 2017 are India, Afghanistan, Syria, Somalia and Saudi Arabia. New Delhi has the highest number of rape reports among the Indian cities. And it is increasing as the year passes. The rape crime against the women in the year 2016 is 338594, out of which 2167 is gang rape.

7.SUGGESTIONS:

Not everyone can afford for ICSE education system that they offer. The schools must be encouraged to introduce conceptual learning which avoids students to mug up what they are being taught. While this will help students to understand the concepts better, they will also be able to retain and apply them better.

Indian schools and colleges must embrace technology and education with an open heart and propagate the same to the students as it is there, where their future lies. The benefit of technology in the form education is great for both students and teachers. Better training should be given to the graduates before they receive the graduate certificate.

Self defense education should be mandatory in the schools and colleges so that they don't need to look for anyone's help at the time of any unexpected attack on them and can be self-reliant and can also become helpful for others and it can easily adopt the forms and positions of the techniques.

8.CONCLUSION:

Our education system is still having the features what colonial educators inbuilt. Education is not always about earnings in lakh or becoming a big, rich man, it should be about humanism. The education serves as a solution to an ever changing educational landscape by utilizing the knowledge Of students, teachers, families and communities to provide an opportunity to empower & exchange idea, assists people to understand problems & become assets for change.

WEBLIOGRAPHY:

- www.straitstimes.com
- www.civilsocietyonline.com
- www.edutopia.org
- www.indiatoday.in>story
- www.deccanheraldtoday.com
- www.timesofindia.com

Paper 12

IMPLEMENTING PRODUCT DIVERSIFICATION STRATEGIES FOR THE SUSTAINABILITY OF A TECHNOLOGY COMPANY - A CASE OF MICROSOFT CORPORATION

Vinayachandra¹ & Krishna Prasad K²

¹Research Scholar, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

² College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

E-mail : veeciashu@gmail.com

Abstract

Started in 1975, with a view to develop and vend BASIC interpreter, today, Microsoft develop, produce, license, support and sell worldwide software, user-level electronics, personal computers, and allied services. The company is world-famous because of its best software products Windows operating systems, Office suits, IE and Edge. The company's notable hardware pieces are Xbox and Microsoft Surface family touch-screen computers. The company is listed as the top software company by Forbes Global for many years. From its inception to date, the company is maintaining top ranking technology-wise, product-wise, service-wise, revenue-wise, and growth-wise. It is possible for the company to sustain growth because of the integration and implementation of product diversification strategy. Over the years the company transformed from just a developer and seller of interpreter to producer & marketer of wide variety of software-hardware products. This paper analyses the strategies the company adopted and incorporated in diversifying product and services lineup to sustain growth and maintain market stability. It also analyses the relevance and acceptability of different Microsoft products, its customer base, and software market share and near future strategies.

Keywords: Microsoft, strategies, product diversification, Windows, generic, intensive.

1. INTRODUCTION

Microsoft is Redmond based American company founded in the year 1975. It develops and supports computer software, IT services, PC hardware and solutions, which afford customers with a special value and help individual users and corporate customers, realize their potential. The company proffers a variety of services and business solutions together with cloud to customers and business. Microsoft presents software, services, platform and content to customers and support & consultation to enterprises. It includes operating systems, productivity/server/business solution applications, system management tools, application development tools, games, support to cloud, IoT, cyber security and design, manufacture & trade devices such as PCs, tablets, gaming & entertainment consoles, intelligent devices and connected accessories. Its business platforms and software tools enable small business to

drive productivity, large business to build competitive advantage, and public-sector to compel efficiency[1-3].

2. BACKGROUND

From a mere developer and seller of the BASIC interpreter for the Altair 8800 systems to produce operating systems, application of different types, system management tools, software development tools, support to emerging technologies and design, manufacture & trade devices, the company has been recording steady growth and maintaining top rankings in the global software company rankings. The company is considered as one of the top-notch technology establishments in the world. The brand Microsoft and its products are ubiquitous today. One may think, what made Microsoft so much famous, relevant and versatile? It is because of the implementation of its own strategies, which placed Microsoft in competitive advantage compared to other technology enterprises. This paper analyses the strategies the company incorporated in diversifying product and services lineup to sustain growth and maintain market stability. It also analyses the relevance and influence of different Microsoft products, its customer base, and software market share and near-future plans [2].

3. THE PROGRESS

Bill Gates and his high school friend Paul Allen established "Micro-soft" on 4 April, 1975 in Albuquerque at New Mexico, encouraged as a result of a strong contract they just signed with MITS to market and distribute their translator as ' Altair Basic. With Bill Gates as its CEO, the company recorded \$16,000 income in total in the year with 3 employees on the roll.

Microsoft was registered in 1976. It developed FORTRAN, COBOL and Assembler, in tune with expanding the PC's capacities in the fields of science and business. In 1978, Microsoft's first offshore office was opened in Japan. In 1979, the company transferred its operations to Bellevue in Washington. With the addition of a fresh Belgian representative, Vector Microsoft, the company is expanding its service to the Europe. By the time, Microsoft has already under agreement with several OEMs. In 1980, Microsoft introduced Z-80 SoftCard, the company's first hardware product, which facilitated to execute programs originated for the CP/M OS on the Apple II computers with very minimum modifications. The year saw entry of Microsoft into the OS business with Xenix. Same year Microsoft introduced Pascal language. However, MS-DOS, the flagship product of the company of the time, consolidated the dominance of the company in the operating system market.

The major break of the company was in 1981 when IBM entered into a partnership to produce and supply crucial operating system, MS-DOS 1.0 to IBM PCs. Microsoft reorganized into a private company in the same year. Gates and Allen took over the responsibility as President & Chairman and Executive Vice President respectively. The company incorporated into Microsoft Inc. The enhanced version of BASIC, GW-BASIC was released in 1983. In the same year the company introduced programming language Microsoft C. The company's first application software Microsoft Multiplan spreadsheet was introduced. Microsoft unveiled Microsoft Windows that provided a graphical operating environment. With the release of Microsoft Mouse the company expanded into different markets. Microsoft Press, the company's own publishing division was started.

Microsoft's decennial celebrations are marked with the launching of Microsoft Windows 1.0 in 1985. The company launched Microsoft Works in 1986. In the same year, Microsoft

shifted its headquarters to Redmond in Washington. The company's stock goes public. In 1987, corporation introduced OS/2 produced with IBM to OEMs. Microsoft brought into its ambit Forethought, Inc and made it as its Graphics Business Unit. It announced the shipment Microsoft Bookshelf, a CD-ROM application containing 10 most popular and helpful creations in a single disk. Microsoft also announced Microsoft Excel for Windows and LAN Manager. The company announced Microsoft SQL Server in 1988. Microsoft moves to Canyon Park, Bothell's new manufacturing and distribution location. The Office Suite was released in 1989 bundled with separate productivity applications.

Microsoft launched Windows 3.0 in 1990 and Windows 3.1 in 1992. Microsoft announced Access Database for Windows in 1992. This relational DBMS offers simple, transparent data access; strong, usability-tested instruments; and a solid environment for development. Windows NT, a client-server solution with a strong, consistent and open platform was unveiled in 1993. In the same year the company introduced 'Creative Writer and Fine Artist', its first ever produce designed exclusively for children. Encarta, the first electronic encyclopedia was made available to the customers in 1994. Microsoft took over SOFTIMAGE Inc. Well known company tag line "Where Do You Want To Go Today" released.

Windows 95 and MSN was made available on its 2nd decennial birth year, 1995, Microsoft Bob for Windows, a social interface, with all new user-interface and eight core features (E-Mail, Address Book, Calendar, Letter Writer, Checkbook, Household Manager, Financial Guide, and GeoSafari) was announced. SideWinder 3D Pro was also announced. In 1996, the company announced ActiveX Technologies. SQL Server 6.5 and Flight Simulator for Windows 95 were also released.

In 1997 Microsoft made available the Office 97 worldwide and acquired Interse Corp. IE 4.0 was released. The year 1998 is most memorable for the company as it made available one of its best sold products Windows 98 worldwide. In the same year the company launched its India Development Center in Hyderabad. Microsoft's commitment to build innovative products for Macintosh continues as it published Office 98for Macintosh, a variety of Office Suite to Mac customers. Exchange Server made remarkable progress as it outsold Lotus Notes in 1998.

In 1999, Microsoft launched Encarta Africana. Microsoft unveiled its first online store, Shop. IE5.0 and Office 2000 were launched. Microsoft acquired Visio Corporation in 2000. Bill Gates assumed a fresh position for himself as Chairman and Chief Software Architect and Steve Ballmer becomes President and CEO. Microsoft launched Windows 2000.

Microsoft Windows XP, MS Office XP and Xbox made available in 2001. In 2002, Microsoft Visual Studio.NET launched incorporating. Tablet PC was launched. In the same year company released Windows Server 2003, announced Windows Mobile & Microsoft Office System. Microsoft unveiled Windows XP Media Center Edition 2005 in 2004.

The company launched Xbox 360 in 2005. Windows Vista was released in 2007. Windows Server 2008, SQL Server 2008 and Visual Studio 2008 were introduced in 2008. Windows 7 was published in 2009. Same year Bing decision engine was also launched. In the same year the company opened its first physical store in Scottsdale, Arizona. In 2010, Microsoft launched Office 2010, Windows Phone 7 and Microsoft Lync. Microsoft launched Office 365 in 2011. It formalized the acquisition of Luxembourg-based Skype in the same year.

Come year 2012, Microsoft acquired Yammer. It released Windows 8, Windows Server 2012, Visual Studio 2012, and Microsoft Surface. Microsoft launched Office 2013 and expands Office 365 in 2013. Microsoft launched Office for iPad in 2014 and also announced

the availability of Office apps for Android tablets. It acquired of Nokia with a nomenclature Mobile Qy in the same year. Also it acquired Mojang, the video game development company. Satya Nadella became the CEO.

Microsoft’s Windows 10, Surface 3 and Office 2016 released in the year 2015. SQL Server 2016, and Dynamics 365 launched in the year 2016. Microsoft acquired LinkedIn in the same year. The first HoloLens headset introduced with blended reality technology. It introduced Visual Studio 2017 and Xbox One X in 2017.

Opening of campus in Dublin, Ireland, announcement of Surface Hub 2, unveiling of Xbox C, made available of Surface Go, release of PowerShell Core 6.0 for the macOS and Linux are the highlights of 2018. Company completed the acquisition of GitHub [2-5].

4. GROWTH STRATEGIES

Microsoft Corporation has adopted two classes of strategies - generic and intensive growth strategies to keep company at competitive advantage in the PC software and hardware business. As shown in below Fig. 1, its generic approach directly intensive approach. This arrangement optimizes companies overall performance. Generally, the generic strategy of a company shows the overall approach to ensuring company competitiveness and intensive growth strategies outline the methods used to guarantee company growth & development.

Fig.1: Microsoft’s generic and intensive strategies alignment

4.1 Generic Strategy

To keep company in competitive advantage over to its rivals, the company uses 'Broad Differentiation' as its competitive advantage strategy. This implies that distinctive software-hardware products targeted to a broad chunk of customers. The company doesn’t keep any stone unturned to make its products distinctive in terms of varied characteristics. Through this approach the company expands its market, reaches wide range of customers and establishes its competitive benefit.

4.2 Intensive Strategies

a. Market Penetration

Microsoft’s this strategy aims to see company’s products present in every part of the global market. The company ensures market penetration by selling variety of products to the market where the company presently operates and introducing new products to prospective markets. This approach is responsible for the worldwide dominance of the company’s brand in the PC operating system industry. Effectively, the corporation ensures market presence by the

generic approach which utilizes product distinctiveness to draw customers from different parts of the market.

b. Product Development

By innovation and up-gradation the company ensures new products are released and existing products are upgraded with modified and added features. This is how the company see that the products of Microsoft are relevant always in line with customers requirements. This is again in alignment with its generic strategy, which insists product distinctiveness as a competitive advantage.

c. Market Development

Market development signifies the expansion of company’s market by entering into new & emerging markets. Though this approach is not that significant to Microsoft on its current business performance as its products are already accepted globally and available everywhere, but through this approach the company expanded its markets at its early years.

d. Diversification

Product diversification is the key factor which helped Microsoft to register growth over the years. Introducing new products and upgrading existing products at regular intervals the company put its customers guessing. This is again in tandem with its generic strategy “product differentiation”[6-7].

5. FINANCE & HUMAN RESOURCE

Microsoft Corporation's earnings rose 14 percent to \$125.84B for the fiscal year ended June 30, 2019. Net income rose 22 percent to \$36.8B before exceptional products. Revenues represent an rise in the segment of Intelligent Cloud from 21% to \$38.99B, an increase in the segment of Productivity and Business Processes from 15% to \$41.16B, and an increase in the segment of Personal Computing from 8% to \$45.7B.[10] As on June 30, 2019, Microsoft has 1,44,106 employees on roll worldwide, among them 1,37,160 are in USA and Puget Sound(Washington State). 45% of employees under Engineering functions, 15.9% in Global Sales and Maintenance & Operations, 17.9% in Worldwide Commercial Business, 10.2% in LinkedIn, 6.1% in Business Functions and 4.8% in Finance, HR & Legal [8]. The company’s growth with respect to revenue & income and human resource stock in the last 7 financial years is shown in the Table-1 below.

Table 1 : Microsoft’s financial and human resource account for last 5 years.
(Period ending: 30/06)

Year	Revenue (US\$M)	Net income US\$M)	Total Assets (US\$M)	Workforce
2019	125,843	39,240	286,556	144,106
2018	110,360	16,571	258,848	131,000
2017	96,571	25,489	250,312	124,000
2016	91,154	20,539	193,468	114,000
2015	93,580	12,193	174,472	118,000

6. MARKETING MIX

The marketing strategy of the company exhibits how the mixture of innovation and efficient solution drives the company to maintain and sustain market share. It is based on 4Ps - Product, Place, Promotion & Price, which determines policies and tactics for a market plan of the company. To safeguard digital products, Microsoft utilizes internet technology and technological interventions. The company is enjoying massive revenue as a significant player in the PC software and hardware industry. This market position is, however, threatened by competitive rivalry and linked problems. To guarantee ongoing achievement on the global market, Microsoft requires matching its marketing mix with the trends of target markets globally [9].

7. ORGANISATION STRUCTURE & ITS ELEMENTS

Microsoft’s organizational structure enables the its trade to grow, particularly, after the change in structure introduced in 2015. The organizational structure of a company relates to the organization's anatomy and arrangement and its elements. The corporate organizational structure signifies the significance of company production in the case of Microsoft. As an eminent player in the OS market, the corporation employs its organization-structure to keep competitive advantage in phase with development approaches. The long-standing success of the business relies on the appropriateness of its organizational structure to market circumstances and strengths of the segment. The company is employing “product-type-division” structure. The essence of this type is the structural divisions based software & hardware products. Following are the highlights of this type structure.

Product type divisions	Global corporate groups
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Productivity & Business Processes ○ Intelligent Cloud ○ More Personal Computing ○ Corporate & Other 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Office of the CEO ○ Worldwide Commercial Business ○ Marketing ○ Global Sales, Marketing & Operations ○ Corporate Strategy and Operations ○ Cloud and Enterprise Group ○ Human Resources ○ Finance ○ Business Development ○ Applications and Services Group ○ Windows and Devices Group ○ Technology and Research ○ Legal
Geographic segments	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ United States ○ International 	

Fig-2 : Microsoft’s organizational structure and its elements [10].

7.1. Product Type Divisions

Divisions based on product-type are the main element of the organization-structure of Microsoft. It utilizes product/production as the significance criterion for grouping staff & associated resources. Also, this structural characteristic exhibits product innovation ability of the company in the organizational structure. The product-type divisions are highlighted in Fig.-2.

7.2. Global Corporate Groups

The very organization-structure of Microsoft is defined by these groups. They are very crucial to company as technology based business totally relies on the task oriented components. The corporate groups are shown in Fig.-2.

7.3. Geographic Segments

The corporate structure of Microsoft Corporation also embodies geographic sections, purely used to group operations in the company’s fiscal reports. The geographic divisions are made known in Fig.-2.

8. SWOC ANALYSIS

SWOC Analysis is an instrument used to determine organizational strengths and weaknesses (inner strategic factors) and company (external strategic factors) difficulties and possibilities. These variables underline the significance of Microsoft's situation of distinctive product development, cyber security, and company diversification. The business can attain continuing development in the market for computer hardware & software through these methods. Figure Fig.3 highlights company’s strength, weaknesses, challenges and opportunities [11].

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Dominant brand image ▪ Product alignment with positive externalities ▪ Strong alliances with other firms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Vulnerability to cybercrime ▪ Imitability of some products ▪ Lack of dominant computer hardware products
Challenges	Opportunities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Cybercrime ▪ Piracy ▪ Strong competitive rivalry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Business diversification ▪ Innovation for computer hardware products ▪ Stronger security against cybercrime

Fig. 3 : Microsoft’s SWOC analysis outcomes

To continue as one of the foremost players in the computer software & hardware industry, Microsoft Corporation has the needed business characteristics. One of the main contributors to such a market condition is the powerful brand image and positive facade. Therefore, Microsoft is recommended to continue to enhance its brand image. It is also suggested to boost the company's collaboration with other enterprises in order to polish & enhance positive facades.

9. MAJOR COMPETITORS

Microsoft is a foremost performer in the computer software-hardware-IT services markets. The company is expanding its business in Media, Games, MSN TV, Mobile software & hardware and Social Networks. Though the company is unparalleled in operating system market, it is facing hard competition in these areas of business. In Mobile Software, Media

and IT services category, the company’s product are under the pressure enforced by big players like Google, Apple, Amazon, and IBM. In social networking the company’s presence is challenged by Facebook and Google+[12].

Domain	Expansion	Main competitors
Computer Software / IT services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Media ▪ Games – Microsoft Studios, Xbox game console ▪ MSN TV ▪ Mobile soft- and hardware Skype, Bing, MSN, Surface (tablet), Windows Phone ▪ Social Networks LinkedIn 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mobile software Google (Android); Apple (macOS, iOS); Apple-IBM ▪ Media Amazon, Google, Apple, game developers ▪ IT services Google, Apple, Amazon, IBM ▪ Social networks Facebook; Google+

Fig.4 : Microsoft, areas of expansion and main competitors

10. STAKEHOLDERS & CSR INITIATIVES

For Microsoft safeguarding the interest of its core stakeholders stands above to its own interest. The company identified, on priority basis, customers, employees, communities, investors and government as its prime stakeholders. It focuses on customer satisfaction & customer retention with respect to customers, human rights, equal compensation, & sophisticated work environment with regard to employees, environmental sustainability & community-reach approaches in view of customers, maximum return, total transparency & time-to-time reporting in case of investors and fall in-line with the prevailing legal & regulatory procedures with respect to government. Figure Fig.5 showcasing key stakeholders of the company according to the priority anti-clockwise from customers to government.

Fig 5 : Microsoft’s stakeholders

1. Customers (Top-Priority Stakeholders). For the sustained growth and long-time existence, Microsoft considered customer as its major stakeholder. The key interests of this

group are diversified, fairly-priced, efficient & user-friendly products and high quality after-sale service. In this regard the company striving hard to bring out variety of software and hardware products priced differently keeping in mind target customers and providing high-quality customer service through top-notch service centers penetrated across the world. Furthermore, feedback systems allow the business to solve the complaints and problems experienced by clients when using the products of company. Microsoft provides some client specific discounts to further fulfill the interests of this group.

2. Employees. Microsoft considers human resources, that is, workforce is the second most significant stakeholders. It views human rights, industry-standard compensation package, congenial work atmosphere and respectful treatment of staff as the interests of this group. The involvement of this group directly influence the production and performance of the Company. To fulfill the interests of staff, the corporate take care of competitive reward and continuous improvement in employment procedures to safeguard the freedoms of workers. These in turn promote the enhancement of human resources while improving workers' morale and skills.

3. Communities. Microsoft considers communities as one of the most precious stakeholders as its product and services, both software and hardware oriented are made for the direct use by the public. Taking care of this group's interest directly benefit Microsoft to enhance business and maintain prevent brand-image. To address this, the company included number of provisions in its market issues like discounts for students, defense staff and ex-servicemen. Also, Microsoft Philanthropies donate fund and extend aid to wide range of CSR programs. Such initiatives improve the accessibility of a large group of users to company's products. Moreover its policy on environmental sustainability reflects Microsoft's commitment to minimize its environmental effect.

4. Investors. Microsoft considered investors in its software-hardware business as another significant stakeholder. Investor supply capital to the Company. Sustained business growth and accurate & transparent fiscal reporting are the key interests of this stakeholder. The corporate responsibility attempts of Microsoft meet interests of this group through a multitude of company. Business stability of the company also addresses the interest of investors in company development.

5. Governments. For Microsoft, government is un-separable stakeholder as rules & regulations and policies of the states directly affect the functioning of the company. In the compliance of legal and regulatory procedures of Microsoft, the involvement of government is desirable, so also in the contribution of economic growth. Microsoft fulfills the interests of this group through the organization's strict policies.

11. CONCLUSION

Microsoft Corporation, being a technology company that deals with producing and selling of computer software, hardware and services across world, has been rising significantly since its inception. The company has registered growth in its revenue over the years from \$16,000 in 1975 to \$125,843 million in 2019. Began with just 3, including the founders, the company has 144,106 employees on a roll today [12]. Microsoft products are ubiquitous today. The company has in its control \$286.556 million assets spread across the world. As of June 30, 2019, more than 800 million devices are loaded with Windows 10. The company has already analyzed more than 6500 billion messages to find out threat issues and by that protecting its valued customers. 18 billion questions has already been asked to Cortana, intelligent

Assistant of Microsoft since its launch. These facts emphasize the popularity of the company. Microsoft continues to grow as a technology giant confronting and overcoming all odds. In line with its 'Be What's Next' tagline, the business has so far succeeded in guessing its customers [14].

REFERENCES

- [1] Microsoft Annual Report 2018. Retrieved from <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/annualreports/ar2018/annualreport>, Retrieved 10 August 2019.
- [2] (n.d.). Microsoft by the Numbers. Retrieved from <https://news.microsoft.com/bythenumbers/en/homepage>
- [3] (2019, August 15). Microsoft. Retrieved from <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Microsoft>
- [4] Crobat. Microsoft Company 15 September 1975. Retrieved from https://www.thocp.net/companies/microsoft/microsoft_company.htm, Retrieved on 10 August 2019.
- [5] Hall, M., & Zachary, G. P. (n.d.). Microsoft Corporation. Retrieved from <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Microsoft-Corporation>, Retrieved on 10 August 2019
- [6] Lawrence Gregory (2017), Microsoft Corporation's Generic & Intensive Growth Strategies, [Online]. Retrieved 10 August 2019, <http://panmore.com/microsoft-corporation-generic-strategy-intensive-growth-strategies>
- [7] Essays, UK. (November 2018). Microsoft's success: Corporate strategy and human resources strategy. Retrieved from <https://www.ukessays.com/essays/business/microsofts-success-in-aligning-corporate-strategy-and-human-resources-strategy-business-essay.php?vref=1>
- [8] Microsoft (MSFT) Financial Summary. Retrieved from <https://in.investing.com/equities/microsoft-corp-financial-summary>, Retrieved 10 August 2019
- [9] Smithson, N. (2017, February 21). Microsoft Corporation's Marketing Mix (4Ps) Analysis. Retrieved from <http://panmore.com/microsoft-corporation-marketing-mix-4ps-analysis>
- [10] Jessica Lombardo (2018), Microsoft Corporation's Organizational Structure & Its Characteristics (An Analysis), [Online]. Retrieved 10 August 2019, <http://panmore.com/microsoft-corporation-organizational-structure-characteristics-analysis>
- [11] Edward Ferguson (2017), Microsoft Corporation's SWOT Analysis & Recommendations, [Online]. Retrieved 10 August 2019, <http://panmore.com/microsoft-corporation-swot-analysis-recommendations>
- [12] Paper, W., & Studies, I. (2017). Retrieved from: www.econstor.eu. Retrieved on 10 August 2019
- [13] Lawrence Gregory, (2017), Microsoft's Corporate Social Responsibility Strategy & Stakeholders (An Analysis), [Online]. Retrieved 10 August 2019, <http://panmore.com/microsoft-stakeholders-corporate-social-responsibility-strategy-analysis>
- [14] (n.d.). Facts About Microsoft. Retrieved from <https://news.microsoft.com/facts-about-microsoft/>, Retrieved on 10 August 2019

Paper 13

**A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY ON COMPARISONS OF
STOCK PRICES PREVAILING IN THE CASH
MARKET AND FUTURES MARKET WITH SPECIAL
REFERENCE TO BANKS**

Wilma Carol Martis, Priyanna Noeline Dcunha

Students of 2nd MCom,

St Agnes Centre for Post-Graduate Studies and Research, Bendoor, Mangaluru – 575002.

Abstract:

In this current era of the 21st century, the economic scenario of our nation has taken altogether a 360 degree turn. Many companies such as Infosys, ITC, TATA, Reliance, etc have established themselves in the national as well as international market. Most of the Indians have come up with various start-ups. This has altogether contributed in the improvement of the economic conditions of our country.

Through the growth of various industries and sectors, many people have started to invest their earnings in various companies of different industries, namely, the banking industry, the pharmaceutical industry, the textile industry, the steel industry, the automobile industry and many more, with an expectation to earn a high rate of return. The investors evaluate the best companies in which they can invest through NSE NIFTY and BSE SENSEX. Sensex is a figure which indicates the relative prices of shares and stocks of the companies listed under the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE). Nifty is a figure which indicates the relative prices of shares and stocks of the companies listed under the National Stock Exchange (NSE).

Derivatives are the products that derive their value on the basis of an underlying asset. The underlying asset can be a commodity, a currency or a security. Among the various types of derivatives, we are going to consider futures as the main highlight in our study. The main aim of our study will be to compare the share prices of various banks in the cash market and the futures market. The data that will be collected by us for our study will be secondary data and we will understand the changes in prices of the cash market and futures market through trends.

Keywords: companies, prices, derivatives, market, industry, stock, shares, banks.

1.INTRODUCTION:

With the development of Systematic Investment Plans (SIPs) and online investment, investment procedures have become easy for every investor. Investors invest in various avenues namely shares, stocks, debentures, gold bonds, mutual funds, commodities and so on. People invest in the shares of various companies which are listed under the

National Stock Exchange (NSE) and the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE). The concept of sensex and nifty serves as a guide to evaluate the companies where an investor can invest. The increase and decrease in the share prices are evaluated by the demand and supply for the shares.

Derivatives are mainly based on the prices at a future date if we enter in a contract today. The type of derivative we are mainly going to focus in our study is futures. We are going to compare the prices under the cash market and futures market of six Indian banks.

2. OBJECTIVES:

- To analyse the changes in the prices prevailing in the cash market and futures market of some banks of India.
- To compare the prices under the cash market and the futures market.
- To evaluate the changes in the trading volumes under the cash market.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW:

Sl. No.	Title	Researcher(s)	Year	Summary
1.	The importance of the financial derivatives markets to economic development in the world's four major economies.	Duc Hong Vo, Son Van Huynh, Anh The Vo and Dao Thi-Thieu Ha.	February 2019	In this paper, the researchers have investigated the dynamic relationship between the derivatives markets and economic development of the 4 large economies, i.e., CIJU (China, India, Japan and the US). They made use of Granger-casuality test in the framework of vector error correction model (VECM) to examine this casual and dynamic relation with data for the period 1998 to 2017. They concluded that development of the derivatives markets had a positive effect on economic growth in the short run, as indicated in India, Japan and the US, although it may gradually turn negative, as in China.
2.	Performance of	Shaik Masood.	September	This study mainly deals

	commodity derivatives market in India: An analytical study.		2018	with commodity derivatives trading which has become indispensable in the hyper competitive era created by globalization and open market economies.
3.	The role of over-the-counter (OTC) derivatives in global financial crisis and corporate failures in recent times and its regulatory impacts.	Dr. Issahaku Salifu (FCCA).	November 2018	This paper deals with the role played by over-the-counter derivatives in the recent global financial crisis and corporate failures, and the extent to which these have impacted the regulation of OTC derivatives products and markets. This study has shown that the global financial crisis that brought world economies to recession indicated that there was a combination of factors that were responsible for this unfortunate economic meltdown.
4.	The impact of the use of financial derivatives on Chinese listed banks.	Rui Deng, Qiutong Ye, Wenrui Zhang and Si Chen.	November 2018	Based on the research on the main users of financial derivatives, commercial banks, using data of 16 listed commercial banks in China from 2012 to 2017, this paper finds that the fair value of financial derivatives of commercial banks is negatively correlated with the risk level.
5.	Next level risk management? Hedging and trading strategies of volatile derivatives using VIX futures.	Ernst J Fahling, Elmar Steurer, Tobias Schadler and Adrian Volz.	December 2018	This paper analyses how volatility derivatives on the volatility index VIX can be used as trading and risk management tools for investors and traders. This paper shows how VIX

				futures and options can hedge equity portfolios and when they are superior to traditional hedging alternative and compares the outcome of a VIX hedging strategy with a Buy and Hold strategy of the S and P 500 index over a time period of 20 years.
6.	Qualitative risk coverage in agriculture through derivative financial instruments based on Selyaninov indices.	Cristian Kevorchian, Camelia Gavrilesu and Gheorghe Hurduzeu	2013	This paper concludes that risk coverage in the case of certain weather phenomena with low risk but high occurrence probability is a necessity that can reduce the negative impact at farm economy level. The weather derivatives market requires certain adjustments in the sense of unifying the price establishment methodologies.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The data collection process was purely based on secondary data. We obtained the secondary data from the websites. We studied the changes in the share prices under the cash market and futures market of six Indian banks by understanding the trend of the movements, whether it was upward or downward.

4.DATA ANALYSIS:

1. HDFC BANK:

About:

- In 1994, HDFC Bank was incorporated with its registered office in Mumbai, Maharashtra.
- Its first corporate office and a full service branch at Sandoz house, Worli were inaugurated by then union finance minister, Manmohan Singh.
- It was founded in august 1994.
- The area served by HDFC Bank is India.

- HDFC bank comes under the banking and financial services industry.
- BSE: 500180
- NSE: HDFCBANK
- NYSE: HDB
- BSE SENSEX Constituent
- CNX Nifty Constituent
- Non exe chairperson of HDFC Bank Shyamala Gopinath.
- Managing director of HDFC Bank is Aditya Puri.
- HDFC Bank deals with products such as credit cards, consumer banking, banking, finance and insurance, investment banking, mortgage loans, private banking, private equity, wealth management.

NSE NIFTY of HDFC Bank:

CASH MARKET					NSE NIFTY OF HDFC BANK LTD FROM 9TH JULY 2019 TO 22ND JULY 2019			FUTURES MARKET
Date	Current closing price	Increase or Decrease	Percentage	Volume	Expiry Date	Close Price	Percentage Change	
09/07/2019	2379	31↓	-1.29%	4,120,672	29/08/2019	2401	-1.35%	
10/07/2019	2389	10↑	0.42%	2,892,287	29/08/2019	2406	0.20%	
11/07/2019	2407	18↑	0.75%	2,274,399	29/08/2019	2421	0.62%	
12/07/2019	2394	13↓	-0.54%	2,244,068	29/08/2019	2410	-0.48%	
15/07/2019	2395	1↑	0.04%	2,058,296	29/08/2019	2411	0.08%	
16/07/2019	2391	4↓	-0.17%	3,192,642	29/08/2019	2398	-0.55%	
17/07/2019	2397	6↑	0.25%	1,939,934	29/08/2019	2400	0.07%	
18/07/2019	2412	15↑	0.63%	2,700,646	29/08/2019	2414	0.59%	
19/07/2019	2376	36↓	-1.49%	2,234,807	29/08/2019	2377	-1.52%	
22/07/2019	2297	79↓	-3.44%	5,542,824	29/08/2019	2311	-2.78%	

Trend Analysis:

Date	Expiry date	Trend	Percentage
9/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.92%
10/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.71%
11/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.58%
12/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.67%
15/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.67%
16/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.29%
17/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.13%

18/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.08%
19/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.04%
22/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.61%

2. STATE BANK OF INDIA (SBI):

About:

- State Bank of India is an Indian multinational public sector banking and financial services statutory body.
- Its headquarters are in Mumbai, Maharashtra.
- It is ranked 216th in fortune global 500 list of world's biggest corporations as of 2018.
- The tagline for this bank is **the banker to every Indian**.
- NSE: SBIN
- BSE: 500112
- LSE: SBID
- BSE SENSEX Constituent
- CNX Nifty Constituent
- SBI comes under the banking and financial services industry.
- It was founded in 2/6/1806 as bank of Calcutta and was named as State Bank of India on 1/7/1955.
- The chairman of SBI is Rajnish Kumar
- The products SBI deals with are retail banking, corporate banking, investment banking, mortgage loans, private banking, wealth management, credit cards, finance and insurance.

NSE NIFTY of SBI:

NSE NIFTY OF STATE BANK OF INDIA FROM 9TH JULY 2019 TO 2ND JULY 2019							
CASH MARKET				FUTURE MARKET			
Date	Current closing price	Increase or Decrease	Percentage	Volume	Expiry Date	Close Price	Percentage Change
09/07/2019	360	5↑	1.41%	16,579,914	29/08/2019	363	1.05%
10/07/2019	354	6↓	-1.67%	18,681,819	29/08/2019	357	-1.53%
11/07/2019	363	9↑	2.54%	20,048,321	29/08/2019	365	2.23%
12/07/2019	364	1↑	0.28%	14,661,748	29/08/2019	366	0.22%
15/07/2019	360	4↓	-1.09%	15,665,939	29/08/2019	361	-1.05%
16/07/2019	364	4↑	1.11%	16,251,836	29/08/2019	366	1.11%
17/07/2019	372	8↑	2.19%	17,545,177	29/08/2019	374	2.16%
18/07/2019	364	8↓	-2.15%	21,691,056	29/08/2019	367	-1.94%
19/07/2019	356	8↓	-2.19%	22,213,173	29/08/2019	359	-2.14%
22/07/2019	351	5↓	-1.40%	19,682,038	29/08/2019	354	-1.38%

Trend Analysis:

Date	Expiry date	Trend	Percentage
9/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.83%
10/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.85%
11/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.55%
12/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.55%
15/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.28%
16/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.55%
17/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.54%
18/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.82%
19/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.84%
22/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.85%

3. KOTAK MAHINDRA BANK:**About:**

- Kotak Mahindra Bank is an Indian private sector bank.
- The headquarters are situated in Mumbai, Maharashtra.
- It was founded in February 2003.
- BSE: 500247
- NSE: KOTAKBANK
- CNX Nifty Constituent
- It was founded by Uday Kotak.
- The chairman of Kotak Mahindra Bank is Prakash Apte.
- The MD and CEO is Uday Kotak.
- It comes under the banking and financial services industry.
- It offers banking products for corporate and retail customers.

NSE NIFTY of Kotak Mahindra Bank:

NSE NIFTY OF KOTAK MAHINDRA BANK LTD FROM 9TH JULY 2019 TO 22ND JULY 2019

Date	CASH MARKET				FUTURES MARKET		
	Current closing price	Increase or Decrease	Percentage	Volume	Expiry Date	Close Price	Percentage Change
09/07/2019	1463	12↓	-0.81%	2,297,420	29/08/2019	1470	-0.98%
10/07/2019	1476	13↑	0.89%	2,180,732	29/08/2019	1481	0.80%
11/07/2019	1485	9↑	0.61%	1,598,491	29/08/2019	1488	0.42%
12/07/2019	1484	1↓	-0.07%	2,072,545	29/08/2019	1489	0.11%
15/07/2019	1508	24↑	1.62%	1,752,154	29/08/2019	1509	1.33%
16/07/2019	1501	7↓	-0.46%	1,351,435	29/08/2019	1504	-0.35%
17/07/2019	1535	34↑	2.27%	6,202,534	29/08/2019	1534	1.99%
18/07/2019	1538	3↑	0.20%	2,266,820	29/08/2019	1540	0.41%
19/07/2019	1499	39↓	-2.54%	2,094,229	29/08/2019	1501	-2.57%
22/07/2019	1454	45↓	-3%	3,423,157	29/08/2019	1463	-2.52%

Trend Analysis:

Date	Expiry date	Trend	Percentage
9/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.48%
10/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.34%
11/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.20%
12/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.34%
15/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.07%
16/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.20%
17/7/2019	29/8/2019	Downward	-0.07%
18/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.13%
19/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.13%
22/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.62%

4. INDUSIND BANK:

About:

- IndusInd bank ltd is a Mumbai based Indian new generation bank, established in 1994.
- The bank offers commercial, transactional and electronic banking products and services.
- NSE: INDUSINDBK
- BSE:532187
- CNX Nifty Constituent
- IndusInd bank was inaugurated in April 1994 by then union finance minister Manmohan Singh.

- IndusInd bank is the first among the new generation private banks in India.

NSE NIFTY of IndusInd Bank:

NSE NIFTY OF INDUSIND BANK LTD FROM 9TH JULY 2019 TO 22ND 2019

CASH MARKET					FUTURE MARKET		
Date	Current closing price	Increase or Decrease	Percentage	Volume	Expiry Date	Close Price	Percentage Change
09/07/2019	1492	15↑	1.02%	3,733,488	29/08/2019	1502	1.18%
10/07/2019	1487	05↓	-0.34%	3,222,571	29/08/2019	1492	-0.69%
11/07/2019	1541	54↑	3.63%	4,337,246	29/08/2019	1543	3.48%
12/07/2019	1510	31↓	-2.01%	10,637,123	29/08/2019	1515	-1.86%
15/07/2019	1475	35↓	-2.32%	5,656,516	29/08/2019	1481	-2.24%
16/07/2019	1473	02↓	-0.14%	3,863,867	29/08/2019	1479	-0.11%
17/07/2019	1501	28↑	1.90%	5,290,039	29/08/2019	1505	1.78%
18/07/2019	1471	30↓	-1.99%	2,404,071	29/08/2019	1476	-1.93%
19/07/2019	1422	49↓	-3.33%	4,698,852	29/08/2019	1422	-3.69%
22/07/2019	1418	04↓	-0.28%	4,578,591	29/08/2019	1411	-0.04%

Trend Analysis:

Date	Expiry date	Trend	Percentage
9/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.67%
10/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.34%
11/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.13%
12/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.33%
15/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.41%
16/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.41%
17/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.27%
18/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.34%
19/7/2019	29/8/2019	Equal	0%
22/7/2019	29/8/2019	Downward	-0.49%

5. YES BANK:

About:

- Yes bank was founded by Rana Kapoor and Ashok Kapoor.
- It was founded in 2004.
- It is headquartered in Mumbai, Maharashtra.
- Yes bank belongs to the banking and financial services industry.
- BSE: 532648
- NSE: YESBANK
- The chairman is Brahm Dutt.
- The MD and CEO is Ravneet Gill.

- Yes bank deals with products such as credit cards, consumer banking, corporate banking, finance and insurance, mortgage loans, private banking, wealth management, investment banking.
- Derives most of its revenues through arranging syndicated loans and through corporate banking.
- It has a strategic partnership with us government based OPIC and with Wells Fargo.

NSE NIFTY of Yes Bank:

NSE NIFTY OF YES BANK LTD FROM 9TH JULY 2019 TO 22ND JULY 2019								
Date	CASH MARKET				Volume	FUTURES MARKET		
	Current closing price	Increase or Decrease	Percentage	Expiry Date		Close Price	Percentage Change	
09/07/2019	91	2↓	-2.15%	137,863,884	29/08/2019	92	-2.07%	
10/07/2019	93	2↑	2.20%	75,776,545	29/08/2019	94	1.79%	
11/07/2019	92	1↓	-1.08%	73,432,269	29/08/2019	93	-0.43%	
12/07/2019	94	2↑	2.17%	60,702,978	29/08/2019	95	1.87%	
15/07/2019	93	1↓	-1.06%	126,736,904	29/08/2019	94	-1.16%	
16/07/2019	104	11↑	11.83%	228,682,135	29/08/2019	105	11.81%	
17/07/2019	98	6↓	-6.12%	238,375,009	29/08/2019	99	-5.76%	
18/07/2019	86	12↓	-12.24%	229,258,092	29/08/2019	86	-12.87%	
19/07/2019	83	3↓	-3.49%	145,863,654	29/08/2019	84	-3.01%	
22/07/2019	91	8↑	9.64%	208,758,719	29/08/2019	92	9.68%	

Trend Analysis:

Date	Expiry date	Trend	Percentage
9/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	1.10%
10/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	1.08%
11/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	1.09%
12/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	1.06%
15/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	1.08%
16/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	0.96%
17/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	1.02%
18/7/2019	29/8/2019	Equal	0%
19/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	1.20%
22/7/2019	29/8/2019	Upward	1.10%

6. BANK OF BARODA(BOB):

About:

- Bank of Baroda is an Indian Multinational public sector banking and financial services company.
- It is owned by the Government of India.
- It is the second largest public sector bank in India.
- BSE: 532134
- NSE: BANKBARODA
- CNX Nifty Constituent
- It was founded on 20th July 1908.
- It was founded by Sayajirao Gaekwad.
- Its headquarters are situated in Vadodara, Gujarat.
- It serves India and countries worldwide.
- The chairman of BOB is Hasmukh Adhia.
- The MD and CEO is P.S. Jayakumar.
- The products and services it deals with are consumer banking, corporate banking, finance and insurance, investment banking, mortgage loans, private equity, savings, securities, asset management and wealth management.
- Based on 2019 data, it is ranked 1145 on Forbes Global 2000 list.

NSE NIFTY of Bank of Baroda:

NSE NIFTY OF BANK OF BARODA LTD FROM 9TH JULY 2019 TO 22ND JULY 2019								
CASH MARKET					FUTURE MARKET			
Date	Current closing price	Increase or Decrease	Percentage	Volume	Expiry Date	Close Price	Percentage Change	
09/07/2019	126	1↑	0.80%	14,869,226	29/08/2019	127	1.28%	
10/07/2019	124	2↓	-1.59%	15,786,409	29/08/2019	125	-1.38%	
11/07/2019	126	2↑	1.61%	14,450,972	29/08/2019	127	1.80%	
12/07/2019	126	0	0.00%	12,403,617	29/08/2019	127	-0.16%	
15/07/2019	122	4↓	-3.17%	15,285,529	29/08/2019	123	-3.31%	
16/07/2019	124	2↑	1.64%	19,467,661	29/08/2019	125	1.83%	
17/07/2019	127	3↑	2.42%	17,922,297	29/08/2019	128	2.24%	
18/07/2019	121	6↓	-4.72%	21,215,697	29/08/2019	122	-4.42%	
19/07/2019	118	3↓	-2.48%	19,834,528	29/08/2019	119	-3.03%	
22/07/2019	118	0	0.00%	18,668,714	29/08/2019	119	0.63%	

Trend Analysis:

Date	Expiry date	Trend	Percentage
9/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.79%
10/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.81%
11/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.79%
12/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.79%
15/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.82%
16/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.81%
17/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.79%
18/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.83%
19/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.85%
22/7/2019	29/8/19	Upward	0.85%

FINDINGS:

- We found many upward trends while comparing the changes in prices under the cash market and futures market.
- The exceptions were :
Kotak Mahindra Bank – 17th July 2019
IndusInd Bank – 19th July 2019 and 22nd July 2019
Yes Bank – 18th July 2019
- Under the cash market of HDFC Bank, we can find a drastic decrease in the value of share price on 22nd July 2019; 79 decrease. The peak level of the trading volume of HDFC Bank was 5,542,824 on 22nd July 2019 and the trough level was 1,939,934 on 17th July 2019.
- We can find a good increase in the share price of SBI on 11th July 2019; 9 increase. There was continuous decrease in the share prices during the three days at the end of the window period. The peak level of the trading volume of SBI was 22,213,173 on 19th July 2019 and the trough level was 14,661,748 on 12th July 2019.
- Kotak Mahindra Bank has faced a drastic decrease of its share price on 22nd July 2019; 45 decrease. The peak level of the trading volume of Kotak Mahindra Bank was 6,202,534 on 17th July 2019 and the trough level was 1,351,435 on 16th July 2019.
- IndusInd Bank has experienced an increase in its share price on 11th July 2019; 54 increase and has faced a drastic decrease on 19th July 2019; 49 decrease. The peak level of the trading volume of IndusInd Bank was 10,637,123 on 12th July 2019 and the trough level was 2,404,071 on 18th July 2019.
- Yes bank has faced a drastic decrease in its share price on 18th July 2019; 12 decrease. The peak level of the trading volume of Yes Bank was 238,375,009 on 17th July 2019 and the trough level was 60,702,978 on 12th July 2019.
- Bank of Baroda has faced a decrease in its share price on 18th July 2019; 6 decrease. The peak level of the trading volume of Bank of Baroda was 21,215,697 on 18th July 2019 and the trough level was 12,403,617 on 12th July 2019.

CONCLUSION:

By the whole study, we can conclude that the futures market seem to be much more profitable as compared to the cash market because the share prices under the futures market are comparatively higher. During the window period of 10 days, i.e 9th July 2019 – 22nd July 2019, investing in the futures market would seem as a feasible option for the investors.

REFERENCES:

- The importance of the financial derivatives markets to economic development in the world's four major economies. Duc Hong Vo, Son Van Huynh, Anh The Vo and Dao Thi-Thieu Ha. February 2019
- Performance of commodity derivatives market in India: An analytical study. Shaik Masood. September 2018
- The role of over-the-counter (OTC) derivatives in global financial crisis and corporate failures in recent times and its regulatory impacts. Dr. Issahaku Salifu (FCCA). November 2018
- The impact of the use of financial derivatives on Chinese listed banks. Rui Deng, Qiutong Ye, Wenrui Zhang and Si Chen. November 2018
- Next level risk management? Hedging and trading strategies of volatile derivatives using VIX futures. Ernst J Fahling, Elmar Steurer, Tobias Schadler and Adrian Volz. December 2018
- Qualitative risk coverage in agriculture through derivative financial instruments based on Selyaninov indices. Cristian Kevorchian, Camelia Gavrilesu and Gheorghe Hurduzeu. 2013

Paper 14

A CRITICAL CASE STUDY ON QUALCOMM AS PIONEERS OF WIRELESS REVOLUTION

Sangeetha Prabhu¹, & Krishna Prasad K²

¹Research Scholar, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

²College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

E-mail: sangeethaprabhu96@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The company Qualcomm established in July 1985 by Irwin Jacobs and Seven at San Diego, California, the United States. Qualcomm is an American multinational company, it aims to design, develop semiconductors and market wireless telecommunications equipment's and services. Qualcomm derives most of its revenue from chip making and patent licensing businesses. Qualcomm has offices at almost 33 countries with a global workforce of approximately 35,400 employees. For the fiscal year 2018, Qualcomm reported annual revenue of US\$21.301 billion, an increase of 2% over the previous fiscal cycle. Its shares traded between \$51 and \$75 per share, and its market capitalization at the end of fiscal 2018 was valued at US\$105 billion. In the Fortune 500 list, the company ranks as 133rd in revenues among the largest US corporations. The company is focused on various industries like automotive, education, healthcare, networking, Internet of Everything, mobile computing, smart homes, smart cities, smart homes, and wearables. Qualcomm's products include Gobi, Hy-Fi, IPQ, IZat, Powerline, Snapdragon, Small Cells, VIVE, Wi-Fi platforms, Mirasol, Pixtronix, AllPlay, 2net, Brew, HealthyCircles, QChat, QLearn, RaptorQ, Vuforia, Halo, and WiPower. In this paper, we are analysing business strategies of Qualcomm by studying various things like the corporate history, financial strategy, STEEP and SWOT analysis, target markets, key company challenges and legal issues of Qualcomm.

Keywords: Qualcomm, Wireless Technology, Electronics Industry, Case Study, IT Company, Telecommunications Industry

1. INTRODUCTION

Today, there is a revolution in the world of communication and information transmission, which is wireless [1]. Wireless engineering allows you to communicate over distances between two or more people without cables and wires. This includes wave interactions with radio frequencies (RF) and infra-red (IR). The Internet affected the way people work, play and communicate. Shopping, research and message are all common uses of PC-based internet applications. In order to ensure cost-effective communications, the internet has rationalized business, personal and monitoring activities. The way people communicate also has an impact on mobile telephones. Cellular use has exploded since culture has been able to talk with each other everywhere at any time. Security and convenience issues are becoming significant motors in their increasing popularity. However, these two functions are combined in the next batch of cell phones. Consumers want to regulate their wireless phones via the

Internet. In all kinds of activities, companies want to be mobile. Therefore, companies will flourish that support and standardize the needed wireless equipment and technology. One such business is QUALCOMM. The basis for global Wireless Systems is the patented QUALCOMM Techniques. Their important research and development actions have enabled them to remain at the top of wireless technology, and a substantial income stream is provided by their wide patent foundation. However, QUALCOMM poses difficulties from multiple sides if it is to maintain its leadership position in the sector. These difficulties arise from other producers of chips, alternative wireless norms and telecommunication technologies sponsored by the government.

The QUALCOMM, Inc. dedicated to developing and supplying the multi-access code division (CDMA) electronic cable communications tools and digital technology centre. CDMA is a safe data transmission method for radio frequency. Qualcomm maintains a number of patents which are essential to its core business worldwide and promote various CDMA technological aspects. Prof. Irwin Jacobs & Andrew Viterbi established the business in 1985 [. Its aim is to create a ' Quality Communications ' company for the public sector, which is why it is called QUALCOMM. Qualcomm was built in 1985 with CDMA technology proposed in 1989 for the wireless industry. The present CDMA patents of Qualcomm are more than 400 US patents and more than 900 US patents. About 12 percent of the 550 million clients who use first-and second-century mobile technology use Qualcomm-based CDMA networks. Qualcomm's primary focus is on the global use of its 5th generation wireless model cdma2000. Qualcomm is divided into several branches including Qualcomm CDMA Technologies (QCT) and Qualcomm Wireless Systems (QWS), Qualcomm Technology Licence (QTL). Qualcomm Technology Licenses (QTL) provides producers with CDMA technology with charges and advantages. More than 90 telecommunications appliance manufacturers have been permitted by the company's portfolios of CDMA patents. The world's main manipulator for built-in circuits, systems software and tools for wireless device manufacturers and network equipment is Qualcomm CDMA Technologies(QCT). QCT now manufactures wireless platform circuits through its subsidiary, Snap Track. QCT generates revenue depending on CDMA from sales of products. Qualcomm Wireless Systems (QWS) provides portable communications and logistics leadership services and equipment for the transport sector with OmniTRACS solutions. QWS also creates and builds portals and equipment for the advanced satellite network Globalstar, which offers continuing mobile communication and data services.

2. AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

This is a company case study paper based on the information collected from Qualcomm's business strategies in wireless Technology industry sector. The paper deals with the following aim and objectives.

1. To learn the operation level and business level strategies of top multinational IT Company qualcomm.
2. To know the growth saga of qualcomm company.
3. To learn about qualcomm strategy of facing the challenges using their innovative slogan "forward thinking".
4. To know about QUALCOMM's strategies of exploring all possibilities as opportunities.

5. To use **STEEP and SWOT analysis** for the recommendation of Qualcomm's future strategies for accelerated success.

3. JOURNEY OF SUCCESS

- Qualcomm was established in 1985 in San Diego and is a leading worldwide wireless chip designer for 3 G, 4 G and 5 G devices.
- Qualcomm can now almost solely focus on its activity by resolving the licensing dispute with Apple.
- The 5 G generation is now under implementation, which means that profits and cash flows can be expected to increase in the foreseeable future.
- Qualcomm's valuation is favourable compared to the peer group and, despite the share prices rally owing to the Apple sale, is essentially undervalued.
- Moreover, a pending share buyback scheme of about \$7.8 billion and a current dividend of more than 3% also speaks in the future of an appealing shareholder value.

4. QUALCOMM'S INNOVATIVE SLOGAN: FORWARD THINKING

The slogan is a commemorative sentence, used for repeated expressions of concept or reasons in a tribe, politics, commerce, religion or other context to convince members of the audience or a more specified target group. The Qualcomm Wireless Reach™ project introduces sophisticated wireless systems to underserved societies around the globe with a view to enhancing financial and social development. The slogan or the business slogan of Qualcomm's publicity is "Forward Thinking". Mission statements and vision statements are written for corporate clients and employees. A Statement of a Mission may be described as a phrase or a brief paragraph published by a company or a corporation reflecting its key objective, identity and values and business principles. A sentence or brief paragraph is the definition of a Vision Statement which gives a wide aspirational future picture. Qualcomm Mission Statement is "Future Perspectives-We can see the future from the high heights of our dreams. Your vision of what may take place tomorrow inspires us every day. We aim every day to make this view the foundation of a new wireless world. So while nobody is sure what is going to be the future, we have a pretty good idea.

The old logo was a sad thing, with far too many inconsistencies to remove the "mm" ligature: the "Q" was too audacious, the "u" was too carved and condensed, and the "m" was the only rounded corner pieces. This new logo retains the essence of the old one— whose share of equity is strange and good— but rewrites it fairly perfectly. The space in each letter matches, the proper capitalization of the word is easier to read and the mm part of the wordmark is now far more integrated. It is still the only uppercase / uncase letters, but it is powerful and unified from the visual perspective. The "m" case and the redundancy were definitely explored but I like that they stuck with the transistor-esque-looking diagonal "ms." I'm sure that they stuck with the "m"s. The subtle shading version of the rendering provides the logo a kind of interesting softness.

5. FINANCIALS

A comparative summary of Qualcomm's Financials for last four years 2015 to 2018 is given in table 1[3-9].

Table 1: Last four years Financial Statement

Revenue		30/9/2018	24/9/2017	25/9/2016	27/9/2015
Total Revenue		2,27,32,000	2,22,91,000	2,35,54,000	2,52,81,000
Cost of Revenue		9,795,000	93,55,000	93,15,000	10,1,06,000
Gross Profit		12,937,000	1,29,36,000	14,239,000	15,1,75,000
Operating Expenses					
Research Development		56,19,000	54,35,000	51,41,000	54,76,000
Selling General and Administrative		21,05,000	21,57,000	22,86,000	22,72,000
Non Recurring		-	-	-	-
Others		-18,000	-18,000	-18,000	-18,000
Total Operating Expenses		1,75,01,000	1,69,47,000	1,67,42,000	1,78,54,000
Operating Income or Loss		52,31,000	53,44,000	68,12,000	74,27,000
Income from Continuing Operations					
Total Other Income/Expenses Net		-47,18,000	-23,24,000	21,000	-9,40,000
Earnings Before Interest and Taxes		52,31,000	53,44,000	68,12,000	74,27,000
Interest Expense		-7,68,000	-4,94,000	-2,97,000	-1,04,000
Income Before Tax		5,13,000	30,20,000	68,33,000	64,87,000
Income Tax Expense		53,77,000	5,55,000	11,31,000	12,19,000
Minority Interest		-	-	-10,000	-7,000
Net Income From Continuing Ops		-48,64,000	24,65,000	57,02,000	52,68,000
Net Income					
Net Income		-48,64,000	24,66,000	57,05,000	52,71,000
Preferred Stock And Other Adjustments		-	-	-	-
Net Income Applicable To Common Shares		-48,64,000	24,66,000	57,05,000	52,71,000

6. SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH GREEN STRATEGY

Qualcomm is devoted to the sustainable use of wireless systems worldwide. Our strategy is sustainable by integrating financial, social and company governance issues into our business model, especially in relation to our key effect fields, such as the workers, supply chain and the local community. From their daily operations to their leadership and governance committee they have integrated sustainability across your business. Sustainability influences their strategic choices, their product design and their workers ' everyday thinking and behaviour.

The sustainable development task of Qualcomm:

- Develop technologies that transform the environment favorably
- operate at the greatest norms of ethics
- Be an excellent location for job
- Be excellent company individuals everywhere we operate
- Keep adding importance to stockholders

6.1 FRAMEWORK 'S PILLARS

The sustainability obligations of Qualcomm are in particular [3-9]:

1. Governance

- During all activities and relationships with their staking parties they show responsibility, honesty, transparency and ethical company methods.
- They are constantly improving their sustainable management, including better transparency, reporting, communications and measurable objectives.
- improve knowledge and exposure within their company and with contractual providers and main suppliers of human rights values..
- Review your corporate management values and procedures on a regular basis in order to guarantee that they serve the greatest interests of our stockholders and others.
- All employees are required to revise and recognize their Code, Foreign and corrupt laws and anti-corruption policies. They are also required to do so.

2. Chain of products and supplies

- They develop technologies to empower individuals around the globe and improve their quality of lives.
- They create products that take their economic and social effect into consideration.
- By applying and allowing accountable privacy and data security methods, they create confidence in the usage of wireless systems.
- They allow their semiconductor providers to behave in conformity with the Code of Conduct of the Coalition for Electronic Industry Citizenship and expect them to acquire products from environmental and socially responsible sources, including conflict free sources within and around the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC).

3. Workplace facilities and staff

- The goal is to boost diversity at all stages of the company and to continually develop and implement measures to tackle our talent pipeline gaps.
- They pledge to reward all their staff fairly and justly.
- They provide possibilities for all our staff for practice, development and promotion and encourage well-being, work / life equilibrium and general health for their staff.
- They are secure and healthy in their surroundings.
- It uses approaches to handle water use responsibly, to lower greenhouse gas emissions, to improve power effectiveness and the use of equipment, to decrease waste and to decrease hazardous substances throughout our activities.

4. Society

- They develop strategic connections with a wide variety of local organizations and programmes, which develop and strengthen communities around the world.
- Sustainable wireless initiatives, focusing on schooling, business growth, health care, the climate and public safety, enhance economic and social development and reinforce wireless technology.
- These programs promote needs in line with the development of Qualcomm and boost the volunteering of employees through creative programs with global local NGOs. They are committed to enhancing education in science, technology and engineering at all levels.

7. QUALCOMM BUSINESS TERATEGIES

You could just display a Qualcomm module on your desktop or on your mobile device. This is the major LTE chip maker and its products are available in nearly every mobile device brand. Only two of the biggest names with Qualcomm parts are Apple and Samsung. Its revenue is generated by the manufacturing and selling of these chips and the lending to other producers of the technology. In other words, comparing Qualcomm with a customer toll company's business model is simple. You are the only person in your business to do that, so you can put your own cost and get individuals to choose whether to pay. In the past 20 years, this business model has generated huge operating margins and incredible development.

Qualcomm is entitled to add its chips to 3 G and 4 G mobile devices in China with suppliers. The only issue is a continuing inquiry into the company structure of Qualcomm—the Chinese edition of the SEC, the NDRC. There is a matter of the quantity of lease charges and use privileges paid by the business. The inquiry resulted in some of the lower contracting organisations underreporting or failing the amount of units transferred for Qualcomm. The business has therefore changed its Wall Street selling figures. The ultimate domino in this adverse cascade is that shareholders have significantly reduced stock value. For Qualcomm there is also a prospective issue in China: the NDRC might start regulating its contract charges in China. China is the fastest increasing industry for intelligent devices and Qualcomm is the leading chip maker. Short-term income has already been impacted. The long-term prospects of Qualcomm in China might be influenced by its model of company.

The invention is a key component of the business model of Qualcomm: the Qualcomm business model shows some sustainability, in particular as far as research and development is concerned. It is not just profitability, it thinks. Qualcomm thinks it must be a goal of creation, for the creation is at the heart of human development. It could be asserted that this philosophy inspires a portable revolution. Qualcomm has created some wonderful stuff but has also motivated others to invent great stuff and use chips as their basis. "Inspire" is the keyword. The ultimate objective is to simplify and improve the connection of all parties. The business model of Qualcomm is as simple as feasible in some ways. They found a issue, solved it and continued to sell it.

8. SWOT and SWEET ANALYSIS :

it seeks at designing, developing semiconductors and business equipment and facilities for wireless telecommunication. The firm focuses on different sectors, including automotive, education, medical care, Internet of All, mobile computing, intelligent household, intelligent cities, intelligent housing, and wearables. Qualcomm is an American-based wireless company. It seeks at developing, developing semiconductors and marketing wireless equipment and facilities. It focuses on different sectors, such as manufacturing, training, healthcare, networking, the Everything Internet, mobile computing, intelligent homes, intelligent cities, intelligent homes, and wearables.

The SWOT analysis shows that[3-9]:

1. Strengths of QUALCOMM:

- In North America, CDMA is extremely invasive.
- Due to their violent security for intellectual estate, their capacity to safeguard patents is an significant competence.
- QUALCOMM offers funds to further expand research and advancement in order to deliver consistent revenues and profitability and growth.

2. Strengths of competitors:

- Cross licenses for new and competitive techniques, available free of royalties.
- The operational history and business existence have been created.
- More brand awareness.
- Longer access to the client base.
- Increased financial, sales, marketing, manufacturing, production and technology assets;

3. QUALCOMM's Weaknesses:

- The revenues of QUALCOMM are due to three Korean clients, losing 39 percent to any of QCT's significant clients. The revenues of Global Star accounted for 30% of the QWS segment revenues.
- A restricted proportion of third-party producers are dependent on the production and testing of goods. Any disruption to the operation of these third parties might damage service commitments, as described in Porter's five forces.
- QUALCOMM provides CDMA network financing to its licensees. If these customers do not recognize their debts, QUALCOMM's economic situation could be affected.
- Globalstar has elevated cost of facilities, which may adversely affect item development

4. Weaknesses of rivals:

- Competitors ' network technology focuses mainly on GSM. If they do not have new technology to meet 3 G networks, their development can be limited.
- Competition in North America has a restricted business share.
-

5. QUALCOMM's Opportunities:

- Opportunities for QUALCOMM:• Third generation wireless communication requires of the sector.

- Emerging economies in Asia, especially China and India. The total population of both these economies is about 2.2 billion or 40% of the world's inhabitants.
- Spinco will contribute to all-embracing its permits.
- CDMA is expected to contribute to significant development in revenues.

6. Competitors' Opportunities:

- Wireless communication needs of the industry for third generation.
- Asian emerging markets, China and India in particular. Both of these markets have a combined population of about 2.2 billion or 40% of the world's population.
- Open the door to new products can be adopted for alternative standards..

7. Common threats both for and against the QUALCOMM:

- Rapid changes in technology could make current goods outdated.
- A deterioration of the execution of a fresh item could affect business share and income.
- Poor economic health will have a negative impact on significant clients ' profitability.
- International overseas exchange instability and fluctuation can hamper development and revenues.
- The acceptance of network technology of third generation.
- Health hazards. In the medical sector, several White Papers debating whether wireless emissions can be associated with various health problems, such as cancer, have been released. This may discourage the consumers of this item, which affects the sale of licenses for technology.

The assessment by STEEP shows[3-9]:

1. **Situation:** Wireless interaction and robotics are the early phase of the product life cycle. During the next century, many fresh technology types could be developed and fresh companies and partnerships could be formed. Satellite communications are developing and can provide a feasible solution to land-based wireless systems.
2. **Technology:** At the beginning of the design phase. New technology is developing quickly and the mental benefit to QUALCOMM is to achieve its economic goals.
3. **Economic:** The scenario is unsure at the moment. In the financial year 2000, QUALCOMM relies on 47% of its global clients. In an abrupt foreign economy, its revenue and earnings are being adjusted. In addition, their income is adversely impacted when customer expenditure continues to stagnate in the US.
4. **Political:** As mentioned, if the policy environment shifts in Korea or China, the effects of QUALCOMM are also immediate and 47% of revenues depend on global customers.

9. CONCLUSION

The document addressed the company's business policies, finance, business policies and pillars to reach its goals. Qualcomm IT Company. The benefits and benefits of these corporate procedures and policies used to distinguish their efficiency within the organization are also examined. Wireless conversion technology and license patent facilities are provided by Qualcomm. Detailed data on business strategies of Qualcomm was given and how these policies had an impact on the company's growth.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bhushan, N., Li, J., Malladi, D., Gilmore, R., Brenner, D., Damnjanovic, A., ... & Geirhofer, S. (2014). Network densification: the dominant theme for wireless evolution into 5G. *IEEE Communications Magazine*, 52(2), 82-89.
- [2] Levin, M. S. (2017). Towards combinatorial modeling of wireless technology generations. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1708.08996*.
- [3] Dr. Irwin Mark Jacobs, & Richard SULPIZIO (1999). Big ideas enabled by CDMA Retrieved from http://www.annualreports.com/HostedData/AnnualReportArchive/q/NASDAQ_QCOM_1999.pdf
- [4] Steve Mollenkopf (2016). QUALCOMM Incorporated Annual report 2016 Retrieved from http://www.annualreports.com/HostedData/AnnualReportArchive/q/NASDAQ_QCOM_2016.pdf
- [5] George S. Davis (2017). QUALCOMM INC/DE Annual report 2017 Retrieved from http://www.annualreports.com/HostedData/AnnualReportArchive/q/NASDAQ_QCOM_2017.pdf
- [6] George S. Davis (2015). QUALCOMM INC/DE Annual report 2015 Retrieved from http://www.annualreports.com/HostedData/AnnualReportArchive/q/NASDAQ_QCOM_2015.pdf
- [7] George S. Davis (2014). QUALCOMM INC/DE Annual report 2014 Retrieved from http://www.annualreports.com/HostedData/AnnualReportArchive/q/NASDAQ_QCOM_2014.pdf
- [8] George S. Davis (2013). QUALCOMM INC/DE Annual report 2013 Retrieved from http://www.annualreports.com/HostedData/AnnualReportArchive/q/NASDAQ_QCOM_2013.pdf
- [9] William F. Davidson, Jr. (2005). QUALCOMM Annual report 2005 Retrieved from http://www.annualreports.com/HostedData/AnnualReportArchive/q/NASDAQ_QCOM_2005.pdf
- [10]
- [11] K. A. Grajski and E. Kirk, "Towards a Mobile Multimedia Age – Location-Based Services: A Case Study," *Wirel. Pers. Commun.*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 105–116, Sep. 2003.
- [12] P. Bender, P. Black, M. Grob, R. Padovani, N. Sindhushayana, and A. Viterbi, "CDMA/HDR: A Bandwidth-Efficient High-Speed Wireless Data Service for Nomadic Users," in *The Foundations of the Digital Wireless World*, vol. Volume 2, 0 vols., Co-Published with Indian Institute of Science (IISc), Bangalore, India, 2009, pp. 161–168.
- [13] N. Gandal, D. Salant, and L. Waverman, "Standards in wireless telephone networks," *Telecommun. Policy*, vol. 27, no. 5, pp. 325–332, Jun. 2003.
- [14] L. Kimmel, "Broadcom's Proposed Acquisition of Qualcomm: A Bad Deal for Innovation and Consumers," *SSRN Electron. J.*, 2018.
- [15] D. B. Yoffie and A. S. Choi, "Qualcomm Inc., 2019," Jun. 2018.
- [16] L. Hou, "Qualcomm: How China has Invalidated Traditional Business Models on Standard Essential Patents," *J. Eur. Compet. Law Pract.*, vol. 7, no. 10, pp. 686–689, Dec. 2016.

- [17] D. H. Ginsburg, J. D. Wright, and L. Edwards, “Section 2 Mangled: FTC v. Qualcomm on the Duty to Deal, Price Squeezes, and Exclusive Dealing,” SSRN Electron. J., 2019.
- [18] M. J. Adeleke, A. Grebe, M. Kretschmer, and J. Moedecker, “Spectrum Utilization Assessment of Wi-Fi Network Using Qualcomm/Atheros 802.11 Wireless Chipset,” in e-Infrastructure and e-Services for Developing Countries, 2018, pp. 180–191.
- [19] J. Gum and C. Patrick, “System and method for integration of wireless computer network in position determining technology,” US7647055B2, 12-Jan-2010.
- [20] Dulababu, T. (2017). Case Study: A Diagnostic Study on Fundamentals of Top Indian IT Companies. *Advances in Management*, 10(3), 8-20.
- [21] Maria Bonaventura Forleo & Nadia Palmieri (2019) The potential for developing educational farms: a SWOT analysis from a case study, *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, DOI: 10.1080/1389224X.2019.1643747 Francisco Javier Forcadell, Elisa Aracil and
- [22] Fernando Úbeda, The Influence of Innovation on Corporate Sustainability in the International Banking Industry, *Sustainability*, 10.3390/su11113210, 11, 11, (3210), (2019).

Paper 15

**IMPULSIVE BUYING AND ROLE OF AI IN
PERSONALISED MARKETING: OPINION OF THE
YOUTH OF DAKSHINA KANNADA**

Sushma M. Marebal

Second year M. Com, St. Aloysius College, Mangalore

Abstract

The market is an ever changing place. From the producers being the decision makers of the consumer's needs, to the consumers being treated as kings, the market has seen it all. With digitalisation and globalisation, the customers now, have a number of choices to choose from, while the producers or the sellers have to deal with a number of competitors. The consumers are more aware and specific about their needs and wants, pushing the sellers to use innovative marketing tools for their benefit. The sellers need to send the right message, to the right customer, at the right time-this can be easily done with the help of AI.

Marketing is no longer considered as the process of informing the consumers about a product. It is now a more detailed, rigorous and well-thought out process; of which the execution too is meticulous. There are various trends in marketing, out of which target marketing is the most prominent one. AI (Artificial Intelligence) is growing in prominence and is taking the load off of the marketers. This study mainly concentrates on understanding the concept of target marketing and the role of AI in target marketing. The study also focuses on the opinion of the youth on target marketing and its effectiveness as a marketing tool.

Keywords: impulsive buying, customers, advertising, marketing

1.Introduction

The market and the way it operates changes every year. A few years ago, the manufacturers or sellers decided the customer's choices for them. But now, the customers are treated as kings and are given with multiple options to choose from. With the changes in the economy, a lot has changed for the marketers and the consumers. The marketers now, need to woo the customers into buying their product, and sometimes even create a need for their product, that the customer does not really need. The consumers on the other hand, have multiple choices of the product they need and many sellers to buy it from. The consumers are usually aware of what they precisely need and are equipped to purchase the product that provides them the satisfaction.

The prominent change in the market is the importance given to the customers a few years ago versus now. The flywheel-and a subsequent focus on service have replaced the one-way direction of the funnel.

The difference is shown below in the diagram:

Diagram no. 01:

This change in the market place has resulted in the need for the change in the marketing tools. One of the most trending marketing tool of today is the targeted marketing or the personalised marketing. The marketers these days use the artificial intelligence to attract the customers with specified or personalised advertisements that are curated according to the recent searches of the targeted customer. The marketers lure the customers in, with a number of personalised offers, making the customers want to buy the product as soon as possible. This makes the whole process of purchasing a product more personal to the consumer, causing an increase in the sales. Amazon, the e-commerce giant was the first business to conceptualise and execute this idea, in the early 2000's.

Digitalisation has caused many changes in the way the things are being bought and sold. One of the major changes is the e-commerce websites. This form of shopping is the most hassle free one, which is the main reason why the youth are leaning more towards this form of shopping. Online shoppers are also more prone towards buying things on an impulse. This weakness is being cashed in by the marketers and producers.

2. Meaning

Using Artificial intelligence is now the latest trend in the marketing world. Though the practice of collecting the consumer behaviours for predicting the future trends has been in the market from almost 1998, collecting data in this day and age, has changed enormously. The Artificial Intelligence is being used in almost every industry. It collects the consumer data, paired with profile information and demographics. AI is the method of leveraging customer data and concepts like machine learning to anticipate the customer's next move and improve the customer's experience in shopping with a particular business. The AI continually adapts to the likes and dislikes of the consumers and tailors the recommendations as required.

Impulsive buying simply put, means unplanned purchasing. These are the buying decisions that are not made neither rationally or habitually and is not characterised by the extent of cognitions alone. The impulsive buying can be the result of various stimuli, such as, motivation and perception, the stimulation having to be stronger enough to overcome restraints, buying situations, impulsive behaviour in general and so on.

Stern (1962) has identified four distinct types of impulsive purchasing: planned, pure, reminder and suggestion impulse purchasing. Planned impulse purchasing is when the shoppers do not plan their purchases, but search for and take advantage of in-store promotions, thus maximising their buying power (Nesbitt-1959). Pure impulse purchasing occurs when consumers experience truly impulsive buying, the novelty or escape purchase breaks a normal buying pattern (Stern 1962, p. 59). Reminder impulsive purchasing occurs when the consumer is reminded of the need to buy an item upon seeing it. Suggestion buying is when the consumer sees the product and then visualises a need for it. (p. 59-60).

3.Literature review

- Beatty and Ferrel (1998) described that “impulse buying refers to immediate purchases which are without any pre-shopping objective either to purchase the specific product category or to fulfil a specific need. They explained that the impulse buying behaviour occurs after experiencing a buying desire by the shopper and without much reflection. The buying of an item which is out of stock and reminded during encountering the product are excluded from the purview of impulse buying.”
- According to Engel and Blackwell (1982) “impulse buying is an action undertaken without previously having been consciously recognised or a buying intention formed prior to entering the store.”
- Sanjiv Mehta, CEO & MD of Hindustan Unilever Ltd. Says, “the core of marketing hasn’t changed, but the way we communicate has changed marketing. It is morphing every day. That’s where the big shift has happened. The art of storytelling is very much there but how we tell the story and the medium through which we tell the story is the key. The big changes that will happen in marketing, just as in business, is artificial intelligence and machine learning.”
- Thomas H. Davenport states, “Contemporary marketing is increasingly quantitative, targeted, and tied to business outcomes. Ads and promotions are increasingly customised to individual consumers in real time. Companies employ multiple channels to get to customers, but all of them increasingly employ digital content. Company marketers still work with agencies, many of which have developed analytical capabilities of their own.”
- According to Xia and Monroe (2009), their study resulted that consumers with a shopping goal are more responsive towards promotional messages such as “pay less” and “discount” while consumers without shopping goal are responsive towards promotional messages such as “save more” and “free gift”. Xia and Monroe (2009, p.691) cited from (Monroe, 2003) that price promotion have several benefits such as to increase demand, adjust fluctuations in supply and demand, and increasing consumers’ purchasing over time.”

4.Objectives

- To analyse the role of artificial intelligence in personalised marketing.
- To study the impact of personalised advertisements on the purchasing behaviour of the youth.
- To understand the opinion of the youth on the use artificial intelligence in personalised marketing.

5.Methodology

- The primary data has been collected through questionnaires.
- The secondary data was collected from various journals and articles.

6.Scope

The study concentrates on the use of artificial intelligence only as a tool in the personalised marketing that is done in online marketing. The study analyses the impact of personalised marketing on the impulsive buying behaviour of the consumer, while shopping online. The respondents are selected randomly, and are in their late teens or early twenties, as they are considered as the youth for the sake of this study.

7.Results and Discussions

The total number of respondents was 100. The respondents were selected in a random manner, the only consideration being their age. The questionnaire was distributed, filled and collected physically.

The respondents were mainly from the Dakshina Kannada district and where of the age 15-26. This age range was chosen as it is the demographic of people that indulge in online shopping. Most of the respondents were of the age 23-26, which means, they were employed and spent their salary on buying the products. The least number of the respondents belonged to the category of 15-18 age range. The number of the female respondents was slightly higher than the male respondents. The same information is given below in the tabular form.

Table no. 01:

Age	Percentage	Gender	Percentage	Employment Status	Percentage
15-18	12	Male	41	Student	29
19-22	25	Female	59	Employed	71
23-26	63	Other	-		

*The percentage total is 100.

Majority of the respondents often shopped online and very few times they had their shopping list pre-determined. Most of them agreed to have purchased an item online, on an impulse.

Table no. 02:

Shop online	Percentage	Pre-determined list	Percentage	Impulse purchases	Percentage
Very often	55	Very often	15	Very often	18
Sometimes	27	Sometimes	57	Sometimes	59
Rarely	10	Rarely	19	Rarely	17
Never	8	Never	9	Never	6

The following table shows that the related advertisements and offers were the main reasons for the impulsive purchases. They did not think that they would have purchased the same item if they had physically gone shopping instead of the online shopping.

Table no. 03:

Motive for impulsive purchasing	Percentage	Purchases made due to the influence	Percentage	Physically purchase the same item	Percentage
Related advertisements	59	Very often	35	Yes	25
Offers	12	Sometimes	23	No	46
Discounts	23	Rarely	39		
Free shipping	3	Never	3	Maybe	29
Others	3				

Though they found that most of the times the advertisements were relevant to their searches, they did not however think that these related advertisements helped them to make rational decisions. The notification of these personalised advertisements were also seen as a nuisance by many and said that they didn't like receiving them.

Table no. 04:

Relevancy of the advertisements	Percentage	Help in making rational decisions	Percentage	Receiving notifications	Percentage
Very often	47	Very often	15	Very often	13
Sometimes	39	Sometimes	21	Sometimes	21
Rarely	12	Rarely	48	Rarely	29
Never	2	Never	16	Never	37

The younger generation of people knew about the use of Artificial Intelligence in marketing, though not in a detailed manner. They were aware that their moves on the internet were being followed and taken advantage of. Though they liked to get the personalised advertisements and offers, they were not too keen on having to compromise their privacy to receive it. They were of the view that these notifications were not worth compromising their privacy.

Table no. 05:

Awareness of AI in marketing	Percentage	Awareness of sharing personal data	Percentage	Favour towards sharing personal data	Percentage
Yes	46	Yes	51	Yes	63
No	24	No	20	No	18
Maybe, not sure	30	Maybe	29	I don't mind	100

8. Conclusion

With the changing times, the techniques and approach to marketing has changed for the general good. The consumers today are aware of more market tactics than our elder generations. This makes it hard for the marketers to sell the products. This is where the Artificial Intelligence comes into play. It plays an important role in marketing the products to the targeted consumers in an efficient manner, thus increasing the consumer base and the sales.

This however, is not the same view point the youth of today has, towards Artificial Intelligence and personalised marketing. Though these marketing tools make it easy for them to choose and buy what they want, the way they want to, it often tends to mislead them. The downhill in this is that the more and more people are being aware of it. The main issue is with the sharing of the privacy, without which the personalised marketing technique is spineless. Hence, the need to make the consumers feel safer about their privacy might become the immediate need in future. But as of now, Artificial Intelligence is making a huge impact on the buying behaviour of the consumers and the marketing tools.

Bibliography

- http://www.academia.edu/Documents/in/Impulse_Buying
- <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/A-Study-of-Impulse-Buying-Behavior-and-Factors-it-Gandhi-Vajpayee/b9ac03dfd123a71c2290831adf71533024ed0174>
- <https://www.quicksprout.com/2018/11/15/10-marketing-trends-that-will-dominate-2019/>
- <https://blog.hubspot.com/marketing/marketing-trends>
- <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbesagencycouncil/2019/01/15/11-trends-that-will-shape-marketing-in-2019/>
- <https://www.emarsys.com/resources/blog/artificial-intelligence-marketing-solutions/>
- <https://www.smartinsights.com/managing-digital-marketing/managing-marketing-technology/how-ai-is-changing-the-role-of-the-marketer-in-2018/>
- <https://successstory.com/inspiration/role-of-artificial-intelligence-in-future-of-marketing>
- <https://emerj.com/ai-sector-overviews/artificial-intelligence-in-marketing-and-advertising-5-examples-of-real-traction/>

Paper 16

WOMEN IN STEAM: A PERSPECTIVE OF PRESENT TRENDS, OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES IN ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY

Dr. Ramakrishna N Hegde*, **Mr. Srinidhi Kukkila****
Professor & Head

*Department of Automobile Engineering, SIT Mangaluru.
Email: ramakrishnahegde_auhod@sitmng.ac.in
Assistant Professor

**Department of Aeronautical Engineering, SIT Mangaluru.
Email: srinidhikukkila@sitmng.ac.in

Abstract

Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics (STEAM) are the major contributors to education policies and curriculum choices in schools. STEAM has been mainly applied and addressed to the preschools, schools and predominantly in high schools. It has played a major role in the overall development of the students and nowadays, is being applied to the Higher Education Institutes (HEIs). The major drawback in the STEAM field is found out to be the discrimination of women in STEAM fields and it has led to a lot of negative effects on the society. The research focuses on the students' perspective of women in STEAM fields and a lot of discussions are done to understand the reasons behind the disparity. Both urban and rural backgrounds were considered for the discussion to understand the kind of support and equality, the learning environment and in the STEAM field professions. Many constraints for women in STEAM fields are taken into consideration like lack of equality, safety problems, financial constraints and pay gap with the male counterparts. Lately, there are some visible changes in the mindset of parents irrespective of different backgrounds. The curtains of old traditions and restrictions are slowly but definitely opening and the girls have the urge to learn, compete and to take responsibly even in unconventional branches of engineering like automobile and aeronautical. But still, a lot of women graduate in STEAM fields but fail to make a successful career out of it. A lot of statistical data from PISA is also taken into consideration for the research.

Keywords: STEAM, disparity, HEI.

1. Introduction

Research and development, creativity and innovations are the basis for modern society. All the major innovations happening across the world is from the Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics fields or popularly referred as STEAM fields. Initially it was only Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) field, arts being added at the later stage. Since for a long time the STEM fields contributed to the society. The origin of STEM field is unknown, but it has come to prominence in last 15-25 years. But it found a major flaw that it has become subject centric and hence STEAM field came to existence which is people centric. Early founder of STEAM field initiative is Georgette Yakman, who has incorporated Arts to STEM field. She also found a formal way

to link the subjects together and connect them to the global socio-economic forum. With this inclusion, design or a touch of beauty is given to this interdisciplinary field. But some experts in STEM fields also argue that Arts acts as a distraction to other hard science fields.

STEAM fields are the major contributors to the students of preschools, schools and high schools. This mainly focuses the students more on the modern ideals like valuing the learning process as much as the results. It creates a knowledge base that is applicable to real life. Now-a-days STEAM fields have also entered the Higher Education Institutes (HEI) and especially it is playing a major role in engineering and technology institutes[1]. However, the major roadblock in the progress is the participation of women in STEAM fields. This has led to a lot of adverse effect in the progress of STEAM fields. So, the main objective of the research is to study a perspective of present trends, opportunities and challenges in engineering and technology fields for women, platform for women in HEI, to find the problems faced by the women and to propose the solution for the disparity of women in STEAM fields.

2.Present Trends

The Agreed Conclusions by the 61st session of the Commission on the Status of Women (CSW61) provided a diagnosis of the existing and growing gender gaps and disparities in key areas of the world of work as well as their root causes. The major gender gaps identified included those relating to wages, income, pension, social security, work force participation, recruitment, retention, promotion, re-entry, leadership, occupational segregation, burden of unpaid care work, and access to economic and productive resources, all of which were comprehensively outlined. Also, it was recognized that progress has been insufficient and that this was impeding the realization of women's full potential and the full enjoyment of their human rights and fundamental freedoms[2]. Multiple and persisting structural barriers which contribute to these gender gaps and disparities in the world of work were identified throughout, along with ways to overcome them[3].

The Gender gap indexing is done by the World Economic Forum. The World Economic Forum is the International Organization for Public-Private Co-operation. The Forum engages the foremost political, business and other leaders of society to shape global, regional and industry agendas and is headquartered in Geneva, Switzerland. It was founded in 1971 and was given the international body status in 2005.

The World Economic Forum conducts surveys on the gender gap and its disparities annually. Annual report are made by the forum, gender gap indexing is done and also the international ranking since 2006. The Gender gap index ranking of India has exponentially increased since 2006. The gender gap index of India in 2006 was 0.6011, it has reached the maximum of 0.683 at 2016[4].

Fig. 1: Gender Gap Index of India by WEF[4]

But after 2016, the index has gone downwards, that is at 2017 it was 0.669 and the latest at 2018 it was 0.665. The current gender gap index ranking of India is 108 and is expected to increase in 2019.

There are four key areas also called as the variables in deciding the global gender gap index, they are the economic participation and opportunity, educational attainment, health and survival and political empowerment. The gender gap index of India at 2018 is 0.665 and the breakdown index of the four key areas, are shown below.

Fig. 2: Index score of the Areas considered for Global Index Score[4]

The first variable in global index score is Economic Participation and Opportunity high includes Labour force participation, Wage equality for similar work, Estimated earned income, Legislators, senior officials and managers, and Professional and technical workers. Here the Labour force, wage equality and income are having more weightage in indexing. This is the most important aspect of participation of women in STEAM fields and to seek out the field as a job. In 2018, the index of the economic participation and opportunities for women was 0.385. It is of very lower ranking because the participation of women in STEAM fields are very less compared to most of the countries. Not only in 2018, it has always been very less index in economic participation of women.

The second variable in education attainment which includes literacy rates, enrolment in primary, secondary and tertiary education. India is having a high literacy rate of women in the latest years compared to the post independence years. A lot of initiatives have been taken up by the governments with various schemes, financial benefits, five year plans and only women education institutes. Even though India is having an index of 0.953 in 2018, still it is well behind many countries. But the drawback is the indexing doesn't include the higher education of women. There is a large negative gap between the education attainment and economic participation. So most of the women have the basic education on STEAM fields, but the enrolment to higher education is less. Comparing to 2006, in present years women entering the STEAM field Higher education institutes are on the rise and also more women graduate with higher performance in academics, thanks to the changed policy of the government at the national level. Of late, in spite of a positive contribution as far as the women pursuing a career in STEAM fields, the overall scenario is not so encouraging.

The third variable is health and survival; it includes sex ratio at birth and healthy life expectancy. Even this has also increased drastically post independence and a lot of governmental supports and schemes were implemented successfully. Because of these initiatives, awareness about the hygiene and the life expectancy of women are on the rise. As per the information available from the NITI Aayog, GOI, during the period 2010-14, it was 69.7 years for women as against 66.4% for men in India. However, on comparing with other countries, India is well behind even though many schemes were implemented by the government, during the last five years. This is because, the awareness amongst people is less and also the participation of women is very low in these fields. So it has adversely affected the health and survival of women in India.

The fourth and final variable is political empowerment of women which includes women in parliament, in ministerial positions and years with female head of state. It is the most successful stint of India post independence that it is one of the top 20 countries in the area of political empowerment. India is ranked 19th globally in the year 2018 and is expected to be within top 10 country in 2019. Many government initiatives like schemes, reservations and political awareness have lead to the maximum growth in this key area. Because of women in power, the upliftment and pro-gender schemes to uplift women could be implemented.

3.Economic Participation - Challenges

Economic participation and opportunity of women is one of the main areas for deciding the global gender gap index. It is the main contributor to the STEAM fields and

participation of women in STEAM fields as a profession. There are five factors deciding the variable, they are Labour force participation, Wage equality for similar work, Estimated earned income, Legislators, senior officials and managers, and Professional and technical workers. These factors have different weightage, when the score of all five factors is added an index of 1.0 is obtained. The index scores are assessed by World Economic Forum is shown below.

Fig. 3: Index score of Economic Participation and Opportunity[4]

The index score of Economic Participation and Opportunity of women in India was always low as compared other areas and also as compared to other countries. India has always been in the list of last ten countries in this gender gap. From the graph, the index score is in between 0.345 and 0.46. It has always been the same and not much deviation or growth is shown in this area. The main reason for the negative performance is women in STEAM fields. The education attainment is very high of the score of 0.9, but the conversion rate of education to career or profession is very low. The education attainment assessment is only till tertiary education and not of higher education. The women pursuing higher education in STEAM fields were always very less because of patriarchal society of India. This has affected adversely on the development of women in STEAM fields. There may be many number of reasons like male dominated society, age old traditions, mindset of parents, safety concerns of women like stalking, accommodation facilities in higher education institutes, time constraints, shift duties and some society barriers[5].

4.Opportunities:

India, being one of the world's fastest-growing major economies, could do a lot better if only it treated its women better. By 2025, the country could add up to \$770 billion, more than 18%, to its GDP, by giving equal opportunities to women, according to a 2018 report by the McKinsey Global Institute. Owing to the drastic policy shift by the government and its serious concern to address this issue, in the coming years one can expect higher participation of women in the workforce, raising the number of hours spent by them on the job etc. Also inclusion of women in higher-productivity sectors will help boost such economic growth. "As

women's contribution to the country's GDP is currently just 18%, one of the world's lowest, with only 25% of India's labour force being female, India's economy also has the second-largest potential in the Asia-Pacific (APAC) region from improving gender parity", the report [6] says.

The IITs conduct the JEE Advanced every year for admission to engineering courses in the IITs, IISc, and a few other top engineering colleges in India. Of late, the Ministry of Human Resources Development (MHRD), Government of India, with an intention of bringing more women in to the economic forum, has directed the IITs across the country to increase the admission of female candidates in the premier engineering colleges (NIT's) in the country, by implementing reservation for girls. Based on this directive a separate merit list shall be declared for female candidates of JEE Advanced to ensure that there is 14 percent candidates given admission to the institutes are female. This new decision of having separate IIT reservation for girls has been taken to reduce the existing gender gap in the best engineering colleges in India. However, the Joint Seat Allocation Authority (JoSAA) is yet to accept the suggestions and hopefully is bound to do that in the coming days. Similar policy shift at the state level HEIs has to be adapted if one really wants to boost the Indian economy and make it \$5trillion worth by 2024.

In general, in recent years women pursuing higher education is on the rise and also the academic performance are also very much higher compared to the male counterparts. This is because the kind of support, equality at home, in learning environment, after graduation and in industry. The support by the family as far as giving education to the girl child, in particular in HEIs it is on the rise. This is true and there is a visible change in the mind set of parents irrespective of the rural or urban background. It seems those curtains of old traditions and restrictions are slowly but definitely opening and the girls have the urge to learn, compete and taking the responsibility even in unconventional branches of engineering like aeronautical and automobile. In most HEIs it is happening, equal opportunities exist in recruitment drives and more or less 50% girl students are picked up by the companies. HEIs give more thrust on personality and skill development apart from curriculum irrespective of gender. More girl students are involved in startup ecosystem and the HEIs give the necessary support and guidance. Even the faculty level recruitment drives also have seen more women. A definite visibility, still the feeling is not satisfactory, as in some rural areas, the parental support is confined mainly due to financial and societal constraints. Lack of public transportation or no transportation and stalking during commuting are the main safety concerns for students from rural areas but urban students feel it is better in this aspect.

5. Conclusion

The women in STEAM fields are on the rise. The study has considered the data from Commission on the Status of Women. There is some kind of discrimination with the gender relate to work force participation, wages, income, pension, social security, recruitment, retention, promotion, re-entry, leadership, occupational segregation, burden of unpaid care work, and access to economic and productive resources. A lot of government scheme and awareness has been implemented post independence and some drastic measures are being taken. But it feels like India is still behind many countries in growth rate.

World Economic Forum assesses the gender gap of the world and annual reports are generated. The performance of India is considered moderate post independence and good improvements are happening since last 10 to 12 years. The gender gap index has increased

continuously from 2006 to 2018. This is because of a lot of awareness among people and also the support for women upliftment in STEAM fields. Even though there are good measures a small decrease in the index is seen. The education attainment of girl students is good and also the political empowerment of women is very good. India is ranked 19th globally in political empowerment of women. But the index is very low and has always been low in economic participation and opportunities and also in health and survival rate of women. Because of this, it has adversely affected the global index ranking. Especially in economic participation and opportunities in STEAM fields, the women entering the academics of STEAM fields and their performance is very good, but making a career in STEAM fields is very less. Mainly because of male dominated society, wage gap and societal barriers. But in HEIs, it is in positive trends. Girls opting for unconventional branches of engineering and technology fields like aeronautical, automobile and aerospace have increased. The company and industry recruitment solely based on the performance, skill and knowledge resulted in good improvement in covering the gender gap and the gender specific jobs are being reformed. Implementing the concept of Arts to STEM fields has also lead to increase in the participation of women in economy of the country.

References:

- [1] Nataliia V. Morze, Liliia O. Varchenko Trotsenko and Anastasiia V. Tiutiunnyk, "Introduction of STEAM Education with the use of 3D Technologies: Modelling, Scanning and Printing", Open educational e-environment of modern University, ResearchGate Publications, ISSN: 2414-0325, January 2016.
- [2] Report on CSW61 and Analysis of the Agreed Conclusions, Commission on the Status of Women, United Nations Women, March 2017.
- [3] Empower Women Organisation, UN Women: <https://www.empowerwomen.org/en/projects>
- [4] Annual Global Gender Gap Report, World Economic Forum, 2006 - 2018.
- [5] World Economic Forum Initiatives: <https://www.weforum.org/system-initiatives>
- [6] Report by McKinsey Institute : <https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/gender-equality/the-power-of-parity-advancing-womens-equality-in-asia-pacific>

Paper 17

**THE GROWTH OF A SERVICE ORIENTED IT
COMPANY THROUGH OUTSOURCING –A CASE
STUDY OF INFOSYS LTD.**

M. Rajeshwari¹ & Krishna Prasad K²

¹ Research Scholar, College of Computer Science and Information Science,
Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

² College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore,
India

Email: rajimuraleedhar@gmail.com

Abstract

Infosys Limited is an Indian multinational IT company, located its headquarters in Bengaluru, Karnataka, and established in the year 1981, which offers information technology, Business consulting and outsourcing services. It was founded by seven engineers with an investment of 250 dollars in India. In 2018-19, Infosys secured fifth rank Globally for IT services. Its brand value increased by 8% to \$6.5 billion. N. R. Narayanamurthy(CEO) was leading the company since its establishment till 2014, for 21 years. Its market cap amounted to 46.52 billion dollars on March 29, 2019. In 2019, it has 228,123 employees working at different roles and campus, all over the world. Infosys offers software development, maintenance, and autonomous validation services to finance, insurance, production, and other businesses. Infosys planned to reduce the amount of work done on site by their manpower travelling visas in the United States by shipping more work overseas. By this way, Infosys aim to protect and improve margin benefits. Charge for onsite projects are 3-4 times more than those delivered out of India. Infosys has nearly 25% work performed onsite and remaining from India. The company offers Insurance Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) services. Infosys BPO secured first rank for offshore services. BPO was renamed as Infosys Business Process Management (BPM), in April 2002. Infosys BPM is meant for client's needs and fulfils them in a sustainable and complete manner. Forrester research has used Forrester wave methodology to classify Infosys as a leader in easy offshore capacities. The study also reviewed that Infosys, using a low-cost GDM or offshore delivery model, is the biggest of the six in terms of income for application-related services. This case study focused on various goals— business vs. operational metrics, profit vs. saving cost, and decreased service needs vs. better customer service. This Case study also helps to investigate the advantages of outsourcing (onshore and offshore) in terms of economic development and client demand.

Keywords: Infosys Limited, Offshore project, BPO, Forrester Wave Methodology, Application-related services.

1. Introduction

Infosys is a well-known multinational consulting and Information Technology Services Company founded in the year 1981. The firm mentioned in NASDAQ was constructed by

N.R. Narayanamurthy and six engineers with an initial investment of US\$ 250 [1]. With powerful business strategy and IT strength, it has grown to a US\$ 4.8 billion organization with market revenue of around 33 billion United States dollars. Infosys has spread its corporation globally by working in 28 countries, including America, the Middle East, Europe, Asia-Pacific, China and Africa. Infosys offers a range of services to improve and expand their growth in a competitive environment. Infosys clubs on-site high-quality consulting on business with off-site perfect execution of technology. This will finally decrease the cost of the full team of business experts to the client site. Application services enable the development, maintenance and modernisation of apps. Those services focus on offering best-quality apps, with less or easy maintenance. Services provided by Infosys BPO combines technology with knowledge of domain to produce processes on outsourcing. Infosys provides services to a wide spectrum of industries, including business functions, including finance, human resource management, data technology and other outsourcing domains [2]. This case study examines the problem of "performance measurement" with outsourcing with following goals: (1) to determine how Infosys benchmarks the inner performance of prospective providers ; (2) to determine how the service organization assesses the expenses of the outsourcing decision ; (3) to develop efficient performance policies to assess the outsourcing decision [2].

2. Vision and Mission

Infosys aims to provide best business solution by having efficient, best-in-class employees to become a standard corporation [3]. Infosys maintains their clients, employees and society with true care, sincerity and consideration to achieve their goals [3].

3. Background

The objective of this case study is to understand the decision-making process used by Infosys Ltd companies to outsource their IT operations [4]. Outsourcing means providing an external provider with the business activity. Outsourcing is based on a long-term, periodic relationship, where the provider is liable for the full outcomes of outsourcing activities. We see companies that have used outsourcing for their development, cost reduction, risk diversification or quality improvement [5-8]. There are only a few effective instances of offshoring, which has brought cost savings, innovation, quality improvement or other advantages, and these are mostly among big, globally engaged companies [9]. Outsourcing should be seen as an instrument that enables the company to focus on its key business. Based on the current growth in outsourcing (and also offshoring), backed by globalization, deregulation, the development of IT and communication techniques, advances in education and the deepening of specialization, we expect outsourcing to grow more and more [9-13].

4. Success saga

Table1: Success saga of Infosys [14]

Year	Milestone
1981	Year of establishment
1992	Transformed into a Public Limited company in India
1993	Received certification of ISO 9001/TickIT

1997	Achieved SEI - CMM Level 4
1999	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mentioned in stock market NASDAQ • Reached \$100 Million in Annual revenues • Achieved SEI - CMM Level 5
2001	Reached 400 million dollars in revenues
2002	Succeeded to cross \$ half a billion in revenues
2004	Succeeded to cross \$ billion in revenues
2006	Succeeded to cross \$ 2 billion in revenues
2007	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reached 3 billion US dollars revenue. Employees count was more than 70,000 • Reported revenue of over 1 billion dollars in the second quarter.
2008	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Succeeded to receive 4.18 billion dollars revenue. • More than 1 billion dollars was the Annual net profit.
2009	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Global Dow considered company as a member. • Employee power reached more than 1,00,000.
2010	Obtained 5 billion dollars revenue
2011	Obtained 6 billion dollars revenue, and employee count reached 1,25,000.
2012	Made an entry on the NYSE market.
2016	Reached revenues of US\$10 billion.
2018	Successfully maintained 25 years on Indian Stock exchanges listing.
2019	Infosys BPM was honoured with Best CSR Practice Award

5. Strategies

Infosys' strategy is to strengthen the value of all its employees and constantly invest in the development of their skills [10-11]. Infosys strongly trusts that the major factor that helps them achieve development is their client-focused approach. Their strategy focuses on a limited number of reputable big organisations paying attention to product quality rather than concentrating on countless tiny organisations without concern for quality. Their strategy focuses on creating a picture rather than cost-differentiating model for quality driven model. It offers value-added alternatives to its new customers by providing deep industry knowledge. The company concentrates on emerging technologies and innovations. In recent years, they have added new services, like infrastructure management and, system integration which have increased the success of the company.

Infosys focuses on gaining the price benefit of their global delivery model [3]. Infosys has its vision on Modular Global Sourcing i.e., an evolutionary outsourcing approach, which enables an enterprise to implement best-of-breed sourcing approaches by structuring business processes and IT systems into individual modules. The main principles for Modular Global Sourcing include, taking an enterprise-wide perspective of aligning the sourcing objectives with the business strategy. The new idea of global outsourcing strategy will focus on what and when to consider outsourcing and also knows the managing skills to deliver the services globally throughout the value chain.

Infosys provides support across all sourcing and procurement management needs—from strategy formulation to BPM services and technology—providing comprehensive services. I.e. Infosys specialists outline the difficulties faced by procurement analytics and the holistic strategy required to resolve them. Fortunately, the combination of state-of-the-art visualization and artificial intelligence technology, coupled with models of 'as a service,' can

finally provide the insights needed for real business value. Procurement solutions are designed to provide access to sophisticated AI-based skills, allowing quicker decision-making [2].

6. Infosys Subsidiaries and Services offered [15]:

- 6.1 EdgeVerve Systems Limited: EdgeVerve Systems, Infosys' fully-owned subsidiary, creates and provides new software goods on-site or as cloud-hosted business platforms. Its headquarters are situated in Bengaluru, Electronic City. EdgeVerve is looking forward to announcing the 18.0 AssistEdge RPA. It offers services like banking, interactive business, distributive trade, credit service, enterprise purchasing service. It provides a universal solution used for banking, Finacle. 547 million clients of financial organization across 84 countries are choosing it.
- 6.2 Infosys BPM Limited: It is an outsourcing business process subsidiary. Infosys BPM provide its customers with transformative advantages through cost reduction, continuing productivity improvements, and process reengineering. It offers services on Human Resource, Finance & Accounting, Legal Process, Sales and Fulfilment, Sourcing and Procurement, Business Transformation Services, BPM Analytics, and Robotic Process Automation using outsourcing [7]. As of June 2019, Infosys BPM operates in India and 16 countries with 32 delivery centers across 5 continents. It provides job for 38,886 people from more than 100 nations.
- 6.3 Infosys Consulting services: It was established in 2004. Infosys Consulting is a worldwide consultant to lead businesses in strategizing, process engineering and managing transformation programs that are enabled by technology. By combining creative and human-focused strategies with the new hi-tech developments, allow organisations to rethink their future and generate viable and sustainable company value for automotive, insurance, life sciences, energy, resources, and financial services, etc. Globally, it offers its services to more than 200 active customers.
- 6.4 Infosys Public Services Inc: U.S.-based Infosys subsidiary, offers service in business consulting and technology solutions. Infosys partner with public sector organisations in the US and Canada. In Rockville, Maryland, it has opened its new headquarters and delivery centre. Digitizing customer experience and ensuring optimal service delivery by adopting innovative technologies through rapid innovation. It provides services to the public such as consulting services, technology services, company mobility, cloud and infrastructure, cyber and safety, legacy modernization, procurement modernization analytics and insights, digital ERP services.
- 6.5 Panaya : It was established in 2006. Delaware Corporation in the United States, is a major provider of automation technology for large-scale enterprise software management. It is software as a service company (SaaS). It is present across Americas, the EMEA and Asia. Infosys fully acquired the Panaya group of companies in 2015.
- 6.6 Skava: Skava is one of the major providers of mobile and multi-touch point solutions to many of the top retailers in the US. The Skava platform transforms its e-commerce platform to mobile web, tablet, Facebook and in-store technologies. Skava has been a pioneer in app growth since 2002. The first retail location is

fully optimized for tablets (t.staples.com) and works with various retailers to develop their in-store technology solutions.

6.7 Noah Consulting, LLC, a leading subsidiary of sophisticated information management consulting services. This firm assists upstream oil and gas businesses to provide worldwide technology and outsourcing services to oil and gas customers.

7. Financial Growth

Infosys annual revenue history and growth rate, for the financial year from 2015 to 2019 is shown below [16-18].

Table 2: Annual revenue of Infosys from financial year 2015 to 2019

Parameter	Mar15	Mar16	Mar17	Mar18	Mar19
Revenue	533,190	624,410	684,840	705,220	826,750
Cost of revenue	- 353,300	419,350	-466,360	-485,870	- 581,290
Gross Profit	179,890	205,060	218,480	219,350	245,460
Sales, general & administrative	-28,990	-32,760	-32,440	-29,240	-36,550
Depreciation	-10,170	-12,660	-17,030	-18,630	-20,110
Provision	0	0	0	0	0
Other operating income or expenses	-2190	-1100	0	0	-2,700
operational income	138,540	158,540	169,010	171,480	186,100
Expense Interest	0	0	0	0	0
Other income Or expense	34,300	31,280	30,800	31,930	24,310
Profit before tax	172,840	189,820	199,810	203,410	210,410
Income tax & other taxes	49,110	53,010	55,980	42,410	56,310
Net income from continuing operations	123,730	136,810	143,830	161,000	154,100
Extraordinary & discontinued ops	0	0	0	0	0
Associates Share	-10	-30	-300	-710	0
Interest of Minority	0	0	0	0	-60
Net Income	123,720	136,780	143,530	160,290	154,040
Net income after preferred Dividend and others	123,720	136,780	143,530	160,290	154,040
Basic shares	4,571	4,571	4,571	4,511	4,347
Diluted Shares	4,571	4,571	4,573	4,515	4,353
EPS Basic	27.06	29.92	31.40	35.54	35.43
EPS Diluted	27.06	29.92	31.39	35.50	35.38

The graph shown in Fig. 1 depicts that company has consistent profit margins [17]. The overall performance, i.e. income and profit of Infosys are also rising, as shown in Fig 2[17].

Fig 1: Gross, Operating, Net Profit

Fig 2: Company performance chart

8. Competitors

Infosys’ major competitors are Accenture, Wipro and TCS. As of July 2019, Infosys had 841.6 K followers on Facebook and 235.5 K followers on Twitter. Infosys has revenues of \$11.8B and 228,000 staff [19]. Accenture, Wipro, CTS, TCS, IBM, Deloitte, Capgemini, Tech Mahindra, HP and HCL are the top 10 competitors in Infosys' competitive set. Together, more than 48.7 million of their approximately 2.4 million staff has increased. Infosys has 228,000 employees and ranks 6th among its top 10 competitors. The top 10 rivals are on average 235,653[18-19].

Table 3: Top10 competitor lists of Infosys

Ranking	IT Company	Workforce	Funding	Revenue
	Infosys	228,000	\$0	\$11.8B
1	Accenture	459,000	--	\$43.3B
2	Wipro	150,000	--	\$8.5B
3	Cognizant	281,600	\$29.2M	\$16.5B
4.	TCS	378,497	--	\$908.8M
5	IBM	350,600	--	\$77.9B
6	Deloitte	286,200	\$19.5M	\$43.2B
7	Capgemini	204,904	--	\$15.1B
8	Tech Mahindra	78,304	--	\$5.1B
9	Hp	55,000	\$538	\$58.7B
10	HCL	120,081	--	\$8.1B

Infosys’ revenue is ranked 7th among its top 10 rivals. The top 10 rivals are on average 26.3B. Infosys’ income increased by 10.4 percent over the last three quarters. Specifically, income was \$3.2B in first quarter 2019; income was \$3.2B in fourth quarter 2018; income was \$2.9B in third quarter 2018 [19].

9. Major Acquisitions

Table 4: Acquisitions of Infosys [22]

Acquired company	Located in	Cost	Date	Services of acquired company
Expert Information Services	Australia	23 million	December 2003	IT service
McCamish Systems	USA	\$38 million	December 2009	Insurance and financial

Portland Group	Australia	AUD 37 million	January 2012	Strategic sourcing and category management
Lodestone Holding AG	Switzerland	US\$345 million	September 2012	Management consultancy
Panaya	Israel	US\$200 million	March 2015	Automation technology
Skava	USA	US\$120 million	April 2015	Digital experience solutions
Noah-Consulting	USA	US\$70 million	November 2015	Information management consulting
Skytree	USA	Undisclosed amount	April 2017	Machine learning
Brilliant Basics	UK	GBP 7.5 million	August 2017	Product design and customer experience
Fluidio	Finland	EUR 65 million	October 2018	Sales force advisor and consulting partner
WongDoody	USA	US\$75 million	January 2019	Advertising and creative strategy
Stater	Netherlands	EUR 127.5 million	April 2019	Mortgage services

10. Corporate Structure

Since its establishment in 1981 till 2019, Infosys has 104 executives and 14 subsidiaries and its main 34 executives are shown in the given organizational chart [20-21].

Fig 3: Infosys Organizational Structure

11. Important Clients

Infosys provides next-generation digital services and consulting and became a leader worldwide. In 45 countries it has around 1,336 happy consumers to pilot their digital change [23].

12. SWOC Analysis

Table 5: Infosys SWOC analysis

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost reduction. • Offers end to end business solutions • Strategic Association with giant companies like Amazon, IBM, and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited markets • Few coverage of growing markets • Huge dependency on Europe and North America

Microsoft <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global Delivery Model • Strong Focus On Innovation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High rate of attrition
Opportunities	Challenges
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invest in young technology businesses • Expansion in spending on digital technology • New Technologies • Increased need for cloud based approaches • Focus on promising markets • IT integration across Industries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong rivalry • Changes in US migration laws • Employee retention.

13. Green Initiatives

Environmental conservation is responsible for creating a better world both for today and for the future. Infosys wants to be identified as a business committed to high standards of environmental management by all stakeholders, including clients, staff, suppliers, share holders and the wider community. Infosys has more concern on its contractors, advisors and staff with a secure and healthy environment. Infosys considers each means of decreasing carbon trace, water usage and power use. Infosys has taken initiatives on Green Infrastructure, Energy Conservation, Water Sustainability, Biodiversity Conservation and Promotion, Waste Management and Green Innovation. Because of its commitment to use renewable energy, in May 2015, Infosys was qualified to join the RE100 renewable energy campaign [24].

14. Stakeholders and corporate social responsibility initiatives

Clients, employees, investors, vendors or partners, government and local communities are the stakeholders of Infosys. Sustainable development of the communities in which it operates is an important part of its CSR [24]. It focuses on education, health care, arts and culture, rural development. Infosys Limited, a digital service and consulting conglomerate, has spent Rs. 342 crore against its prescribed CSR spending of Rs. 340 crore (2 percent of net profit of Rs. 17,018 Cr) on multiple CSR schemes as provided for in Section 135 of the Act [24].

15. Conclusion

This case study explores that Infosys work on its strategies with new ideas of information technology to reach each and every customer on their own way. With their strategic planning and leadership, Infosys has worked hard and even managed to remain competitive even in the era of a worldwide financial downturn. They still need to concentrate on inner and external variables that help to win the weakness and challenges [23][25]. It is very evident that Infosys services will play a significant part in their overall income. That is to say, 31.6% of its total income from economic services, 15.9% from retail, 13.5% from communications, 12.7% from energy, utilities, infrastructure and services, 10% from manufacturing, 7.7% from hi-tech and 6% from life sciences[26]. By outsourcing its services worldwide, i.e. 2.3 percent from India, 24 percent from Europe, 61.2 percent from North America and 12.5 percent from the rest of the globe, Infosys obtained its total revenue. Also Infosys increased their employees count from 2,04,107 (March 2018) to 2,28,123(in March 2019) [26]. Outsourcing may be used to improve cost, quality, and service and time-to-market effectiveness.

16. Future plans

Infosys focuses on innovative digital techniques to make the correct choices to enhance its efficiency in order to achieve its goals. The firm also intends to expand its workforce in the US, its biggest market. It announced a plan to employ 10,000 Americans in the United States [23]. Digital labour management, process re-engineering, talent and value chain sharing innovation—these are future outsourcing opportunities.

17. References

- [1] Guragain, N., & Vanja, S. (2019, July 7). Infosys Success: From Borrowed \$250 To Global IT Giant. Retrieved from <https://brandriddle.com/infosys-from-borrowed-250-to-global-it-giant/>, Retrieved- on 10/08/2019
- [2] Moorthi, Y. (2011). Non-linear growth: The road ahead for Indian IT outsourcing companies. *IIMB Management Review*, 23(2),91–101. doi:10.1016/j.iimb.2011.04.009
- [3] (n.d.). Vision And Mission Of Infosys In Consulting And It Services Business Essay. Retrieved from <https://www.ukessays.com/essays/business/vision-and-mission-of-infosys-in-consulting-and-it-services-business-essay.php>
- [4] Arora, A., V. S. Arunachalam, J. Asundi and F. Ronald, 2000. “The Indian software services industry”, *Research Policy*, vol. 30, pp. 1267-1287.
- [5] Patel, D. (2017, July 17). The Pros And Cons Of Outsourcing. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/deeppatel/2017/07/17/the-pros-and-cons-of-outsourcing-and-the-effect-on-company-culture/>. Retrieved- on 31/08/2019
- [6] (n.d.). A Study of Performance Measurement in the Outsourcing Decision. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/book/9781856176804/a-study-of-performance-measurement-in-the-outsourcing-decision>. Retrieved- on 20/08/2019
- [7] Mcivor, R., Humphreys, P., Mckittrick, A., & Wall, T. (2009). Performance management and the outsourcing process. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 29(10), 1025–1048. doi: 10.1108/01443570910993474
- [8] Soltanifar, M. (2016). Infosys: A Case Study on Becoming a Global Brand in Consulting Technology and Outsourcing Solutions. *Multinational Management*, 149–170. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-23012-2_9
- [9] Heeks, R., 1996. “India’s Software Industry: State Policy, Liberalization and Industrial Development”, *Sage Publications*, New Delhi, Thousand Oaks, London.
- [10] Narayanamurthy, N. R., 2000. “Making India a significant IT player in this millennium”, in Romila Thapar (ed.), *India: Another Millennium*, New Delhi: Viking and Penguin Books.
- [11] Schware, R. (1992). Software industry entry strategies for developing countries: A “walking on two legs” proposition. *World Development*, 20(2), 143–164. doi: 10.1016/0305-750x(92)90096-e
- [12] Secretariat, U. (1992). Enhancing Competitiveness of Potential Export Sectors in Developing Countries--Lessons from Experience. *Foreign Trade Review*, 27(3), 305–317. doi: 10.1177/0015732515920306
- [13] Rouse, A. C. (2010). Managing E-Collaboration Risks in Business Process Outsourcing. *IT Outsourcing*, 1648–1655. doi: 10.4018/978-1-60566-770-6.ch104
- [14] Standard, B. (n.d.). Infosys Ltd. Retrieved from <https://www.business-standard.com/company/infosys-2806/information/company-history>.

-
- [15] Infosys Limited. (n.d.). Subsidiaries. Retrieved from <https://www.infosys.com/about/Pages/subsidiaries.aspx>, Retrieved- on 15/08/2019
- [16] (n.d.). Infosys Total Assets 2006-2019: INFY. Retrieved from <https://www.macrotrends.net/stocks/charts/INFY/infosys/total-assets>
- [17] (n.d.).Craytheon.Retrieved from https://craytheon.com/financials/fundamental_stock_analysis_cagr_annual_growth_rate_trend_chart.php?company=INFY ,Retrieved- on 20/08/2019
- [18] (n.d.). Home. Retrieved from <https://finshiksha.com/finshiksha-quick-company-analysis-it-sector-in-india-infosys-ltd/>, Retrieved- on 12/08/2019
- [19] (n.d.). Infosys Competitors, Revenue and Employees - Owler Company Profile. Retrieved from <https://www.owler.com/company/infosys>, Retrieved- on 20/08/2019.
- [20] (n.d.). onkarsule. Retrieved from <https://onkarsule.files.wordpress.com/> Retrieved- on 29/08/2019
- [21] (n.d.). Org Chart Infosys. Retrieved from <https://www.theofficialboard.com/org-chart/infosys>
- [22] (2019, August 28). Infosys. Retrieved from <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Infosys>
- [23] Mendonca, J., & Pramanik, A. (2019, February 28). Infosys sees cloud & analytics as future billion-dollar units. Retrieved from <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/industry/tech/infosys-sees-cloud-analytics-as-future-billion-dollar-units/articleshow/68194524.cms?from=mdr>, Retrieved- on 21/08/2019
- [24] Infosys Limited. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.infosys.com/sustainability>, Retrieved- on 10/08/2019
- [25] Gupta, S., & Dzharova, H. (2014). Innovation and adaptation: Continuing the infosys journey In conversation with S. D. Shibulal, co-founder, CEO & Managing Director, Infosys. *IIMB Management Review*, 26(4), 212. doi: 10.1016/j.iimb.2014.10.006
- [26] Infotech. (2019, April 13). Infosys achieves \$1.035 billion digital revenues. Retrieved from <https://infotechlead.com/bpo/infosys-achieves-1-035-billion-digital-revenues-58235>
- [27] Madhushree.,Revathi R, Anil Kumar, & Aithal P.S., (2018). Business Strategy of Top Indian IT Company:MindTree. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 2(1), 22-36.

Paper 18

**SWACCH BHARATH’’ A STEP TOWARDS
SUSTAINING CLEANLINESS - A CASE STUDY OF
MRPL MANGALORE.**

Pratheeksha

Lecturer in Govinda Dasa College, Surathkal and Research scholar, Srinivas Institute of management studies, Srinivas University, Mangalore - India

Email: pratheeksha.anchan@yahoo.com or pratheeksha@gdc.edu.in

Abstract

Corporate social responsibility is the concept of the day. Modification of Companies' Act 1956 to 2013 has emerged the importance of corporate social responsibility. Companies Act 2013 made it compulsory for the companies to spend 2% of their turnover or profit (with certain categories) on societal well being. CSR is the responsibility of the organisation to work for the development of the nation through contributing their percentage of profit for the improvement of society and the environment. CSR is not the donation it is one way of doing business and improving organisations image through contributing to education, poverty, SwacchBharath, women empowerment, health and many more. CSR represents the company's norms, values, and principles to society. Because of compulsion by the Government, all the organisations are seriously involved in CSR activities. SwacchBharathAbhiyan is one of the components on CSR. This case study is to analyse the contributions made by the MRPL to CSR in general and SwacchBharath in particular. MRPL is a central public sector organisation, earning huge profits and turnover over a decade. MRPL contributing much to the societal well being. The study is to examine the impact of CSR and SwacchBharath on sustaining cleanliness in the society and also to identify the progress of CSR activity. The case study is based on secondary data collected from journals, websites, newspaper and informal conversation with the CSR committee head of MRPL.

Keywords: corporate social responsibility, Swacch Bharath, MRPL, sustaining.

1. Introduction

CSR was discovered in the United States in 1980 as the notion of corporate personal accountability. The US encountered social and environmental issues during this era owing to the enormous decline in dollar prices which led to the focus on CSR. The duty of the organization is to strive for better culture and environment. Corporate social responsibility for profit and survival, the Organization takes advantage of society and environment, so it is up to the Organization to give it to society. In education, gender equality, poverty, starvation, empowerment of women, hygiene issues, Swacch Bharath can contribute their earnings. From 1980 to till today the organisations started to show their responsibilities towards stakeholders – i.e. shareholders, employees, environment, customers and the society as a whole. It is therefore correct for Brownie to say that ‘CSR is the companies ' duty to follow the strategies and to make the choices that favor community and its principles.’The

provisions of CSR are contained in Clause 135 of company's bill 2012. The Companies bill list the CSR activities in paragraph 135 contains five sub-clause of the CSR Schedule, The primary focus is to build a stronger connection between enterprises and the society, and to improve company perspectives. For some classifications of organization, Clause 135(5) CSR activity is mandatory. For those firms whose net worth of Rs 500 crore or more, turnover of Rs. 1000 crore or more, net gain of Rs. 5 crore or more, CSR activity is obligatory. It is a pride to state that India is the first nation to render CSR operations mandatory in compliance with Section 135 of the Company Act 2013.

2. CSR models:

The evolution and scope of company personal behavior are described in some models. The model of Carroll's pyramid of CSR is noteworthy.

CSR is described by Archie B. Carroll as the full spectrum of obligations businesses have towards society. A 3-d conceptual business results model has been suggested. Carroll says that a company has four classes of corporate responsibility commitments.

- ✓ Economic: the company as an economic organization is primarily responsible for the satisfaction and sustainability of the economic requirements of society. excess generation and further extension and diversification to reward investors.
- ✓ Legal: Land regulations and global trade and trade laws are to be respected in accordance with the impact of the organization.
- ✓ Ethical: Ethical obligations are standards that the society expects the company to follow although not codified by legislation. Like not involved in mismanagement.
- ✓ Philanthropic: philanthropic responsibilities refer to the voluntary contribution of company to social well-being such as participation in the growth of a society or in other social initiatives relating to health, hygiene, healthcare, schooling, and mass consciousness.

Debbie haskie (2018) developed a four strategies for the sustainable growth and development of organisation through CSR activities.

1. Develop a vision for society's advantage.
2. CSR vision communication
3. Go to the CSR sight model
4. Crate the dedication of all parties concerned to the vision.

3. CSR as a business strategy:

CSR is, of course, mandated under company law, but beyond this obligation, CSR is a business strategy of one sort that attracts and maintains social perception. To determine their CSR activities level, Andrew (1980) created four issues:

1. Organizational competences determination: what can we do?
2. To analyze the danger and possibilities for businesses: what could we do?
3. Reviewing key implementers ' values: what are we going to do?
4. Social accountability involvement: what should we do?

The organization can be aimed toward fulfilling strategic requirements by identifying the responses to these issues.

4. History of MRPL

The Assam petroleum company was the monopoly in the country's oil production before independence. After the independence government realized the need to develop oil and gas manufacturing and regarded the emergence of the gas and oil sectors in industrial policy of 1948. The oil manufacturing industry had been in private hands until 1955 and had been associated with the Indian government. At end of 1955, under the governance of Mr. K.D.Malviya, the Minister of Natural Resources took the assistance of the European specialists to explore the prospective oil and to eventually drill operation and was established as a separate department under the Ministry of Natural Resources and Scientific Research.

In 2003, MRPL was acquired by the ONGC (OIL AND NATURAL GAS CORPORATION LIMITED). Mangalore refinery and petrochemical limited (MRPL) is a core public sector venture under the Ministry of Oil and Natural Gas, located in an enticing area to the north of Dakshina Kannada, Karnataka state district(INDIA). In 1988, the MRPL was established. With an initial annual capacity of 3 million tonnes. According to the 2018 report 15 million metric tonne refinery has got a variety design with complex secondary processing system of crudes of various API, delivering varieties of quality products. ONGC is MRPL's parent enterprise. Total Birla group shares and equity capital of Rs. 600 crores were acquainted by ONGC on 28 March 2003. MRPL is therefore an ONGC subsidiary with a majority stake. Before the acquisition by ONGC, MRPL was a joint venture oil refinery promoted by M/s Hindustan petroleum corporation limited(HPCL) Now MRPL and ONGC jointly operates OMPL(ONGC MANGALORE PETROCHEMICAL LIMITED). That produces of xylene 1 million tons. In and outside India, the MRPL provides quality products. For centuries, MRPL has been supplying state trading corporation Mauritius with fuel requirements.

A vision to be a world class petrochemical and refining company with a powerful focus on productivity, customer satisfaction, security, health and environmental management, corporate social responsibility and care for employees. with a mission to Energizing sustainability, effectiveness, productivity and innovation leadership, Capitalize on the national and global emerging business possibilities, To cater to the needs of the customers strive, Strong dedication to public welfare sustaining global health, security and environmental standards, Continued concentrate on healthcare and relationships with employees, Imbibe maximum company morality and values norms.

5. Objective of the case study:

- To know the CSR concept and to comprehend the social significance.
- In general, the operations of the CSR in MRPL and the Swacch Bharth Abhiyan programme in particular, to identify the social effect of the MRPL's CSR
- Identifying the evolving Swacch Bharath trend in the MRPL.

6. Case Methods:

Exhaustive literature review regarding the concept and theories has been done through collecting latest Journals from Google Scholar. Secondary data has been collected from various like books, journals, annual report of MRPL, websites of MRPL, magazine, newspapers and informal discussion with CSR committee head of MRPL.

7. Review of literature:

Wood, (1991) argued that CSR is a commitment through social policies and values. The work of CSR is reflected in firms overall performance, this can be assessed by how a firm manages its social relationship, outcome of CSR Policies and impact of organisation development.

Jorge A. Arevalo, Itziar Castelló, Simone de Colle, Gilbert Lenssen, Kerstin Neumann, Maurizio Zollo (2011) in their study on "Introduction to the special issue: integrating sustainability in business models" reveals that sustainable challenges and development of a organisation can be achieved through CSR.

Amit Kumar Srivastava, Gayatri Negi, Vipul Mishra, Shraddha Pandey (2012) in their study "Corporate Social Responsibility: A Case Study Of TATA Group," Explains how an awareness of social responsibility in companies (CSR) is established, and how it can be examined through the case study conducted by the TATA Group under Mr. Ratan Tata, who demonstrated accountability for raising crowds and protecting the atmosphere and growth of the country

Sinha Sanchali, Dr. Panda Abhaya Kumar (2018) in their study on "Corporate Social Responsibility in India" explains that CSR activities are still evolving in India, Indian companies designed by keeping in view of education, environment, health and safety, rural development through dedicated efforts.

8. MRPL & CSR

"To be a world-class Refining and Petrochemicals Company, with a strong emphasis on Productivity, Customer Satisfaction, Safety, Health and Environment Management, Corporate Social Responsibility and Care for Employees".

The CSR activities of the Company are under the "Samrakshan" brand title, which reflects the purpose and engagement of the Company's CSR strategy: to "safeguard, maintain and support" the social, cultural and environmental legacy and the assets of its companies and the nation's sustainable development.

Ensuring an enhanced involvement at all stages of the organisation, while acknowledging the interests of all its players and managing its activities economically, socially and environmentally sustainable. To take up programs that benefit communities in and around their premises with unique regard and commitment to the poorer segment of community to strengthen the standard of living & social well being of local individuals. To build a favorable socially responsible image of the company as a corporation by its CSR projects, it has a strong view for MRPL. Said by MRPL President D.K Sarraf.

9. Composition of CSR Committee.

As the analysis of CSR activity for 5 years, Shri Nalin Kumar Srivastava was the chairman and Shri. B. K. Namdeo Member and other 5 members constitute committee of CSR for the year 2014-15. Smt. Perin Devi, was the Director Chairperson and Shri. B.K. Namdeo,

continues to be a Director Member and other 5 members for the year 2015-16 and 2016-17. . Ms. Manjula C, Chairperson and ShriSewa Ram, and other 5 members for the year 2017-18 and 2018-19.

10. Analysis of various CSR activities under the brand name “Samrakshan”

Shiksha Samrakshan

Shiksha samrakshna's idea of the MRPL CSR operation must be used for education. Bundle of clothes were given to the learners in need, the books and the cupboard were supplied for the government school , computer lab has been built, training courses for young people in rural areas were carried out and self-development programs conducted , midday meal to 400 learners in the rural area. Rangamandira building, a multipurpose spastic physiotherapy vehicle, classroom construction, revamping of the top roof of the Govt School, scientific lab building, auditorium and restore, computer equipping, building of special lion school , infrastructure advancement of government schools and colleges, etc.

Arogya Samarakshan:

The system is centered on the provision of health advantages to the society by constructing free primary health centres, school toilet blocks, a medical camp ,financial aid for the poor, The test of physical equipment, infrastructure and other health facilities for the hospitals concerned, eye donation awareness camp, the organization of a artificial limb camp, the proving of physical equipment for physically challenged and/or spasticized persons/ endosufline persons, together with a district health officer Mangalore.

Bhaujan samrakshan:

Under the Bhaujan Samrakshan concept of CSR, it contributes for the overall development of the society by keeping in mind all the people of the society. Conducted 6 months fashion designer training to the girls of rural area, funding has been done for the construction of community meeting hall, constructed bath cum toilets for Ramakrishna mission boys hostel. Construction of roads, support to backward community entrepreneur, Modification and painting of community hall, construction of retention wall for the road, provided sports equipment, construction of library, construction of veterinary hospital, construction of roofing for community hall, contribution to army fund, infrastructure development of SC/ST community area, procurement of furniture for ashakirana HIV affected children care centre.

Sanskriti samrakshan

CSR activity of the MRPL contributed for the culture and beliefs of the local area by providing Funding and furniture to temple and daivastana, promotion of local cultural art yakshagana through all India Radio, provided plastic chairs to SC/ST community daivastana.

Prakruthi Samrakshan

Environmental safety is most important element; it's the duty of every individual must contribute for the natural environmental safety. MRPL has undertaken the responsibility of garden maintenance at Mangaluru. The major activity of the MRPL through CSR activity is

to contribute for the Swacch Bharath Abhiyan , under this concept various programmes have been conducted such as cleanliness around Surathkal area, Swchatha Pakwada programme, construction of toilets etc.

From past 5 last year tremendous activities have been undertaken regarding Swacch Bharth, the major Swacch Bharath activities are construction of sewage treatment plant, construction of individual toilets, toilets for schools and colleges and public toilets, beautification of Surathkal flyover area under the programme of Swacch Surathkal, distribution of waste disposal machine, distribution of napkin burner machine, beach cleaning, Swacch Bharath Pakwada, Swachata hi seva, providing pure drinking water facility, contribution to relief fund for rehabilitation in kodagu, restoration and development of lakes , provided free LPG kit to BPL cardholder under the concept of smoke free village, solar projects, construction and beautification of bus stop, beautification of compound walls through verliart and beautiful paintings and many more.

This case study is mainly based on **SWACCH BHARATH ABHIYAN** of MRPL on CSR activity head. The study concentrated on the analysis of the activities conducted under Swacch Bharath and the amount spent by the organisation over five years.

Journey of Swacch Bharath Abhiyan:

Swacch Bharath mission is a nationwide campaign with slogan” one step towards cleanliness” in India, aims to clean up the street, roads and to develop the infrastructure of the country. Honourable Prime Minister Narendra Modi launched this abhiyan on 2 October 2014 in Raj Ghat. And aims to achieve the mission by 2nd October 2019 on the 150th birthday of Mahatma Gandhi.through ensuring cleanliness and sanitation (solid and liquid waste management and making gram panchayats open defecation-free).Mahatma Gandhi dream is to make India aClean country. In this regard he said that “Sanitation is more important than Independence”. To fulfil the dream of clean India ,Narendra Modi started a mission called “SWACCH BHARATH ABHIYAN.”

“Swachh Bharat Abhiyan is a clean India Abhiyan.” explains that it is very much required for the people in India to really get the feeling of physical, mental, social and intellectual well-being. Overall scheme to make India, clean India has been discussed. Vishwakarma,

D(2016).Situation analysis with swacch bharath to determine the SWOT, financing is the key strength and opportunity for waste management. Jangra B et al (2016) there is an increase of number of toilet construction , in 2014-15. 0.49 to 6.9 in 2017-18 in the rural areas report given by India Brand Equity Foundation.

Table showing the average net profit and amount of CSR activity for the past 5 years:
(2 % on average net profit of 3 years will be utilised in the next financial year, based on that criteria table has been prepared)

Years	PBT(in crores)	Average PBT of preceding 3 financial year)	CSR budget(2% of NP preceding 3 financial years)
2011-12	1320.20		

2012-13	(476.85)		4.65
2013-14	409.70	417.68	3.47
2014-15	(2155.89)	nil	8.36
2015-16	1173.53	nil	Nil (4.04 carry forward from 2014-15)
2016-17	5531	1516.28	5
2017-18	3349.75	3352.86	30.32
2018-19			67.06

Source: annual report of MRPL.

MRPL ltd PBT with average PBT of preceding 3 financial years exhibited in the above table projecting a clear vision towards CSR budget to the extent of 2 % of the same. The budgeted amount spent by the company as per the proposed proposal in the current financial year and subsequent years.

11.CSR activities by MRPL before the introduction of Companies Act 2013.

Before the compulsion by Companies Act 2013, MRPL was actively contributed for the development of societal wellbeing through CSR activities. Such as construction of anganavadi building, infrastructure to the schools, equipments to government hospital in the year 2007, 12 lakh worth equipments were donated to government lady goschen hospital in the year 2008. various modern teaching aid has been provided to government schools of Dakshina Kannada, community awareness programme on environmental protection awareness to the Balagramapanchayath and in government school, contributed 50 lakhs to chief minister flood relief fund and in addition to that MRPL employees also contributed their one day salary amounted to Rs. 11.43 lakhs for this purpose, repairing of water dam, provided infrastructure facilities to SC/ST communities in the year 2009. A substantial budget of Rs. 10 crore has been spent during the year 2009-10. construction of class rooms, scholarship to students, construction of community hall etc during the year 2012 and started construction of separate block for lady goschen hospital, which was 162 years old and spent 21 crores for the purpose in the year 2012-13 and more.

By the analysis of various CSR activities conducted by MRPL before the introduction of companies Act 2013,Compulsion by the Companies Act does not resultin CSR activities conducted in MRPL. MRPL has a concern towards societal well being from the beginning of MRPL. More than mandatory they are doing it as a responsibility and care towards society and nation development.

Table showing the five years SwacchBharathactivity list and investment on SwacchBharathAbhiyan

Activities	2014-15 (lakh)	2015-16 (lakh)	2016-17 (lakh)	2017-18 (lakh)	2018-19 (lakh)	total
Construction and maintenance of Toilets and sanitation at different schools and colleges in and around the premises.	21.5	153.62	76.48	532.34	892.38	1651.32

Garden Maintenance at Custom House, Mangalore	3.5					3.5
Installation of napkin vending and destroyer machine at various schools of Dakshinakannada ,yadgiri and raichur district of Karnataka.					442.35	442.35
Smoke free village: under this concept free LPG kit connection is provided at jokkaattevillage,chelairu, soorninje			10.26		12	22.26
Drinking water facility through installation of water purifier to various schools and colleges, neighbouring areas and to Bar associations Badravathi.					118.82	118.82
Financial assistance for SwachMangaluruAbhiyaan by Ramakrishna Mission.		14.00	50.00	264.74	554.07	882.81
Support to MathaAmrithanandamayi Mutt Mangalore.			10.00	7.08	43.09	60.17
CSR activity at JokatteGrama Panchayat-Retention wall.			14.00			14
Construction of Sewage treatment plant foreducational institute at Vivekananda College,Puttur.				57.25		57.25
Beach cleaning in association with Department of Forest, Ecology and Environment				0.59	0.59	1.18
'Swachhatha Hi Sewa' Campaign as per the Ministry Letter, Swachatha Hi Seva - 16/09/2018 to02/10/2018				4.53	17.41	21.94
SwachaSurathkaI- Beautification of SurathkaIFlyoverunderswachaBharath Abhiyaan Program.				5.78	0.66	6.44
Installation of Bio Gas Plant in 29 Hostels in Dakshina Kannada District.				14.82		14.82
SwachhBharathPakhwada Programme as per Ministry directive, SwachaBharathPakhwada -01/07/2018 to 15/07/2018, 16/08/2018 to31/08/2018				11.93	20.22	32.15
SwachaBharathAbhiyaan in Association with VyakthiVikasa Trust (Art of Living)-					48.69	48.69

Distribution of Waste Disposal Machine						
Contribution to SwachathaKosh					200.00	200
Construction of Overhead tank in around refinery					70.80	70.80
Contribution to Karnataka Chief Minister Relief Fund- Rebuilding of Kodagu District					100	100
Restoration and Development of lakes in Dakshina Kannada District					141.60	141.60
Solar project at Schools and colleges.					126.85	126.85

Source: annual report of MRPL.

12. Analysis:

Out of 110.74 crores of CSR budget of 5 years, 40.17 crores has been utilised for Swacch Bharath Abhiyan programmes from past 5 years. It's a remarkable contribution made by MRPL a step towards sustaining cleanliness.

Among the activities are undertaken under Swachh Bharath Abhiyan by MRPL, the following activities are highly appreciated by the Beneficiaries.

- The case study found that, under the concept of CSR, MRPL more focused on Swacch Bharth Abhiyan, through this concept various programmes have been conducted, they have concentrated more on construction of toilets, maintenance of toilets to contribute for the hygiene factor. They contributed more amounts for this purpose. Their intension is to have toilets for each house of backward community and to maintain hygiene in schools and colleges.
- CSR activities has also given importance to women health and hygiene, they have provided napkin vending machine and napkin burner machine to various schools and colleges in rural areas, they invested 442.35 lakh on this purpose.
- Ramakrishna mission Mangaluru is making remarkable activities under Swacch Bharath Abhiyana, MRPL providing financial assistance from past 4 years. Ramakrishna mutt undertakes the cleaning activities every Sunday in different areas of Mangaluru. MRPL spent 881.82 lakh for this purpose in past 4 years. And also assisting to mathaamruthanadamayi mutt regarding Swacch Bharth.
- Swachh Bharath Pawaada and Swachatha hi Sewa is the unique programme by MRPL, according to this concept, one week continuous Swachatha programmes were conducted in different places by creating awareness through street plays, rallies, vanamahostava, beach cleaning, various competitions in schools and colleges relating to cleanliness etc. from past 2 years MRPL is involved in such activities and 54.09 lakh were utilised.
- Under the scheme of smoke free village, free LPG kit were distributed to the backward communities in the rural areas and spent 22.26 lakh on this regard.

- Pure drinking water facilities have been provided in different schools and rural areas and spent 118.82 in this regard.
- It's remarkable to note that all the CSR activities are funded directly to the source and not by agency middleman.
- It's true that after the compulsion by companies Act, the amount spent on CSR activity has been increased, but it is important to note that before the companies act 2013 also MRPL had contributed to the societal wellbeing in crores.

13. Conclusions:

It is apparent that a thorough thinking and wise action on CSR is required to bring back and maintain the overall stability in the social and economic field. Every company owes some obligation for all human, physical and natural resources to community, the nation and the globe in particular. Taking into account long-term growth and sustainable development, the creation and effective implementation of new policies according to the CSR standards, it is inevitable that a balance can be struck among the global business and society.

As for the MRPL, its mission and accountability towards community and the country have been long accomplished. CSR operations are the driving force behind society's sustainable growth. Different welfare operations lead to social welfare. MRPL has dedicated a considerable amount to attaining Mahatma Gandhi's vision of 'clean India' by means of the Swachh Bharath scheme. In almost all the schools and colleges and rural regions around Dakshina kannada District, the MRPL contributes to the preservation of sanitation and sustainable hygiene development and cleanliness MRPL strives for the cleanliness aid.

Reference:

1. Andrews, Kenneth R, The Concept of Corporate Strategy (Homewood, IL: Dow Jones-Irwin, 1971)
2. Wood D. Towards improving social performance, business horizon vol 34 No.4, world business council for sustainable development (1991) pp.66-73
3. Annual report of MRPL for the year 2011-12, 2012-13, 2013-14, 2014-15, 2015-16, 2016-17, 2017-18, 2018-19.
4. Arevalo, J., Castelló, I., de Colle, S., Lenssen, G., Neumann, K. and Zollo, M. (2011), "Introduction to the special issue: integrating sustainability in business models", *Journal of Management Development*, Vol. 30 No. 10, pp. 941-954. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02621711111>
5. Amit Kumar Srivastava, GayatriNegi, Vipul Mishra, ShraddhaPandey(2012) Corporate Social Responsibility: A Case Study Of TATA Group, IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSRJBM) ISSN: 2278-487X Volume 3, Issue 5 (Sep,-Oct. 2012), PP 17-27 www.iosrjournals.org
6. Vishwakarma, D. (2016). Swachhbharatabhiyan clean India abhiyan. *International Research Journal of Management, IT and Social Sciences*, 3(3), 48-52. Retrieved from <https://sloap.org/journals/index.php/irjmis/article/view/353>
7. Jangra B et al.(2016) Swachhbharatabhiyan (clean India mission): SWOT analysis

Int J Community Med Public Health. 2016 Dec;3(12):3285-3290
<http://www.ijcmph.com> p International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health | December 2016 | Vol 3 | Issue 12 Page 3290.

8. Sinha Sanchali, Dr. Panda AbhayaKumar(2018) " Corporate Social Responsibility in India" ZENITH International Journal of Business Economics & Management Research
Volume : 8, Issue : 4,pp 97-106.Online ISSN : 2249-8826.
9. Archie B. Carroll (2016)"Carroll's pyramid of CSR: taking another look"
international journal of corporate social responsibility article 3
10. Archie B. Carrol, The pyramid of Corporate Social Responsibility: Toward the moral management of organizational stakeholders, from Business Horizons, July-August 1991,The Foundation for the School of Business at Indiana University
<http://www.cba.ua.edu/~aturner/MGT341/MGT341%20Readings/Pyramid.pdf>
11. Debbie Haskie- Leventhal, " strategic corporate social responsibility: tools and theories for responsible management" (sage 2018)

Webilography"

[https://www.ongcindia.com/wps/wcm/connect/en/home](https://www ONGCIndia.com/wps/wcm/connect/en/home)

<https://www.mrpl.co.in/csr>

Paper 19

NETFLIX BIGDATA ANALYTICS-A STUDY ON IMPROVING CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE

Srivatsa Maddodi¹ and Krishna Prasad. K.²

¹Research Scholar, College of Computer and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India

²College of Computer and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India

Email: srivatsa.maddodi@gmail.com

Abstract

Netflix is one of the largest online streaming mediaproviders. It began its operations in 1997. Founded by two tech entrepreneur Reed Hastings and Marc Randolph. The Company's head office is in Los Gatos, California. Netflix's initially started selling DVDs or provide them on a rental basis. Over the period with growth of internet users and the decline of DVD sales and rental services, it changed its business model to video on demand. From 2012 onwards, it started producing its original TV-series and movies. Netflix uses bigdata analytics to understand its customer base better. By using these data, they provide better service or product to the customer. Netflix collects huge amounts of data from a vast variety of subscriber base. It collects data such as the location of a user; content watched by the user, user interests, the data searched by the user, and the time at which user watched. Based on these parameters its algorithm gives a personalized recommendation based on the user interest. Netflix has constantly focused on changing business needs they have moved their business model from DVD rental to video on demand and currently producing original shows. In this paper we analyze various business strategies of Netflix. This paper also analyzes how Netflix with the help of bigdata analytics focused on improving the subscriber's experience and how it helped to be more customer-centric and increased its user base.

Keywords: Netflix, Bigdata, Data analytics, Customer experience, Video on demand, Streaming

1. INTRODUCTION

Netflix, Inc was founded by two tech entrepreneur Reed Hastings and Marc Randolph. It began its operations in the year of 1997. The Company's head office is in Los Gatos, California. Netflix's Main business is subscription-based online streaming services of TV Shows, Originals, Movies, etc. Being the largest media service provider, it has over 148 Million members operated across 190 countries except for China, Iran, North Korea, Crimea, and Syria [1]. During the initial days Netflix suffered huge loss but with the raise of internet users and Netflix changed its business model from traditional DVD rental and sales to the introduction of

online video streaming in 2007. Netflix was able to reduce the loss. To make this possible Netflix needed to change their business strategy. Along with the streaming on movies, TV-Shows from another studios Netflix is also producing its own movies and TV-Shows. From 2010 Netflix started its expansion worldwide starting from Canada in 2010 than in Latin American countries in the year 2011 followed by United Kingdom and other European Countries like Denmark, Netherlands, Norway etc. from 2012 till 2015. In the year 2012 Netflix has split its business of DVD rental service as a Separate division from online streaming division. Till 2017 DVD rental division has around 3.3 million customers and Netflix has plans to keep this service for few more years. The biggest challenge currently faced by Netflix are Maintaining the existing subscribers and increasing the new subscriber count, increase in competition by other streaming providers like Hulu, Disney, Warner Media, Amazon, the rise of the cost to produce the original content. To overcome these challenges Netflix uses Bigdata Analytics. Netflix has heavily invested in research on bigdata analytics it spends over \$1 billion for it. As of today, they have a separate division called Netflix Research that mainly concentrates on data analytics areas such as customer experience, recommendations, machine learning, etc. They are heavily invested in Data Sciences and Data Analytics for their recommendation systems. These recommendation systems understand the users and provide recommendation accordingly.

2. OBJECTIVES

Below are the objectives of study

1. To understand about the evolution of business model at Netflix.
2. To understand about the strategies of Netflix and how new strategies are used to overcome challenges faced by competition.
3. To understand how Bigdata analytics is used by Netflix to improve customer satisfaction.
4. Use of SWOT and PESTLE analysis for recommendation of Netflix future strategies.

3. NETFLIX vs. BLOCKBUSTER: Evolution of Business model

Netflix was the main competitor for Blockbuster Inc which is into the business of DVD sales and rental through their physical stores. Blockbuster started in year 1985 was an undisputed leader in the entertainment service business with more than 2800 physical stores. Blockbuster was selling and renting DVD through its stores across worldwide [2]. Netflix came with the unique idea of DVD sales and rental business without physical store. Using the Netflix website from the catalogue one must choose the movies/TV-shows what they want, and Netflix used to send the DVD through postal service. During the early days Netflix started offering DVD on rental basis. Netflix realized that it is spending more per customer than what it was earning through rent of DVD. So, it changed its business model to Subscription method where it was offering DVD rental to its customers who subscribed for a fixed fee. Unlike its rival Blockbuster Netflix was not charging any late fee from the return of the DVD. Since inception Netflix was not profitable and was losing money one of its founder Reed Hastings in the year 2000 approached Blockbuster CEO John Antioco with the offer of Netflix being taken over by Blockbuster for \$50 Million. His idea was Netflix team would manage Blockbuster's Online brand and Blockbuster needs to

promote Netflix in their stores however this deal was rejected by Blockbuster's team [3]. The major challenge the Netflix faced is a very high demand for new and super hit movies, sometimes this resulted in customer being not happy due to movies not been available. To address this Netflix came up with the idea of Netflix recommendation system this resulted in the decrease of 20% for the demand of new releases compared to the traditional DVD rental services like Blockbuster. Both Blockbuster and Netflix competed against each other for the same market, but their business model was different. Blockbuster business model was based on idea that most movie rentals happen based on the impulse decision of user who may want to watch the movie immediately these are new releases or hit movies, so their stores mainly concentrated on that aspect. Netflix business model was based on considering movies as regular entertainment. Instead of pickup like Blockbuster Netflix delivered the movies through postal service. Customer ability to keep the movies for longer time and convenience to return through postal service attracted more customers to Netflix. Blockbuster was very late to adapt changes and by the time when they realized the threat from Netflix and planned to launch similar model as of Netflix in the year 2004. But due to change in management the idea did not materialize, and they continued their older business model. Finally, the company went bankrupt and closed its operations in 2013.

4. BIGDATA ANALYTICS at NETFLIX:

Netflix was one of the early adapters of Bigdata Analytics in the year 2006 Netflix came up with a challenge that would award \$1 Million to anyone who would improve their existing recommendation system by 10% [4]. The challenge was to develop an algorithm to predict the subscriber movie preference based on the older data. The prize was awarded to BellKor's Pragmatic Chaos team which consisted of Mathematician, data scientist and engineers from different countries [5]. Netflix uses Data Science and Bigdata Analytics in their recommendation systems. In late 1990's, the term recommender system was introduced for the first time in literature of information system [6]. The interest in recommendation system remains as it is widely applicable to solve the practical problems of many companies. Many companies like Amazon, Microsoft etc. have a commercial recommendation system [7-8].

4.1 Netflix Recommendation System: It recommends the subscribers various choices based on their interests. Recommendation systems use Machine learning. It takes inputs from user and recommends appropriately. In Netflix recommendation system collects user data such as the location of a user; content watched by the user, user interests, the data searched by the user, and the time at which user watched. Based on these parameters its algorithm gives a personalized recommendation based on the subscriber's interest. Mostly recommendation systems take user profile as an important parameter. Subscriber profile consists of different types of information such as interest of a subscriber, history of subscriber search query, interaction with system etc. Whenever a new subscriber account is created, or a new profile is added to existing account Netflix will ask the subscriber to choose few genre or titles which can be used as initial parameters for recommendation system. If the subscriber skips this step, then Netflix will populate the user homepage with the popular set of contents. Once the user starts watching the

content then this will super cede any initial preferences provided by subscriber. As the subscriber continues to watch.The content which was watched previously will be used to provide the recommendation further [9-10].

There are two types of recommendation system [11]

1. Content-based
2. Collaborative filtering

Content-based filtering:This type of recommendation system takes the customer information [12]. Suppose a subscriber has watched aComedy movie on Netflix as described in Fig.1. This recommendation system suggests similar action movies to the subscriber.

Collaborative filtering: This kind of recommendation system is based on similar profiles of users [13]. For instance, if a subscriber A watches crime, action, horror movies and subscriber B watches crime, action, comedy movies then subscriber A will like to watch comedy movies and subscriber B will like to watch horror movies. Please refer Fig.1.

Netflix uses Hybrid recommendation system that is the combination of content and collaborative recommendation system.

Fig.1: Recommendation Techniques

5. ANALYSIS:

Both SWOT and PESTLE analysis are performed as per the guidelines mentioned in Company analysis case study [14-20]

Company Background [21]

Company: Netflix

CEO: Reed Hastings

Year founded: 1997

Headquarter: Los Gatos, USA

Number of Employees (2018): 5,500

Public or Private: Public

Ticker Symbol: NFLX

Market Cap (Feb 2019): \$155.81 Billion

Annual Revenue (2018): \$15.79 Billion

Profit |Net income (2018): \$1.21 Billion

Products & Services: Video on demand, online streaming

Competitors: Hulu | Disney+ | HBO| Warner Media | Amazon |

SWOT Analysis:

Strengths:

- Established Brand Name
- Global Customer Base: Netflix is serving over 190 countries worldwide.
- Technology: Netflix is ready to embrace changes rapidly it is one of the early adapters of bigdata analytics and data science.
- Original Content: Netflix is in production of original content and the quality of the content which Netflix produces are liked by many viewers.

Weakness:

- Huge Debt: The production of original content involves huge costs this results in debts.
- Limited Copyrights: For many of shows or movies Netflix has taken rights from other studios. It is becoming difficult to manage the content library as the rights taken from other studios expire and the content will be taken off from Netflix.

Opportunities:

- Expansion into other countries including China.
- Partnership in Europe to meet European laws.
- Alliances: It can partner with various service providers to provide bundle packages at discounted price.
- Potential to earn revenue by other means like advertisements.

Threats:

- Increased Competition: Other Providers like Hulu, HBO, Amazon, Disney and Warner Media are entered or entering the online streaming service.
- Piracy: It is the biggest threat many users download the content by illegal means.
- Increasing the Subscription price lead to subscribers switch to other providers.
- Sharing of Single Subscription between multiple users.

PESTLE Analysis:

Political:

- Due to European regulations Netflix belonged to same category as television distributors. Netflix needs to follow the European rule that 30% of the content needs to be European.
- Due to restrictions of US on some countries like Crimea, North Korea Netflix cannot expand to those countries.
- Due to permission issue by Chinese government Netflix could not expand its business to china.

Economical:

- Change of exchange rates impacts the revenue of Netflix.
- Competitive pricing.

Socio-Cultural

- Many Customers are moving to watch content through their smartphone.
- Netflix is known for charity work like providing scholarships.

Technological:

- Improving quality of streaming with less data consumption to support 4K content efficiently.
- A new software called 'Hermes' is developed by Netflix Research which automatically grades a translation. With the use of this Netflix will be able to serve the faster and good quality translation of shows to different countries.

Legal:

- Due to copyright laws Netflix has introduced blockers that will block the users accessing the contents from other countries this will affect the user base.
- They need to handle the video piracy affectively.

Environmental:

- Netflix needs to work more towards using of renewable energy and reduce the carbon footprint of its data centers.

6. SUGGESTION

Based on the SWOT and PESTLE analysis below are few recommendations

- Netflix to continue its use on Data analytics and Data Science to improve the customer experience.
- It is recommended to reduce the subscription cost as similar as its competitor for developing countries like India.
- Explore other territories for expansion.
- Produce more original content region specific.
- Use of advanced authentication techniques like finger print or facial recognition [22-25] or Multi factor authentication [26-27] for subscriber authentication.

7. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have discussed regarding business model of Netflix comparing it with the business model of Blockbuster Inc and how Netflix was able to beat its competitor to become leading online streaming service provider. We have also discussed about the different kinds of recommendation system and the type of recommendation system used by Netflix. We discussed about the Netflix prize competition and how the winning team algorithm made the existing algorithm of Netflix more accurate. Also, we have analyzed how with Bigdata Analytics is used for its recommendation system to improve the customer experience. Based on the SWOT and PESTLE analysis we have provided few recommendations to Netflix to improve their business strategy.

REFERENCES

- [1] Netflix, Wikipedia, Accessed: 09-Aug-2019, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Netflix>
- [2] Blockbuster, Wikipedia, Accessed: 09-Aug-2019, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Blockbuster_LLC
- [3] Davis, Todd and Higgins, John, "A Blockbuster Failure: How an Outdated Business Model Destroyed a Giant" (2013). Chapter 11 Bankruptcy Case Studies. http://trace.tennessee.edu/utk_studlawbankruptcy/1
- [4] R.M. Bell and Y. Koren. Lessons from the netflix prize challenge. ACM SIGKDD Explorations Newsletter, 9(2):75–79, 2007.
- [5] Data Science at Netflix- A Must Read Case Study for Aspiring Data Scientists, Accessed: 09-Aug-2019, <https://data-flair.training/blogs/data-science-at-netflix/>
- [6] Resnick P, Varian H (1997). Recommender systems. Commun.ACM30(3):56-58
- [7] Linden G, Smith B, York J (2003). Amazon.com Recommendations: Item-to-Item Collaborative Filtering. Published by the IEEE Computer Society, IEEE Internet Comput. 7(1):76-80.
- [8] Shani G, Gunawardana A (2011). Evaluating Recommendation Systems. Springer pp.257-298
- [9] How Netflix Recommendation System Works, Accessed: 09-Aug-2019, <https://help.netflix.com/en/node/100639>
- [10] Carlos A. Gomez-Uribe and Neil Hunt. 2015. The Netflix recommender system: Algorithms, business value, and innovation. ACM Trans. Manage. Inf. Syst. 6, 4, Article 13 (December 2015), 19 pages. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/2843948>
- [11] Adomavicius G, Tuzhilin A (2005). Toward the Next Generation of Recommender Systems: A Survey of the State-of-the-Art and Possible Extensions. IEEE Trans. Knowl. Data Eng. 17(6):734-749.
- [12] Pazzani M.J., Billsus D. (2007) Content-Based Recommendation Systems. In: Brusilovsky P., Kobsa A., Nejdl W. (eds) The Adaptive Web. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 4321. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg
- [13] Balabanovic, M., Shoham Y.: FAB: Content-based, Collaborative Recommendation. Communications of the Association for Computing Machinery 40(3) (1997) 66-72

- [14] Aithal, P. S. (2017). Industry Analysis – The First Step in Business Management Scholarly Research. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 2(1), 1-13. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.810347>.
- [15] Aithal, P. S. and Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2015). Applying SWOC Analysis to an Institution of Higher Education. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, 5(7), 231-247. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.163425>.
- [16] Aithal, P. S. (2017). An Effective Method of Developing Business Case Studies Based on Company Analysis. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME)*, 2(1), 16-27. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.400579>.
- [17] Aithal, P. S., (2017). ABCD Analysis as Research Methodology in Company Case Studies. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 2(2), 40-54. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.891621>.
- [18] Aithal P. S. (2017). Impact of Domestic, Foreign, and Global Environments on International Business Decisions of Multinational Firms: A Systematic Study. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 2(2), 57-73. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1067103>.
- [19] Aithal, P. S., (2017). Company Analysis – The Beginning Step for Scholarly Research. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 1(1), 1-18. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.573769>.
- [20] Aithal, P. S. and Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2015). Applying SWOC Analysis to an Institution of Higher Education. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, 5(7), 231-247. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.163425>.
- [21] Netflix Annual SEC Report (2019), Accessed: 09-Aug-2019, <https://www.netflixinvestor.com/financials/sec-filings/default.aspx>
- [22] Krishna Prasad, K., Aithal, P. S. (2017). A Conceptual Study on Image Enhancement Techniques for Fingerprint Images. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 1(1), 63-72. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.831678>.
- [23] Krishna Prasad, K. and Aithal, P. S. (2017). A Conceptual Study on User Identification and Verification Process Using Face Recognition Techniques. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, (ISSN Applied), 1(1), 6-17. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.810343>.
- [24] Krishna Prasad, K. & Aithal, P.S. (2017). Fingerprint Image Segmentation: A Review of State of the Art Techniques. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 2(2), 28-39. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.848191>.
- [25] Krishna Prasad, K. & Aithal, P.S. (2017). A Study on Fingerprint Hash Code Generation using Euclidean Distance for Identifying a User. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 2(2), 116-126. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1133545>.
- [26] Krishna Prasad, K. & Aithal, P.S. (2018). A Comparative Study on Fingerprint Hash Code, OTP, and Password based Multifactor Authentication Model with an Ideal System and Existing Systems. *International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research*, 3(1), 18-32. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1149587>.

[27] Krishna Prasad, K. & Aithal, P. S. (2018). A Study on Multifactor Authentication Model Using Fingerprint Hash Code, Password and OTP. International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology, 3(1), 1-11. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1135255>.

Paper 20

PRODUCTION CULTURE IN MICRO AND SMALL INDUSTRIES AND THE USE OF COMPUTER-ASSISTED KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT IN MANUFACTURING PROCESSESSathyaprakash A^{1,2,a}, Shrinivasa Mayya D^{3,4, b}¹Research scholar, ²Department of ME, Srinivas Institute of Technology Mangaluru³Research Guide, ⁴Principal, Srinivas Institute of Technology Mangaluru^asathya2148@gmail.com, ^bsri_mayya@yahoo.com**Abstract:**

This article outlined the culture of manufacturing in micro and small sectors. Knowing the answers from the manufacturing culture gathered from 20 manufacturing sectors through study with 87 questionnaires. With the assistance of Agile manufacturing enablers, all the questionnaires prepared. The sample companies are customer-based manufacturers of identical products with distinct shapes and sizes. It has been observed from the study that micro-and small-scale sectors do not work with a single production methodology and no strategic method has been adopted. Most sectors face skilled labor shortages and market requirements shift. The main reason for this issue is bad data storage and reuse and bad adoption / non-adoption of the method of knowledge management in micro and small sectors.

Keywords: Agile Manufacturing, Data storage, Knowledge management**1. INTRODUCTION**

The type of production and knowledge management back bone for its achievement in any of the sectors. When industrialization began, the manufacturing process began with craft manufacturing and when the industry became a big manufacturing process was moved to mass production scheme for craft manufacturing. However, mass production method provides a solution to satisfy big amounts but not quality. There, mass production system moved to lean manufacturing system for Japanese people to satisfy both the quality and low price by changing mass production system. However, this Lean production system is not good enough to satisfy the present vibrant market. Now the market for a day is completely dynamic in nature and this requires more and more item of variety as per client requirement. Lean or mass manufacturing is hard to meet the vibrant market requirements. There is a need to create one of the kind agile production systems[1] to react with quality product as soon as possible.

The manufacturing sectors are classified into three kinds based on employee numbers and

ceiling limits.

- Large scale
- Medium scale
- Small and micro scale

Here, the application of mass production, lean manufacturing and agile manufacturing[1] is quite simple for big and medium-sized sectors due to greater ceiling limits, which means that big and medium-sized companies can deal with vibrant markets by altering their production culture. But the vibrant market for micro and small-scale sectors is hard to deal with due to restricted resource and ceiling.

The research focused on small-scale and micro-industry production culture and how comparable to agile manufacturing ? The way of using technology, individuals, and organizational structure is crucial because it is the agile manufacturing's three main pillar. 2,3,4].

From the literature it is noted that, most of the small scale industries are used different type of tools/ philosophies to improve sustainability of the industries. There is no clarity about the manufacturing process in the industry and which manufacturing culturing is using, that is not sufficient for dynamic market. The manufacturing culture followed by the industries not mass production system or lean production system or flexible manufacturing system [5].

One manufacturing system was not followed by most sectors. It is quite hard to achieve dynamic client requirements with the present production system. Also, when the client requirement changes during the day, this leads to industry failure.

All small and micro-scale companies should change their present traditional manufacturing culture to one of the kind or agile manufacturing is essential to create profit in this vibrant requirement market situation. The way the techniques are integrated and used in the present production scheme is inappropriate [6,7,8]. It is most essential to follow the systematic manner in the manufacturing process in order to satisfy client requirements. In order to reach the market early, the sector should have adequate back-up data on the product and process, process standardization and concept of method and product development, it should reach all the company's staff with a minimum of time. Knowledge management is one of the most promising tools for small and micro-scale sectors to achieve their objective and market sustainability.[8,9] Computer and IT system application is crucial for effective knowledge management processes[10,11].

2. METHODOLOGY

In this research to know the production culture in small and micro industries, questionnaires were originally prepared based on agile enablers in manufacturing [1]. On the basis of technology, organisation and individuals, around 87 questions were prepared. Personal interview was discovered for all the responses to the questionnaires. Specifically, chosen manufacturing companies are ordered for this research to define manufacturing culture and industry agility. The gathered responses were transmitted to excel file after interviewing and that excel file was uploaded to Chronbach's SPSS statistical analysis instrument, the alpha questionnaire reliability check.

Figure1. Methodology

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Chronbach’s alpha reliability test

In this research a total of 87 questionnaires were used in small and micro-scale sectors to define manufacturing culture. All information including issues and responses uploaded to the SPSS statistical analysis instrument to verify the accuracy of questionnaires after completing the study of 20 sectors. The most common alpha method used by Chronbach was acquired from assessment to understand reliability and satisfactory outcome 0.836. Table 1 demonstrates the alpha outcomes of the Chronbach.

Table .1 Reliability statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.836	.877	86

Type of industries

Figure.2 Type of industries

The research is a manufacturer of identical products with distinct shapes and sizes based on client requirements for 20 small / micro sample companies. The private interview undertaken at managerial level and information uploaded to Google forms throughout this research. It took approximately 2-3 hours to finish the assignment. Fourteen small and six micro industries are taken as a sample in this study. For survey Likart scale is used 1- very low

- 2- low
- 3- medium/moderate
- 4- high
- 5- very high

Hierarchy in organization

Figure.3 Hierarchy in organization

In organisation, hierarchy is growing from flat to distinct levels. It is noted from the study that 75% of small and micro-scale sectors have no hierarchy in their organizational structure. Most sectors are running flat organizations. It implies that individuals with greater power also involve themselves in the process of manufacturing. But in the production or manufacturing process, people who are higher in authority can not be there in all the moment.

Organization structure

Figure.4 Organization structure

Of the 20 industries, the 10 industries have a moderate-level systematic organizational structure, 4 industries are good, followed by only one very good organizational structure. The five sectors have poor structure of organisation. Making organisation more and more effective is the appropriate arrangement of equipment, individuals and equipment.

Level of formal communication

Figure.5 Level of formal communication

The official communication scheme for sustainability is the backbone of any sector. By study, 17 sectors follow very bad formal communication and this type of communication is literally casual communication. Informal communication is cost-effective and helpful in fast coverage, but informal communication will not assist for long-term sustainability. For this it is necessary to have official communication with information recording scheme.

Level of employee transfer

Figure.6 Employee transferability

Worker transfer rate for other jobs in sector is nearly 60%. Transfer and communication process of employees in interconnected activity. The method of transferring employees or rotating jobs is a good practice of creating multi-skill workers. But while the employee should be updated for each employee whenever associated information / knowledge is transferred, this may improve the manufacturing lead time.

Level of group decision making

Figure.7 Level of group decision making

The study demonstrates that around 50% of sectors are very poor in group decision-making processes and 25% in mild stage and only 25% of sectors are prepared to adopt group decision-making. The habit of group decision making is interlinked with the transfer of employees and the management of information.

Achievement of productivity

Figure.8 Achievement of productivity

In order to enhance productivity, approximately 55 percent of sectors are not given any significance to information sharing culture. Only when using the method of knowledge management can any industry enhance its productivity.

Level of willingness to share knowledge

Figure.9 Level of willingness to share knowledge

According to study, 30 percent of staff in sectors are prepared to share their understanding at a moderate level and about 60 percent of staff are prepared to share knowledge above a mild level and only 10 percent are prepared to share expertise in sectors. The desire does not imply sharing the worker's understanding.

Level of infrastructure to promote knowledge share

Figure.10 Level of infrastructure to promote knowledge share

Every sector must provide the right infrastructure for information sharing. If the sharing of knowledge is done informally, it is considered a waste of time and resources. Once a skilled worker leaves his job then it is very difficult to train a fresh employee. Data and information stored in this moment will help to train the employee as soon as possible. It is noted that 95% of sectors do not provide any facilities for information sharing within the organisation.

Level of formal communication

Figure. 11. Level of formal communication

For efficient knowledge management sectors, formal communication must be followed and any process of knowledge sharing should be registered and stored. By doing so, the same can be achieved for training freshly joined staff.

Level of maintenance of previous data

Figure.12. Level of maintenance of previous data

The old / previous information or designs help us most in the manufacture of identical products with distinct shapes and sizes depending on client requirements to reach the market very soon or to respond quickly to client requirements.

Knowledge transfer through wall poster

Figure.13. Knowledge transfer through wall poster

S

ufficient product-related data should be given for workspace. Information about the item makes it simple to do work in the manufacturing house. Survey claims no industry posts any data linked to the product in walls. This again leads to the manufacturing process being slowed down.

Level of knowledge transfer through hand book

Figure.14 Level of knowledge transfer through hand book

Providing adequate handbooks with identical product information facilitates job when staff receive the same item of distinct sizes each day. It's very hard to remember the distinct size aspect.

Level of Knowledge transfer through training

Figure.15 Level of Knowledge transfer through training

The worker knowledge can enhance by giving proper training to update their skills. Around 80% of industries are not organizing any training program for their employees. This may leads down skilling of the employees year by year.

Level of technology used

Figure. 16 Level of technology used

Worker knowledge can be enhanced to update their abilities by providing adequate training. Approximately 80 percent of sectors do not organize their workers ' training programmes. This can lead to the workers ' skills down year after year.

Data storage

Figure.17 Data storage

In the future manufacturing phase, data storage enables a lot. But 80-90% of the sectors do not store any information or full manufacturing process information. This type of habit makes the manufacturing process work double. If any comparable information are accessible then the information can be modified and reused with minimal price for fresh manufacturing method. Use of computer

Figure.18 Use of computer

It is essential to use computers in manufacturing processes efficiently and cost-effectively. The computer assists in multiple ways in the manufacturing process. Production details, design, modeling, and other work information can be stored in a computer and computer-based preparation. When repeated order is obtained, this type of work behavior decreases a lot of job burden. But study shows that about 90% of sectors do not use computer technology in

manufacturing processes. This leads to the vibrant market failing to respond rapidly.

Reuse of data

Figure.19 Reuse of data

Reuse of product information facilitates the process of product growth. That only 20 percent of sectors that reuse prior information in the manufacturing process are noted from study. Thirty-five percent of sectors partly affected by information reuse. 45 percent of the remaining sectors do not reuse any information. This leads to industry failure when they produce the same item of distinct sizes.

Repeated Order

Figure.20 Level of repeated order

Approximately 45 percent of sectors are in repeated order, and 45 percent of sectors are in in

moderate order. Only 10 percent of sectors do not receive repeated order or very minimal order. This statistics suggests that a decent number of repeated orders are being received by most sectors.

Level of constant updating knowledge

Figure 21. Level of constant updating knowledge

The competitive company climate of today is very vibrant. The market is a sort driven by the client. The item should be manufactured in accordance with their requirement supplier and the lead time should also be much less. The product should be reached with the customer within a short period of time. In this situation, it is very critical to constantly update employee understanding. If employees are not great in the generation of ideas and poor in understanding of job then the reason for bad results will be. Only 15 percent of sectors confronting this competitive climate by updating understanding, 40 percent of sectors partly doing this, and about 45 percent of sectors have failed to do so.

Level of skilled labor problem

Figure.22 Level of skilled labour problem

Small-scale industries real issue is skilled labor. The issue of qualified labor is faced by 100% of sectors at distinct rates. The moderate level of the 40 percent of sectors facing labor problem, the high level of 40 percent and the very low level of 20 percent..

4. CONCLUSIONS

It is observed from the literature and survey of 20 manufacturing sectors that no small or micro-scale companies follow the same manufacturing technology and most companies are still following old traditional manufacturing culture and there is no integration between people technology and organisation. Each of these will play its part separately, and due to fewer individuals, most sectors will have a flat organizational framework. Because of bad faith in new technology and absence of understanding, the sectors were unable to take benefit of the flat organization structure. There is no adequate median / methodology for transferring understanding between the employee and management, resulting in industry failure or reduced effectiveness. There is plenty of scope for knowledge management application to effectively and efficiently integrate technology individuals and organisation. Those industries are still running with order technology they should follow knowledge management tool to improve agility with the help of computer system. By doing so, agility can be achieved. To gain agility or quick response to the dynamic market equal importance should given to people, technology and organization structure.

REFERENCES

1. Kidd, Paul T, Agile manufacturing : forging new frontiers
2. Darshak A. Desai "Improving customer delivery commitments the Six Sigma way: case study of an Indian small scale industry", International Journal of Six Sigma and Competitive Advantage >Volume 2, Issue 1 DOI: 10.1504/IJSSCA (2006).

3. Sonali Deraniyagala “The Impact of Technology Accumulation on Technical Efficiency: An Analysis of the Sri Lankan Clothing and Agricultural Machinery Industries”, journal of oxford development studies, (101- 114), (2010)
4. Ludovico Alcorta, “Technical and Organizational Change and Economies of Scale and Scope in Developing Countries”, journal of oxford development studies, 29(1), (77-100), (2001)
5. G.S. Dangayach, S.G. Deshmukh “Advanced manufacturing technology implementation:” 16(5),(483-496), (2005)
6. Parijat Upadhyay, Saeed Jahanyan, Pranab K. Dan “Factors influencing ERP implementation in Indian manufacturing organisations”, Journal of Enterprise Information Management, 24(2), (130-145), (2011)
7. H.B. Marri, A. Gunasekaran, R.A. Sohag, “Implementation of advanced manufacturing technology in Pakistani small and medium enterprises” Journal of Enterprise Information Management, 20(6), (726-739), (2007)
8. Maryam S. Mirian, Leila Beig, and Mahmood Kharrat, “A Unified Architecture to Establish Knowledge Network”, proceedings of the International Symposium on telecommunication, Iran, IEEE press.
9. Neeta Baporikar, “Knowledge Management in Small and Medium Enterprises”, DOI: 10.4018/978-1-4666- 7332-8.ch001
10. Kitimaporn Choochote, “An Analysis of Knowledge Management Process for SMEs in Developing Countries: A Case Study of SMEs in India and Thailand”, International Journal of Information and Education Technology, (2/3), (239-242), (2012)
11. Kuan Yew Wong and Elaine Aspinwall "Characterizing knowledge management in the small business environment", Journal of Knowledge Management, (8/3), (44-6), (2004)

Paper 21

**CONTENT DELIVERY NETWORK'S PIONEERING
LEADER- A CASE STUDY ON AKAMAI
TECHNOLOGIES INC.**

Yogish Pai U¹, Krishna Prasad K²

¹Research Scholar, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

²College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

Email: yogish77pai@gmail.com

Abstract

Akamai Technologies, Inc. a content delivery network company founded by Dr. Leighton and Mr. Lewin on August 20, 1998. Akamai's headquarter is situated in Cambridge city of Massachusetts state in the United States. In 20 years of inception Akamai has grown as a pioneering leader in CDN field and also started providing solutions pertaining to Web Performance, Media Delivery, Network Operator and Security field. Applications, Software and Content Delivery over the internet, enterprise professional services etc. are some of the services rendered by Akamai Technologies. The cause for inception of Akamai Technologies was from an academic research that hatched the algorithms which could route and reproduce web content intelligently over the distributed server network. With Dr. Leighton and Mr. Lewin, Randall Kaplan and Jonathan Seelig teamed up to incorporate Akamai. Dr. Leighton was serving as a head of the Algorithms Group of Computer Science Laboratory at MIT. The content delivery network of Akamai is one among the few biggest distributed computing platforms in the world. Akamai CDN serves 15-30% of all Internet traffic. The business runs a global networked servers and resources on these servers are rented to clients who are looking for significant improvement in the performance of their website. Performance gain will be achieved by distributing user's web content from nearby places. Akamai has a worldwide presence with around 7,500+ staff with annual revenue of \$2.7 billion. As of July 31, 2019, the Company has deployed globally-spread content delivery network (CDN) comprising of 2,39,000 servers approximately in almost 139 countries and closely 1,600 networks all around the world. Akamai ranked number 1 in the 2019 Boston Business Journal for the second year in a row as the Massachusetts Largest Cyber Security Company. The goal of Akamai is to ensure faster Internet experience without compromising security and reliability. In this paper, we analyze Akamai Technologies business and operational strategies along with services and products strategy, new product development strategies sustainability strategy and CSR strategy. Some recommendations are also provided based on the SWOC analysis to accelerate sustainable development.

Keywords: Akamai, Case study, CDN, Content Delivery Network, Performance and Security Solutions.

1. INTRODUCTION :

End to end reliability or performance is not assured in the world of Internet [1]. Internet communications, on the other hand, are always susceptible to a number of obstructions that badly influence efficiency, including high latency, packet drops and network outages [2]. The two common challenges faced by internet users are congestion issues in the Internet infrastructure and the high latency resulting in slow browsing. Tim Berners-Lee World Wide Web inventor had foreseen this challenge that would impact Internet customers two decades ago and challenged his colleagues who were working in the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) to devise a totally fresh and effective way of providing contents over Internet. Dr. Tom Leighton recognized that applied mathematics and algorithms could find a solution to Internet congestion, and in early 1995 he assembled a team of scientists to address the issue. Danny Lewin went to work with Dr. Leighton at the MIT in the fall of 1996. Together with the fellow scientists, Dr. Leighton and Mr. Lewin developed the algorithms which could route and reproduce web content intelligently over the large distributed server network. Dr. Leighton and Mr. Lewin began to determine whether their technology could be used commercially in 1997, resulting in the birth of Akamai Technologies on August 20, 1998[3]. Content Delivery Networks have been designed to enhance the efficiency of static content internet pages. The evolution of CDN technology resulted in delivering the big videos, dynamic websites, online games and apps to distinct device kinds [4]. Today Akamai Technologies provides internet content, applications and software, mobile and security solutions, IoT Edge Cloud as well as professional business services. The content delivery network of Akamai is one among the few biggest distributed computing platforms in the world. Akamai CDN serves 15-30% of all Internet traffic. The business runs a global networked servers and resources on these servers are rented to clients who are looking for significant improvement in the performance of their website. Performance gain will be achieved by distributing user's web content from nearby places [5]. Akamai has a worldwide presence with around 7,500+ staff with an annual revenue of \$2.7 billion. As of July 31, 2019, the Company has deployed globally-spread content delivery network (CDN) comprising of 2,39,000 servers approximately in almost 139 countries and closely 1,600 networks all around the world.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY :

In this paper, we analyze Akamai Technologies business and operational strategies along with services and products strategy, new product development strategies, sustainability strategy and CSR strategy [6-8]. Some recommendations are also provided based on the SWOC analysis to accelerate sustainable development.

3. METHODOLOGY :

An attempt has been made in this research paper to carry out research on the basis of secondary data from publications, journals, conference proceedings, Company websites, Research network websites, Focus group discussions, Various Analysis Frameworks like SWOC Analysis, Competitive Analysis, Financial Analysis, the Internet articles, prior research paper focusing on the multiple elements of the operations of products and services.

4. SOLUTIONS AND SERVICES :

Akamai Technologies is a Content Delivery Network (CDN) and cloud service provider based in Cambridge, Massachusetts, USA, providing internet content, applications and software, mobile and security solutions, as well as professional business services. Akamai’s application delivery networks can accelerate whole web based applications, Media distribution networks providing live and on-demand media of high quality, and Edge Computing networks facilitate distributed deployment of network-enabled applications.

The solutions offered by the company include,

- Akamai Security Solutions

Akamai Security Solutions provide the scale to deter the massive Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) and web application attacks without decreasing efficiency, as well as information on the recent threats and knowledge to adapt to changing tactics and attack vectors.

- Akamai Web Performance Solutions

Akamai Web Performance Solutions offers high speed personalized web experiences, allowing customers to improve possibilities for income, gain agility in IT and scale worldwide.

- Akamai Media Delivery Solutions

Akamai Media Delivery Solutions enables to engage audiences worldwide by delivering content such as high- definition video content, software updates, games, social media, news, etc. to the highest quality wherever and whenever consumers want — without building expensive infrastructure — to scale up the development and complexity of distinct kinds of connected devices.

- Akamai Network Operator Solutions

Akamai's network operator solution allows new clients and business services to optimize internet traffic and price control [9].

- Akamai Professional Services

Akamai Internet specialists around the world with over ten years of professional expertise providing world-class support, problem solving and customized service – ensuring optimized internet achievement for all their clients.

Akamai Solutions are listed in the Table1 below,

Table1:Akamai Solutions

Akamai Solutions	Description
Ion	Automated Intelligent performance enhancer improves user experience on both system and mobile devices.
Dynamic Site Accelerator	It speeds and secures interactive websites by using real-time network optimizations and sophisticated caching methods.

IP Application Accelerator (IPA)	Speed up IP based apps to global enterprise customers to guarantee maximum efficiency, accessibility, and cost reduction.
China CDN	Extends the global presence of Akamai to capitalize on the unprecedented development of Chinese internet users.
Fast DNS	Cloud-based DNS to improve efficiency, accessibility and resilience DDoS attack
Image Manager	Increase the involvement of customers with lovely, quick digital experiences.
Cloudlets	Use controls and capacities to expand investment with Akamai to simplify internet activities and enhance user experience
Global Load Balancing Traffic Management	As name indicates it balances load across cloud and multiple data centers settings.
Identity Cloud	Build unified, data-rich client profiles — extremely safe and meets compliance requirements — while providing strong perspectives to assist deliver personalized client experiences.
mPulse	Bring stakeholders from business and IT into line with important market initiatives, priorities and measurements
DataStream	Smart insight into the efficiency of the CDN
CloudTest	Tool to perform stress test on web applications and mobile applications to ensure that apps work as per the requirement under high load condition.
API Gateway	Increase scalability and efficiency of API management by unloading to the edge
OTA Updates	Secure, over - the-air updates on worldwide scale of connected cars and IoT devices.
IoT Edge Connect	IoT information collection and application messaging in real-time, with scale safety.
Kona Site Defender	Extensive use of the Web and API
Web Application Protector	Simple tool to protect websites against assaults by Distributed Denial of Service and web applications threats.
Client Reputation	Additional defense layer for Kona Site Defender based on latest customer behavior
Enterprise Application Access	Complete user activity audit and reporting
Enterprise Threat Protector	Proactively mitigates threats from zero day malwares.
Prolexic Routed	Fastest DDoS Terabit Scale Attack mitigation

Zero Trust Security	Users, devices, apps and information move out of the company premises and control area
Fast DNS	DNS service hosted on Cloudforenhanced performance, endurance against Distributed Denial of Service attacks.
Kona DDoS Defender	Managed Distributed Denial of Service security service for web applications and important websites
Site Shield	Defend the origin of websites and internet infrastructure by cloaking
DNS Security and Services	The mapping system uses DNS to ensure fast and high quality Internet content delivery
API Capabilities	API-specific skills for efficiency, scale, unload and reliability
Bot Manager	Stops the most advanced bots
Scalable Cloud Security	Facilitates consistent and error free watching experience with secure data, applications and websites.
Identity Cloud	Mission-critical client identity and access management to provide the end user with trusted digital experiences
SPS Secure Business	Value-added service to subscribers that deters security threats and enables them to filter inappropriate content in their workplace.
SPS Secure Consumer	Value-added service to households that protects them from web threats such as phishing and malware and enables them to customize their internet access to suit their preferences and values.
SPS ThreatAvert	An automated defenses against threats like bots and DNS-based DDoS
SPS Reach	Use in-browser messages to communicate with subscribers and to advise them while they are involved online.
SPS Secure Public Wi-Fi	Deliver cyberthreat protections and support Acceptable Use Policies for small and midsize businesses that offer guest or public Wi-Fi
DNSi CacheServe and AnswerX	Implement feature-rich DNS resolvers that enhance network responsiveness, handle unwanted traffic, and allow premium home and business services.
DNSi Big Data Connector	Integrates security data and live streamed DNS data into open big data platforms to enable reporting and analytics for operations, forensics, and management teams
DNSi AuthServe	Enable high-performance, always-on-name services on a huge scale to guarantee visibility of internet, video, VOIP and other apps on the Internet for everyone

Aura Licensed CDN	Operator CDN Software Licensed Suite Enables IP video services, improves QoE and lowers network expenses
Licensed Multicast Solution	Reduces network expenses by normalizing traffic volumes for live simulcasts during peak demand.
Aura Managed CDN	Managed Operator CDN suite facilitates to deploy an extremely scalable, turnkey CDN.
Aura Object Store	Use a extremely scalable, persistent media content store to originate CDN content
Akamai Network Partnerships	Work with Akamai to provide subscribers with superior quality of service

5. FINANCIALS :

Akamai's capacity to attract recurring income commitment for their web-performance and security solutions, boost media related traffic on their network and build fresh products are some of the important factors that affect the economic success of Akamai. Akamai's ability to attract recurring income commitments for its web-based performance and security solutions, boost media traffic on its network, and create new solutions and products are some of the key variables affecting Akamai's financial success. For most of Akamai's products, their clients are dedicated to minimum one-year contracts that enable them to have a consistent and stable basic income level [10]. As per the financial reports issued for the first quarter of 2019, Akamai generated a revenue of \$707 million, an improvement of 6 percent over the Q1 of 2018 was \$669 million.

The Table2– Akamai Financial Data, presents financial details from 2014 to 2018.

Table 2:Akamai Financial details

Financial Year till 31 December	2018	2017	2016	2015	2014
Income	\$2,714,474	\$2,489,035	\$2,347,988	\$2,197,448	\$1,963,874
Capital and Revenue Expenses	2,351,975	2,174,746	1,881,478	1,731,298	1,474,355
Revenue from business	362,499	314,289	466,510	466,150	489,519
Profit	298,373	222,766	320,727	321,406	333,948
Profit attributable per share	1.78	1.30	1.83	1.80	1.87
Profit attributable per diluted share	1.76	1.29	1.82	1.78	1.84
Liquid assets	2,101,171	1,279,528	1,616,329	1,524,235	1,628,284
Total Assets	5,461,770	4,648,916	4,432,190	4,181,684	4,001,546
Convertible senior notes - Due 2019	686,552	662,913	640,087	624,288	604,851
Convertible senior notes - Due 2025	874,080	-	-	-	-
Long term Debt	185,121	166,840	156,329	110,319	117,349

Shareholders fund	3,191,860	3,362,469	3,270,218	3,120,848	2,945,335
-------------------	-----------	-----------	-----------	-----------	-----------

Various acquisitions took place over the years described in the chart above. The outcomes of which are provided from the date of acquisition prospectively. The comparability of the consolidated economic information described above may be affected by these purchases.

Media and Carrier recorded \$330 million revenue which is growth of 5% year after year. Web department generated \$376 million revenue which is increase of 7% year after year.

6. SUSTAINABILITY STRATEGY :

Akamai's environmental sustainability initiative focuses on addressing the effects of their energy consumption, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and e-waste generation on the environment. Environmental stewardship is also becoming increasingly important for Akamai's clients, and their achievement helps them attain sustainability objectives in their supply chain. Looking through the sustainability lens offers a fresh view, stimulating new methods of thinking about activities, markets, and supply chain, and inspiring innovation. For the greatest impact, Akamai's sustainability programs concentrate on several main fields such as carbon efficiency network, renewable energy, electronic waste management, and corporate offices with the lowest environmental impact. Akamai's goal is to mitigate their worldwide operations environmental effect, infusing measurable sustainability practices into the organization.

In 2009, Akamai began its corporate sustainability program with a focus on gathering energy data linked to energy savings and carbon intensity reduction programs. Their various categories of criteria for managing carbon effects were extremely complicated, including:

- Various worldwide geographical centers and a complicated organizational hierarchy composed of owned, co-located and third-party data centers
- Requirements for tracking power and carbon data at asset level (servers, switches, etc.) at owned and rented locations added another complexity layer.
- Employee travel with more than 30,000 flights per year with the need to monitor carbon per flight
- Report on large amounts of information and display outcomes instantly
- Manual data collection process
- Inability to alter or customize workflows and automate overhead data center calculations such as cooling, heating, etc.

Akamai managed to overcome all the above challenges by making major changes to their processes, such as

- Started to manage carbon effects at the level of granular assets rather than the general level of operation, which enabled Akamai to monitor the effects of individual equipment at each of its thousands of data centers
- Implemented on-the-fly and instantaneous impact workflows and calculations for data center infrastructure (cooling, heating, etc.)
- Enabled to upload thousands of airport coded flights in bulk or individually with immediate results calculation based on large circular distances and flight routes

- Maximizing the use of virtual machines and allocating low voltage laptops, Macintosh and monitor to decrease power consumption for staff.
- By promoting teleworking with advanced video conferencing solutions and team-working tools there by reducing travel attempts
- By improving efficiency in corporate offices and reducing material consumption and waste.
- Engaging network data center vendors to enhance their operations energy, carbon and water efficiency etc. are some of Akamai Technologies measures taken.

A Cleaner, More Efficient Network is accomplished by lowering server energy consumption and related greenhouse gas emissions by providing renewable energy and growing server energy efficiency and productivity. Being an e-Stewards Enterprise Akamai is the socially and environmentally accountable management of their decommissioned electronic resources by upgrading reuse, reselling and recycling systems in collaboration with e-Stewards certified suppliers. Akamai shares its sustainability objectives, strategies and advancement on its business page and through collective annual disclosure to the CDP by keeping transparency and accountability. The environmental management system of Akamai is structured in accordance with the ISO 14001 PDCA model and covers its global operations and services. Akamai's inventories starting from Scope 1 to 3 follow various International standards. It is ensured that Greenhouse gas emissions are ISO 14064-3 compliant.

7. CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY :

There is a committed group of individuals working on their community outreach programs continuously at Akamai. Returning is one of the key principles of Akamai and an essential part of their Diversity & Inclusion programs. Akamai thinks that people are stronger when individuals from distinct cultures, backgrounds, and personalities come together as a team. Everyone thinks differently, so they see challenges and the way they can be solved differently. Therefore, everybody's outreach is part of a corporate efforts to ensure that everyone actively contributes to the community's well-being. Akamai think in making technology available to all because it's essential for everyone. The Corporate Social Responsibility programs of Akamai range from big to small and revolve around three key pillars: education, community development, and inclusion. In India, Akamai run Math for Fun program, through which they have partnered with about 900 colleges to provide some 50,000 learners with a basic math base. This program is aimed at children aged 9 and 10. Maths for Fun aims at giving young people the abilities to make them employable early in their education. Feedback from their studies showed an enhancement in multiple aspects of mathematics by more than 35 percent. Other examples of outcomes from CSR programs by Akamai include having reached nearly 500 colleges in and around Bangalore with menstrual hygiene education. They built washrooms to offer the advantages of cleanliness to young individuals. Akamai also conducted a skill training program for 150 youth with different skills, preparing them for significant job possibilities. Akamai staff are always volunteering in these CSR programs. They find it an advantage for staff to feel that they are giving back to the society. This could be in-person, engaging actively with participants in their CSR programs, or raising cash for activities like local floods through a compilation.

8. CUSTOMERS AND STAKEHOLDERS :

For the largest companies in the world, Akamai provides digital experiences and protects them against attacks, threats, etc. Akamai Technologies smart edge solution encompasses all from the cloud to business, so clients, their business can function quickly, smartly, and safely. Akamai has a highly skilled customer support and round the clock monitoring team to support portfolio of edge security, web and mobile performance, business access and video distribution solutions and OTT solutions. Some of the key customers of Akamai are listed here, Adobe, Airbnb, Asus, Bangkok Bank, Best Buy, Hotstar, IBM, MTV Networks, NASDAQ OMX Group, NDTV, Sophos, US Army, US Airforce, Viacom, WorldNow etc. Akamai selects suppliers based on their capacity to consistently deliver the highest general value in terms of high quality goods, professional services, competitive pricing, and established track record for continuing and proactive client support.

9. COMPETITORS :

The content delivery network domain is quite competitive. For decades, some CDNs have been around while others are still quite fresh. There are important variations, however, which distinguish each CDN from the others. Akamai has been around in the CDN field for more than 20 years and is a trusted name. Akamai's solution market is extremely competitive and distinguished by quickly altering technology, evolving sector norms and frequent fresh product and business innovations. Akamai can expect competition from current rivals as well as fresh market entrants to boost their offers.

Below are the top 5 Akamai Technologies competitors [11]:

1. Level3 Communications, Inc.

Level3 has its own worldwide Tier1 network. Level3 CDN lies on top of that. Tier-1 Network has POPs in various geographic areas. Their product focuses on the distribution of video and huge objects. Level3 content delivery network is interconnect' s element of Google Cloud content delivery network.

2. Limelight Networks, Inc.

Limelight is providing services related to content delivery network ever since 2001. Its advanced POP network spread across the globe. Limelight offers digital content delivery, real time streaming and on-request video, cloud security, and advanced computing services.

3. CloudFront

CloudFront is Amazon Web Services ' Content Delivery Network, the world's largest cloud service provider. CloudFront provides numerous CDN products including APIs and has POPs spread throughout the world. CloudFront has a thorough documentation to make life easier for developers.

4. Verizon Digital Media Services

Verizon Digital Media Services is the division of Verizon. Established in 2011, VDMS purchased EdgeCast CDN for its streaming video technology in 2013 and launched Lynk. VDMS focuses on streaming video and aims to be a major OTT service provider

5. Cloudflare

Cloudflare offers distinctive performance capacities for a worldwide CDN with a powerful concentration on security. The firm has a worldwide infrastructure constructed using higher end latest technology devices of the next generation — no legacy software or hardware.

Product comparison of all the six CDN service providers can be seen in below table3.

Table 3:CDN feature list

Product	Level 3	Limelight	CloudFront	Verizon	Cloudflare	Akamai
Dynamic content delivery	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Small file delivery	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Large file delivery	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Live video	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Video on demand	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes
Image Optimization	No	Optional	No	No	Yes	Yes
DNS	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
WAF	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Anti-DDoS	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Private CDN	No	Yes	No	No	No	Unknown

In the future, Akamai may have more competition as telecommunications companies like AT&T add content distribution capabilities to their telephone networks. As such, the competitive reactions of Akamai in the future are likely to be more drastic.

10. ANALYSIS

Akamai Management is happy with the great beginning of the year as revenues, margins and income exceed expectations. The outstanding performance was stimulated due to the steep increase in their security and media business. Their ability to enhance effectiveness while continuing to invest in innovation and fresh products in order to drive future development also contributed towards the financial growth [12].SWOC Analysis is a well-known tool used to understand the company's present condition by evaluating Strengths, Weakness Opportunities & Challenges [13].

Below is SWOC Analysis details of Akamai Technologies [14].

Strengths

1. Excellent client base, consistent income

2. Distributed products Portfolio enables a range of markets to be served
3. Competitive advantage over strong network capability
4. Sturdy research and development with solid finances
5. More than 7,500 staff working for the company
6. Facebook, Apple, Twitter are among their clients

Weaknesses

1. Revenue depends heavily on the United States market
2. Shortterm liquidity issues
3. Akamai is geared more towards enterprise customers
4. New feature releases may take more time than smaller, more agile CDNs
5. Akamai's bandwidth costs are expensive

Opportunities

1. Increase in bandwidth requirements for cloud computing to be used
2. Inorganic growth
3. Cyber and Information security – an ever green domain

Challenge

1. Strong competition in the industry from old and newcomers
2. The data privacy guidelines
3. Rapid technological progress

11. SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER IMPROVEMENT :

We propose following suggestions for further enhancement on the basis of the above assessment.

- Affordable bandwidth cost would attract SMBs and boost income as a result.
- By paying equal attention to non-enterprise clients, it will help Akamai to sell its solution among mid-level industries.
- Quick turn around and take a more solid approach to developing and releasing fresh features would keep Akamai on an equal footing with its competitors.

12. CONCLUSION :

Over a span of two decades, the firm that founded to fix the internet slowness challenge has become a multi-solution supplier firm and now Akamai has solutions to more than thirty distinct kinds of problems in the internet world. Akamai made an entry into CDN field in the late 90's and started focusing on increasing the website speed of their clients. Over time, Akamai has improved their technology and purchased various businesses to deliver other kinds of CDN services. Several external development activities, purchases of Nine Systems, Netli, Speedera Networks and Cotendo have been carried out by Akamai since its establishment. It is obvious that by embracing both organic and inorganic methods, Akamai is expanding its grip on the field of digital experiences.

REFERENCES

- [1] Nygren, Erik & Sitaraman, Ramesh & Sun, Jennifer. (January 2010). The Akamai network: a platform for high-performance internet applications. *Operating Systems Review*. 44(3). 2-19. DOI: 10.1145/1842733.1842736
- [2] Qin, Xiaowei & Zhou, Linlin & Kong, Ning & You, Junling. (June 2017). An Adaptive Upload Acceleration Mechanism for Wireless Upload Services. 437-441. DOI: 10.1109/IThings-GreenCom-CPSCoM-SmartData.2017.71.
- [3] Company History. (n.d.). In Akamai. Retrieved July 30, 2019, from <https://www.akamai.com/uk/en/about/company-history.jsp>
- [4] Moustafa, H., & Zeadally, S. (2012). *Media Networks: Architectures, Applications, and Standards*, New York: CRC Press, pp. 211–211.
- [5] Akamai Technologies. (n.d.). In Wikipedia. Retrieved August 06, 2019, from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Akamai_Technologies
- [6] Madhushree, Revathi R. Anil Kumar, & Aithal, P. S. (May 2018). Business Strategy of Top Indian IT Company: MindTree. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT, and Education (IJCSBE)*, 2(1), 22-36. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1249871>
- [7] Aithal, P. S., (2017). Company Analysis – The Beginning Step for Scholarly Research. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 1(1), 1-18. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.573769>.
- [8] Aithal, P. S. (2017). Industry Analysis – The First Step in Business Management Scholarly Research. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 2(1),1-13. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.810347>
- [9] USSEC. (n.d.). In Srockpup. Retrieved August 09, 2019, from <http://www.stockpup.com/companies/AKAM/10-K.html>
- [10] USSEC. (n.d.). In Sec. Retrieved August 09, 2019, from <https://www.sec.gov/Archives/edgar/data/1086222/000108622216000245/akam10k123115.htm>
- [11] Level 3 versus Akamai. (n.d.). In Cdnplanet. Retrieved August 14, 2019, from <https://www.cdnplanet.com/compare/level3/akamai/>
- [12] Defining the Next-Generation Content Delivery Network | Akamai Technologies Inc.. (n.d.). In Akamai. Retrieved August 06, 2019, from <https://akamai.gcs-web.com/news-releases/news-release-details/akamai-ibc-2014-defining-next-generation-content-delivery?ID=1963218&c=75943&p=irol-newsArticle>

- [13] Principal Financial SWOT Analysis Matrix [step by step] Weighted SWOT. (n.d.). In fernfortuniversity. Retrieved August 14, 2019, from <http://fernfortuniversity.com/term-papers/swot/1433/236-principal-financial.php>
- [14] NASDAQ_AKAM. (n.d.). In Annualreports. Retrieved August 14, 2019, from http://www.annualreports.com/HostedData/AnnualReportArchive/a/NASDAQ_AKA_M_2002.pdf

Paper 22

THE STUDY OF PSYCHOLOGICAL PARAMETERS ON FEMALE VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS

Ashwini Venkanagouda Patil^{1*} and Dr. Hanumanthayya Pujari²

¹Research Scholar, Department of physical education and sports sciences, Karnataka State Women's University, Vijayapura, Karnataka, India-586108.

^{1*} corresponding author, e-mail address: ashwiniv.patil90@gmail.com

²Associate Professor, Department of physical education, Vijayanagara Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Bellary, Karnataka, India- 583105.

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to examine the impact of psychological parameters on female volleyball players in the age group of 16 to 18 years. In this investigation, a total of 12 female players from SDM sports hostel, Ujire, Mangalore participated. Anthropometric and psychological measurements were recorded and analyzed. Basic anthropometric parameters like age, height and weight were recorded. Players responses to 27 questionnaires were documented. For psychological study, anxiety and self-confidence measurements were taken. Anxieties like cognitive anxiety and somatic anxiety were analyzed. The recorded data has been interpreted to determine the psychological status of the players.

Keywords: Psychological parameters, volleyball.

1.INTRODUCTION

When the volleyball players are subjected to extreme physical activities in training sessions and matches, maintaining calmness and patience becomes the requirements [1]. The psychological status of a player plays a crucial role here. Getting hold in this psychological profile, a player should have acceptable anthropometric profile [2, 3 and 4]. In psychology study of a player, anxiety and confidence holds the important factor [5]. Illinois competition test was conducted to know the anxiety and confidence levels of the players. Competitive state anxiety inventory – II (CSAI-II) have 27 statements to be recorded. The responses to these 27 statements or questions were recorded to know the feelings of the player. The purpose of this study is to know the player's anxiety levels, confidence levels, the psychological status and finally, the impact of anthropometric and psychological parameters on the female volleyball players.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS AND DISCUSSION

In this investigation, female student players from SDM sports hostel, Ujire, Mangalore (under 18 category-female) were taken. To know the anxiety level of volleyball players, each one of the players were asked to respond to 27 questions with 4 optional responses. This set of questions is known as Illinois Competition Test. Minimum of 9 to maximum of 36 can be scored by a player and that score will help us to know the anxiety levels and self-confidence level. In addition to the above psychological measurements their age (years), height (in centimetre) and weight (in kilogram) were recorded.

Table 1: The Anthropometric and psychological measurements of female volleyball players.

<i>Players No.</i>	<i>Age (yrs)</i>	<i>Height (cm)</i>	<i>Weight (kg)</i>	<i>Cognitive state anxiety</i>	<i>Somatic state anxiety</i>	<i>Self-confidence</i>
<i>Player 1</i>	18	154	43	30	25	31
<i>Player 2</i>	17	166	56	29	25	31
<i>Player 3</i>	17	169	52	33	19	35
<i>Player 4</i>	16	169	58	35	29	36
<i>Player 5</i>	17	165	50	33	25	31
<i>Player 6</i>	18	169	51	34	21	31
<i>Player 7</i>	16	152	44	25	21	33
<i>Player 8</i>	18	170	51	32	23	30
<i>Player 9</i>	16	155	42	31	25	31
<i>Player 10</i>	18	171	57	34	25	35
<i>Player 11</i>	16	161	46	29	20	30
<i>Player 12</i>	17	167	55	27	19	31

Table 2: The Questionnaire or the Illinois Competition Test questions for female volleyball players.

<u>Q. No.</u>	<u>Statements - Question</u>	<u>Q. No.</u>	<u>Statements - Question</u>
1.	I am concerned about this competition.	15.	I'm confident I can meet the challenge.
2.	I feel nervous.	16.	I'm concerned about performing poorly.
3.	I feel at ease.	17.	My heart is racing.
4.	I have self-doubts.	18.	I'm confident about performing well.
5.	I feel jittery.	19.	I'm worried about reaching my goal.
6.	I feel comfortable.	20.	I feel my stomach sinking.
7.	I am concerned I may not do as well in this competition as I could.	21.	I feel mentally relaxed.
8.	My body feels tense.	22.	I'm concerned that others will be disappointed with my performance.
9.	I feel self-confident.	23.	My hands are clammy.

10.	I am concerned about losing.	24.	I'm confident because I mentally picture myself reaching my goal.
11.	I feel tense in my stomach.	25.	I'm concerned I won't be able to concentrate.
12.	I feel secure.	26.	My body feels tight.
13.	I am concerned about losing.	27.	I'm confident of coming through under pressure.
14.	My body feels relaxed.		

Table 1 shows anthropometric and psychological measurements of the female volleyball players. In order to know the anxiety and confidence levels, Illinois competition test, competitive state anxiety inventory – II (CSAI-II), was conducted. Here the players were exposed to 27 statements to which they have to reply with any one of four responses. The 27 statements are listed in Table 2. The four responses were: Not at all (score 1), somewhat (score 2), moderately so (score 3) and very much so (score 4). All the scores of 27 statements were added to get in between minimum score of 9 to maximum score of 36. However, for statement no. 14, scores were inverted from 4 to 1 in the response. Cognitive state anxiety was recorded taking the sum of replies from statements 1, 4, 7, 10, 13, 16, 19, 22 and 25. Somatic state anxiety was recorded taking the sum of replies from statements 2, 5, 8, 11, 14 (inverted response score), 17, 20, 23 and 26. Self-confidence was recorded taking the sum of replies from statements 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18, 21, 24 and 27.

By looking into table 1, player no. 4 and 10 have not only shown good anthropometric profiles but also have shown positive anxiety and self-confidence scores. In fact all the players of the team are having good scores in cognitive anxiety and self confidence. Cognitive anxiety representing mental anxiety status of the players is quite healthy. But somatic or physical anxiety status is just average with not more than 29+ score because of the fact that players are subjected to extreme physical activities in training and matches. As the game demand extreme physical activities, players are supposed to have an good anthropometric and psychological profiles.

3.CONCLUSION

Psychological status of a player influences the game proceedings and also the game result. Psychology profile can be good only if a player is first maintaining a healthy anthropometric profile. Players self confidence levels were found to be exceptionally positive when compared to their anxiety levels. Especially somatic anxiety, also known as physical anxiety, was found to be low. However, Cognitive anxiety, known as mental anxiety, was found to be above average value of 18+ score. This shows the team is having acceptable high self confidence level, which is required by any player/team. And with the score just more than average value of 18+, the anxiety level is also acceptable. This is because the team is not having low score indicating low anxiety and high score indicating high anxiety, which in both cases leads to undesirable game results. Maintaining the optimal range of anxiety score will be suitable and helpful for a player.

4.ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I sincerely thank all the staff members and research scholars of department of physical education and sports sciences, Karnataka State Women's University, Vijayapura, Karnataka, India for their support and encouragement towards this paper.

REFERENCES

1. Marques MC, van den Tillaar R, Gabbett T, Reis VM, González-Badillo JJ, Physical fitness qualities of professional volleyball players: determination of positional differences, *Journal of Strength Cond. Res.*, 2009 ; no. 23, 2009, pages 1106–1111.
2. J. Pena, D. Moreno-Doutres, J. Coma, M. Cook, B. Busca, Anthropometric and fitness profile of high level basketball, handball and volleyball players, *MedicinadelDeporte, Rev Andal Med Deporte* 11(1), 2018: pg. 30-35.
3. Liliana dacica, The formative role of physical education and sports, *Procedia - Social and behavioral sciences* 180, 2015: pg. 1242-1247.
4. Liliana elisabetaradu, FatihHazar, Alexandrurarespuni, Anthropometric and Physical fitness characteristics of university students, *Procedia - Social and behavioral sciences* 149, 2014: pg. 798-802.
5. Juan Mielgo Ayuso, Michael C. Zourdos, Vicente J. Clemente Suárez, Julio Calleja González, Amber M. Shipherd, Can psychological well-being scales and hormone levels be used to predict acute performance of anaerobic training tasks in elite female volleyball players?, *Physiology & Behavior*, Volume 180, 15 October 2017, pg. 31-38.

Paper 23

**TEACHING FOR SOCIAL CHANGE: CAN
EDUCATION BRING A SOCIAL CHANGE IN A
SOCIETY?**

Prof. Ketan V.*, Sutaria, Jay V, Gala**

*Lecturer, Bal-Bharati's MJP College of Commerce

**Student, Bal-Bharati's MJP College of Commerce

Abstract

For shaping the character of an individual education plays a very important element in life and to bring social order in the society there should be a social change. Therefore Education and Social Change goes Hand in Hand. Education preserves the values, morals and beliefs and keep factual data record which will act great utility for the future generations. It gives learner an ability to think, take rightful decisions and to innovate. It eliminates the lack of knowledge which is main stimulus for human stagnation.

Learning can initiate a social change in to order o change the viewpoint and mind-set of an individual person. Slowly there is an increase in automation in education system. This results in absorbing large volume of informational material in short time but it reduces the judgment ability of the learner because of dependability of learners on classes rather than self-learning.

It distracts the liberal thinking of learners. Society will change socially and culturally only because of education. Education act as a link for learners between socialization and expectations of society. Education is the essential technique of social progress and reform. It leads the learner towards new principles, ethics, standards, morals, ideals and help in growth of intelligence and improves the society potential for a good change.

The present paper focuses on the role of edification and technology as a mechanism of social change and growth with introduction of technology for the development of teaching-learning process. It also focuses on obligatory professional knowledge and channels the educators to develop the teaching skills so that it can be more effective. The most influential and valuable instrument of social change and social growth in current time is the education. It emphasize that education has major impact in society, but that it is allocated a conventional role because its main utility is in the socialization of the leaner and the preservation of the social order. Economically when things are going good, more support is given on education experimentation and more optimistic objectives are achieved, such as equity of educational opportunity.

Objectives

1. To understand the concept and functions of 'Social Change in Teaching'.

2. To study the perception level of learners towards change in edification socially.
3. To give brief idea about how education can transform individual with help of socialization

Methodology

The interpretations conversed in this paper are based on our conceptual understanding about the topic. We have tried to describe the topic using secondary data sources such as research paper, journal, the internet websites and related articles related to social changes in education from the newspapers, magazines and publications.

Meaning

Social change is responsive process to many types of changes, changes in the manual circumstances of life, changes in the outlook and philosophy of human being and changes that go far off human control to the biological and the corporeal personality of things.

Teaching is a procedure in which one individual edify or inculcate another individual. It is regarded as the act of communicating information to the learners in the classroom circumstances. It can also be considered as a operation of the circumstances, where the student will attain skills, knowledge and insight with his own instigation.

Introduction

Innovation in culture will only be successful with the help of culture experimentation. To bring a change in mindset of learners there is a need of socialization and that the objective could be achieved only through teachers and education.

Whenever there is discussion with teachers, they often articulate the need to be aware of the modalities of teaching subjects in better way. Teachers are always in finishing the yearly syllabus on are cleared with good marks. The image of the school and educators totally rely on examination scores of students. Some of the best educationists wonder about the importance of subjects in overall education, about its real meaning, responsibility and function of education which are prescribed by the government in their documents. The real meaning of education is to help students to make them realise their true potential.

As per policy, Role of education in India, “edification is primary for our overall development — both materialistic and spiritualistic. Education helps in purifying sensitivities and perceptions that add to national unity, construct methodical temper and self-determination of mind and spirit — thus increasing the aims of socialism, secularism and democracy. Because of education Individual power is also improved at different levels of economy adding to the country’s self-sufficiency.”

Education is not to make any arrangement for life but is it helps in imbibing the dignity, moral and values in individual life. By evaluating the relationship between education and social change, only one question arises i.e how does education lead to social change? Due to social change in education, it helps society to generate and strength and modernizes in a very

different and unique way. Education has been acknowledged as one major element of socialisation, and educators and institutions as socialising instrument.

An important role played in our life is by a teacher because of their efforts an individual become successful in career and business. An individual becomes a good human being in society and good civilian of the country with the efforts and sacrifices made by a teacher. Teachers are very well aware about the fact that students are the future potentials of any country. The efforts and sacrifices of teachers should be appreciated because they are the persons that build future nation. But it is sad to see that in today's world teachers are affected by business, politics, and society.

Social change may take place (i) When a change is needed by human, (ii) When the existing social system or network of social institutions fall short to meet the existing human needs and (iii) When human finds innovative ways for meeting their needs. A social change cannot take place in a society directly or indirectly. Only education can commence social changes by bringing modification in the viewpoint and approach of a individual. It also bring a change in pattern of social relationship and this results bringing social changes.

In order to study the connection between education and social change, it is essential to outline the contribute role of education in social change in the following manner:

1. An individual becomes a good human being in society and good civilian of the country socially with help of education
2. It establishes the principles which act as decisive factor for the examination of social change before its acceptance.
3. It originates, direct and channel social change and assists in elimination of a mass of social tribulations and melancholy.
4. It creates social change and leaders who make strenuous efforts to bring about changes in the society.
5. It assists in progression and enlargement of mind—the opportunity of knowledge for generating changes.
6. It assists in propagating knowledge and ability in the improving intelligence to work for the advancement of the society.
7. It verifies the nature of social changes which ought to bring about—slow or fast, violent or peaceful.

Suggestions

1. Promoting dynamic participation and analysis of ideas with learners.

Regrettably, professor and learners whose main objective is paper-based development often thrust for a lot of memorizing of records, information, and definitions. But this typical way of learning is not shifting the society towards right path. Educators should always try to innovate and raise lively learning opportunities, where learners can be completely affianced with the substance and engage in recreation of ideas without being castigate for going too far afield. Educators should always assist a learning environment include letting learners educate each other, setting up a method for students to ask anonymous subject question and conveying open-ended assignment in which learners are not given the intuition that they are expected to take prearranged steps in anticipation of getting “right” answer.

2. Train learners for innovative thinking instead of training them what to think.

Many studies recommend that theoretical inquisition is not above the heads of elementary-aged students. The learner impersonation and dilemma is what taken at centre stage, not a concrete idealistic mode or text. Learners are always being trained how to think instead of what to think. It is teachers responsibility to train learners for innovative learning instead of training them what to think. Teachers should try to show the difference between How to Think and What to think. Substantiation opine that learners respond well to the viewpoint in the Classroom exercise which was taught to them a week before and this resulted in improvement of students’ interpretation levels, essential judgment skills, and emotional happiness.

3. To make them judge their own capability to take optimistic steps for the advantage of society.

Teachers should always encourage learners to play an influential part in well built societal enhancement for a creation of classroom where learners are given accountability and power to make some important decision.

It is believed that if all answers are available with educators then it is assumed that learners are expected to receive If teachers have all the answers, it’s implied that students are expected to receive knowledge but cannot offer explanation or enhancement. But if educators make it clear and transparent that they also lack some sort of knowledge then learners have more opportunity to rely on their own analytical powers and problem-solving skills.

Teacher should create a learning atmosphere in which learners are taught to observe the benefit of being failure rather than learning to trepidation of doing something wrong.

4. Democratic Classroom practices establishes idea of active contribution which result in social change

Equality should be kept as “structure of illusion” in classrooms if education systems want to provide advantages of healthy democratic society. Individuals are forgotten that every day they should be participating in democracy because it’s a skill that should be practiced in our daily lives. Teachers should make classrooms more democratic than rigid, starting at a very tender age.

Learners should always be taught about the theoretical and practical aspect of learning as how to cast a vote and how that opportunity is presented to them and how their thoughts and ideas can be applied for the benefit of society.

5. Discussions among group of teachers – starting with learners educators – about the choice that can oblige social change.

If you are aware of fact or not but it is believed that Educators and school had great persuasion over society. Teachers should always encourage learners to come mutually as a group to share ideas, facts, knowledge, skill, failure and triumph. The bigger and broader these group discussion will be, teachers should come up with queries and by providing solution to queries it will help learners to know the difference between the good and bad and it will result into social change. Even if one small step is consistently, then there will be enhancement in stronger societal material, structuring better democratic methods, trying to benefit learners. As learners are survive in classroom and societies are being faked, positively a social change will be developed among learners.

It is very much crucial that teaching organization recommends empirical and objective-based guidance to sustain their individual and certified growth because learners are looking for significant careers in the social sector. Multifaceted local and universal challenges insist inventive solutions which are enlarged collaboratively by educationist with knowledge, associations, principles and ethics to successfully progress social change. There is no proper formal model for learning social change but if teachers try to bring learners to internal and external social problems then they would be able to develop effective solutions practically.

Learners will be trained to design program to provide future invention of social change leaders with a variety of proficiency—and the modesty—that they require in their work. Internal and External Experimental learning will help learners to witness innovative new approaches to social-change problems. They are would be able to examine how institutions gear up to face challenges with inspiration, compassion and a partnership-based approach, which will assist in providing a holistic set of morals, ethics, values and principles that will supply them in their future careers.

6. Creating a Desire for Change

Education not only helps in casting the outlook of learners but also assist in crafting a aspiration for change by providing right acquaintance and grind of thinking. Learners become conscious of the social tribulations and stigma like dowry, casteism, infanticide, child marriage, alcoholism, drug addiction, gambling, begging, bonded labour, child labour,

corruption, nepotism, bribe, prostitution etc. and this will help learners in practising the mentality to fight for them in order to improve the pace of development of the society.

Education helps under-privileged groups and below poverty line families by generating alertness of their plights which provides a boost to them to improve their circumstances. It also assist in recognizing additional points in our communal composition, social gaps and in attaining required acquaintance and skills which are basic fundamentals for accomplishing outstanding growth in the society.

7. Evaluation of Social Change

Education can evaluate social change in society in the form of grinding the intelligence and ascertaining certain principles, values and morals which play important decisive factor for analysis of social change. Through the exploration of significant study, objectionable elements of social change are criticized and discarded and enviable elements of social changes are acknowledged and transmitted.

8. Leadership Role in Social Change

Education can help learners to imbibe leadership responsibility in enhancing competence to confront various types of social tribulations and problem contaminating our society. Learners should be trained leadership roles as social reformers and nation builders and this can be done only with help of education.

9. Economic Development:

Social order is very much required in society for fair play of liberty, parity, social justice and equal chance. Social order can be emerged only with help of education. Economic development is necessary for victuals of new social order and edification act essential role in the economic development of the country by infusing knowledge and skill in the mentality of learners for the enhancement of financial system—the basic fundamental for the country's progress and richness.

Education also assist in organising resources such as human and non- human for accelerating economic advancement of a nation. Education will always be considered as mechanism of economic growth is education because it construct and build up human resource.

10. National Development:

Education helps in opening new outlook of country's enhancement. The key role for nation enhancement comprises each and every views of country to be augmented to its fullest—political, economic, cultural, scientific, social, and development of human resources.

Knowledge base is required for improving the pace of country's development. This could be achieved only when learners are disengaged from normal learning process to innovative learning process which brings social change in society and in the end it results into overall

development of a nation. Education by its objectives, curriculum, techniques and multifaceted functions can bring a revolutionary change in the society.

Intelligence is the principal instrument of societal change and education assist in evolving liberated and inspired minds which acknowledges and circulate social change in its accurate outlook.

Education endows realistic acquaintance and encourages thoughts for development of intelligence which adds to the advancement and modernisation of the society. Role of the educator cannot be ignored because it is a teacher's responsibility not to train learners in negative way but to train them in such a manner that learners can accelerate the transformation in the society.

Conclusion

A right type of social change in society can only be bought with help of right type of education. The function of education in different society and nations divulge the obtrusive note that effectual of educational system establish the swiftness of social change. Education is one of the most prominent instruments of social change in society in spite of hindrances of slow and limited growth of education. Education cannot be perceived as controlling force to protect cultural legacy and agent of social change but it could be perceived as driving force of social and cultural change which is undertaken for improvement of the community to keep in pace with modern changing society.

Education is the only way through which society can bring enviable transformation and modernize itself. A society can be transformed by education only by offering opportunities and skills so that individual can encourage himself for modification with the promising needs and attitude of the changing society. In every phase of existence, social progress requires proper and cautious development –social, cultural, economic, and political. Education must be developed in a right manner so that it fulfils the needs and ambition of the individual as a whole.

An improper and faulty education can pilot unacceptable social changes. So if society wants to transform in accurate path then fundamental awareness is to be given to educational process because education is originator of social change. Environment and socialization techniques are important aspects adding to academic achievement and character building of students.

Social scientist, social psychoanalyst, politicians, instructor and educational planners are considered as an apparatus of social change. In can be concluded that educationists, teachers, colleges and schools have a incredible accountability in social change.

References

- <https://classroom.synonym.com/major-objectives-social-studies-education-6803269.html>

- <http://www.teachhub.com/working-together-students-teaching-students-through-video>
- http://www.ascd.org/ASCD/pdf/journals/ed_lead/el_195703_andrews.pdf
- https://ssir.org/articles/entry/teaching_values_and_purpose_for_social_change#
- <http://www.yourarticlelibrary.com/education/education-and-social-change-in-india/76837>
- <http://www.teachhub.com/working-together-students-teaching-students-through-video>
- <http://theconversation.com/we-need-to-teach-children-how-to-think-not-what-to-think-33060>
- https://www.academia.edu/8402428/Role_of_Education_in_Social_Change

Paper 24

**OUTSOURCING: RECENT TRENDS IN
MANAGEMENT FOR DEVELOPING INDIA**

Dr. Pradip M. Joshi,

Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce and Management,
M. J. College, Jalgaon, Maharashtra,
pmj21575@gmail.com

Abstract:-

Entire world is a jointed with each other due to globalization. IT plays a vital role in it. By using IT techniques and new trends in Management, India can be take opportunity to be a developed country. This new trends of management is Outsourcing. Now a day developed countries outsource too many jobs to India. Such benefit should also to be taken by Indian. Indians Entrepreneurs are sharp minded, hard worker, creative, etc., just need to do some financial management, time management and stress management. To manage all these things need to accept foreign strategy i.e. Outsourcing. Outsourcing is strategic management model transferring business process to other country.

As per a rapid growth of Indian Economy, very soon India will become a Developed Country. As compare to other developing country, India moves upward in rank. Thus it beneficial as India can outsource their work to other country. And concentrate on main or core functions of the business. It helps to increase productivity, quality of product, reduction in cost, expansion of business, profit making and etc.

This research paper discusses and focuses on various criteria of outsourcing which is useful for Entrepreneurs. Paper also evaluates the benefits and the challenges in outsourcing and offshoring. To take the reap of outsourcing, Indian Entrepreneurs must be accepted the outsourcing opportunity. This paper discusses that how Indians Entrepreneurs use this new trends in Management i.e. outsourcing and become developed country very soon.

Key Words:- Outsourcing, Entrepreneurs, Management.

Introduction:

India is developing country. The dream of Dr. APJ Abdul Kalam was to make India as a developed nation in the world. Dr. Kalam said India will become developed nation because by the year 2020. To achieve such biggest dream of big person is really attribute him. Outsourcing is the right path for transfer this dream into reality. Today in global world, too many developed country outsource their work to India. But it is not sufficient to achieve our

target, thus it is necessary that India also use offshore outsourcing. This paper discussed how Indian do offshore, benefit of offshore outsourcing, where India can be outsource, etc.

Outsourcing-

Outsourcing means when a company contracts with an outside company for services or other business processes, rather than employing in the own company. These services may be provided on-site or off-site.

Outsourcing is one of the fastest growing segments of BPO and ITES industry. BPO is a strategy which promotes in a unique way either by putting in new technology or applying existing technology to improve a process. IT-enabled outsourcing services use information technology in the processing and delivery of the services. These services are typically delivered through a telecommunications or data network, or other electronic media.

India in the recent years has as shown huge developments in the areas of communication, power and software developments. It has already established itself as a global BPO hub and is fast becoming a popular outsourcing destination for major manufactures across the globe.

Types of Outsourcing

There are two kinds of outsourcing, namely near-shore outsourcing, onshore outsourcing and off-shore outsourcing.

1) Off-shore outsourcing

Off-shore outsourcing means that some of the company's work is done by people with other countries.

2) On-shore outsourcing

On-shore outsourcing is also called domestic outsourcing. It means that work or service of the company is done by another company in the same country.

There are too many countries which currency value is less than India. T take the benefit of such currency value India can use offshore outsourcing. It means Indian can be outsourcing their work to other country.

Research Methodology:

Objectives:

Main objective of the research articles find out the various countries to whom India can be outsource. To discuss various point which motivate to India for offshore outsourcing. To study of benefits of offshore outsourcing to India.

Data Collection:

This article is based on Primary and Secondary data. Secondary data are collected though the web survey of Entrepreneurs, books, articles, newspapers, reports etc. On the basis of secondary data the primary data is collected through the observation method.

Data Analysis and Interpretations:-

Outsourcing Partner:-

Outsourcing Partner means organizations to whom outsourcing work is given. The partner may be within country or outside of the country. Entrepreneurs select their outsourcing partner as per the requirements and convenience.

➤ Off-shore Outsourcing:-

Off-shore outsourcing means outsource the work to other country. There are too many countries which are under develop than India. As well as their currency rate is also less than India. So Indian can outsource to that country can take benefits of cost reduction. The following table show the list of countries whose currency is less than India.

Name of Country	Rate of Exchange with India
Vietnam	1 Rupee = 333.98 Vietnamese Dong
Indonesia	1 Rupee = 197.02 Indonesian Rupaiah
Laos	124.89 LAK
Paraguay	1 Rupee = 83.31 Paraguayan Guarani
Cambodia	1 Rupee = 61.29 Cambodian Riel
Uzbekistan	1 Rupee = 44.76 Uzbekistani Som
Mongolia	1 Rupee = 33.31 Mongolian Tugrik

If Indian Entrepreneurs outsource their work to these countries it is benefited as cost reduction. The following table show the cost difference of India and other countries due to exchange rate. In other words to take the benefit of high exchange value of Indian Rupee, Indian Entrepreneurs should control cost.

Cost Saving Comparison:-

Bookkeeper/Jr. Accountant	Indian Employee	Offshore Cost			
		Vietnam	Indonesia	Laos	Paraguay

Monthly Salary	35000	104.80	177.65	280.25	420.12
Other Charges (10%)	3500	--	--	--	--
Total Cost	38500	104.80	177.65	280.25	420.12

(Source: Primary Data)

This table shows cost saving comparison when Indian outsource to other country. All these countries are capable to do every types of outsourcing work. It means India can outsource any type of work. The processes or activities that are being outsourced could range from customer service and telemarketing to IT management software development, market research and even financial portfolio management. The services that can be outsourced to other countries. The following table shows the literacy rate of country.

Name of Country	Literacy Rate
Vietnam	93.7%
Indonesia	95.38%
Laos	84.66%
Paraguay	94.66%
Cambodia	78.3%
Uzbekistan	83.8%

Benefits of Outsourcing:

Outsource the work to other countries is benefited as:

- Cost Saving.
- Concentrate on Core functions of business.
- Saving on infrastructure and technology.
- Saving the resources.
- Faster and Better Services.

1. Cost Saving-

The most observable and evident benefit relates to the cost savings that outsourcing brings about. Work can be done at a lower cost and with better quality. Due to the difference in wages between India and other countries, the same kind of work that is done over there can be done in India at a higher of the cost. There is a cost savings of around 70% to 80% by outsourcing your work to other countries.

2. Focus on core areas-

Businessman can be free due to Outsourcing. Businessman can be free from unnecessary process of business and enable to focus on building brand, invest in research and development and move on to providing higher value added services.

3. Save on infrastructure and technology-

Due to outsourcing reduce the investment in infrastructure as the outsourcing partner takes the responsibility of the business processes and hence develops infrastructure for the same.

4. Saving the Resources-

Outsource to other countries is benefited as saving of other resources of production. For production purpose need various factors or resources such as machinery, manpower, factory, etc., such types or resources can be save with the help of outsourcing.

5. Faster and better services-

Make service offerings better with high quality deliverables and decrease the lead time it takes for product to reach the marketplace. Thus you would be faster in getting ideas converted into products and better at delivering the value-added proposition.

Conclusion:

Outsourcing is new management trend for developing Entrepreneurial skills with help of ICT. It benefited to entrepreneurs as cost saving, concentrate on core functions, concentration on market etc. It not only benefited to entrepreneurs but Indian economy also such as increase source of national income, increase source of employment opportunities, development of all states and cities, reduce heavy burden of particular cities. At glance outsourcing increase the growth rate of Indian economy and push it towards developed country and make sure India will become developed country very soon.

References:

1. Essential of Business Processing Outsourcing – Thomeas N. Duening and Click, John Wiley & Sons.
2. Online Bookkeeping Processes
3. Dissertation.co.uk
4. Indian Journal of Finance Volume No. 6 March 2012
5. The Business Review, Cambridge Vol.10 Nov. 2008
6. <https://www.quora.com/How-many-countries-have-currencies-less-valuable-than-the-Indian-rupee>

7. <https://www.skyscanner.co.in/news/7-places-around-world-where-rupee-will-make-you-feel-rich>
8. <http://www.thrillophilia.com/blog/countries-that-have-lower-currency-value-than-indian-rupees/>

Paper 25

**CREDIT RISK MANAGEMENT WITH FOCUS ON
THE COOPERATIVE BANKING SECTOR**

Arati.N.Rawal

Research scholar, Department of commerce, Rani Chennamma University, Belgavi,
Mail.Id: aru265@gmail.com

Abstract

Credit risk is one of the most common risk in the cooperative banking sector. It is the hidden feature, if not timely controlled, will negative impact on banking business. The credit risk management is need for an hour therefore, it is very necessary to implementing the credit risk management processes in the banking transactions. It helps the banks in identifying, measuring, monitor and control the credit risk.

The purpose of the present study is to focus on the state of credit risk management process in cooperative banks in Dharwad district. Further, the paper makes an assessment of the extent to which cooperative banks were following the standard practices and identify the focus area of improvement in near future.

Keyword: credit risk management process,

Introduction

Credit risk is always associated with banking business, and taking risk is the important part of any banking operation to earn the profit and growth. By being exposed to the risk banks have faced lot of problems, the banks have realized that credit risk is important and the bank need to identify, measure, monitor and control the risk very significant. Due to this the effective management of credit risk has become the critical component of approaching risk management.

The credit risk management is defined as the borrower will fail to pay principle amount with interest in accordance with agreed terms. The main objective of credit risk management is to minimize the risk and maximize the profit.

The purpose of the present study is to focus on the state of credit risk management process in cooperative banks in Dharwad district. Further, the paper makes an assessment of the extent to which cooperative banks were following the standard practices and identify the focus area of improvement in near future.

Need for the study

The credit risk management provides a framework for understand the nature of credit risk presented in the banking organization. While credit risk management helps the bank in maximizing the profitability and more precisely to help the credit officers to improve in

future. Therefore, a need was felt by the researcher to understand the of credit risk management processes helps the banks in identify, measure, monitor and control the risk of cooperative banking sector. Hence the study entitled “Credit risk management with focus on cooperative banking sector in Dharwad district.

Literature review

Anupam Mitra (2012): The study attempt to identify the credit risk emerged as biggest risk for cooperative banks, which evidence arises due to rising of non-performing assets of banks and also have inference of politicians in the organizations. The study concluded that to control and reduce the non-performing assets, bank should adopt the strategies of pre sanction in depth and post sanction supervision follow up.

Bodla and Richa verma (2009): The authors examine the credit risk management in commercial banking sector. The study observed that risk rating is most important instrument, and proper credit administration, prudential limits, risk pricing help the bank in mange the credit risk effectively.

Research objective and methodology

The main objective of the study is access the risk profile of cooperative banks; to examine the credit risk management processes of managing key risk areas.

The data relating to the research includes both primary and secondary data. Primary data was collected through the questionnaire and secondary data has been collected through the Reserve Bank of India guidelines, journals, books.

Analysis of the study

The analysis of the study based on all ten cooperative banks which are situated in Dharwad district. There are total eight cooperative banks which are operating in urban area and two cooperative banks are operated in rural area. All the banks are following the Reserve Banks of India guidelines to manage credit risk. The information is collected from the credit officers at head office level. The credit risk management helps the banks in long term success of banking business.

Credit risk management processes

The credit risk management process contains the four elements to successfully manage the risk, such are identifying, measuring, monitoring and controlling the risk within a time. The banks have to identify with pre-sanctioning process by implementing the KYC norms and collecting the proper documentation. Measure the risk by pricing the credit and by assess the credit scoring of the borrowers. The risk monitored at organizational level by constituting the committees and by fixing the credit exposure limits. The credit risk controlled by the bank, with periodically loan review mechanism and by collecting collateral security from borrowers.

A. Identify the credit risk

Credit risk is identification various risk associated with the banking organisation. Generally credit risk is identified most important for the banking business. While, identify the risk within the time helps the banks in decision making process. The bank have identify the credit risk by KYC norms.

KYC norms (Know Your Customer)

The KYC norm is required for the banks to verify the borrowers address through documents listed in the circular. It has been noticed by the RBI that a large number of persons, especially. Those belonging to low income group, both in urban and rural area are not able to produce such documents to satisfy the bank about their identity and address. This leads to their inability to access the banking services and result in their financial exclusion. It involves the true identification of credit beneficiaries, source of funds, nature of customers business etc. The KYC norms helps the banks understand their customers and their financial dealings better and help them manage their risk prudentially.

The study found that all the Urban and Rural area sample banks have following the RBI guidelines by implementing the KYC norms (RBI/2015-16/42).

Table 1
KYC norms

KYC norms	Urban area banks	Rural area banks	Total
Yes	8 (80)	2 (20)	10 (100)
	(100)	(100)	(100)
No	0 (00)	0 (00)	0 (00)
	(00)	(00)	(00)
Total	8 (80)	2 (20)	10 (100)

Source: Field survey

Note: Figures in brackets opposite to the figures in the cells represent the percentage of the respective cell figures to the respective row total.

: Figures in brackets below the figures in different cells represent the percentage of the respective figures to the total of the respective columns.

Table 1 reveals that out of 8 urban area banks all the sample banks have following the practice of KYC norms and out of 02 rural area banks all the sample banks have following the practices of KYC norms.

B. Measure the credit risk

The credit risk is measurement should be comprehensive enough to cover all the significant sources of risk exposures. The measurement process should be based on the accuracy of information available. The credit risk measured by the bank can be collected through CIBIL to identify the credit history of the borrowers. Further, bank have pricing the credit depending on the risk factor.

Credit Information Bureau (CIBIL)

The RBI has made compulsory to all the cooperative banks to register the credit information bureau to identify the credit history of borrowers. It provide the information regarding credit history of borrowers. There are three credit information bureau are registered by the cooperative banks are Equifax, Experian and Highmark. They are Equifax credit Information Services Pvt. Ltd. High Mark Credit Information Services Pvt. Ltd.; Experian Credit Information Company of India Pvt. Ltd (RBI/2009-10/84).

Table 2
Members of Credit Information Bureau

Credit Information Bureau	Urban area banks	ural area banks	Total
Experian	1 (100)	0 (00)	(100)

	(13)	(00)	
High mark	3 (60) (38)	2 (40) (100)	(100)
High mark and Equifax	1 (100) (13)	0 (00) (00)	(100)
Highmark and Experian	1 (100) (13)	0 (00) (00)	((100) (10)
High Mark, Experian and Equifax	1 (100) (13)	0 (00) (00)	(100)
Not registered	1 (100) (13)	0 (00) (00)	(100)
Total	8 (80)	2 (20)	(100)

Source: Field survey

Note: Figures in brackets opposite to the figures in the cells represent the percentage of the respective cell figures to the respective row total.

: Figures in brackets below the figures in different cells represent the percentage of the respective figures to the total of the respective columns.

Table 2 observed that 01 urban area sample banks have registered all the three CIB are Equifax, Experian and Highmark and 01 sample banks have registered Highmark and Equifax.

Further, 01 sample bank have registered Highmark and Experian and 03 sample banks are registered only High mark. However, 01 urban area sample bank have registered Experian only and 01 urban area sample bank have not registered Credit Information Bureau. Whereas 02 rural area sample banks have registered Highmark only.

Credit pricing

Risk-based pricing, in its simplest terms, is the alignment of loan pricing with the expected loan risk. Typically, a borrower's credit risk is used to determine whether a loan application will be accepted or declined. That same risk may also be used to drive the loan price. This means charging a higher interest rate for a higher-risk transaction and a lower rate for a lower-risk transaction. Additionally, risk-based pricing builds on the net interest margin calculations by adding to the cost of funds.

The study observed that out of 8 sample banks, 04 urban area sample banks have credit pricing on basis of cost of funds, 03 urban area sample banks have pricing the credit on the basis of price quoted by cost of funds, competitors and market conditions. Further, 01 urban area sample banks have credit pricing on the basis of future business potential.

However, 01 rural area sample banks have pricing the credit on the basis of cost of funds and 01 rural area of sample banks have pricing the credit on the basis of price quoted by cost of funds, competitors and market conditions.

C. Credit risk monitoring

Credit risk monitoring is most necessary for the banking business because risk profile changing over a period, it is necessary monitor risk profile on an ongoing basis. Risk

monitoring is process maintained by the organisational structure and by fixing the credit exposure limits.

The organisational structure has monitoring the credit by constituted the committees such as credit policy committees, credit data management cell, credit audit committees.

Table 3
Credit risk monitoring committees

Committees	Urban area banks		Total	Rural area banks		Total
	Yes	No		Yes	No	
Credit policy committees	06	02	08	01	01	02
Credit audit committees	05	03	08	02	00	02
Credit counselling cell	03	05	08	00	02	02
Credit data management cell	06	02	08	02	00	02

Source: Field survey

Note: figures in the table represents number of committees.

Table 3 represents that out of 8 urban area banks, 06 sample banks have framing the credit policy committees and 05 sample banks have framing the credit audit committees. Further 03 sample banks have framing the credit counselling cell and 06 sample banks have framing the credit data management cell.

It was observed that out of 02 rural area banks, 01 sample bank have framing the credit policy committee and all the sample banks have framing the credit audit committee and credit data management cell. However, none of the sample bank have framing the credit counselling cell.

Credit exposure limits

The banks have diversify the credit by fixing the credit exposure limits to concentrate the credit to different sectors to monitoring the risk, such as single borrowers exposure limits, group of borrowers exposure limits, priority sector and weaker sector limits and industrial sector limits.

The Reserve Bank of India has set the limits to single borrower's limits 15% of cost of funds and 40% for group of borrowers and for 40% for priority sector lending and 10% for weaker sector.

- The study observed that the both urban and rural area sample banks have following RBI guidelines to single borrower's exposure limits that is 15% of capital funds.
- The group of credit exposure limits of both urban and rural area banks have low concentration on group of credit exposure limits that is below the 40% of capital funds. It indicates that the sample banks have low concentration or avoid the risk.
- The credit exposer limits to priority and weaker sector lending, the urban and rural area banks have high concentrate on the priority and weaker sector lending. It is high risk for bank.

D. Control the credit risk

Credit risk control means taken the action to reduce the risk or control the bad debt in the banks.

Usually banks have control the credit risk by periodic monitoring the accounts, loan review mechanism conducted by credit officers and chartered accountants.

Loan review mechanism or credit audit

The bank have control the credit risk by periodically audited the bank branches. The both urban and rural area banks have periodically audited the bank branches. There is three types of credit audit has been conducted by cooperative banks; internal audit, external audit and credit risk inspection.

- **Internal audit:** The internal audit is conducted by credit officers on quarterly and monthly bank branches depending on the banking business. Both the urban and rural area banks have internal audited the bank branches on quarterly and monthly basis.
- **External audit:** The urban and rural area sample banks have external audited the banks on yearly basis appointed by external auditors.
- **Credit risk Inspection:** The CRI is an auditor's simultaneous internal check of the transactions and recorded documents of the banks. It is mandated by the RBI in association with the Institute of Chartered Accountants of India (ICAI), to select from the list chartered accountants for the banks inspection. They are close monitoring of loans and advances and check the records. If the chartered accountant rectify the any irregularities bring to the notice of the board.

The Chartered accountants are inspect the banks and reporting the compliances, it grade the banks on their audit reports. Such as A, B, C and D grades are given to the banks. The grade A and B banks have a with good audit reporting and C and D grade sample banks have poor performance or considered as poor audit report banks.

The summarized findings are:

- The study found that all the urban and rural area sample banks have following the practices KYC norms, while sanctioning credit.
- The urban and rural are banks have registered the Credit Information Bureau and one of the urban area bank have not registered the credit information bureau.
- The urban and rural area sample bank have pricing the credit on the basis of cost of funds.
- The 75% of urban area sample banks have constituted the credit policy committee and credit audit committee, 35% of urban area sample banks have framing the credit counselling cell.
- The 50 % of rural area banks have constituted the credit policy committees and credit audit committees and credit data management cell and none of the bank have framing the credit counselling cell.
- The credit exposure limits: The single borrower's exposure limits the urban and rural area banks have following the RBI guidelines while single borrower's exposure limits.
- The group of exposure limit, urban and rural area banks have low concentrated on group of group of borrowers, it indicates the risk avoid by the bank.
- Credit exposure to priority and weaker sector lending, the urban area banks and rural area banks have high concentration on priority sector lending and wreaker sector lending, it indicates high risk for the banks.
- The urban and rural area banks have periodically audited the bank branches and external audit is conducted by chartered accountants, further, credit risk inspection is conducted by the cooperative groups.

Conclusion of the study

The credit risk management process provide the principle guidelines to the banks, to identify, measure, monitor and control the risk within a time. It helps the banks in reduce the risk in the banking business. However, the cooperative bank in Dharwad district must be improved regard credit risk management. Further, it must have concentrate on framing the committees, concentrate on credit exposure limits towards the group of borrowers and bank must have periodically review the credit risk management policy for updating and strengthen the banking business.

References:

1. Anupam Mitra (2012), "Evaluation of credit risk management in urban cooperative banks-A study in Hoghly district", the management account, March 2012, Pp. 328-348.
2. S. Bodla and RichaVerma (2009), "Credit risk management framework at banks in India", the ICFAI journal of bank management, vol. VIII, No.1, Pp. 47-72.
3. Hennie van Greuning Sonja BrajovicBratanovic (2010), "Managing Banking risk", A JAICO book Mumbai.
4. S.N.Bidani, P.K. Mitra, Pramod kumar; "credit risk management" Taxman's allied service private limited.
5. Programme on risk management for state and central cooperative banks, BIRD, Mangalore, 2015.
6. www. RBI guidelines.

Paper 26

**ROLE OF TEACHERS IN SOCIAL CHANGE: A STUDY
WITH REFERENCE TO SOCIAL WORK TEACHERS**

Ganesh Prasad G. Nayak*, Dr. Duggappa Kajekar**

* Research Scholar, Kannada University Hampi.

**Assistant Professor, GFGC Thenkanidiyur Udupi

Introduction

In recent years there has been a growing tendency towards change in all the spheres of society. In this ever-changing world there is nothing, which is static or not subject to any change. In India, villagers are subjected to change in many ways and in fact they have been undergoing changes since independence. These changes have touching and stressing impact on social, economic, political and cultural lives of the rural people. It cannot be denied that there is only a predominant cause or factor, i.e., education which is related to any change. Therefore, it may be noted that education plays a vital role in bringing about change in society from traditional to modern status.

Education is the agent or instrument for social change. Education as it stands for itself, elevate a given set of situation into a new level of state with significant change. It awakens the human consciousness into higher state and results in bringing change; a state where standard of human understanding alters or modify into transforming setting.

Social change occurs when humans edification are enhanced through different kinds of educative vehicles or agencies. Nevertheless, human edification by oneself in isolation cannot impact a social change because education for social change is a process of mutual interaction. Shared interface in a social set up involves cultures of that given situation. And therefore, a thorough study is required to see how educative elements creep into society and bring change: a social change.

After independence, the Constitution adopted by the Govt. of India has declared all citizens to be equal and the government also provided scope to the rural people to choose any form of education and professional training. In the contemporary period, because of impact of industrialization and westernization, the society as a whole and consequently the pattern of education has largely been changed. The aim of education is to facilitate the people for adjustment of changing society. The aims of education are based upon a conception of human nature, and they aim at attaining certain permanent goals. Indeed, education socializes the individuals and this provides them with the ability to adjust in the society. It also develops individual's personality so that he can challenge the evils of society and also suggest remedial measures. Thus education may give birth to leaders, reformers and revolutionary thinkers.

Review of Literature

Weber (1946 : p-426) has emphasized on the educational system and points out that “the attempt rationally to transmit to the individual certain traits, to train him for specific skills by challenging him to think and act independently – which is generally characteristic of educational spheres of rational bureaucratic organizations”. Thus according to Weber the principal aim of modern education is to develop rational faculties of human beings so that they can have independent thinking and their actions are not governed by any stereotype norms and principles. This type of training helps the individual to challenge the dogmatic beliefs and to inculcate rational thinking.

Myrdal (1968 : p-1541) in his book “Asian Drama : An Enquiry into the Poverty of Nations” points out “the more elaborate models all reduce investment in man to one factor, education”.

Dube (1974) in his paper “Modernization and Education” pointed out that through modern education the motivation of the people may be changed. Dube emphasized on the psychological aspect of education. Further, education may help in the formulation of new set of values. Finally, education will help in the development of complex organization. To run the government, to recruit people etc. education is very essential. As matters stand today though change finds its entry in rural India, yet even today a large number of villagers have remained backward and they are educationally also not well advanced. Still vast majority of the farmers is not using latest agricultural techniques in their agricultural operation, and as such the output on the whole is very meagre. Most of the villages located in isolated areas are deprived of road and facility of electricity, water supply and communication.

As regards to the changes of the villages **Altekar (1956; P.124)** has mentioned that “a village life to a great extent remains the same, people still till their lands and sow their crops in the old manner, but even here the changes are coming and coming fast enough. The theory, therefore, that the Indian village communities do not change, is completely disproved by the teaching of history”. It needs no explanation to highlight the fact that village is the unit of the rural society. It is the theatre wherein the quantum of rural life unfolds itself and functions. In this regards, like every social phenomenon the village is a historical category.

Desai (1969 : P.14) remarks that “the student of rural society should study the village, the basic unit of rural society as it originated, and underwent a constant state of development and change due to the action of its own developing internal forces as also due to its interaction with other societies”. The increasing spread of modern education among the rural people because of the establishment of schools and other educational institutions is one of the very effective means to bring about change in the rural life and structure.

Education and social change are two different concepts. In India, the changes have been taking place in the rural areas due to the impact of various measures of the Union Government. So, Indian society has been experiencing one of its greatest traditions in history since the advent of the British rule. In fact, village economic structure and institutional frame-work are based on

caste and the joint family systems. But its technological framework, economic system, social framework (caste, kinship and joint family system etc.), political organization, ideological orientation and cultural value system have been undergoing a qualitative transformation.

Objectives

- To examine the role of social work teachers in making students pro-social.
- To know the role played by social work teachers in bringing social change.
- To know whether the students have developed societal consciousness.
- To understand strategy used by social work teachers to enable all round development of students.
- To know how social work teachers motivate youth towards social change.

Methodology

In this study ,the researcher adopted the scientific methodology from the selection of the problem of research to obtaining of data and generalization. Researcher selected the topic ‘Role of Teachers in Social Change: A Study with reference to Social Work Teachers’ and the study was conducted in Udupi district. Udupi and Kundapura taluks were selected in Udupi. 50 respondents were selected on the basis of purposive and snow ball sampling. Primary data were collected from the field by interview schedule to the respondents and secondary data were collected from various books, journals, Government reports.

Analysis and Interpretation

Discussions related to social change

Majority 35 (70%) of respondents have said that in their teaching method they give major priority for discussions related to social change. Classroom atmosphere plays productive role in enhancing students thinking and perception level and also makes them to develop critical thinking skills. While teachers give major priority to induce the concept of social change in their teaching methods then it will be more useful in moulding students personality.

Impact of field work practicum

Majority 47 (94%) of respondents have said that field work practicum makes student to explore the society. Field work practicum unveils the various phases of society and makes students to know more about it. Field work practicum makes the students to understand the society in depth and also gives them a platform to cultivate social consciousness.

Classroom atmosphere and interpersonal relationship

Majority 41 (82%) of respondents have said that classroom atmosphere is equally significant in making students to develop interpersonal relationship. When teachers take necessary steps to make their classroom interactive students will be benefited to a larger extent. Activity oriented teaching always bears fruits.

Education as agent of social change

Majority 48 (96%) of respondents have said that education is the agent or instrument for social change. Education makes youth to understand the problems in society and also makes them to establish cause effect relationship. Social work teachers should always make their class equipped with necessary information which will help their students to develop strong perception level and also critical thinking and respond towards society.

Education awakens human consciousness

Majority 45 (90%) of respondents have said that education awakens the human consciousness into higher state and results in bringing change. Education also makes youth to undergo self actualization and also evaluate themselves and inculcate necessary skills required to develop pro social personality.

Contribution of field work conference

Majority 30 (60%) of respondents have said that counseling contributes towards making students to understand about a cause which is needed to be handled in a best possible way. Field work conference creates a platform for establishing rapport between students and teachers and also makes students to unlock their potential.

Role of education in nation building

Majority 43 (86%) of respondents have said that education has always played an important role in the task of building an enlightened, strong and prosperous nation. Since majority of developing countries focus on empowerment of youth due to their percentage in total population, youth should be exposed to necessary education in order to make them to empowered and thus help in nation building.

Role of social work education

Majority 40 (80%) of respondents have said that social work education has played major role in making students to come across noble ideals of humanity. Since social work education makes students to introspect and also makes them to develop rational thinking, which is major ingredient for social change.

Social work teachers play major role in bringing attitudinal change

Majority 29 (58%) of respondents have said that social work teachers play significant role in initiating attitudinal change in students. Social work teachers can mould their students by establishing effective rapport both during classes and also during field work conferences.

Opinion about present educational system

Majority 30 (60%) of respondents have said that they support present educational system. Present educational system is comprised of those things which are needed for students to become a major contender in competitive market.

Spread of education in villages leads to social change

Majority 33 (66%) of respondents have said that spread of education in villages leads to social change. Village system is having few rigid practices which are blindly practiced without any logical thinking and also without valid reasons. Spread of education provides them an opportunity to introspect and decide which things should be followed and which shouldn't.

Social work education and social change in social institutions

Majority 34 (68%) of respondents have said that education brings change in social institutions viz., family, caste, marriage and religion. Education can empower individuals. Social institutions will be effective while they have a strong foundation or base of education. Education can strengthen social institutions.

Attitude towards female education

Majority 46 (92%) of respondents have said that they support female education since it is playing crucial role in bringing social change. Females should get education in order to make them empowered. Education also plays important role in making her independent and also strive for a healthy society and also build an awareness in her family.

Social work education and sense of belongingness

Majority 32 (64%) of respondents have said that social work education creates sense of belongingness among youth towards society and it creates we feeling. Social work provides ample of opportunity for youth to know and understand each other. It amplifies their voice of societal development and also helps in building a strong bond between them. Professional social work lays emphasis on giving self respect to each other and says that each individual is important. It enriches the concept of oneness and we feeling.

Awareness regarding agriculture

Majority 30 (60%) of respondents have said that while teaching they spread awareness regarding agriculture and try to motivate youth to build interest in agriculture. While teachers hesitate to speak about rural aspects then students also start neglecting and loose interest to discuss about such things. Teachers play pivotal role in making their students to inculcate interest about agriculture. Making youth to turn back towards agriculture is a major social change which will bear fruits.

Relationship between caste and politics

Majority 29 (58%) of respondents have said that caste and politics are not interrelated. Social change happens when people cast their vote without the influence of the caste which is represented by the contenders. But from the beginning caste and politics are said to be two faces of the same coin. This view should not be supported. Social work believes that caste has nothing to do with politics. Respondents said that ability and track record of the contender plays significant role in choosing the person.

Political participation of women and social change

Majority 26 (52%) of respondents have said that education can be a potent force to inspire the women folk for political participation which in turn can contribute to social change. Women will become more empowered if she is being exposed to certain level of education. If women is brought into societal mainstream by providing her opportunity to contest in elections like Panchayat Raj and higher level, she will play major role in maximizing societal development which will lay emphasis to social change.

Social work education and savings

Majority 35 (70%) of respondents have said that education plays an important role in arousing the idea of saving money among the youth. Youth, if inculcate the habit of engaging in social work they will become thrifty and will develop pro social mindset and also will be away from social evils. This in turn will make them socio-economically sound.

Major Findings

- Majority 35 (70%) of respondents have said that in their teaching method they give major priority for discussions related to social change.
- Majority 47 (94%) of respondents have said that field work practicum makes student to explore the society.
- Majority 41 (82%) of respondents have said that classroom atmosphere is equally significant in making students to develop interpersonal relationship.
- Majority 48 (96%) of respondents have said that education is the agent or instrument for social change. Education makes youth to understand the problems in society and also makes them to establish cause effect relationship.
- Majority 45 (90%) of respondents have said that education awakens the human consciousness into higher state and results in bringing change.
- Majority 30 (60%) of respondents have said that counseling contributes towards making students to understand about a cause which is needed to be handled in a best possible way.
- Majority 43 (86%) of respondents have said that education has always played an important role in the task of building an enlightened, strong and prosperous nation.
- Majority 40 (80%) of respondents have said that social work education has played major role in making students to come across noble ideals of humanity.

- Majority 29 (58%) of respondents have said that social work teachers play significant role in initiating attitudinal change in students.
- Majority 30 (60%) of respondents have said that they support present educational system.
- Majority 33 (66%) of respondents have said that spread of education in villages leads to social change.
- Majority 34 (68%) of respondents have said that education brings change in social institutions viz., family, caste, marriage and religion.
- Majority 46 (92%) of respondents have said that they support female education since it is playing crucial role in bringing social change.
- Majority 32 (64%) of respondents have said that social work education creates sense of belongingness among youth towards society and it creates we feeling.
- Majority 30 (60%) of respondents have said that while teaching they spread awareness regarding agriculture and try to motivate youth to build interest in agriculture.
- Majority 29 (58%) of respondents have said that caste and politics are not interrelated.
- Majority 26 (52%) of respondents have said that education can be a potent force to inspire the women folk for political participation which in turn can contribute to social change.
- Majority 35 (70%) of respondents have said that education plays an important role in arousing the idea of saving money among the youth.

Conclusion

The principal aim of the present study was to examine the role of teachers in bringing social change among youth. The basic assumption is that education can bring change in the attitudes of the youth towards different social institutions i.e. caste, marriage, family, and religion, age old agricultural practices, political participation and also in the matter of saving. Education can certainly play a decisive role in motivating the youth for giving up traditional practices and to welcome change and development. Focus was given to social work teachers in this study.

It came to know from the study that teaching method gives major priority for discussions related to social change. Social work teachers play significant role in initiating attitudinal change in students and also they play major role in creating sense of belongingness among youth and making them to inculcate pro social mindset. Social work teachers are having a opinion that education awakens the consciousness of youth into higher state and results in bringing social change.

References

1. Ahuja, R. (1993), Indian social System, Rewat Publication, Joypur and New Delhi.
2. Christopher, A.J., Thomas William, (2016), Community Organisation and Social Action, Himalaya Publishing House.
3. Gandhi, M.K. (1992), Quoted from "Philosophy and Sociology of Education"
4. Sharma, R. N. Surjeet Publications, Delhi-07.
5. Kothary C.R., (2004), Research Methodology, New Age International.

6. Kuppaswamy, B., (1972), Social Change in India, Konark Publishers Pvt. Ltd., Delhi-92.
7. Mathur, I. (1987), Change in Agrarian Society, Print well Publishers.
8. Sharma, R.N. (1992), Philosophy and Sociology of Education, Surjeet Publications, Delhi. 07.
9. Srinivas, M.N. (1966), Social Change in Modern India, Orient Longman, New Delhi.

Paper 27

**SELECTIVITY AND MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE:
AN EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION OF SELECTED
EQUITY DIVERSIFIED SCHEMES IN INDIA**

Akshatha Suvama

Assistant Professor

Government First Grade College Haleyangadi,
Mangaluru.

Abstract

The mutual fund industry in India has grown to a remarkable extent in the recent decade, therefore performance evaluation is potentially important. The present paper is an empirical study of investment performance of 52 selected Indian equity diversified mutual fund (growth) schemes for the period from 1st April 2009 to 31st March 2019. The performance is evaluated in terms of rate of return, risk and diversification and stock selectivity skills of fund managers. Measures such as Jensen and Fama is used in the analysis of stock selection skills of fund managers. Results shows that about 65% of the mutual fund schemes were able to beat the benchmark markets. All the schemes under study were relatively exposed to less risk than the market, however with high degree of volatility. A majority of the funds were reasonably diversified. Empirical evidence also suggests that fund managers of some of the sample mutual fund schemes were engaged in micro forecasting (or stock selection) as the alpha values in about 38% of the schemes were found to be positive and statistically significant.

Keywords: Return, Risk, Jensen alpha, Fama's measure, Selectivity

1. INTRODUCTION

Economic liberalization and globalization have brought a fervent environment for the medium and small investors in India. With emphasis on increase in domestic savings and improvement in deployment of investment through markets, the need and scope for mutual fund operation has increased tremendously. The mutual fund industry, which began its journey in India with the setting up of the Unit Trust of India in 1964 has grown several folds in terms of size and operations during the past five decades of its existence. There has been substantial growth in terms of assets under management, variety of investment schemes. From a single player the number of players has increased to 44 with managed assets of Rs.23,79,584 crore as on 31st March 2019.

The evaluation of performance of mutual funds and the identification of successful fund managers are of great interest to both investors and academics. Two possible methods are

presumed to be used by fund managers for generating superior performance are identified as 'stock selection' and market timing. Stock selection involve micro forecasting of the price movements of the individual stocks relative to the market and identification of the individual stocks that are under or over valued relative to the equities in general. Market timing skills imply assessing correctly the direction of the market, whether bull or bear, and positioning the portfolios accordingly. These two abilities constitute the major components of active management skills of fund managers. From an academic perspective, the existence (and persistence) of mutual fund managerial ability will imply a rejection of the efficient market hypothesis.

The present paper evaluates the performance of mutual fund schemes through risk-return analysis and also evaluates the stock selection ability of fund managers of selected equity diversified schemes in India. The study contributes to the literature by providing evidence on stock selection ability of fund managers of equity diversified mutual funds in India.

2. Objectives of the Study

1. To evaluate the performance of selected mutual fund schemes on the basis of risk-return parameters.
2. To evaluate the stock selection skills of the fund managers of equity diversified mutual fund schemes in India.

3. Selection of Schemes and Database description

The study uses a sample of 52 equity diversified open ended mutual fund schemes (regular plan with growth option) of various fund houses. The period of the study is for 10 years form 1st April 2009 to 31st March 2019. The sample of 52 schemes has been drawn from the population of Indian equity diversified mutual fund schemes which invests in variety of equity financial assets and which are not sector specific. The schemes may be active or passive in nature. The study has focused on only the active equity diversified schemes for which the stock selection ability is relevant. Mutual fund schemes have both the dividend and growth options, as well as direct and regular scheme. The study has focused on only the regular schemes with growth option.

The mutual fund schemes selected are of varied size and are based on different benchmarks. Schemes launched before April 2009 are included in the study period. The choice of the sample is largely based upon the availability of the necessary data. Only those equity schemes where the continuous data was available for all the 10 years of study period were included in the sample.

Daily net asset values (NAVs) obtained from the official website of the association of mutual funds in India (www.amfiindia.com) has been used for the purpose of the study. NSE Total return index is used as a benchmark. Total returns index reflects the returns on the index arising from (a) constituent stock price movements and (b) dividend receipts from constituent index stocks. From February 2018 all the mutual funds have been mandated to use Total return index as the new benchmark. Data on NSE Total return index and 91 day Treasury bills is collected from NSE website and RBI website respectively.

Table 1: Description of Sample Mutual Fund Schemes and Benchmark Index

	Name of the Scheme	Sub Category	Type	Benchmark	Launch Date
1	Principal Multi Cap Growth Fund(G)	Equity - Multi Cap Fund	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	3-Oct-00
2	DSP Equity Fund-Reg(G)	Equity - Multi Cap Fund	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	4-Apr-97
3	Franklin India Equity Fund(G)	Equity - Multi Cap Fund	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	29-Sep-94
4	HDFC Equity Fund(G)	Equity - Multi Cap Fund	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	8-Dec-94
5	LIC MF Multi Cap Fund(G)	Equity - Multi Cap Fund	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	16-Apr-98
6	Quant Active Fund(G)	Equity - Multi Cap Fund	Open ended	NIFTY 500	19-Feb-01
7	Kotak India EQ Contra Fund(G)	Equity - Contra Fund	Open ended	NIFTY 100 - TRI	2-Jun-05
8	Principal Dividend Yield Fund(G)	Equity - Dividend Yield Fund	Open ended	NIFTY DIV OPPTS 50 - TRI	6-Sep-04
9	Templeton India Equity Income Fund (G)	Equity - Dividend Yield Fund	Open ended	NIFTY DIV OPPTS 50	22-Mar-06
10	UTI Dividend Yield Fund-Reg(G)	Equity - Dividend Yield Fund	Open ended	NIFTY DIV OPPTS 50 - TRI	11-Apr-05

			d		
1 1	Aditya Birla SL Dividend Yield Fund(G)	Equity - Dividend Yield Fund	Open ended	NIFTY DIV OPPS 50 - TRI	23-Jan-03
1 2	Canara Rob Emerg Equities Fund-Reg(G)	Equity - Large & Mid Cap Fund	Open ended	Nifty LargeMidcap 250 Index - TRI	11-Feb-05
1 3	DSP Equity Opportunities Fund-Reg(G)	Equity - Large & Mid Cap Fund	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	11-Mar-00
1 4	Kotak Equity Opp Fund(G)	Equity - Large & Mid Cap Fund	Open ended	NIFTY 200 - TRI	10-Sep-04
1 5	Sundaram Large and Mid Cap Fund(G)	Equity - Large & Mid Cap Fund	Open ended	NIFTY 200 - TRI	10-Jan-07
1 6	Principal Emerging Bluechip Fund(G)	Equity - Large & Mid Cap Fund	Open ended	Nifty LargeMidcap 250 Index - TRI	22-Sep-08
1 7	Franklin India Equity Advantage Fund (G)	Equity - Large & Mid Cap Fund	Open ended	Nifty LargeMidcap 250 Index	17-Jan-05
1 8	ICICI Pru Large & Mid Cap Fund(G)	Equity - Large & Mid Cap Fund	Open ended	Nifty LargeMidcap 250 Index - TRI	1-Jun-98
1 9	SBI Large & Midcap Fund-Reg(G)	Equity - Large & Mid Cap Fund	Open ended	Nifty LargeMidcap 250 Index - TRI	1-Jan-93
2 0	UTI Core Equity Fund-Reg(G)	Equity - Large & Mid Cap Fund	Open ended	Nifty LargeMidcap 250 Index - TRI	20-May-09
2 1	Quant Large & Mid Cap Fund(G)	Equity - Large & Mid Cap Fund	Open	Nifty LargeMidcap 250	20-Nov-06

			ende d	Index	
2 2 2	Mirae Asset Large Cap Fund-Reg(G)	Equity - Large Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	NIFTY 100 - TRI	11-Feb-08
2 3	ICICI PruBluechip Fund(G)	Equity - Large Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	NIFTY 100 - TRI	8-Apr-08
2 4	Aditya Birla SL Frontline Equity Fund (G)	Equity - Large Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	NIFTY 50 - TRI	23-Sep-02
2 5	HDFC Top 100 Fund(G)	Equity - Large Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	NIFTY 100 - TRI	19-Aug-96
2 6	Franklin India Bluechip Fund(G)	Equity - Large Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	NIFTY 100 - TRI	1-Dec-93
2 7	HSBC Large Cap Equity Fund(G)	Equity - Large Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	NIFTY 50 - TRI	14-Nov-02
2 8	LIC MF Large Cap Fund(G)	Equity - Large Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	NIFTY 100 - TRI	1-Sep-94
2 9	DSP Midcap Fund-Reg(G)	Equity - Mid Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Midcap 100 - TRI	29-Sep-06
3 0	HDFC Mid-Cap Opportunities Fund(G)	Equity - Mid Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Midcap 100 - TRI	7-May-07
3 1	Kotak Emerging Equity Scheme(G)	Equity - Mid Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Midcap 100 - TRI	12-Feb-07
3	Aditya Birla SL Midcap	Equity - Mid Cap	Ope	Nifty Midcap 100	9-Sep-02

2	Fund(G)	Fund	n ende d	- TRI	
3 3	ICICI Pru Midcap Fund(G)	Equity - Mid Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Midcap 150 - TRI	6-Sep-04
3 4	Invesco India Midcap Fund(G)	Equity - Mid Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Midcap 100 - TRI	2-Jan-03
3 5	UTI Mid Cap Fund-Reg(G)	Equity - Mid Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Midcap 150 - TRI	21-Feb-05
3 6	SBI Magnum Midcap Fund-Reg(G)	Equity - Mid Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Midcap 150 - TRI	15-Jun-94
3 7	Tata Mid Cap Growth Fund(G)	Equity - Mid Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Midcap 100 - TRI	12-Feb-01
3 8	Quant Mid Cap Fund(G)	Equity - Mid Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Midcap 150	5-Sep-94
3 9	Taurus Discovery (Midcap) Fund-Reg (G)	Equity - Mid Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Midcap 100 - TRI	9-Apr-07
4 0	Aditya Birla SL Small Cap Fund(G)	Equity - Small cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Smallcap 100 - TRI	16-Nov-05
4 1	Franklin India Smaller Cos Fund(G)	Equity - Small cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Smallcap 250 - TRI	30-Dec-04
4 2	Kotak Small Cap Fund(G)	Equity - Small cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Smallcap 50 - TRI	23-Sep-96

43	Quant Small Cap Fund(G)	Equity - Small cap Fund	Open ended	Nifty 250 Smallcap	23-Aug-07
44	ICICI PruSmallcap Fund(G)	Equity - Small cap Fund	Open ended	Nifty 250 - TRI Smallcap	27-Nov-06
45	DSP Tax Saver Fund-Reg(G)	Equity - ELSS	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	11-Dec-12
46	ICICI Pru LT Equity Fund (Tax Saving) (G)	Equity - ELSS	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	1-Jan-96
47	Principal Tax Savings Fund	Equity - ELSS	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	10-Apr-94
48	Franklin India Taxshield(G)	Equity - ELSS	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	30-Sep-05
49	Kotak Tax Saver Scheme(G)	Equity - ELSS	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	31-Mar-96
50	HDFC TaxSaver(G)	Equity - ELSS	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	10-Apr-94
51	Quant Tax Plan(G)	Equity - ELSS	Open ended	NIFTY 50 - TRI	16-Dec-93
52	HDFC Capital Builder Value Fund(G)	Equity - Value Fund	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	16-Dec-93

4. Research Methodology

Return and Risk of selected equity schemes

Fund returns are assumed to be continuously compounded and are calculated as follows:

The daily log returns are computed on the basis of the Net asset values of different schemes and returns on the market index are calculated on the basis of various index values on the respective date for the 10 years.

The log returns from a mutual fund scheme (R_{pt}) at time t , is as follows

p^t

L_n

n^t

C

$=$

$\$$

Where σ_p is the total risk of the scheme portfolio.

The total risk of the market line portfolio is:

m

=

p

)		x))		
Principal Multi Cap Growth Fund(G)	0.0654	36	0.0626	1.0710	1.0709	0.9262	0.9625
DSP Equity Fund-Reg(G)	0.0661	35	0.0626	1.0388	1.0709	0.9001	0.9202
Franklin India Equity Fund(G)	0.0690	26	0.0626	0.9416	1.0709	0.9321	0.8489
HDFC Equity Fund(G)	0.0741	18	0.0626	1.1327	1.0709	0.9009	1.0039
LIC MF Multi Cap Fund(G)	0.0475	49	0.0632	1.1352	1.0759	0.8855	0.9929
Quant Active Fund(G)	0.0675	31	0.0628	1.0953	1.0702	0.5924	0.7877
Kotak India EQ Contra Fund(G)	0.0639	39	0.0627	0.9834	1.0950	0.9216	0.8621
Principal Dividend Yield Fund(G)	0.0640	38	0.0705	0.9997	1.0227	0.8535	0.9031
Templeton India Equity Income Fund (G)	0.0664	32	0.0706	0.9035	1.0229	0.6573	0.7161
UTI Dividend Yield Fund-Reg(G)	0.0596	45	0.0705	0.9157	1.0227	0.8518	0.8263
Aditya Birla SL Dividend Yield Fund(G)	0.0609	43	0.0705	0.9253	1.0227	0.8047	0.8115
Canara Rob Emerg Equities Fund-Reg(G)	0.1012	1	0.0711	1.0256	1.0823	0.8255	0.8610
DSP Equity Opportunities Fund-Reg(G)	0.0691	25	0.0626	1.0093	1.0709	0.9315	0.9097
Kotak Equity Opp Fund(G)	0.0682	30	0.0621	1.0282	1.0850	0.9425	0.9200

Sundaram Large and Mid Cap Fund(G)	0.063 1	41	0.062 1	1.0375	1.0850	0.8399	0.8763
Principal Emerging Bluechip Fund(G)	0.088 7	5	0.071 1	1.0799	1.0823	0.9051	0.9492
Franklin India Equity Advantage Fund (G)	0.069 2	24	0.071 1	1.0165	1.0829	0.9095	0.8953
ICICI Pru Large & Mid Cap Fund(G)	0.060 3	44	0.071 1	0.9950	1.0823	0.8618	0.8535
SBI Large & Midcap Fund-Reg(G)	0.069 5	23	0.071 5	1.0030	1.0792	0.9148	0.8889
UTI Core Equity Fund-Reg(G)	0.027 8	52	0.071 2	1.6975	1.0803	0.3089	0.8734
Quant Large & Mid Cap Fund(G)	0.066 3	33	0.071 3	1.9343	1.0761	0.1856	0.7745
Mirae Asset Large Cap Fund-Reg(G)	0.083 0	8	0.062 7	1.0381	1.0950	0.9470	0.9225
ICICI PruBluechip Fund(G)	0.069 7	22	0.062 7	1.0009	1.0950	0.9469	0.8895
Aditya Birla SL Frontline Equity Fund (G)	0.068 6	28	0.059 2	1.0117	1.0985	0.9517	0.8985
HDFC Top 100 Fund(G)	0.068 4	29	0.062 7	1.1195	1.0950	0.9255	0.9835
Franklin India Bluechip Fund(G)	0.061 8	42	0.062 7	0.9500	1.0950	0.9415	0.8417
HSBC Large Cap Equity Fund(G)	0.050 5	48	0.059 2	1.0151	1.0985	0.9348	0.8934
LIC MF Large Cap Fund(G)	0.055 9	46	0.063 3	1.0932	1.0996	0.8977	0.9419
DSP Midcap Fund-Reg(G)	0.086 7	6	0.072 8	1.0746	1.1748	0.8678	0.8521
HDFC Mid-Cap Opportunities Fund(G)	0.091 5	2	0.073 2	0.9397	1.1747	0.6736	0.6565
Kotak Emerging Equity	0.079	12	0.073	0.9747	1.1747	0.8756	0.7764

Scheme(G)	4		2				
Aditya Birla SL Midcap Fund(G)	0.0773	15	0.0732	1.0826	1.1747	0.0773	0.0732
ICICI Pru Midcap Fund(G)	0.0791	13	0.0800	1.0082	1.1561	0.8586	0.8081
Invesco India Midcap Fund(G)	0.0893	4	0.0732	0.9647	1.1747	0.8530	0.7584
UTI Mid Cap Fund-Reg(G)	0.0844	7	0.0800	1.0573	1.1561	0.9079	0.8714
SBI Magnum Midcap Fund-Reg(G)	0.0819	9	0.0805	1.0792	1.1508	0.8389	0.8589
Tata Mid Cap Growth Fund(G)	0.0802	11	0.0732	1.0194	1.1747	0.8745	0.8115
Quant Mid Cap Fund(G)	0.0375	50	0.0802	0.6134	1.1457	0.2996	0.2930
Taurus Discovery (Midcap) Fund-Reg (G)	0.0741	19	0.0732	1.1635	1.1747	0.8921	0.9355
Aditya Birla SL Small Cap Fund(G)	0.0816	10	0.0629	1.0648	1.3328	0.8380	0.7313
Franklin India Smaller Cos Fund(G)	0.0913	3	0.0684	1.0055	1.2350	0.8490	0.7502
Kotak Small Cap Fund(G)	0.0774	14	0.0511	1.0443	1.4863	0.8030	0.6296
Quant Small Cap Fund(G)	0.0330	51	0.0687	1.2126	1.2340	0.0098	0.0974
ICICI PruSmallcap Fund(G)	0.0643	37	0.0698	0.8208	1.2568	0.6117	0.5108
DSP Tax Saver Fund-Reg(G)	0.0736	20	0.0626	0.9977	1.0709	0.9381	0.9023
ICICI Pru LT Equity Fund (Tax Saving) (G)	0.0764	16	0.0626	0.9146	1.0709	0.8915	0.8063
Principal Tax Savings Fund	0.0661	34	0.0626	1.0799	1.0709	0.9272	0.9710

Franklin India Taxshield(G)	0.071 6	21	0.062 6	0.9316	1.0709	0.9300	0.8389
Kotak Tax Saver Scheme(G)	0.063 5	40	0.062 6	1.0379	1.0709	0.9518	0.9455
HDFC TaxSaver(G)	0.068 7	27	0.062 6	1.0139	1.0709	0.8859	0.8911
Quant Tax Plan(G)	0.052 5	47	0.059 3	1.0469	1.1013	0.5415	0.6995
HDFC Capital Builder Value Fund(G)	0.075 8	17	0.062 6	0.9431	1.0709	0.9094	0.8398

Return and Risk Analysis

The average daily return along with the ranking based on this return is presented in Table 2. All the schemes have recorded positive average daily return values during the study period. A close look at the Table 2 indicates that out of the total 52 schemes 34 schemes (65%) have outperformed the market by earning returns higher than the market/benchmark returns, whereas 18 schemes have under performed the market index. The risk free return 0.0193 for the study period and all the schemes have earned returns greater than the risk free rate of return.

The ranking pattern based on return statistics shows that Canara Robeco Emerging Equity Fund (Equity Large & Mid-cap fund), HDFC Mid-Cap Opportunities Fund(G) (Mid-cap), Franklin India Smaller companies Fund (Small-Cap) have got the top 1st, 2nd and 3rd ranks respectively.

The **total risk** (Standard deviation) incorporates systematic and unsystematic risk (beta). The standard deviation of all the schemes lies between 1.9343 (Quant Large & Mid Cap Fund) and 0.6134 (Quant Mid Cap Fund). Taking the Scheme wise risk in terms of **Standard deviation** only 8 schemes (15%) have undertaken higher risk than the market whereas all other funds analysed in this study have lower risk compared to market in general.

Positive value of **beta** in the case of all the mutual fund schemes indicates that the fund return closely follows the market return. All the schemes except one scheme that is HDFC Equity Fund have recorded beta less than 1 indicating holding of relatively less risky portfolio than the market portfolio. However, majority of the schemes are highly volatile as their betas have high value, 38 schemes have recorded a beta of more than 0.8.

Diversification: Co-efficient of determination (R^2)

Table 2 also shows the values of co-efficient of determination for each of the 52 equity diversified schemes, when measured with the market index, 42 out of 52 schemes i.e about 81% of the sampled funds have recorded R^2 value of more than 0.8 which indicates that these schemes have reasonably exploited the diversification strategy in forming their portfolio. The highest R^2 value was found in Kotak Tax saver scheme (0.9518) and the lowest R^2 value was found in Quant Small Cap fund (0.00981).

Sl. no	Scheme	Jensen Measure				Fama's measure					
		Jensen Alpha	Rank	t-Stat	P-value	Rf	Compensation for systematic risk	Compensation for inadequate diversification	Net superior returns	Average (Fund)	Rank (Fama net selectivity)
1	Principal Multi Cap Growth Fund(G)	0.00438	39	0.7461	0.4557	0.0193	0.0401	0.0032	0.0028	0.0654	35
2	DSP Equity Fund-Reg(G)	0.00698	32	1.0532	0.2924	0.0193	0.039	0.003	0.0048	0.0661	30
3	Franklin India Equity Fund(G)	0.013 *	20	2.6245	0.0087	0.0193	0.0404	-0.0023	0.0117	0.069	18
4	HDFC Equity Fund(G)	0.01133 *	23	0.1156	-0.0028	0.0193	0.039	0.0068	0.009	0.0741	21
5	LIC MF Multi Cap Fund(G)	-0.0153	51	-1.969	0.0491	0.0193	0.0389	0.0075	-0.0181	0.0475	49
6	Quant Active	0.0139	18	0.9854	0.3245	0.0193	0.0258	0.0188	0.0037	0.0675	32

	Fund(G)										
7	Kotak India EQ Contra Fund(G)	0.0072	31	1.2945	0.1956	0.0193	0.04	-0.001	0.0056	0.0639	27
8	Principal Dividend Yield Fund(G)	0.0016	46	-0.206	0.8366	0.0193	0.0438	0.0064	0.0054	0.064	43
9	Templeton India Equity Income Fund(G)	0.0104	26	1.4834	0.1381	0.0193	0.0337	0.0116	0.0018	0.0664	37
10	UTI Dividend Yield Fund-Reg(G)	0.0021	47	-0.29	0.7722	0.0193	0.0437	0.0022	0.0056	0.0596	44
11	Aditya Birla SL Dividend Yield Fund(G)	0.0001	45	0.0008	0.9994	0.0193	0.0412	0.0051	0.0048	0.0609	41

12	Cana ra Rob Emerg Equiti es Fund- Reg(G)	0.037 29 *	3	4.31 07	0	0.019 3	0.042 8	0.0063	0.032 8	0.1012	2
13	DSP Equity Oppor tunitie s Fund- Reg(G)	0.010 37	2 7	1.94 54	0.05 18	0.019 3	0.040 4	0.0005	0.008 9	0.0691	22
14	Kota k Equity Opp Fund(G)	0.009 47	2 9	1.90 16	0.05 73	0.019 3	0.040 4	0.0002	0.008 3	0.0682	25
15	Sund aram Large and Mid Cap Fund(G)	0.006 28	3 5	0.75	0.45 33	0.019 3	0.036	0.005	0.002 9	0.0631	34
16	Princ ipal Emerg ing Bluec hip Fund(G)	0.020 25 *	1 1	3.01 53	0.00 26	0.019 3	0.046 9	0.0048	0.017 7	0.0887	11
17	Frankl in India Equity	0.003 48	4 2	0.56 41	0.57 28	0.019 3	0.047 2	0.0015	0.001 2	0.0692	40

	Advan tage Fund (G)										
18	ICICI Pru Large & Mid Cap Fund(G)	- 0.003 2	4 8	- 0.42 4	0.67 16	0.019 3	0.044 7	0.003	- 0.006 6	0.0603	46
19	SBI Large & Midcap Fund-Reg(G)	0.003 74	4 1	0.62 97	0.52 89	0.019 3	0.047 8	0.0008	0.001 6	0.0695	38
20	UTI Core Equity Fund-Reg(G)	- 0.036 8	5 2	-1.29	0.19 72	0.019 3	0.016	0.0655	- 0.073	0.0278	52
21	Quant Large & Mid Cap Fund(G)	0.006 75	3 3	0.19 13	0.84 83	0.019 3	0.009 7	0.0838	- 0.046 5	0.0663	51
22	Mira Asset Large Cap Fund-Reg(G)	0.023 74 *	8	4.91 95	0	0.019 3	0.041 1	0	0.022 6	0.083	7

23	ICIC PruBluechip Fund(G)	0.01183 *	22	2.5403	0.0111	0.0193	0.0411	-0.0014	0.0108	0.0697	19
24	Aditya Birla SL Frontline Equity Fund (G)	0.01348 *	19	3.003	0.0027	0.0193	0.038	-0.0012	0.0126	0.0686	16
25	HDFC Top 100 Fund(G)	0.00643	34	1.042	0.2975	0.0193	0.0402	0.0042	0.0047	0.0684	31
26	Franklin India Bluechip Fund(G)	0.00604	36	1.3025	0.1929	0.0193	0.0409	-0.0032	0.0049	0.0618	29
27	HSBC Large Cap Equity Fund(G)	-0.0045	49	-0.851	0.395	0.0193	0.0373	-0.0004	-0.0057	0.0505	45
28	LIC MF Large Cap Fund(G)	-0.0048	50	-0.678	0.4978	0.0193	0.0395	0.0042	-0.0071	0.0559	47
29	DSP Midcap	0.0218 *	10	2.7631	0.0058	0.0193	0.0465	0.0025	0.0185	0.0867	9

	Fund-Reg(G)											
30	HDFC Mid-Cap Opportunities Fund(G)	0.03685 *	4	3.3991	0.0007	0.0193	0.0363	0.0068	0.0291	0.0915	4	
31	Kotak Emerging Equity Scheme(G)	0.01833 *	14	2.6416	0.0083	0.0193	0.0472	-0.0025	0.0155	0.0794	12	
32	Aditya Birla SL Midcap Fund(G)	0.87107	1	1.5572	0.1195	0.0193	0.0042	0.0455	0.0084	0.0773	23	
33	ICICI Pru Midcap Fund(G)	0.01076	25	1.4049	0.1602	0.0193	0.0521	0.0008	0.0069	0.0791	26	
34	Invesco India Midcap Fund(G)	0.02917 *	7	3.9056	0.0001	0.0193	0.046	-0.0017	0.0258	0.0893	6	
35	UTI Mid Cap	0.01225	21	1.8902	0.0589	0.0193	0.0551	0.0004	0.0096	0.0844	20	

	Fund-Reg(G)										
36	SBI Magnum Midcap Fund-Reg(G)	0.01004	28	1.1435	0.253	0.0193	0.0514	0.0061	0.0052	0.0819	28
37	Tata Mid Cap Growth Fund(G)	0.01723 *	15	2.3631	0.0182	0.0193	0.0471	-0.0004	0.0142	0.0802	14
38	Quant Mid Cap Fund(G)	0.00042	44	0.0408	0.9675	0.0193	0.0183	0.0144	-0.0143	0.0375	48
39	Taurus Discovery (Midcap) Fund-Reg (G)	0.00437	40	0.5669	0.5708	0.0193	0.0481	0.0053	0.0014	0.0741	39
40	Aditya Birla SL Small Cap Fund(G)	0.03044 *	6	4.1114	0	0.0193	0.0366	-0.0017	0.0275	0.0816	5
41	Franklin India Smalle	0.03517 *	5	4.4593	0	0.0193	0.0417	-0.0017	0.032	0.0913	3

	r Cos Fund(G)										
42	Kotak Small Cap Fund(G)	0.03805 *	2	4.0692	0	0.0193	0.0256	-0.0032	0.0357	0.0774	1
43	Quant Small Cap Fund(G)	0.0089	30	0.3645	0.7155	0.0193	0.0005	0.0481	-0.0349	0.033	50
44	ICICI Prusmallcap Fund(G)	0.01915 *	13	2.7371	0.0062	0.0193	0.0309	0.0021	0.012	0.0643	17
45	DSP Tax Saver Fund-Reg(G)	0.01529 *	17	3.0505	0.0023	0.0193	0.0407	-0.0003	0.014	0.0736	15
46	ICICI Pru LT Equity Fund (Tax Saving) (G)	0.02222 *	9	3.6532	0.0003	0.0193	0.0386	-0.0016	0.0202	0.0764	8
47	Principal Tax Savings Fund	0.00481	38	0.9122	0.3617	0.0193	0.0402	0.0035	0.0032	0.0661	33

48	Franklin India Taxshield(G)	0.01602 *	16	3.2189	0.0013	0.0193	0.0403	-0.0026	0.0147	0.0716	13
49	Kotak Tax Saver Scheme(G)	0.00324	43	0.7038	0.4816	0.0193	0.0412	0.0008	0.0022	0.0635	36
50	HDFC TaxSaver(G)	0.01079	24	1.5598	0.1189	0.0193	0.0384	0.0026	0.0084	0.0687	24
51	Quant Tax Plan(G)	0.00517	37	0.3606	0.7184	0.0193	0.0217	0.0164	-0.0049	0.0525	42
52	HDFC Capital Builder Value Fund(G)	0.02019 *	12	3.5235	0.0004	0.0193	0.0394	-0.0012	0.0184	0.0758	10
					Average		0.0193	0.0377	0.0071	0.0049	
					(in percentage)		27.80	54.49	10.36	7.34	100

Assessing Stock selectivity using Jensen Measure

Table 3. gives the results of Jensen measure of the selected mutual fund equity diversified growth schemes. A close examination of the Table reveals that 45 schemes have posted positive alpha values out of 52 equity diversified schemes considered in this study, which indicates that about 86% of fund managers out of the sampled schemes were able to beat the market by using their skill in the selection of the portfolio. This is an indication of the superior stock selection ability of equity fund managers. Best performing funds in terms of Jensen’s alpha during the study period are Aditya Birla SL Small Cap fund, Kotak Small Cap fund (Both from small-cap category) and Canara Robeco Emerging Equity fund (from the Large and Mid-cap fund category)

Out of the schemes with positive alpha values 20 schemes (38%) have generated a significantly positive alpha value at five percent level of significance. This is an evidence of portfolio manager's predictive ability to earn superior returns.

The schemes with significant positive value consists of two multi-cap funds (Franklin India Equity and HDFC Equity) , two Large and Mid-cap fund (Canara Robeco Emerging Equity and Principal Emerging Bluechip) and three Large-cap fund (Mirae Asset Large-cap, ICICI PruBluechip and Aditya Birla SL Frontline Equity), five Mid-cap fund (DSP Mid-cap, HDFC Mid-cap, Kotak Emerging Equity, Invesco India Midcap and Tata Mid-cap) and four Small-Cap fund (Aditya Birla SL Small cap, Franklin India Small-cap, Kotak Small-cap, ICICI Pru Small cap) and three ELSS schemes (DSP Tax saver, ICICI Pru Equity, Franklin India Tax Shield) and One Equity Value fund (HDFC Capital builder value fund) have successfully generated significantly positive alpha values at five percent level of significance. This indicates that the fund managers of these schemes have shown superior selectivity skills in India.

Assessing Fama's components to evaluate the performance of selected schemes

Results on Fama's decomposition measure have been placed in Table 3. The Fama model result shows that risk premium is positive for all the schemes. This means that all the 52 schemes considered in the study had provided positive performance on account of risk bearing activity of fund managers. Risk premium is found to be very high for the schemes compared to the other components of investment performance. In average, as expected risk premium is found to be very high (0.0377) (about 54.5%) and eats up a substantial portion of the actual average daily return earned by the scheme. This is mainly because of high systematic risk assumed by the schemes as represented by their beta values close to 1.

With regard to compensation for inadequate diversification 36 schemes (69%) out of 52 had shown positive performance.

After accounting for diversification, the residual performance on selectivity is attributed to net selectivity and it will be equal to (or less than) that on selectivity. A positive net selectivity will indicate superior performance. However, in case net selectivity is negative it would mean that the portfolio manager has not justified the loss of diversification.

In terms of net selectivity 40 schemes (77%) showed positive values indicating superior stock selection ability of the fund managers of these schemes and the rest 12 schemes (23%) have shown negative return. Kotak Small Cap Fund (Rank 1), Canara Robeco Emerging Equity (Rank 2) and Franklin India Smaller Cos Fund (Rank 3) are the top three schemes in the context of overall stock selection ability following Fama (1972).

Analysis of Jensen and Fama results It is important to report that all the schemes which have shown negative selectivity following Jensen criterion, have scored negative selectivity values following this measure also. In the selectivity analysis as per Jensen measure 7 schemes have shown negative returns. And as per net selectivity of Fama's measure of performance 12 schemes have shown negative performance. For the five schemes Aditya Birla SL Dividend Yield,

Quant Large & Mid Cap, Quant Mid Cap, Quant Small cap and Quant Tax plan though the overall selectivity scores are positive, their net selectivity scores turn to be negative. This means that these 5 funds have failed to generate enough returns to recover even a part of the compensation for the inadequate diversification of their portfolio. This suggests that these schemes could not justify the loss of diversification.

In this context, the results of Quant Small cap fund is worth to be mentioned separately. On the selectivity aspects, this scheme has earned a positive return of 0.0089 and ranked 30th. But due to very poor diversification ($R^2=0.00981$), compensation expected by the investors for the same is reported to be very high (0.04809). Hence, net selectivity of the scheme (-0.03486) becomes one of the worst schemes and contributed enough to bring down the rank of the scheme to 50.

Thus 39 schemes out of 52 schemes considered in the study, which had reported positive net selectivity seem to be more reliable as far as the professional skill of the managers is concerned during the study period. On an average there is a positive net selectivity of 0.00492.

4. Conclusion

The present study has evaluated the performance of Indian equity diversified mutual fund schemes in terms of return and risk and diversification. Study also assessed the stock selection ability by applying the measures such as Jensen and Fama. The analysis of average return indicated that all the schemes were able to earn a positive return greater than the average risk free rate of return. About 65% of the mutual fund schemes outperformed the market. Beta values revealed that schemes were relatively exposed to less risk than the market as all the schemes under study except one have a beta value less than one. But beta values greater than 0.8 indicated a high degree of volatility. A majority of the funds were reasonably diversified. Empirical evidence also suggests that fund managers of some of the sample mutual fund schemes were engaged in micro forecasting (or stock selection) as the alpha values in case of 20 schemes (38%) were positive and statistically significant at five percent level. This is an evidence of portfolio manager's predictive ability to earn superior returns. 40 out of 52 (i.e about 77%) schemes had reported positive net selectivity which indicates professional skill of the managers. We can therefore say that Indian mutual fund industry has been able to add value to its investors wealth through its stock selectivity ability. It still has the potential to outperform the market.

References

1. Aman Srivastava and Rakesh Gupta (2010), "Performance appraisal of equity schemes of Indian Mutual funds", JIMS –September 2010, pp.4-13.
2. Beehary Nitish, Rojid Sawkut, "Analysing mutual funds performance: The case of Emerging Mauritian Economy", The Icfai University Journal of Financial Economics, Vol.VII, No.2, 2009, pp.47-57.
3. Deepti Sahoo and Naresh Kumar Sharma, "Performance evaluation of Indian Mutual Fund Industry: A Case Study".
4. Himanshu Puri (2010), "Performance evaluation of Balanced Mutual Fund Schemes in Indian Scenario", Paradigm, Vol.XIV, No.2, July-December, 2010, pp. 20-28.

5. Himanshu Puri and Sakshisaxena (2012), "Construction and evaluation of optimal portfolio using Sharpe's single index model", *Journal of Accounting and Finance*, Vol.26, No.1, October 2011-March 2012, pp.109-121.
6. Jayadev M (1998), "Performance evaluation of portfolio managers: An empirical evidence on Indian mutual funds", *The IUP Journal of Applied Finance* 5, No.2, pp.41-67.
7. Jensen (1967), "The Performance of Mutual Funds in the period 1945-1964", *Journal of Finance*, Vol.23, No.2, pp.389-416, 1967.
8. Malik N.S (2008), "Portfolio Management: Country Funds" *SCMS Journal of Indian management*, January-March, pp.19-35.
9. Musa Essayyad and H.K.Wu (1988) "The performance of U.S. International Mutual Funds", *Quarterly Journal of Business and Economics*, Vol.27, No.4, pp.32-46.
10. Rakesh Kumar (2012), "Market timing, selectivity and mutual fund performance: An empirical investigation of selective equity diversified schemes in India" *The IUP Journal of Financial Economics*, Vol.X, No.1, pp.62-84.
11. Shrinivas R Patil, Prof Prakash Rao K.S (2011) "An Empirical Study on performance of mutual fund in India" *Journal of contemporary research in management*, April-June 2011, pp.91-103.
12. Sondhi H.J and Jain P.K (2006), "Market Risk and investment performance of equity mutual funds in India: Some Empirical Evidences", *Finance India*, Vol.XXIV, No.2, June 2010, pp.43-462.
13. Soumya Guha Deb (2008), "Performance of Indian Equity Mutual Funds vis-à-vis their Style Benchmarks", *The Icfai Journal of Applied Finance*, Vol.14, No.1, pp 49-81.
14. Sushil Kumar Mehta (2010), "State Bank of India Vs. Unit Trust of India: A comparison of Performance of Mutual fund schemes.", *Indian Journal of Finance*, February 2010, pp.24-31.
15. Vangapandu Rama Devi and Nooney Lenin Kumar (2010), "Performance evaluation of Equity mutual funds", *JIMS*, April-June, pp.22-35.
16. Chetna Vashisht (2017), "Manager's Stock selection and Market timing ability: Application of unconditional models in Indian Mutual Fund Industry", *Indian Journal of Economics and Development* 133, pp.507-513.
17. Suveera Gill, Arshdeep (2012), "Selectivity and Market Timing ability of Mutual Fund Managers in India: An Empirical Investigation", *Prajnan*, Vol. XLI, No.1, pp. 21-41.

Websites:

www.amfindia.com,

www.mutualfundsindia.com.

www.moneycontrol.com

www.rbi.org.in

Paper 28

JOB FAIR AND CSR

Varun Shenoy & P. S. Aithal

Srinivas University, Mangalore – 575 001, India

E-mail : varun_shenoy@rediffmail.com

Abstract

Socially organizing, participation and supporting Job Fairs is a mandatory obligation of all stakeholders involved towards employment generation in the economy. However, Job Fairs are also viewed with commercial intention by stakeholders for benefits or profits. A commercial approach in such a situation over runs the social patriotic agenda of societal development, economy and manpower development of a country. Though CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility) mandates organizations to conduct social activities, sponsoring or holding public job fairs or at least freewill participation in such career fairs as a social responsibility has always remained a rare sight for corporations or employers. Further presence of third-party business-oriented consultants in the market with lobbying tactics has also made government agencies responsible for holding employment fairs enticed towards favouritism. Therefore, this research investigates the differences involved in holding a Social job fair as compared with Commercial motives of participating recruiters in those fairs. The paper also propagates national and international sensitivity towards employment generation by listing out Employers' positions and standing in job fair participations for social-national-global cause and its importance with relation to CSR.

Keywords : CSR Job Fair, Social Job Fair, Social Employment Fair, Social Career Fair

I. Introduction :

Career fairs continue to be a popular method for employers looking for human talent and they should be considerate for any parties organizing the same for them especially Not for Profit Firms, NGO's or HEI's. However, there is also a paid outsourced practice of holding customized job fairs by commercial event management firms. Opportunistically, Organizations in order to minimize operating expenditure depend on social organizations for holding job fair, but pressurize them through predatory tactics to use the platform for filling manpower from society for business requirements (Experience Interviews). This action conflicts the generally perceived Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in the eyes of general public. Thus, this study analyses the relationship significance of a Pure CSR Action with a Commercial Motive in holding recruitments in a JOB FAIR.

II. Objectives of the Research :

This study thrives to accomplish following noble objectives :

- (1) To understand the commercial motive of business organizations participating in job fairs.

- (2) To propagate the importance of aligning recruitment and selection with Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).
- (3) To educate the significance of social cause at Job Fairs to business organizations.

III. Research Methodology :

Direct Opinion Interviews and Experience Interviews were conducted with a Focused Group of HR from select 30 Business Organizations. The responses so obtained was analysed for findings and thereby conclusions.

IV. Analysis and Interpretations :

Following is the concluded Summary of Discussions related to the topic :

- (1) HRM Function is not a part of CSR but a part of primary business function for profit organizations. Therefore, commercial and professional expectations are demanded with job fair organizers.
- (2) Job Fair is one of the sources of manpower recruitment methods.
- (3) There is no mandated rules or law to be followed in holding and participating in job fairs to be viewed as a social cause.
- (4) Holding Job Fairs is the responsibility of social institutions like Not for Profit Organizations, District Employment Centres, District Industries Centre, NGO's, Trust and Foundations, Educational Institutions with social standing and NOT Business Organizations.
- (5) Business Organizations do not want to hold job fairs as it does not want to incur expenditure from its profit centre. Job Applications are welcome instead.
- (6) Confirmed participating business organizations can cancel participations in job fair even in last minute citing business urgency or meetings.
- (7) The law says a company can undertake its CSR activities only through a registered trust, a registered society or a non-profit firm. Hence, it is extra efforts and expenditure to promote recruitments when it is easy to promote the same as a business function instead.

V. Findings :

Upon analysis and interpretation of above summary of discussions following findings were deduced :

- (1) Organizations are not favourably directed towards joining the social cause of employment generation in job fairs from a CSR Perspective. They hold Organizers accountable if no candidate walks in to their centre in the venue.
- (2) Lack of uniform law across organizations to align Employment Opportunity Provision as a CSR does not exist making organizations to approach business as usual approach in job fairs.
- (3) Organization Officials demand in exorbitantly hospitality demands from fair organizers to provide travel, food and accommodation for job fair participations.
- (4) Purposefully provide negative feedback for character assassination of job fair organizers to obtain publicity.
- (5) Social Enterprises or Not for Profit Organizations find it hard to bring job seekers and business minded companies bring together for a social job fair.

VI. Extended Suggestions :

- (1) Keeping in view of Employment Creation, Government should make Employment Opportunity Provision (EOP) as an integral part of CSR through appropriate amendments in the Schedule VII, Companies Act 2013.
- (2) Minimum number of Participation in Job Fair should be made mandatory in a financial or business year as CSR through appropriate amendments in the Schedule VII, Companies Act 2013.
- (3) Business Organizations should also take Onus in promoting their company in the job fair for better job seeker visibility and shoulder support with organizers. For example, like supplying their flyers, banners, business cards with recruiter contact details as well as SPONSORSHIP for better cause.
- (4) Companies should start by listing out all points of interaction with society across its value chain to derive a complete list of possible initiatives it could execute. The next step is to rank each of the items on this long list on the basis of the extent of social impact and impact on the firm's long-term competitiveness.

VII. Conclusions :

To conclude, employment creation efforts still lay outside the gambit of CSR for Business Organizations. For Business Organizations, Employment Opportunity efforts through Job Fair are primary business requirement initiatives and not social cause. Pre-existing Industry Academia Gap at Market is due to a lack of alignment of mandatory employment opportunity creation requirement on to CSR laws. Job Fairs could be a Social Cause for Organizations from Publicity and Marketing perspective only. Moreover, there is tax benefit for companies actually undertaking CSR activities for specific activities only, which is unfair.

References :

- [1] Karani, A. P., & Day, J. G. (2011). Corporate social responsibility and employee recruiting in the tourism industry. *scholarworks.umass.edu*.
- [2] Duarte, A. P., Gomes, D. R., & Das Neves, J. G. (2014). Tell me your socially responsible practices, I will tell you how attractive for recruitment you are! The impact of perceived CSR on organizational attractiveness. *Tékhné, 12*, 22-29.
- [3] Gond, J. P., Igalens, J., Swaen, V., & El Akremi, A. (2011). The human resources contribution to responsible leadership: An exploration of the CSR–HR interface. *In Responsible Leadership Springer, Dordrecht*, pp. 115-132.
- [4] Jamali, D. R., El Dirani, A. M., & Harwood, I. A. (2015). Exploring human resource management roles in corporate social responsibility: the CSR-HRM co-creation model. *Business Ethics: A European Review, 24*(2), 125-143.
- [5] Cohen, E. (2017). *CSR for HR: A necessary partnership for advancing responsible business practices*. Routledge.
- [6] Inyang, B. J., Awa, H. O., & Enuoh, R. O. (2011). CSR-HRM nexus: Defining the role engagement of the human resources professionals. *International Journal of Business and Social Science, 2*(5), 118-126.
- [7] Szczepańska-Woszczyzna, K. (2015). Responsible leadership contribution to human resource management-a study of csr-hr interface. *Procedia Economics and Finance, 34*, 403-409.
- [8] Lam, H., & Khare, A. (2010). HR's crucial role for successful CSR. *Journal of International Business Ethics, 3*(2), 3-15.

[9] Ledwidge, J. (2007). Corporate social responsibility: the risks and opportunities for HR: Integrating human and social values into the strategic and operational fabric. *Human resource management international digest*, 15(6), 27-30.

[10] Bučiūnienė, I., & Kazlauskaitė, R. (2012). The linkage between HRM, CSR and performance outcomes. *Baltic Journal of Management*, 7(1), 5-24.

Paper 29

APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN DIGITALIZATION OF HUMAN RESOURCES

***Dr. Babu Tejavath, **Dr. Wahed Mohiuddin**

*Dr. Babu Tejavath, Assistant Professor, Department of HRM, University Arts and Science College, Hanamkonda, KU, Warangal. Email ID: babutejavath@gmail.com

**Dr. Wahed Mohiuddin, Associate Professor, Department of Management Studies, Nigama Engineering College, Karimnagar. Email ID: wahedhr@gmail.com.

Abstract

In a fierce competitive era, organizations have moved from traditional human resource management to digital human resource management for their survival and to be market leaders. Present days the companies are having competitive edge with the digital technologies from one another in order to dominate the business empire. To be global, companies are digitally transforming their human resource management. Innovations and advances in digital technology has made easier for HR manager to take decisions and manage the people. Companies are incorporating digital technology in order to transform their business. Digitalization of human resource management also reduces costs, improves the speed and quality of human resource processes. We are using technology to deliver human resource management activities. Digital work place can be created fully with the help of HR technologies such as Artificial Intelligence, robotics, cloud computing etc. The organizations have to identify the area of their opportunity to betterly work and efficiently use the HR tools.

The workplace of present days is infused with technology and systems. Digitalization processes now have come as angels for the companies which will help them to predict different aspects such as attrition, engagement level, retention and development of employees. The aim of this paper focuses on the application of artificial intelligence and digitalization of human resources with the objective to accelerate and withstand in a global competition of the companies.

Keywords: Collaboration, Resources, Application, Global, Development, Technology.

Introduction

A digital technology plays an important role in the lives of employees and human resource management. Digitalization poses many new challenges and opportunities to reshape their role and responsibilities to strategically driven. The greatest challenge for the managers is to identify the changes, groom, prepare them and connect with digital information and communication technologies. Due to innovations in computing and telecommunication

technologies the capacity of humans to store, transmit and manipulate information has expanded to a large extent. An innovative strategy can create more digital opportunities where companies can position as a market leader. Human Resource strategy enables the employees to learn and grow and develops amazing talent among them. A strategic plan has to be developed in order to increase company value and performance and should be integrated with technology. HRD professional should focus more on retaining workforce and also keeping them actively engaged even in times of mass retrenchments and economic slowdown. Employees are to be recruited, developed, compensated and then integrated in an organized manner so, as to give their best to the organizations.

The new technologies are reshaping employee skills, experience and enabling greater integration and flexibility by building innovative human strategies. With the help of new technologies the repetitive task will be streamlined and efficiency can be increased as the firm can concentrate on problem solving and learning activities.

Present days are the age of artificial intelligence which has predominated the world and used by various professionals and disciplines to foster their growth. Due to the use of HR technologies the physical barriers has come down. The organizations are transforming themselves with the collaborations and communicating by using artificial intelligence. According to Donald Sothorn, Artificial Intelligence helps in handling recruitment process, retention of employees and also increased productivity more efficiently than traditional human resources methods.

Though human resource is very difficult to control, if it is utilized efficiently gives outstanding results and adds value to the business. Human resource is the power of the organization. Among all, human resources are one of the important resources in managing stakeholders with the help of artificial intelligence. Josh Bersin in an article, “How will Artificial Intelligence in HR be a game-changer”? explained that Artificial Intelligence based tools are transforming human resource processes and eliminating human errors. According to him Artificial Intelligence does the following functions such as HR screening, reading documents, to interpret, selecting prospective candidates through video based interviews. Companies can tap inherent potential and retain them for a longer time. Managing HR data properly and efficiently is one of the major threats to the company and also a challenge that is posed to the human resource department. Digitalization involves new organizational processes as well as changes in artifacts themselves. To lead digitalization initiatives, expertise is needed and the required tools and technology to be adequate. With the help of messaging, team communication and collaboration has become easier for keeping employees in touch of information.

Need of the Artificial Intelligence

Many disciplines such as electronics, electrical, mechanical, marketing, agriculture and bio-technology where Artificial Intelligence is adopted. Artificial Intelligence has already penetrated into the leading sectors like banking, medical, telecommunication, healthcare, pharmaceuticals and information technology, transportation, education, advertising, film

industry, legal services and insurance sectors for assistance and development of the organizations. Embracing artificial intelligence is the key for success of the organizations and to digitally transform themselves. There is a need to study and to do research of Artificial intelligence in human resources field. To provide solutions to the organizations as they have to struggle in terms of managing cost, quality, innovation etc. The present paper discuss about the Artificial Intelligence in different purposes related to Human Resources in companies.

Artificial Intelligence in Human Resources

Delays in hiring and recruitment of human resources can be reduced due to use of artificial intelligence. The HR software tools are designed in such a way that it analyzes, gather information and identify candidates. Through artificial intelligence the following functions of human resource department can be done.

1. Recruitment

Using human resource tools help the companies to save lot of time, money and energy. The cost of poor hiring and wrong decisions can be avoided. The human resource tool helps in reading, interpreting, translating and scanning the applications applied for jobs.

2. Training

The planning, organizing, learning and training of the employees can be done effectively by the use of digital technologies applied by the organizations. Today, in the age of online courses, video-conferencing and webinars, companies which are applying the human resource tools for digitalization process are successfully competing with other and also giving required knowledge to the employees in handling their jobs. Social tools such as whatsapp, facebook, linkedin, twitter etc., playing an important role in training the employees.

3. Employee Engagement and Performance Appraisal

Engaging employees is one of the biggest and difficult tasks for an organization. Constant monitoring their behavior is also a big challenge in these days. By using human resource tools such as artificial intelligence gives better results. It also helps in improving productivity and boosts the engagement of employees in a proper way.

4. Retention

Retaining the talented employees can be done with the help of artificial intelligence in an effective way. The tool helps in identifying the efficient and hardworking employees, so that they can be retain the skilled people in a right manner.

The workplace can be more efficient, vibrant, thrilling and employees will be highly dedicated to work if we bring artificial intelligence into human resources for doing speedy work. In today's world artificial intelligence has become the reality. As the activities of human resources are digitally transforming, companies has to catch up to the expectations of the

employees and customers in order to prosper and be in the competition. The google company is using next generation artificial intelligence training system. According to Nick Stat, google organization uses technologies to improve google translate, google photos and software etc.,

Conclusion

As the world is becoming more complex, dynamic and increasingly uncertain the digitalization process helps the companies in reaching their goals. The present days with the help of Artificial Intelligence the company can engage the candidate either before or after they apply for a job in the companies. Re-engagement can also be done with the help of artificial intelligence to update candidate to learn new positions, work experiences. In the present days, the technology has completely redefined the role of human resources. It is mechanizing huge task that employees are doing to improve their work process. With the application of artificial intelligence in human resources an immense amount of time can be saved. By application of artificial intelligence in organizations, administrative work of the managers will be saved for doing repetitive work. In this way it can make a huge difference and artificial intelligence will be a game changer. Artificial intelligence is extending human capability and performance in the companies.

References

1. Fahimeh Babaei Nivlouei, (2014), "Electronic Human Resource Management System :The Main Element in Capacitating Globalization Paradigm", International Journal of Business and Social Science, February, Vol. 5 No.2.
2. <http://searchhrsoftware.techtarget.com/opinion/How-will-AI-in-HR-be-a-game-changer>
3. <http://www.newspatrolling.com/digital-hr-organizing-for-the-future/>
4. <http://bigdata-madesimple.com/5-ways-to-use-artificial-intelligence-ai-in-human-resources/>
5. <https://workology.com/artificial-intelligence-recruiting-human-resources/>
6. <https://hr.shiras.in/blog/Artificial-Intelligence-in-Human-Resources.php>
7. <https://yourbusiness.azcentral.com/can-hr-become-competitive-advantage-organization-1456.html>
8. <https://www.brookings.edu/blog/techtank/2015/10/26/how-robots-artificial-intelligence-and-machine-learning-will-affect-employment-and-public-policy/>
9. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/jeannemeister/2017/11/09/the-future-of-work-how-artificial-intelligence-will-transform-the-employee-experience/#130b8b723c96>.
10. <http://www.digitalistmag.com/future-of-work/2017/05/04/artificial-intelligence-moves-workplace-hr-needs-to-respond-05058899>.
11. <http://blogs.workday.com/the-research-says-how-to-digitize-hr/>.
12. <http://www.a-performersconference.com/highlight/highlight.jsp>.
13. <http://ideal.com/ai-recruiting>.

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Campus Office :Srinivas Campus, Srinivas Nagar, Mukka,
Surathkal, MANGALURU - 574 146 Karnataka State, INDIA.

E-mail: info@srinivasgroup.com, Website:www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

COURSES OFFERED BY SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

College of Engineering

- B.E - Mechanical (4 years)
 - Computer Science (4 years)
 - Civil (4 years)
 - Electronics & Communication (4 years)
- M. Tech - Structural Engineering (2 years)
- M.Tech - **Intergrated in** Computer Science/
Structural Engineering- 5 Years

College of Allied Health Sciences

- B.Sc. - Cardio Vascular Technology
 - Perfusion Technology
 - Medical Lab Technology
 - Renal Dialysis Technology
 - Optometry
 - OT & Anaesthesia Technology
 - Imaging Technology
 - Respiratory Care Technology

College of Bussiness Management & Commerce

- BBA - Logistics & Supply chain /
Aviation Management/
Honours.
- B.Com - Corporate Auditing with CA
intermediate Syllabus/
International Accounting with
ACCA Syllabus/
Professional with ACCA & CA
Intermediate Syllabus / Hons./
Aviation Management
- B.Sc. - Interior Design
- MBA - Regular with Dual specialization/
Business Analytics /
Aviation Management
Enterprises Management & Marketing

College of Physiotherapy

- BPT- (USA APTA equivalent curriculum)
- MPT

College of Computer & Information Science

- BCA - Software Application/
Aviation Management/
Data Analytics &
Cloud Computing
- MCA - Lateral Entry &
Dual Specialization

College of Social Science & Humanities

- M.S.W. - Dual Specialization

College of Hotel Management & Tourism

- BHMCT
- B.Sc. (Hotel Management)

College of Education

- Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.)

For details and enquiries, Please contact :

A.O. :G.H.S. Road, Mangaluru - 575 001

Phone : 0824 - 2412382, 2423588, 2422381 Fax : (0824) 2442766

E-mail : admission@srinivasuniversity.ac.in, info@srinivasgroup.com